

Analysis of mechanosensor RNA
expression during the activation of T cells
and differentiation of macrophages in
response to chemical and mechanical
stimuli

Theodoros Simakou

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Declaration

I, Theodoros Simakou, hereby declare that the work presented in this thesis is my own work and has not been submitted in part or whole, for any other degrees at this or any other University or Institute. Where other sources of information have been used, they have been acknowledged in the appropriate format.

Signed:

Date:

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List of abbreviations

ACTB	Actin beta
APCs	Antigen presenting cells
BCR	B cell receptor
bp	Base pairs
BSA	Bovine serum albumin
CCL	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand
CD	Cluster of differentiation
cDNA	Complementary deoxyribonucleic acid
CT	Cycle threshold
CTCF	Corrected total cell fluorescence
CTLs	Cytotoxic lymphocytes
CXCL	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand
DAG	Diacylglycerol
DAPI	4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole
DC	Dendritic cell
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
FBS	Foetal bovine serum
FITC	Fluorescein isothiocyanate
FSS	Fluid shear stress
GAPDH	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase

GZMB	Granzyme B
HLA	Human leukocyte antigen
HLA-DMB	Major histocompatibility complex, class II, DM beta
HLA-DRA	Major histocompatibility complex, class II, DR alpha
HMGB1	High mobility group box 1
Hz	Hertz
ICAM-1	Intercellular adhesion molecule 1
IFN	Interferon
IFNGR1	Interferon gamma receptor 1
IL	Interleukin
IL2RA	Interleukin 2 receptor subunit alpha
IL7R	Interleukin 7 receptor
IP3	Inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate
IP3R	Inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate receptor
ITAMs	Immunoreceptor tyrosine-based activation motifs
JAK	Janus kinase
KLRG1	Killer cell lectin-like receptor G1
LAT	Linker for activation of T cells
LCK	SRC family protein kinase LCK
LEF1	Lymphoid enhancer binding factor 1
LPS	Lipopolysaccharide
mRNA	Messenger ribonucleic acid
MS	Multiple sclerosis

N	Newton
NFAT2	Nuclear factor of activated T cells 2
NK	Natural Killer cells
nM	nano-molar
PC1	Polycystin 1
PCR	Polymerase chain reactions
pDC	Plasmacytoid dendritic cell
PE	Phycoerythrin
PHA	Phytohaemagglutinin
PI	Propidium iodide
PI3K	Phosphatidylinositol 3-kinases (or phosphoinositide 3-kinase)
PIEZO1	Piezo type mechanosensitive ion channel component 1
PIP2	Phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate
PKC	Protein kinase C
PKD1	Polycystic kidney disease 1 (or polycystin 1)
PKD2	Polycystic kidney disease 2 (or polycystin 2)
PLCγ1	Phospholipase C gamma 1
PMA	Phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate
pMHC	Peptide-loaded major histocompatibility complex
PTEN	Phosphatase and Tensin Homolog
RA	Rheumatoid arthritis
RPL37A	Ribosomal protein L37a
rpm	Revolutions per minute

RPMI	Roswell Park Memorial Institute Medium
SLE	Systemic lupus erythematosus
STAT	Signal transducer and activator of transcription
T1D	Type 1 diabetes
TBE	Tris, boric acid and EDTA buffer
TCF3	Transcription factor 3
TCF4	Transcription factor 4
TCF7L2	Transcription factor 7 like 2 (T-cell-specific transcription factor 4)
TCM	Central memory T cells
TCR	T cell receptor
TE	Terminal effector T cells
TEM	Effector memory T cells
Th17	T helper 17
TLR	Toll-like receptor
TNF	Tumour necrosis factor
TOP1	DNA topoisomerase I
Treg	Regulatory T cells
TRM	Tissue-resident memory T cells
TRP	Transient receptor potential channels
TRPP	Transient receptor potential polycystic
VCAM-1	Vascular cell adhesion molecule 1
ZAP70	Zeta-chain-associated protein kinase 70

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Abstract

T cells and macrophages are involved in many autoimmune pathologies. One such autoimmune condition is alopecia areata, which results from immune responses targeting hair follicles and impairing the hair growth cycle. The immune infiltrates in alopecia areata are mainly lymphocytic, with CD8⁺ T cells being the main contributors to the disease in humans and mouse models. This study looked at the mechanosensitivity of immune cells, which is a factor that can influence inflammatory responses.

In this project, CD8⁺ T cell activation was studied at transcriptional level, looking into the regulation patterns of many genes encoding cytokines, effector proteins, mechanosensors, cell surface markers and transcription factors. This study demonstrated that the mRNA encoding the mechanosensor *PIEZO1* was downregulated in activated Jurkat and CD8⁺ T cells. Based on the regulation patterns of *IL2RA*, effector proteins such as *GZMB*, and receptors such as *IL7R* and *KLRG1*, the *PIEZO1* downregulation was occurring simultaneously to the CD8⁺ T cell activation and early effector differentiation.

In addition, this study investigated T cell responses to 1000Hz nanovibrations. The results from these experiments were inconclusive and lacking reproducibility. In contrary, when the cells were activated chemically, the results were highly reproducible. Jurkat cell responses were also assessed when cross-linking CD3 with PHA-L and applying nanovibrations at 24 hours. Discrepancies in responses were observed, with IL-2 found upregulated and downregulated in the supernatant of stimulated cells in two identical experiments, whereas the *IL2RA* expression was not affected in any experiment. Furthermore, many of the assays could not be tested for reproducibility, as the device used for the nanovibrational stimulation failed and was not suitable for further work.

Other experiments assessed the macrophage differentiation upon stimulation of monocytes with vitamin D3, 1000Hz nanovibrations, and both. The vitamin D3 induced macrophage differentiation, which was characterised by upregulated macrophage markers such as *CD14*, downregulation of *HLA-DRA*, and an inverse regulation of *LEF-1* and *TCF7L2*. The vitamin D3 also upregulated *PKD2 (TRPP2)*, encoding for a non-selective cation channel with mechanosensory abilities. The nanovibrational stimulation caused upregulation of *PIEZO1* and *TCF3* in monocytes, showing response towards this mechanical stimulus. However, the 1000Hz vibrations did not induce macrophage differentiation because no regulation of *CD14*

and *TCF/LEF* transcription factors took place. Furthermore, in the presence of vitamin D3, the effects of 1000Hz stimulation were cancelled and the cell responses were comparable to those induced by the vitamin D3 when applied alone.

Overall, this study identified interesting patterns of gene expression upon activation and differentiation of T cell and macrophages. The experiments did not demonstrate that the nanovibrational stimulation, which was studied as alternative therapy for alopecia areata, could modulate T cell responses. In monocytes, the presence of vitamin D3 cancelled the observed response towards the nanovibrational stimulation, which may indicate that in an environment rich in chemical signals such as the site of inflammation, the cells would not be affected by its application.

Chapter 1

Mechanobiology of the immune cells

1.1. Introduction to mechanotransduction

In mammalian cells, physical forces have shown to have an important role in many cellular functions such as stem cell differentiation (Engler *et al.*, 2006), cellular motility (Vogel and Sheetz, 2009), and cell behaviour (Fedorchak, Kaminski and Lammerding, 2014). Examples include muscle growth in response to exercise, bone remodelling based on their mechanical load, or endothelial cells aligning under fluid shear stress (Fedorchak, Kaminski and Lammerding, 2014).

Mechanosensation is defined as the process by which different mechanical stimuli occurring extracellularly or intracellularly are sensed by living cells and converted into intracellular biochemical signals which can influence cell proliferation, differentiation and behaviour (Isermann and Lammerding, 2013; Fedorchak, Kaminski and Lammerding, 2014; Piperi, 2015; Tsimbouri, 2015; Chin *et al.*, 2016). Mechanotransduction is the term used to describe the signal transduction in response to mechanical stimuli, although the term is often used interchangeably with mechanosensation (Isermann and Lammerding, 2013; Fedorchak, Kaminski and Lammerding, 2014; Piperi, 2015; Tsimbouri, 2015; Chin *et al.*, 2016).

Mechanotransduction involves interaction of several cellular protein complexes, such as cytoskeleton filaments, actin microtubules, adherent junctions, desmosomes, integrins, focal adhesion points, and mechanosensor receptors and channels (Bukoreshtliev, Haase and Pelling, 2013; Eijkelkamp, Quick and Wood, 2013; Piperi, 2015). Although many of the upstream molecular mechanisms for initiating the mechanotransduction remain elusive, there is a variety of identified downstream signalling pathways and target genes which are regulated in response to mechanical and physical stimuli (Eijkelkamp, Quick and Wood, 2013; Fedorchak, Kaminski and Lammerding, 2014; Piperi, 2015; Tsimbouri, 2015).

The way mechanotransduction works relies on the processes that affect protein allostery (Seifert and Gräter, 2013). The allostery can be termed as regulation by any kind of external perturbation, such as ligand binding or mechanical stretching (Seifert and Gräter, 2013). Both ligand binding and mechanical stimuli generate forces on the cell proteins that affect

their 3D conformation and thus, their allostery (Seifert and Gräter, 2013). Because of this phenomenon, the protein can get activated and transmit signals not only under chemical stimulation, but also under mechanical stress, explaining why cells have the ability to sense and respond to the physical parameters of their environment (Figure 1.1) (Seifert and Gräter, 2013).

Figure 1.1: Allosteric regulation of proteins under chemical ligation or mechanical stress. Chemical perturbations such as binding of a ligand, phosphorylation, or protonation upon pH change, can present molecular forces which cause conformational changes and alter protein activity. This can result in opening of channels allowing compounds to move in and out of cells (A), or activation of receptors (C), which initiate intracellular signalling pathways. Similarly, an applied mechanical force can regulate protein activity by causing conformational changes that result in altered protein activity. The mechanical forces can influence channel opening (B) or receptor activation (D), thus initiating intracellular signalling. The proteins that are sensitive to mechanical forces and activate in their presence, are known as mechanosensors.

For example, receptors like integrins and transient receptor potential (TRP) channels can activate in the presence of mechanical forces generated by cell to cell contact, fluid dynamics, pressure and membrane deformation (Miyamoto *et al.*, 1995; Zhu and Assoian,

1995; Eijkelkamp, Quick and Wood, 2013; Tsimbouri, 2015). Other proteins, such as p130Cas, are activated in a force dependent manner with possible direct coupling between the mechanical force and the chemical signalling (Sawada *et al.*, 2006), whereas stretching of the protein complexes found at the focal adhesions has shown to expose either cryptic binding sites or cryptic phosphorylation sites, that eventually activate signalling pathways (del Rio *et al.*, 2009).

The cell nucleus also plays a crucial role in cellular mechanosensation, by processing incoming signals generated from mechanical stimuli (Isermann and Lammerding, 2013; Fedorchak, Kaminski and Lammerding, 2014). It has been speculated that the nucleus is a large cellular mechanosensor itself, which can directly influence gene expression in response to mechanical stimulation (Wang, Tytell and Ingber, 2009; Isermann and Lammerding, 2013). The nucleus is linked to cytoskeleton through protein complexes known as LINC (Linker of the nucleoskeleton and cytoskeleton), which enable communication between the two (Isermann and Lammerding, 2013). Lamins, which are the major components of the nuclear lamina, extend into the LINC and play a crucial role in transmission of forces over the nuclear envelope (Crisp *et al.*, 2006; Isermann and Lammerding, 2013). These forces when transmitted in the nucleus cause deformations which could alter chromatin structure, induce release of transcriptional regulators or translocation of chromatin segments away from transcriptionally repressive regions, thereby regulating gene expression (Isermann and Lammerding, 2013).

The mechanical forces and mechanotransduction are also involved in a variety of pathologies. Mechanical stimuli are involved in cancer, where they influence disease hallmarks such as angiogenesis, migration and metastasis of tumour cells (Chin *et al.*, 2016). Although solid tumours have a high tissue stiffness, individual tumour cells are paradoxically less stiff than the healthy cells, which results in altered behaviour that influences disease progression (Chin *et al.*, 2016).

It has been shown that areas of cardiovascular system that are exposed to FSS below or above the haemodynamic average are susceptible to developing cardiovascular disease. For example, areas of low FSS such as curvatures of arteries, are susceptible to atherosclerotic lesions with strong plaque phenotypes (Cheng *et al.*, 2006), whereas areas that are exposed

to both high and low FSS, are susceptible to form aneurisms (Meng *et al.*, 2007; Bousset *et al.*, 2008).

Tissue stiffness is another parameter that is altered in disease states and affects the way healthy cells function. For example, after myocardial infarction, the damaged tissue is replaced by scar tissue, which increases myocardial tissue stiffness from 18 to 55 kPa (Berry *et al.*, 2006). An increase in myocardial tissue elasticity around 35-70 kPa, has shown to inhibit cardiomyocyte beating *in vitro* (Engler *et al.*, 2008). In breast cancer, the stiffness of mammary gland increases from 167 Pa to 4 kPa, which promotes tumour formation and metastasis in both *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies (Paszek *et al.*, 2005).

Therefore, the ability of cells to sense and respond to the physical cues in their environments, is important for the maintenance of tissue homeostasis and health, whereas altered physical properties of tissues can influence disease.

1.1.2. The immune system and the exposure of leucocytes to physiological mechanical stimuli.

The immune system is a complex network of cells and molecules, which has evolved to protect the host from pathogenic microbes, foreign harmful substances, and mutated cells (Abbas, Lichtman and Pillai, 2018). The immune responses that lead to the recognition and elimination of microbial, toxic, or allergenic molecules can be divided into two general categories, the innate and the adaptive responses (Chaplin, 2010). The innate immune responses are hard-wired and encoded by genes in the host's germ line that recognize molecular patterns shared both by many microbes and toxins that are not present in the mammalian host (Chaplin, 2010). The adaptive responses are encoded by gene elements that somatically rearrange to assemble antigen-binding molecules with exclusive specificity for individual foreign structures (Chaplin, 2010).

The innate responses are the first to activate when foreign antigens are encountered, because the recognition molecules used by the innate system are inherently expressed on a large number of cells (Chaplin, 2010; Abbas, Lichtman and Pillai, 2018). The innate immune cells initiate inflammation and do not produce memory phenotypes (Chaplin, 2010; Abbas, Lichtman and Pillai, 2018). Cell-mediated innate immune responses involve leucocytes, such as neutrophils, monocytes, eosinophils and macrophages, that get directly involved in

clearing the antigens mainly through the process of phagocytosis (Abbas, Lichtman and Pillai, 2018). The innate humoral responses involve a system of circulatory proteins that become activated upon encountering foreign compounds known as the complement system, as well as different cytokines and chemokines used for cell communication and migration (Abbas, Lichtman and Pillai, 2018).

The adaptive system is composed of small numbers of cells with specificity for individual pathogens, toxins or allergens, thus it is necessary that the responding cells proliferate after encountering the antigen in order to attain sufficient numbers to mount an effective response (Chaplin, 2010; Abbas, Lichtman and Pillai, 2018). Therefore, the adaptive response generally expresses itself temporally after the innate response. However, the adaptive responses are more efficient in clearing antigens and can create memory phenotypes that provide long-lasting protection (Chaplin, 2010; Abbas, Lichtman and Pillai, 2018). Like the innate response, adaptive immune responses can be cell-mediated and humoral. Cell-mediated response is characterised by direct activity of T cells, whereas the humoral response is characterised by cytokines and antibodies produced by B cells. Cytokines produced by adaptive immune cells regulate the activity of other cells, whereas the antibodies neutralise the pathogens, or label them to enhance phagocytosis (Abbas, Lichtman and Pillai, 2018). A link between the innate and adaptive responses are the antigen presenting cells, that are specialised cells capable of recognising, processing, and presenting antigens to T cells (Abbas, Lichtman and Pillai, 2018).

From the traditional immunological perspective, immune responses are generally regulated through intercellular signalling induced by molecular initiators, which include cytokines and chemokines secreted by immune cells and tissue cells (Kim *et al.*, 2019). However, similar to different tissues around the body, the immune cells have evolved mechanism to perceive and respond to the physical forces around them, and thus the physical parameters of tissues can influence immune responses (Kim *et al.*, 2019). The immune cells are exposed to a variety of mechanical forces while in circulation and when they get recruited in inflamed tissues (Previtera, 2014). There are different fluid-phase and solid-phase stresses to which the circulating and tissue leucocytes are exposed to. Fluid-phase stresses include fluid shear stress (FSS) and interstitial fluid pressure (IFP). Solid-phase stresses include solid tissue

stimuli, strains, and elasticities. Depending on the tissue and organ, there is a physiological range for each of these mechanical stresses (Previtera, 2014).

Circulating leucocytes are exposed to dynamic FSS, which is a frictional force generated by fluid flow over the surface of the cell, ranging from 0.1-15 dynes/cm² (Previtera, 2014). One dyne is equal to 10 μ N or 10⁻⁵ N (International System of Units). Leucocytes experience different FSS depending on their location during the circulation. For example, the leucocytes circulating in the arteriole system experience an FSS >15 dynes/cm² (Malek, 1999; Previtera, 2014), in the venous system an FSS of 1-6 dynes/cm² (Malek, 1999) and in microcirculatory systems an FSS of 0.1-4 dynes/cm² (Kim and Sarelius, 2003; Makino *et al.*, 2007). On the other hand, leucocytes attached to the endothelial monolayer experience a non-uniform FSS stimulation. At the contact site, the cell membrane experiences a FSS close to zero, whereas the exposed membrane surface experiences an FSS of 1-10 dynes/cm² (Previtera, 2014). This is referred to as wall shear stress. After the cells have attached the endothelial monolayer, leucocytes will undergo transmigration during which they can exert compression forces of up to 250nN on nearby cells (Rabodzey *et al.*, 2008).

Depending on the tissue they are migrating, leucocytes will be experiencing a wide range of tissue elasticity. For example, immune infiltrates in fat tissues are exposed to elasticities about 17 Pa (1 Pa= 1 N/m²), whereas in tendons, about 310 MPa (mega-Pa) (Levental, Georges and Janmey, 2007).

In addition, the tissue residing leucocytes are also exposed to interstitial fluid pressures (IFPs) that range from -1 to 11 kPa, with negative pressure resulting from lymphatic action (Previtera, 2014). The highest IFPs are in arterioles, at 5-10 kPa, and the lowest values are for muscle tissues, at -300 Pa (Provenzano and Hingorani, 2013). It has been speculated that the leucocytes may also be exposed to 0.1 dynes/cm² by the interstitial fluid flow around the cells and through the extracellular matrix (ECM) pores (Pedersen, Boschetti and Swartz, 2007; Mitchell and King, 2013; Tarbell and Shi, 2013; Previtera, 2014).

However, the immune cells are also exposed to a variety of altered physical parameters in the tissues, caused by disease states or inflammatory responses (Previtera, 2014).

Furthermore, the inflammation itself can cause changes in tissue parameters (Previtera, 2014). It is an overall observation that the altered mechanical properties of tissues in

disease states contribute to the activation of immune cells, regulation of their activities and persisting inflammation (Previtera, 2014; Kim *et al.*, 2019). The mechanisms by which the different physical stimuli affect immune cells responses are covered further in this introduction.

1.2. Mechano-regulation of the innate immunity

The recruitment of circulating neutrophils and monocytes to the damaged tissues is influenced by mechanical stimuli applied throughout the process (Figure 1.2). Unregulated neutrophil activity has been linked to progression of many immune-related diseases, such as rheumatoid arthritis, asthma and sepsis (Jannat *et al.*, 2010).

Figure 1.2: Recruitment of neutrophils from blood to the damaged tissue. This process has different steps including attachment to endothelium (1), rolling (2), adhesion (3), transmigration through endothelium (4) and migration to site of inflammation (5). L-Selectin and E-Selectin are used for rolling adhesion (2, 3). Tissue stiffness regulates VCAM-1 allocation to the basal membrane of the endothelial cells, to reduce the affinity for neutrophils that have already transmigrated. ICAM-1, an integrin ligand, regulates transmigration through the endothelium (4). The neutrophil migration in tissue (5) is directed by the chemoattractant gradient and tissue stiffness.

1.2.1. Rolling adhesion: FSS prevents unnecessary adhesion of leucocytes to the endothelial layer.

In order for the adhesion to take place, the rolling leucocytes must overcome the haemodynamic force, specifically the FSS originating from pulsating blood (Previtera, 2014). The leucocytes in circulation are spherical in shape, but when the blood flow is halted, they form pseudopodia formations (Figure 1.3; A,B) (Moazzam *et al.*, 1997). These pseudopodia facilitate adhesion, thus the FSS negatively regulates them in order to avoid leukocytes from attaching to the endothelium (Worthen *et al.*, 1989). Application of FSS at 0.4-1.5 dynes/cm² makes the adherent and non-adherent neutrophils to retract their pseudopodia projections (Figure 1.3;B) (Moazzam *et al.*, 1997; Fukuda *et al.*, 2000).

This effect of FSS on leucocytes is strong in the absence of chemical stimulants, which if present, override this influence (Moazzam *et al.*, 1997; Fukuda *et al.*, 2000; Chen *et al.*, 2010). For example, adherent neutrophils when treated with chemoattractants PAF and fMLF, continue to keep their pseudopodia when the FSS is applied (Figure 1.3;C) (Fukuda *et al.*, 2000). Furthermore, FSS has shown to enhance the effect of chemical signalling. In the presence of platelet activating factor (PAF), fluid shear stress (0.1–2.75 dyn/cm²) exposure increased PAF-induced neutrophil activation in a shear stress magnitude and time-dependent manner (Mitchell, Lin and King, 2014).

Interestingly, shear pressure does not have an inhibitory effect when neutrophils are treated with glucocorticoids. Dexamethasone-treated neutrophils have fewer projection than untreated neutrophils in static conditions (Fukuda, Mitsuoka and Schmid-Schönbein, 2004). However, when FSS is applied, both adherent and non-adherent neutrophils increase the number of pseudopodia projections (Fukuda, Mitsuoka and Schmid-Schönbein, 2004).

Figure 1.3: FSS regulates neutrophil rolling adhesion. When blood flow is halted, neutrophils project pseudopods that facilitate adhesion (A). Under FSS created from blood flow, the neutrophils retract their pseudopods and become circular (B). However, FSS does not have an inhibitory effect if chemoattractants are in the environment (C) but instead enhances their activity.

Physiological FSS seems to reduce unnecessary adhesion of circulating neutrophils which if occurs can cause inflammation (Moazzam *et al.*, 1997; Fukuda *et al.*, 2000; Chen *et al.*, 2010). This allows rolling adhesion to take place only under the presence of chemoattractants which signal tissue damage. When chemoattractants are present, the FSS can enhance rolling adhesion, which suggests an important involvement of mechanotransduction in coordinating the cellular responses to both mechanical and chemical signalling (Fukuda *et al.*, 2000; Mitchell, Lin and King, 2014).

1.2.2. Transmigration: Tissue damage-increased elasticities enhance endothelial permeability.

Transmigration is the process following leukocyte adhesion, in which the leukocytes transmigrate through the endothelial cells into the sub-endothelial tissue (Figure 1.2). The normal stiffness of sub-endothelial tissue as measured in healthy bovine arteries ranges from 2.1 to 3.3 kPa (Peloquin *et al.*, 2011). In disease and inflammation, the sub-endothelial tissue stiffness increases, due to the degradation of elastin by matrix metalloproteinases released from the immune cells and production of fibrotic material, mostly collagen,

produced by smooth muscle cells (Chatzizisis and Giannoglou, 2007). Atherosclerotic plaques for instance, have a stiffness that ranges from 33 to 2300 kPa (Akyildiz *et al.*, 2011). In fact, larger transmigration of mononuclear cells (MNCs), such as monocytes, Natural Killer (NK) cells and lymphocytes (of the adaptive immunity), has been observed on stiffer substrates ranging 5-280 kPa, as opposed to softer ones ranging 1-3 kPa (Hayenga and Aranda-Espinoza, 2013).

Mechanically, the cells' transmigration towards sub-endothelial tissue is facilitated by VCAM-1 translocation from the apical to basal plasma membrane (Figure 1.2), which reduces the affinity of neutrophils to the endothelial cells, and pushes them towards the tissue (Hayenga and Aranda-Espinoza, 2013). In addition, substrate stiffness of 5-280 kPa, allows pores to form between the endothelial cells through myosin light chain kinase (MLCK) – induced endothelial cell contractions (Stroka and Aranda-Espinoza, 2011). These pores facilitate the transmigration of neutrophils, and when MLCK is inhibited, the transmigration levels are reduced to those observed for soft stiffness tissues (Stroka and Aranda-Espinoza, 2011).

Furthermore, transmigration of neutrophils has been reported to increase from < 1% to 26%, on soft 0.87 kPa substrates, when the endothelial cells are affected by OxLDL (Stroka, Levitan and Aranda-Espinoza, 2012). This alteration has been explained by synergistic effect of increased expression of intercellular adhesion molecule-1 (ICAM-1) on endothelial cells when stimulated by OxLDL, and MLCK-mediated endothelial contraction (Stroka, Levitan and Aranda-Espinoza, 2012).

Based on these observations, the tissue stiffness alters the endothelial cells communications amongst themselves and neutrophils, and in turn facilitates transmigration (Previtera, 2014). Increased transmigration of neutrophils and leucocytes can therefore be a result of simultaneous stimulation from chemical stimuli (as in ICAM-1 induction) and mechanical stimuli (such as MLCK and VCAM-1 induction), indicating involvement of mechanosensation during this stage (Previtera, 2014).

1.2.3. Migration: Tissue stiffness and dimensionality influence leucocyte recruitment

After endothelial transmigration, the leucocytes will migrate towards the damaged or infected area (Figure 1.2). Studies of neutrophil migratory behaviour have shown that the

stiffness of tissue can influence the speed and direction of migration in 2D gels (Oakes *et al.*, 2009; Stroka and Aranda-Espinoza, 2009). Neutrophil speed and motion is dependent on the number of adhesions the cells will make with the surrounding substrate (Oakes *et al.*, 2009; Stroka and Aranda-Espinoza, 2009). In soft gels, the neutrophils move faster because they are less adherent and experience lower traction forces, whereas in stiff gels, their motion is slower because there is more adhesion which generates greater traction forces (Oakes *et al.*, 2009; Stroka and Aranda-Espinoza, 2009). On softer gels of 5 and 10 kPa, neutrophils travel faster but are disorganized and change the direction often, whereas on stiffer gels of 20, 50 and 100 kPa, the motion is slower but more directional and efficient (Oakes *et al.*, 2009).

The effects of substrate stiffness on motion and speed of neutrophils are not passive. The neutrophils that are treated with inhibitors of phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3K) lose their ability to sense substrate stiffness, suggesting that phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase is involved in neutrophil mechanosensing (Oakes *et al.*, 2009). Although PI3K influences the acceleration of chemotaxis towards chemoattractant fMLP, its signalling is not required for neutrophil chemotaxis itself, therefore the loss of stiffness-dependent motion when the kinase is inhibited is not related to chemical signalling but rather mechanotransduction (Heit *et al.*, 2008; Previtiera, 2014).

In addition, the dimensionality of the substrate is important for leucocyte migration. In 2D substrates, integrin-deficient dendritic cells (DCs) cannot adhere nor migrate (Lämmermann *et al.*, 2008). 2D structures naturally make it necessary for the cells to adhere using integrins, even during migration (Lämmermann *et al.*, 2008). In 3D substrates however, the integrin deficient DCs continue to travel in the direction of the chemoattractant (Lämmermann *et al.*, 2008). Since adhesion is not necessary for motion in 3D structure, then the cells do not involve integrins, but rather expansions of actin cytoskeleton which generate a force on the leading cell edge and provides protrusive motion (Lämmermann *et al.*, 2008). Both these cellular structures are involved in mechanosensing, suggesting involvement of mechanotransduction when responding to the dimensionality of the surrounding tissue (Lämmermann *et al.*, 2008; Previtiera, 2014).

3D matrix architecture can also impact macrophage migration. While most leukocytes migrate via an amoeboid migration mode, macrophages employ both amoeboid and

mesenchymal migration modes (Guet *et al.*, 2011; McWhorter, Davis and Liu, 2015). Using 3D fibrillar and gelled type I collagen, it has been demonstrated compellingly that matrix architecture dictates macrophage migration modes (Van Goethem *et al.*, 2010; McWhorter, Davis and Liu, 2015). In gelled collagen, a dense matrix with few distinct fibrils, human monocyte-derived macrophages adopt the mesenchymal migration mode, whereas in fibrillar collagen, macrophages migrate via the amoeboid mode (Van Goethem *et al.*, 2010; McWhorter, Davis and Liu, 2015). Remarkably, when presented with matrices of variable stiffness and architecture, macrophages adopt migration modes primarily based on architecture, thus establishing it as the dominant factor (McWhorter, Davis and Liu, 2015).

1.2.4. Mechanical stimuli influence activation of macrophages.

At the site of inflammation, macrophages will activate and start phagocytosis and production of cytokines that regulate inflammation, enhance recruitment of other immune cells, and promote tissue healing (Mosser and Edwards, 2008). The cellular functions of tissue-resident macrophages and peripheral blood-derived macrophages are affected by the tissue-specific microenvironment, which can create many types of mechanical stress on cells (McWhorter, Davis and Liu, 2015; Mennens, van den Dries and Cambi, 2017).

Hypertension, tissue damage and inflammation cause alteration in extracellular pressure. Normal interstitial tissue pressure ranges from 20 to 30 mm Hg (Wiig, Rubin and Reed, 2003), however, this pressure can increase or decrease in infections (Schnall *et al.*, 1996; Schaser *et al.*, 2003; Wiig, Rubin and Reed, 2003). It has been shown that macrophages, respond to increased tissue pressure by increasing their phagocytic activity, which is mediated by increased $\beta 1$ -integrin T789 phosphorylation (Bhalla *et al.*, 2009), and/or FAK-ERK pathway (Shiratsuchi and Basson, 2004). In addition, increased pressure stimulates the uptake of IgG complexes by macrophages in a manner that involves mechanically-increased intracellular Ca^{2+} (Mattana, Sankaran and Singhal, 1996).

At the same time, alterations in pressure have shown to stimulate cytokine secretion from macrophages. Exposure to cyclic pressure, induces secretion of IL-6, TNF- α and IL-1 β , which are proinflammatory cytokines (Ferrier *et al.*, 2000; Mevov *et al.*, 2002). Decreased interstitial pressure on the other hand (<20 mm/Hg), as in acute infection or inflammation, has shown to induce TNF- α production from macrophages, and has inhibitory effect on the

production of IL-1 β in both macrophages and monocytes even when they were chemically stimulated with LPS (Shiratsuch and Basson, 2005).

The mechanical stress induced by hypertension on vascular monocytes/macrophages has implication in diseases such as atherosclerosis (Yamamoto, Ikeda and Shimada, 2003). In human monocytes/macrophages and THP-1 cells, biomechanical strain can induce expression of the class A scavenger receptor, an important lipoprotein receptor in atherogenesis (Yamamoto, Ikeda and Shimada, 2003). In addition, DNA microarray analysis has shown that cyclic mechanical strain induces expression of genes encoding for IL-8 and IEX-1 in THP-1 cells (Yamamoto, Ikeda and Shimada, 2003). In these cells, biomechanical deformation contributes to degradation of extracellular matrix, monocyte differentiation, and promotion of atherosclerosis (Yamamoto, Ikeda and Shimada, 2003).

Apart from pressure, substrate rigidity and topography, which are mechanical properties of the extracellular matrix, regulate the differentiation, proliferation, and function of macrophages such as phagocytosis (Patel *et al.*, 2012; McWhorter, Davis and Liu, 2015). Substrate rigidity mechanically induces phagocytosis in macrophages by changing their elasticity, which is done by promoting actin polymerization and organization, and by increasing the activity of rhoGTPases such as Cdc42 (Patel *et al.*, 2012). This response is similar to what is observed when phagocytosis in macrophages is induced chemically by LPS or IFN- γ (Patel *et al.*, 2012).

1.2.5. Mechano-regulation of the complement system

Mechanical forces have been implicated in the regulation of the complement system activity. Laminar and physiological FSS applied on endothelial cells, causes expression of CD59, a protein that inhibits complement activation (Kinderlerer *et al.*, 2008). In contrast, when the endothelial cells are exposed to non-laminar FSS, as caused by presence of atherosclerotic plaque, the expression of CD59 is reduced (Kinderlerer *et al.*, 2008), which can increase the chances of complement activation. In fact, activated complement proteins have been identified in atherosclerotic plaques (Niculescu and Rus, 1999). Furthermore, application of high FSS of 18 dynes/cm² on endothelial cells enhances expression of gC1qR and directly activates the classical complement pathway (Yin *et al.*, 2007).

The activation of the complement from pathophysiological mechanical forces can lead to inflammation and recruitment of immune cells that can result in tissue damage and disease manifestation and/or progression (Previtera, 2014). Physiological FSS on the other hand seems to reduce the inflammatory responses related to the complement activation, through cell mechanotransduction which regulates CD59 expression (Kinderlerer *et al.*, 2008).

1.3. Mechano-regulation of the Adaptive Immunity

1.3.1. Mechanobiology of CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells

T cell activation, proliferation and effector roles can be influenced by the physical parameters of tissues. Softer polydimethylsiloxane substrates of <100 kPa have shown to stimulate stronger IL-2 production from *ex vivo* human CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells, when compared to stiffer substrates of more than 2 MPa (Figure 1.4). In addition, naïve CD4⁺ T cells when spread on softer substrates, tend to differentiate into IFN- γ -producing Th1-like cells (Figure 1.4) (O'Connor *et al.*, 2012). On polyacrylamide substrates with elasticity of 10-200 kPa and coated with CD3 and CD28 ligands, naïve CD4⁺ T cell activation has shown to be more strongly linked to CD3 than CD28 signalling (Judokusumo *et al.*, 2012; O'Connor *et al.*, 2012).

Many studies have attributed the mechanosensation abilities of the T cells to the T cell receptor (TCR). It has been shown that the direction of forces applied on the TCR upon specific peptide-loaded MHC (pMHC) ligation affects the signalling, and the TCR has been described as an anisotropic mechanosensor capable of converting the mechanical stimuli into biochemical ones (Kim *et al.*, 2009). Application of an external tangential but not a normal force (~50 pN) via optical tweezers has resulted in the activation of TCR-CD3 signalling (Kim *et al.*, 2009). Activating anti-CD3 monoclonal antibodies used in research for the activation of T cells mimic this force via their intrinsic binding mode (Kim *et al.*, 2009). Furthermore, the magnitude, duration and frequency of forces applied upon TCR-pMHC ligation have shown to affect activation of T cells, by prolonging the lifetime of TCR-pMHC bonds allowing for stronger Ca²⁺ signalling (Liu *et al.*, 2014).

The force-dependent activation of the T cell receptor (TCR) has shown to require cytoskeletal function (Comrie and Burkhardt, 2016). In Jurkat T cell, actin cytoskeletal-derived forces have shown to increase the mechanosensitivity of the TCR, and inhibiting

actin dynamics has led to reduction of traction forces produced by the cells (Hui *et al.*, 2015). Similarly, in primary T cells, inhibition of F-actin dynamics has led to diminished force-dependent activation upon TCR-antigen binding, by reducing Ca^{2+} signalling (Hu and Butte, 2016). Furthermore, in studies that have shown involvement of the actin cytoskeleton and the professional mechanosensor channel PIEZO1 in T cell mechanotransduction, the physical forces have shown to have an additional effect to the TCR signalling upon antigen presentation by enhancing intracellular signalling and/or TCR-pMHC interaction (Hu and Butte, 2016; Zhong *et al.*, 2018; Liu and Ganguly, 2019).

Figure 1.4: At softer substrates of less than 100 kPa immature T cells differentiate more efficiently than of stiffer substrates of more than 2 MPa. At softer substrates, the cells produce four times higher IL-2 compared to the stiffer substrates. In addition, in softer substrates, naïve T helper cells differentiate into Th1 subtypes. These indicate that topography influences the differentiation and activation of T lymphocytes (O'Connor *et al.*, 2012).

Mechanical forces are also utilized by effector $CD8^+$ cytotoxic cells when attacking infected or cancerous cells (Basu *et al.*, 2016). Upon synapse formation with affected cells, $CD8^+$ T cells coordinate exertion of mechanical forces and perforin release (Basu *et al.*, 2016). A strong correlation exists between the magnitude of force exerted by the $CD8^+$ T cells and the speed of perforin pore formation on the target cell, implying that forces potentiate cytotoxicity by enhancing perforin activity (Basu *et al.*, 2016). Similarly, another lymphocyte, the Natural Killer cells, utilise the actin cytoskeleton to generate forces which are used in immune synapses with target cells (Ben-Shmuel *et al.*, 2019).

Another physical parameter, the temperature, has shown to influence T cell activation. Increasing the temperature has resulted in enhanced IL-2 production in Jurkat and primary T cells (Zynda *et al.*, 2015). This enhanced response has been a result of the thermal forces affecting the anti-CD3 stimulation, but also anti-CD28 co-stimulation at a weaker degree (Zynda *et al.*, 2015).

1.3.2. Mechanobiology of B cells

B cells activation is also regulated by the physical influences of the immune synapse, APC membrane and antigen-presenting substrates. When spread on polyacrylamide gels with stiffness ranging from 2.6 – 22.1 kPa, B cells activation when encountering antigens has shown to be stronger for the stiffest substrates (Wan *et al.*, 2013). The activation of B cells on higher stiffness gels has been associated with B cell receptor (BCR) and phospho-spleen tyrosine kinase (Syk) co-localisation in microclusters, and increased expression of activation marker CD69 (Wan *et al.*, 2013). In addition, it has been demonstrated that cytoskeleton microtubules contribute to mechanosensing of stiffness in B cells, whereas actin plays a mild role (Wan *et al.*, 2013).

Furthermore, B cells internalize antigens more efficiently on substrates which are flexible and mimic APC plasma membrane viscoelastic properties (Natkanski *et al.*, 2013). This has also been true *in vivo*, where the membrane flexibility of different APC types regulates antigen extraction (Spillane and Tolar, 2017). For example, follicular dendritic cells are stiff cells that promote strong B cell pulling forces and strongly regulate affinity discrimination (Spillane and Tolar, 2017). In contrast, dendritic cells are soft and promote acquisition of low-affinity antigens through low forces (Spillane and Tolar, 2017).

Antigen internalization itself is a mechanical process which involves dynamic myosin IIa-mediated contractions that pull-out and enfold the presenting membranes (Natkanski *et al.*, 2013). These contractions generate forces that rupture most individual BCR-antigen bonds and promote internalization of only high-affinity, multivalent BCR microclusters (Natkanski *et al.*, 2013). In fact, antigen internalization is strongly force dependent. B cell enzymatic release, a process in which enzymes are released into synapse to digest the antigen before internalization, is utilised only if the mechanical forces have failed to retrieve the antigen (Spillane and Tolar, 2017).

1.4. Introduction of mechanosensors studied in this project.

The main mechanosensors studied in this project are PIEZO1, polycystin 1 and polycystin 2, encoded from *PIEZO1*, *PKD1* and *PKD2* genes, respectively. Many putative mechanosensors exist, but these three have strong mechanosensory abilities and have not been studied thoroughly in immune cells. In addition, PIEZO1 is considered a professional mechanosensor in human tissues because its main purpose is mechanosensation (Zhong *et al.*, 2018).

PIEZO1 is a mechanosensitive channel which converts different mechanical forces into biochemical signals, usually by regulating pathways involving Ca^{2+} , calpain 2 and cytoskeleton (Nourse and Pathak, 2017; Zhong *et al.*, 2018). This channel activates upon membrane deformations (Ge *et al.*, 2015; Zhong *et al.*, 2018), which made it a potential receptor for sensing the 1000Hz vibrational stimulation studied in this project.

Many studies have shown PIEZO1 mechanotransduction to be involved in the physiology of tissues, with roles in cardiovascular development (Hyman, Tumova and Beech, 2017) and endothelial functions (Wang *et al.*, 2016), myotube formation in skeletal muscle (Tsuchiya *et al.*, 2018), gastrointestinal tract smooth muscle contraction (Alcaino, Farrugia and Beyder, 2017), cancer progression (C. Li *et al.*, 2015; Han *et al.*, 2019; Huang *et al.*, 2019), platelet activities (Ilkan *et al.*, 2017), and red blood cell energy release (Cinar *et al.*, 2015) and structural maintenance (Svetina, Švelc Kebe and Božič, 2019).

More importantly, recent studies have shown important roles of PIEZO1 in $CD4^+$ and $CD8^+$ T cells. PIEZO1-induced Ca^{2+} influx in T cells leads to calpain activation and organization of cortical actin scaffold, optimising TCR signalling and thus T cell activation (Figure 1.5) (Liu and Ganguly, 2019). In transgenic mice, Ca^{2+} signals mediated by an uncharacterised activator of mechanosensitive Piezo1 channels were involved in TCR activation in naïve T cells, Th17 cells, and regulatory T cells (Dong *et al.*, 2017). In addition, the Piezo1 knockdown by siRNA has resulted in T cells becoming unresponsive to priming by the antigen presenting cells, as was observed by failure of $CD4^+$ T cells to proliferate upon antigen presentation (Liu *et al.*, 2018).

PIEZO1 has shown to be involved in monocyte mechanotransduction in response to cyclical hydrostatic pressure (Solis *et al.*, 2019). Mechanosensation of cyclical hydrostatic pressure by PIEZO1 results in Ca^{2+} -dependent activation of activating protein-1 (AP-1), transcription and secretion of endothelin-1 (EDN1), HIF1 α stabilization, and production of neutrophil chemoattractant CXCL2 (Solis *et al.*, 2019). These observations have shown that PIEZO1 is involved in the induction of inflammation to physical stimuli by the innate immune cells (Solis *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 1.5: Piezo1-mediated mechanotransduction optimises T cell activation. When the T cells interact with beads containing anti-CD3 and anti-CD28 or antigen presenting cells (APCs) during antigen presentation, forces are generated which activate Piezo1 channels and cause Ca^{2+} influx. The increase of Ca^{2+} concentration inside the cells activates Calpain which subsequently triggers polymerisation of actin fibres. The organisation of actin cytoskeleton results in stabilization of the immune synapse and optimal T cell activation. Image is based on recent observations about the roles of Piezo1 channels in T cell activation (Liu *et al.*, 2018; Liu and Ganguly, 2019).

Mechanosensor polycystin 1 (PC1, *PKD1*) is a large transmembrane protein resembling a G-protein-coupled receptor (Zhang, Tran and Wessely, 2018). Polycystin 2 (PC2, *TRPP2*, *PKD2*) belongs to transient receptor potential (TRP) channel family, and has shown to be a

mechanosensitive channel (Piperi, 2015). PC2 and PC1 form a complex which regulates Ca²⁺ signalling and acts as mechanosensor in the primary cilia (Mekahli *et al.*, 2013; Wang *et al.*, 2019). In absence of PC1, PC2 forms homotetramers, which function as non-selective cation channels (Wang *et al.*, 2019). In addition, PC2 has shown to interact with PIEZO1 through its N-terminus and negatively regulates the stretch sensitivity of this channel in renal epithelial cells (Peyronnet *et al.*, 2013; Retailleau and Duprat, 2014).

PC1 has shown to be an integral part of the primary cilia (Berbari *et al.*, 2009), and together with PC2 it is involved in mechanosensation in a variety of tissues and organs, such as kidney (Nauli *et al.*, 2003), cardiovascular system (Qiu and Yu, 2013; Pedrozo *et al.*, 2015), bone (Xiao and Quarles, 2010; Dalagiorgou *et al.*, 2013, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2014) and the central nervous system (CNS)(Ohata *et al.*, 2015; Galati, 2016). In kidneys, polycystins regulate internal signalling in response to fluid shear stress (Nauli *et al.*, 2003; Piperi, 2015). In the cardiovascular system, PC1 is involved in endothelial mechanotransduction and NO production, thus regulating blood pressure in response to fluid shear stress (Qiu and Yu, 2013). PC1 mechanosensation is also involved in cardiomyocyte functioning (Pedrozo *et al.*, 2015). In bone PC1 and PC2 play important roles in osteogenesis and bone modelling, in response to mechanical stimuli (Xiao and Quarles, 2010; Dalagiorgou *et al.*, 2013, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2014). In the CNS, the PC1 is important for the integrity of the primary cilia found on glial cells, and mechanosensation to cerebrospinal fluid flow (Ohata *et al.*, 2015). In psoriasis, and autoimmune disease affecting skin, PC1 expression has shown to be lowered in psoriatic plaques, and the mechanosensor can contribute to the pathogenesis through the PC1/ERK/mTOR signalling axis (Gargalionis *et al.*, 2018).

In immune cells, few studies have looked at polycystins. It has been observed that patients with PC1 mutations have lower lymphocytes (lymphopaenia), as well as monocytes and thrombocytes, suggesting that loss of PC1 affects the common progenitor cells leading to decreased proliferation or increased apoptosis in early phases of haematopoiesis (Van Laecke *et al.*, 2018). In fact, loss of expression of polycystin 1 and/or polycystin 2 has led to decreased proliferation of Epstein–Barr virus immortalized lymphoblastoid cells and lymphocyte production (Aguari *et al.*, 2004; Van Laecke *et al.*, 2018). In addition, erythroid and macrophage cell lines downregulate PC1 as they differentiate (Aguari *et al.*, 1998). It

has been hypothesised that this occurs in order for the cells to decrease proliferation and focus on the differentiation (Aguiari *et al.*, 1998).

It has been recently demonstrated that in T cells, PC1 and PC2 modulate the ERK, mTOR, NFκB and MIF signalling pathways, and thus may control cell proliferation and migration and contribute to inflammation (Magistrini *et al.*, 2019). The mutation of the gene in ADPKD2 or silencing of *PKD2* in Jurkat cells or normal T cells has resulted in strong reduction of ATP-evoked calcium, induction of cell aggregation and activation of cell proliferation (Magistrini *et al.*, 2019). In terms of expression in inflammatory responses, a study investigating the inflammatory role of TRP channels in leucocytes taken from non-valvular atrial fibrillation (NVAF) patients, found that the genes encoding most of the channels, including *PKD2*, were upregulated, whereas *PKD1* (gene encoding PC1) was not regulated (Düzen *et al.*, 2017).

1.5. The objectives of this projects

From the literature there is a clear understanding that different physical parameters affect the cells of the immune system, which in turn regulate their responses towards such stimuli. However, there is still a lot more to learn about the mechanobiology of immune cells. In addition, the mechanical manipulation of cell behaviour is of great importance for the development of novel therapies which until recent decades have been focused mostly on chemical manipulation.

The specific aims of this project were:

- 1) Study the expression of genes encoding for mechanosensors in T cells and monocytes in response to stimuli that induce their activation or differentiation.
- 2) Study the effects of nanovibrational mechanical stimulation on T cells and monocytes/macrophages, looking at their activation and differentiation, respectively.
- 3) Analyse whether the vibrational mechanical stimulation could be an alternative treatment for an autoimmune condition affecting hair follicles known as alopecia areata.

This project was partly funded by the Alopecia UK, which was looking at alternative treatments for the autoimmune disease alopecia areata. The above objectives were set to

study the regulation of genes encoding mechanosensors upon activation of T cells and macrophages, and to assess whether the application of vibrational mechanical stimulation alone or in combination with chemical stimuli would result in altered cell behaviour which could be beneficial in alopecia areata.

Alopecia areata is an autoimmune condition affecting hair follicles (Simakou *et al.*, 2019). Incidence of disease in the USA and UK is about 2%, but the data varies for different populations and in different studies, with global incidence ranging from 0.57% to 3.8% (Yang *et al.*, 2004; Guzmán-sánchez *et al.*, 2007; Mirzoyev *et al.*, 2014; Villasante Fricke and Miteva, 2015). Paediatric studies have report a higher prevalence in children ranging from 10-50%, especially for those with a family history of alopecia areata, indicating a genetic basis for disease development (Nanda, Al-Fouzan and Al-Hasawi, 2002; Tan, Tay and Giam, 2002; Xiao *et al.*, 2006; Rocha *et al.*, 2011). A systemic review of alopecia reata publications has shown that while the majority of epidemiology studies have recorded female predominance, many other studies have shown either the opposite (i.e. male predominance), or no difference in prevalence between males and females (Villasante Fricke and Miteva, 2015). Other factors that may influence alopecia areata in genetically predisposed patients include oxidative stress, psychological stress, infectious agents, gut microbiota, and diet (Simakou *et al.*, 2019). However, controversial studies exist and the ways by which these factors influence disease are not elucidated (Simakou *et al.*, 2019).

From an immunological perspective, alopecia areata manifests when the immune privilege of the hair follicle is lost, and immune cells infiltrate around the lower part of hair follicles during the anagen phase (i.e. the active growth phase) and interfere with the functioning of hair follicle cells (Figure 1.6) (Gilhar, 2010; Paus, Bulfone-Paus and Bertolini, 2018; Simakou *et al.*, 2019).

The collapse of immune privilege during the anagen could be a result of gene polymorphisms affecting the expression of proteins on the hair follicle cells that can induce inflammation, such as MHC class I, natural killer cell 2D ligand (NKG2DL), or chemokines like CXCL9, CXCL10 and CXCL11 (Simakou *et al.*, 2019). In fact, a locus on chromosome 6 which contains the genes encoding the natural killer (NK) cell receptor D (NKG2D; *KLRK1*) and its ligands NKG2DL3 (*ULBP3*) and retinoic acid early transcript 1L protein (*RAET1L*; also known

as *ULBP6*), has been found to be implicated only in alopecia areata and not in other autoimmune diseases, suggesting a crucial role in this disease (Petukhova *et al.*, 2010; Betz *et al.*, 2015; Pratt *et al.*, 2017).

Different environmental factors such as oxidative stress, infectious agents and nutrition could impair the immune privilege of the hair follicles during the anagen and initiate the autoimmune responses against the hair follicle cell in genetically predisposed patients (Simakou *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, the IFN- γ responses, which predominate in alopecia areata could cause upregulation of the MHC class I and NKG2D on hair follicle cells and loss of immune privilege (Simakou *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 1.6: The model explaining the collapse of the immune privilege of the hair follicles during the anagen in alopecia areata. In healthy scalp, the immune privilege is maintained by the downregulation of major histocompatibility complexes (MHC) class I, and the production of immunosuppressive cytokines such as α -melanocyte stimulating hormone (α -MSH), transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β), IK, indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO), and IL-10. The hair follicles of patients with AA lose the immune privilege by downregulation of these cytokines and upregulation of MHC molecules and NKG2D ligands, a process that can be genetically and environmentally influenced. The presentation of hair follicle autoantigens can drive immune responses against the cells, that eventually lead to autoimmunity and hair loss. However, the same mechanism can be a result of inflammatory responses, especially IFN- γ signalling, which can upregulate MCH class molecules on hair follicle cells, resulting in the collapse of the immune privilege. Other compounds elevated in AA scalp such as substance P (SP), can cause upregulation of nerve growth factor (NGF) which subsequently influences disease by activation of mast cells and interferes with the normal functioning of hair follicle cells.

IFN- γ induced JAK/STAT signalling can also interfere with the hair growth cycle. JAK/STAT signalling is suppressed in hair follicles during the anagen (Harel *et al.*, 2015; Triyangkulsri and Suchonwanit, 2018), as such signalling can inhibit proliferation and activation of hair stem cells (Harel *et al.*, 2015), and reduce angiogenesis (Meephansan *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, IFN- γ induced JAK/STAT signalling could be the reason of the premature termination of the anagen phase in alopecia areata (Gilhar, Etzioni and Paus, 2012; Paus,

Bulfone-Paus and Bertolini, 2018). Other polymorphisms on autoimmune regular gene *AIRE*, in patients with alopecia areata without polyendocrinopathy candidiasis ectodermal dysplasia syndrome (APECED), may give rise to autoimmune responses by affecting the central tolerance processes that occurs in thymus (Tazi-Ahnini *et al.*, 2002; Wengraf *et al.*, 2008; Arousse *et al.*, 2018) .

The immune infiltrates are mostly lymphocytic, composed of CD8⁺ and CD4⁺ T cells, but NK cells and plasmacytoid cells have also been observed (Figure 1.7) (Simakou *et al.*, 2019). Antibodies targeting the hair follicle cells have also been identified in this disease, implicating B cells too (Tobin *et al.*, 2002).

CD8⁺NKG2D⁺T cells (cytotoxic T cells) have been identified as major contributors of hair loss in alopecia areata and the first to infiltrate around the hair follicles (Gilhar, Etzioni and Paus, 2012; Xing *et al.*, 2014; Pratt *et al.*, 2017; de Jong *et al.*, 2018). These cells are necessary and sufficient for the induction of the disease in mouse models (Xing *et al.*, 2014; Pratt *et al.*, 2017). In addition, *Cd8a* transcripts, the alpha component of the CD8 costimulatory molecule on CD8⁺ T cells, increase early after engraftment of alopecia areata skin on mice, suggesting CD8⁺ T cells recruit early in disease (McPhee *et al.*, 2012). Similarly, transcriptional profiling of mouse and human affected skin has revealed gene expression signatures indicative of cytotoxic T cell infiltration, such as increased production of interferon- γ (IFN- γ) and γ -chain (γ_c) cytokines and receptors which are known to promote the activation and survival of IFN γ -producing CD8⁺NKG2D⁺ effector T cells (Xing *et al.*, 2014). When IFN- γ , interleukin-2 (IL-2) or interleukin-15 receptor beta (IL-15R β) are inhibited, the disease development is prevented by reducing the accumulation of CD8⁺NKG2D⁺ T cells and the dermal interferon response on the skin of mouse models (Xing *et al.*, 2014). In hair follicles of humans affected by alopecia areata, Granzyme B (GZMB) and cytotoxic granule associated RNA binding protein I (TIA1) are both elevated (Ghoreishi, Martinka and Dutz, 2010). In alopecia affected C3H/HeJ mice however, only *Gzmb* transcripts are increased, with no *Tia1* expression, suggesting that GZMB secretion may be more important for CD8⁺ T cell driven pathology (McPhee *et al.*, 2012).

CD4⁺ subtypes Th17 (CD4⁺IL-17A⁺) and Treg cells contribute to autoimmunity in alopecia areata (Tanemura *et al.*, 2013; Han *et al.*, 2015). In alopecia areata patients, Th17 cells are

infiltrated in dermis and around the hair follicles, and can be involved in cell-mediated autoimmunity (Tanemura *et al.*, 2013). These cells are also implicated in psoriasis and vitiligo, two autoimmune diseases reported as comorbidities of alopecia areata (Tanemura *et al.*, 2013; Villasante Fricke and Miteva, 2015; Pratt *et al.*, 2017). In addition, alopecia areata sufferers have an imbalance between Th17 and Treg cells, with Th17 levels in blood exceeding the Treg levels during active stages of disease (Han *et al.*, 2015). For more severe alopecia areata however, Treg cells exceed the Th17 (Han *et al.*, 2015). Such imbalance between Th17 and Treg cells in alopecia areata can result in inflammation and autoimmunity through similar pro-inflammatory mechanisms reported in other autoimmune diseases (Noack and Miossec, 2014).

Plasmacytoid dendritic cells (pDC) have been identified in infiltrates around the hair follicles of alopecia areata patients (Abou Rahal *et al.*, 2016). These are specialized dendritic cell populations with plasma cell morphology, express CD4, CD123, HLA-DR, blood-derived dendritic cell antigen-2 (BDCA-2) and Toll-like receptor (TLR)7 and TLR9 within endosomal compartments (Charles *et al.*, 2010; Abou Rahal *et al.*, 2016). The pDCs are a link between the innate and adaptive immunity by controlling the function of myeloid DCs, T, B and NK cells (Charles *et al.*, 2010; Abou Rahal *et al.*, 2016). They are absent from normal skin but can infiltrate upon injury or pathology, and are linked to inflammation towards infections, as well as autoimmunity in diseases such as lupus and psoriasis (Charles *et al.*, 2010; Abou Rahal *et al.*, 2016), two comorbidities of alopecia areata (Chu *et al.*, 2011). Upon activation they produce large quantities of type I interferons (IFN- α/β) (Charles *et al.*, 2010), which have been implicated in alopecia areata for inducing CD4⁺, CD8⁺ and NK responses towards the hair follicles (Figure 1.7) (Ghoreishi, Martinka and Dutz, 2010).

Figure 1.7: Immune responses towards the hair follicle cells in alopecia areata. The hair follicle cells have upregulated expression of MHC molecules, NKG2DL and chemoattractants such as CXCL9 and CXCL10. CD8⁺ T cells expressing NKG2D become effector upon binding MHC class I-antigen complex and the NKG2D ligand on hair follicle cells. Effector CD8⁺ T cells are maintained by the production of IL-2 and IL-15, and they produce granzyme B and IFN- γ . Granzyme B may cause cell lysis, but evidence suggests that hair follicle tissue is not destroyed in alopecia areata. IFN- γ accumulates at the site of inflammation, signals through the JAK-STAT pathway and can induce further abnormal expression on hair follicle cells and impair the hair growth cycle. CD4 and natural killer (NK) cells also recruit in hair follicle cells in response to chemoattractants. NK cells also express NKG2D and may attack the hair follicle cells upon binding the NKG2DL in similar manner to the CD8⁺ T cells. Effector CD4⁺ T cells and NK cells both produce IFN- γ . Plasmacytoid dendritic cells (pDCs) are a source of type I interferons in alopecia areata and they recruit and maintain the immune infiltrates around the hair follicles.

Understanding the regulation of genes encoding for mechanosensors can help understand the involvement of their products in early stages of T cell activation and macrophage differentiation. Knowing the important roles of PIEZO1 in T cell activation (Liu and Ganguly, 2019), one can assume the involvement of mechanosensation in inflammatory conditions and autoimmunity, and thus manipulation of mechanosensor expression can be beneficial for the modulation of disease.

Furthermore, altered mechanosensor expression can result in autoimmune pathologies. For example, psoriasis is an autoimmune condition characterised with plaques that are usually located in the knees and elbows, areas that are particularly subject to mechanical stress resulting from bending and friction (Gargalionis *et al.*, 2018). Psoriasis is also the most common comorbidity of alopecia areata (Simakou *et al.*, 2019). In psoriasis, downregulation of polycystin 1 expression has resulted in disease pathogenesis by the activation of ERK-dependent mTOR pathway (Gargalionis *et al.*, 2018).

In alopecia areata, manipulation of signalling, such as inhibition of JAK/STAT signalling has shown to reverse alopecia symptoms and induce hair growth (Triyangkulsri and Suchonwanit, 2018). As described earlier, mechanotransduction can alter intracellular signalling in response to external mechanical stimuli. Therefore, in this project the ability of vibrational mechanical stimuli to influence T cell and macrophage responses is tested in the experiments presented in the following chapters. Interfering with intracellular signalling, or cell to cell communication can be therapeutic for alopecia areata and other inflammatory conditions.

Chapter 2

Activation of Jurkat cells *in vitro* by PMA and PHA-L modulates the expression of genes encoding mechanosensor proteins.

Abstract

T cell activation is an important initial step in the adaptive immune responses. When T cells activate, they start expressing IL-2 and IL2RA (CD25), which are needed for the expansion of T cells and eventual differentiation into effector subtypes. In this chapter the regulation of genes encoding for mechanosensor proteins during the activation of Jurkat T cells was investigated. Originally, the initial experiments described in this chapter were designed in order to yield enough RNA for primer efficiency assessment, to observe what patterns of gene regulation were to be expected upon activation, help determining the future experimental set-ups, and prepare for primary T cell work. However, since the initial results were interesting, other experiments were performed to further study the regulation of mechanosensor genes during the activation of T cells when stimulated with PMA and PHA. The results and their interpretations are presented in this chapter.

2.1. Introduction

Jurkat E6-1 cells are immortalised T cells obtained from acute lymphoblastic leukaemia, and they have historically been utilised in *in vitro* studies that developed the field of immunology, contributed to the discovery of T cell receptor (TCR), antigen presentation processes, co-stimulation, and signal transduction in T lymphocytes (Weiss, Wiskocil and Stobo, 1984; Manger *et al.*, 1986; Abraham and Weiss, 2004). Jurkat E6-1 are lymphoblasts (i.e. expanding T lymphocytes), and have constitutive IL-2 expression which supports their growth and proliferation in culture (Pawelec *et al.*, 1982). The surface phenotype of Jurkat cells has been described as CD3⁺ CD4⁺ CD28⁺ CD11a⁺ CD18⁺ CD2⁺ LFA3⁺ CD45RA⁺ Leu-8 (L-selectin)⁺ and HLA-DR⁻, and they express $\alpha\beta$ TCR, as well as many intracellular components of TCR signalling pathway (Fraser, Newton and Weiss, 1992; Dong, Jackson and Murphy, 1999; Bani *et al.*, 2001; Abraham and Weiss, 2004; Bartelt *et al.*, 2009).

Over the years, some concerns have been raised about how closely the Jurkat cell line paralleled normal human T cells. A genome-wide analysis of Jurkat E6-1 has shown that the cells have damaging mutations in genes that are involved in TCR signalling (*PTEN*, *INPP5D*,

CTLA4, and *SYK*), maintenance of genome stability (*TP53*, *BAX*, and *MSH2*), and O-linked glycosylation (*C1GALT1C1*) (Gioia *et al.*, 2018). Amongst these, mutations of *PTEN* and *INPP5D* (SHIP-1), encoding for lipid phosphatases that regulate phosphoinositide-3 kinase (PI3K) function, lead to several irregularities including constitutive expression of AKT, increased levels of phosphorylated phosphoinositide lipids, and the constitutive association of Itk with the plasma membrane (Shan *et al.*, 2000; Freeburn *et al.*, 2002; Seminario *et al.*, 2004). Dysregulation of PI3K signalling due to loss of PTEN and SHIP-1, as well as abnormal phosphorylation of phospholipase C- γ 1 (PLC- γ) in Jurkats, result in about 7-fold higher TCR-induced Ca^{2+} flux in Jurkat cells than in normal T cells (Bartelt *et al.*, 2009).

Even though some differences in TCR signalling between the Jurkat E6-1 and primary T cells exist, they still make a good model for studying T cell activation, and their exaggerated signalling can be useful for detection of cell responses (Bartelt *et al.*, 2009). Furthermore, many of the findings regarding TCR signalling, initially observed in Jurkat cell lines, have been reproducible in primary T cells (Abraham and Weiss, 2004; Bartelt *et al.*, 2009).

In this study, the activation of Jurkat cells was performed by using mitogens targeting the TCR signalling pathway. The IL-2 production from Jurkat T cells, and expression of other genes such as *IL2RA*, can be greatly enhanced upon stimulation with phorbol esters such as PMA, and phytohaemagglutinin (PHA) (Morgan, Ruscetti and Gallo, 1976; Weiss, Wiskocil and Stobo, 1984; Manger *et al.*, 1986; Lowenthal *et al.*, 1988).

In T cells, TCR engagement leads to PLC γ 1-mediated hydrolysis of membrane inositol phospholipids and subsequent production of inositol phosphates and diacylglycerol (DAG). These two second messengers stimulate, in turn, an elevation in intracellular Ca^{2+} concentration and activation of protein kinase C (PKC), which downstream signalling induces IL-2 production and cell proliferation (Isakov and Altman, 2002). The phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) is a small compound which has a structure analogous to diacylglycerol (DAG), and activates protein kinase C (PKC), hence it is a useful compound used for the activation and IL-2 production in T cells (Isakov and Altman, 2002).

Phytohaemagglutinin (PHA) is a lectin extracted from red kidney bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) which contain agglutinating and mitogenic abilities (Sharon, 2004). PHA contains a family of five isolectins, L₄, L₃E₁, L₂E₂, L₁E₃, and E₄, each being a tetramer built of leukocyte reactive (L)

and erythrocyte reactive (E) polypeptide subunits in all possible combinations (Hamelryck *et al.*, 1996). PHA-L used in the experiments of this thesis, consists of only L-type subunits (i.e. isolectin L₄ or leucoagglutinin) (Hamelryck *et al.*, 1996), and it is especially useful for the induction of activation of T lymphocytes according to documents provided by the manufacturer SigmaAldrich (product number 11249738001). The PHA has shown to bind the TCR-CD3 and induce downstream signalling that leads to T cell activation (Weiss, Wiskocil and Stobo, 1984; Ohtsuka, Kaziro and Satoh, 1996). In addition, it has been shown that the PHA (more specially PHA-P) can also induce T cell activation by binding to CD2 (Tiefenthaler and Hünlg, 1989), which is a co-stimulatory protein in T cells that induces phosphorylation of the TCR-proximal signalling complex (Skånland *et al.*, 2014).

The aim of the experiments described in this chapter was to look at the expression patterns of genes encoding for mechanosensory proteins such as *PIEZO1*, *PKD1* and *PKD2*, which have not been described earlier in Jurkat cells upon activation with PMA and PHA-L. This investigation also provided a template for the regulation of these genes, used as reference in the next chapters when the same cells were to be stimulated mechanically.

There is little knowledge about the roles of polycystin 1 (*PKD1*, PC1) and polycystin 2 (*PKD2*, PC2) in Jurkat or T cells overall. It has been reported that that PC1 and PC2 may control cell proliferation and migration by modulating the ERK, mTOR, NFκB and MIF signalling pathways in T lymphocytes and could contribute to inflammation, as occurs in kidney and endothelial cells (Magistrini *et al.*, 2019). The silencing of *PKD2* in Jurkat cells or mutation of the gene in ADPKD2 T lymphocytes has resulted in strong reduction of ATP-evoked calcium, induction of cell aggregation and activation of cell proliferation (Magistrini *et al.*, 2019). It has also been observed that loss of expression or function of polycystin 1 and/or polycystin 2 has resulted in decreased proliferation of Epstein–Barr virus immortalized lymphoblastoid cells and lymphocyte production (Aguari *et al.*, 2004; Van Laecke *et al.*, 2018). In renal epithelial cells, PC1 and PC2 work to amplify inositol trisphosphate (IP3)-induced Ca²⁺ release (Mekahli *et al.*, 2012), which in T cells is a crucial step in the TCR signalling pathways that leads to downstream activation of calcineurin and NFAT and regulation of *IL-2* expression (Gaud, Lesourne and Love, 2018). In renal cells, PC2 has shown to interact with PIEZO1 through its N-terminus and negatively regulates its stretch sensitivity (Peyronnet *et al.*, 2013; Retailleau and Duprat, 2014).

Even though at the start of the project only the *PKD1* and *PKD2* were investigated, later more focus was given to another mechanosensor called PIEZO1, because studies around 2019 revealed that this channel was important for the optimisation of TCR signalling upon antigen presentation, by regulating Ca^{2+} signalling and subsequent cytoskeletal arrangement in primary CD4^+ and CD8^+ T cells (Liu *et al.*, 2018; Liu and Ganguly, 2019). In T cells, PIEZO1-induced Ca^{2+} influx leads to calpain activation and organization of cortical actin scaffold, optimising TCR signalling and thus T cell activation (Liu *et al.*, 2018). In addition, in transgenic mice, Ca^{2+} signals mediated by Yoda1, an activator of Piezo1 channels, have been involved in TCR activation in naïve T cells, Th17 cells and Treg cells (Dong *et al.*, 2017). PIEZO2 was not chosen for investigation as it has been found not to be expressed in T cells (Liu *et al.*, 2018).

In addition to the experiments looking at the regulation of genes, this study included the investigation of CD4 expression on the surface of unstimulated and PMA-stimulated Jurkat cells. It must be noted that past studies have described CD4 expression on Jurkat E6-1 cells differently, such as detectable (CD4^+) (Dong, Jackson and Murphy, 1999), very low or undetectable (CD4^-) (Bartelt *et al.*, 2009), or simply mentioned as low expression (Roose *et al.*, 2003). The investigation presented in this chapter took place in order to clarify the expression of this protein in the unstimulated and stimulated cell populations and assess whether the Jurkats could be considered as CD4^+ T cell model.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Jurkat E6-1 Growth

Jurkat clone E6-1 (ATCC® TIB-152™) were reconstituted from liquid nitrogen storage and allowed to recover for more than 2 weeks in cultures, splitting every 2-3 days. The culture medium needed for cell growth was composed of RPMI-1640 (ATCC, 30-2001), 10 % Foetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (Gibco, A3160802) and 1% Antibiotic-Antimycotic 100X mix (Gibco, 15240062). The cells were cultured at 37°C, 5% CO₂, until ready for the experiments.

2.2.2. Chemical stimulation experimental set up

In order to chemically stimulate the cells, the growth medium was supplemented with phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) (Sigma-Aldrich, P8139-1MG) and phytohaemagglutinin-L (PHA-L) (Sigma Aldrich, 11249738001). The PMA concentrations varied in different experiments, whereas the PHA-L concentration was 1 µg/mL in all experiments. The control cells were grown in complete growth medium supplemented with DMSO at the corresponding concentrations to the stimulated cells. The Jurkat cells were collected from T75 flasks (25mL suspension) and pelleted by centrifugation at 1500 rpm (300 x g) for 10 minutes. Cells were diluted at the desired concentration, and aliquoted in 6-well plates.

For the first experiment, there were 6 chemically stimulated replicates containing 2.5x10⁵ cells/mL (2mL suspension, 5x10⁵ cells per well), and 6 control replicates of 2.5x10⁵ cells/mL (2mL suspension, 5x10⁵ cells per well). The cells were stimulated with 50 ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L.

For the second experiment the cell number was lowered, with 6 control replicates containing 1.5x10⁵ cells/mL (2mL suspension, 3x10⁵ cells per well) and 6 stimulated replicates containing 1.5x10⁵ cells/mL (2mL suspension, 3x10⁵ cells per well). The cells were stimulated with 50 ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L.

The third experiment had 6 replicates of chemically stimulated cells at a concentration of 1.5x10⁵ cells/mL (3mL suspension, 4.5x10⁵ cells per well) and 6 control replicates of 1.5x10⁵ cells/mL (3mL suspension, 4.5x10⁵ cells per well). The cells were stimulated with 10 ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L.

The fourth experiment had six replicates of chemically stimulated cells at a concentration of 1×10^5 cells/mL (3mL suspension, 3×10^5 cells), and 6 control replicates of 1×10^5 cells/mL (3mL suspension, 3×10^5 cells). The cells were stimulated with 20 ng/mL PMA and $1 \mu\text{g/mL}$ PHA-L.

In all experiments, the cells were incubated at 37°C , 5% CO_2 , 95% air incubator (LEEC, 190D CO_2) for 24 and 48 hours.

2.2.3. RNA extraction

The RNA from Jurkat cells was extracted using the Ribozol-chloroform method for cells in suspension as recommended by the manufacturers (VWR LifeScience, 9508-200 mL). In the fourth experiment, the TRI Reagent (Trizol) was used for RNA isolation (ThermoFisher Scientific, AM9738). The cells were centrifuged at 1400 rpm ($260 \times g$) for 7 minutes to pellet and the supernatant was removed. Then the cells were lysed using 1mL Ribozol/Trizol solution and homogenised using a 25g syringe. The RNA extraction from the lysed cells in Ribozol/Trizol solution was done by separating the aqueous phase after addition of 0.2mL chloroform and centrifugation at 13000 rpm ($17950 \times g$) for 15 minutes at 4°C . The RNA was washed with isopropanol and 75% ethanol and stored in $30 \mu\text{L}$ of nuclease-free water (Gibco, 10977035). Quantification of the RNA in $\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$ was done on Nanodrop 1000, using the RNA nucleic acid programme.

2.2.4. DNase treatment

The DNase treatment was performed following the protocol of DNA-free Kit (Invitrogen, ThermoFisher Scientific, AM1906), in order to degrade any genomic DNA that contaminated the RNA solutions during extraction. Each sample contained up to $5 \mu\text{g}$ RNA per $50 \mu\text{L}$ DNase reaction. Removal of genomic DNA contamination allows efficient detection of amplification during the real-time PCR.

2.2.5. Complementary DNA synthesis

The synthesis of cDNA was done as instructed on the protocol of High-Capacity cDNA Reverse transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems, 4368814). The reaction was comprised of $10 \mu\text{L}$ of 2X RT Mastermix and $10 \mu\text{L}$ of purified RNA solution from the previous step. Reaction was started by warming at 25°C for 10 minutes, followed by incubation at 37°C for 2 hours for the synthesis of the cDNA, and termination of reaction at 85°C for 5 minutes. The newly synthesised cDNA was stored at -20°C until used for PCR reactions.

2.2.6. Real-time polymerase chain reactions

The PCR amplifications were performed in 25 μ L reactions containing 12.5 μ L SYBR Green, 0.5 μ L Forward Primer and 0.5 μ L Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1 μ L of cDNA and topped up to 25 μ L with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035). For experiments 1-3, the SYBR green mastermix that was used was from Applied Biosystems™, catalogue number 4309155, whereas for experiment 4, Power-up SYBR green mastermix was used (Applied Biosystems™, A25742) (Table 2.1).

The collected CT values were used for the $\Delta\Delta C_T$ relative quantification of expression, comparing the stimulated cells to the untreated controls (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001). For the first and second experiments, the ΔC_T was obtained by comparison of C_T values of genes of interest to the C_T of housekeeping gene *TOP1*. For experiment 3, the ΔC_T was obtained by comparison of C_T values of genes of interest to the mean C_T of housekeeping gene *TOP1* and *GAPDH*. For experiment 4, the ΔC_T was obtained by comparison of C_T values of genes of interest to the mean C_T of housekeeping gene *TOP1*, *RPL37A* and *ACTB*. For this experiment, the 24-hour data were also normalised to the mean C_T of housekeeping gene *TOP1*, *RPL37A* and *ACTB* and *GAPDH*, with similar results (Appendix A.3). The $\Delta\Delta C_T$ was the difference of the ΔC_T of each sample to the mean ΔC_T of the control unstimulated cells, separately at 24 and 48 hours. The fold change was calculated using the equation $2^{(-\Delta\Delta C_T)}$ as described in the Livak's method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001).

The primer pair used for the amplification of housekeeper *TOP1* were *TOP1* forward 5'-GACGAATCATGCCCCGAGGAT-3' and *TOP1* reverse 5'-CAGTGTCGCTGTTTCTCCT-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of the housekeeper *ACTB* were *ACTB* forward 5'-ATTGCCGACAGGATGCAGAA-3' and *ACTB* reverse 5'-GCTGATCCACATCTGCTGGAA-3'. The primer sequences for amplification of housekeeper *GAPDH* were *GAPDH* forward 5'-CGAGATCCCTCCAAAATCAA-3' and *GAPDH* reverse 5'-TTCACACCCATGACGAACAT-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of the housekeeper *RPL37A* were *RPL37A* forward 5'-ATTGAAATCAGCCAGCACGC-3' and *RPL37A* reverse 5'-AGGAACCACAGTGCCAGATCC-3'.

The primer sequences for amplification of *IL-2* transcripts in the first experiment run were *IL-2* forward 5'-GAATCCCAAACCTACCAGGATGCTC-3' and *IL-2* reverse 5'-TAGCACTTCTCCAGAGGTTTGAGT-3'. The second primer sequences for amplification of *IL-2*, that were used in the second experiment. were *IL-2''* forward 5'-

AGAACTCAAACCTCTGGAGGAAG-3' and *IL-2* reverse 5'- GCTGTCTCATCAGCATATTCACAC-3'.

The primer sequences for amplification of *IL2RA* were *IL2RA* forward 5'-

GAGACTTCTGCCTCGTCACAA-3' and *IL2RA* reverse 5'-GATCAGCAGGAAAACACAGCCG-3'.

The primer sequences for amplification of *IFNG* were *IFNG* forward 5'-

TCGGTAACTGACTTGAATGTCCA-3', and *IFNG* reverse 5'-TCCTTTTTCGCTTCCCTGTTTT-3'.

The primer pair used for amplification of *PIEZO1* were *PIEZO1* forward 5'-

CATCTTGGTGGTCTCCTCTGTCT-3' and *PIEZO1* reverse 5'-CTGGCATCCACATCCCTCTCATC-3'.

The primer pair used for detection of *PKD1* were *PKD1* forward 5'-

CGCCGCTTCACTAGCTTCGAC-3' and *PKD1* reverse 5'-ACGCTCCAGAGGGAGTCCAC-3'. The

primer pair for amplification of *PKD2* were *PKD2* forward 5'-GCGAGGTCTCTGGGGAAC-3' and

PKD2 reverse 5'-TACACATGGAGCTCATCATGC-3'.

The primer pair used for amplification of *NFAT2* were *NFAT2* forward 5'-

CACTCCTGCTGCCTTACACA-3' and *NFAT2* reverse 5'-AAGATGCGAGCATGCGACTA-3'. The

primer pair used for amplification of *TCF3* were *TCF3* forward 5'-TGACCTCCTGGACTTCAGC-

3' and *TCF3* reverse 5'-ACCTGAACCTCCGAACTGC-3'. The primer pair used for the

amplification of *TCF7L2* were *TCF7L2* forward 5'-CCGGGAAAGTTTGAAGAAG-3' and *TCF7L2*

reverse 5'-ACTGAAAATGGAGGGTTCGG-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *LEF-1*

were *LEF-1* forward 5'-GACAGTGACCTAATGCACGT-3' and *LEF-1* reverse 5'-

CCACCTTCTGCCAAGAATCT-3'.

The primers for *IL-2*, *NFAT2* and *GAPDH* were obtained from Dagna *et al.* (Dagna, Pritchett

and Lusso, 2013). The primers for *ACTB* and *RPL37A* were obtained from Maeß *et al.* (Maeß,

Sendelbach and Lorkowski, 2010). The primers for the amplification of *IL2RA*, and the

second primer pair for amplification of *IL-2* in experiment 4, were purchased from Origene

(Cat. number: HP200397 and HP200553). The primer sequences for *PKD1* and *PKD2* were

obtained from Dalagiorgou *et al.* (Dalagiorgou *et al.*, 2013). Primers amplifying *TCF3*, *TCF7L2*

and *LEF-1* were provided from Dr. Robin Freeburn. Primers amplifying *TOP1* were provided

by Dr. Fiona Menzies and had been designed for the mRNA sequence NM_003286.3.

Primers amplifying *PIEZO1* were designed using the NCBI primer design tool for the mRNA

sequence NM_001142864.4.

The efficiency of primers taken from the literature has been assessed in the corresponding papers mentioned above. Analysis of the melt curve and the T_m was performed for each primer pair, as shown in appendix A.2.1.

Table 2.1: Standard cycling mode (primer $T_m \geq 60^\circ\text{C}$) and dissociation curve parameters for the different SYBR Green master mixes.

Master Mix	Polymerase Chain Reaction				Melt curve			
	Step	Temperature	Duration	Cycles	Step	Ramp rate	Temperature	Time
SYBR Green PCR Master Mix (Applied biosystems 4309155)	Reaction Start-up	95°C	10 minutes	Hold	1	1.6°C/second	95°C	15 seconds
	Denaturation	95°C	15 seconds	x40				
	Anneal/extend	64°C	1 minute					
PowerUp SYBR Green Master Mix (Applied biosystems A25742)	UDG Activation	50°C	2 minutes	Hold	2	1.6°C/second	64°C	1 minute
	Dual-Lock DNA Polymerase	95°C	2 minutes	Hold				
	Denaturation	95°C	15 seconds	x40	3	0.15°C/second	95°C	15 seconds
	Anneal/extend	64°C	1 minute					

2.2.6. Amplicon gel electrophoresis

The amplified PCR products from the first and second experiment were run in 2% agarose gels for the visualisation of the amplicons and determination of fragment lengths in base pairs (bp). This was performed as quality control to assess the specificity of the amplification using the selected primer pairs, in addition to the melt curve analysis. The gels were made of 3.5g of agarose powder (Thermo Scientific, R0492) dissolved in 175 mL 1X TBE, with 1 μL ethidium bromide. The gel was left to solidify for at least 30 minutes, after which the DNA products were added to the wells. The electrophoresis took place at 120V for 45 minutes. Fragment sizes were identified by comparing the travel distance of the amplicons, to the travel distance of fragments from a 100 bp DNA ladder (HyperLadder™ Bioline, 33056).

2.2.7. Statistical analysis of gene expression

The gene expression data were presented as mean of six replicates \pm standard error (SE) of the mean. The statistical difference between the stimulated samples and the control samples for each gene was assessed by unpaired T test analysis with Welch's correction, separately for 24 and 48 hours. Statistical analysis was carried out using GraphPad Prism® version 6. P values <0.05 were accepted as significant.

2.2.8. Surface staining of CD4 and CD3 on Jurkat cells

Three replicates of unstimulated cells and three replicates of stimulated cells with 20 ng/mL PMA were used in this experiment. The cell suspension contained 1×10^6 cells/mL. The Jurkat cells were pelleted by centrifugation at 1200 rpm (191 x g) for 7 minutes. The supernatant was discarded, and cells were resuspended in 1 mL FACS buffer (1X PBS with 2% FBS and 2mM EDTA). The wash step was repeated another time, and the 100 μ L of cells were transferred into sterile FACS tubes. To each tube, 1 μ L of anti-CD3 FITC (Thermofisher scientific, 11-0039-42), and anti-CD4 PE (Thermofisher scientific, 12-0048-42) monoclonal antibodies were added to the cells. The cells were incubated in dark for 30 minutes on ice. After incubation, 1 mL of chilled FACS buffer was added to each tube, and cells were washed three times by centrifugation at 1300 rpm (224 x g) for 8 minutes at 4°C. The supernatant was discarded, and cells resuspended in 500 μ L of FACS buffer. The fluorescence was measured using the BD FACSCalibur apparatus.

2.3. Results

2.3.1. Experiment 1: Regulation of gene expression upon stimulation with 50ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L

Stimulation of Jurkat cells with PMA and PHA-L resulted in upregulation of *IL-2* and *NFAT2* at 24 and 48 hours, compared to the controls. *PKD1* gene expression was found downregulated in stimulated cells at 24 hours, whereas the *PKD2* mRNA transcripts were upregulated in stimulated cells at 24 and 48 hours (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Gene expression upon chemical stimulation of Jurkat cells, experiment 1. Gene expression in stimulated cells was compared to unstimulated controls at 24 hrs (A) and 48 hrs (B). The C_T values were normalised to the housekeeping gene *TOP1*. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE of the mean. Statistical significance was determined by comparing stimulated replicates with the control replicates using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

2.3.2. Experiment 2: Regulation of gene expression upon stimulation with 50ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L, with lowered cell concentration compared to experiment 1

Stimulation of Jurkat cells with PMA and PHA-L resulted in upregulation of *IL-2* and *IL2RA* at 24 and 48 hours, compared to the controls. *NFAT2* gene expression was upregulated at 24 hours and 48 hours. *PKD1* gene expression was comparable to the controls. *PKD2* mRNA transcripts were upregulated in stimulated cells at 24 and 48 hours (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2: Gene expression upon chemical stimulation of Jurkat cells, experiment 2. Gene expression in stimulated cells was compared to unstimulated controls at 24 hrs (A) and 48 hrs (B). The C_T values were normalised to the housekeeping gene *TOP1*. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE of the mean. Statistical significance was determined by comparing stimulated replicates with the control replicates using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

2.3.3. Experiment 3: Regulation of gene expression upon stimulation with 10ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L

Stimulation of Jurkat cells with 10ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L resulted in upregulation of *IL-2* at 24 and 48 hours, compared to the controls (Figure 2.3). Genes encoding for mechanosensors were regulated at 48 hours (Figure 2.3, B). *PKD1* gene expression was downregulated in stimulated cells at 48 hours. *PKD2* mRNA transcripts were upregulated in stimulated cells at 48 hours. *PIEZO1* mRNA transcripts were downregulated in stimulated cells at 48 hours (Figure 2.3, B).

Figure 2.3: Gene expression upon chemical stimulation of Jurkat cells, experiment 3. Gene expression in stimulated cells was compared to unstimulated controls at 24 hrs (A) and 48 hrs (B). The C_T values were normalised to the mean of housekeeping genes *TOP1* and *GAPDH*. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE of the mean. Statistical significance was determined by comparing stimulated replicates with the control replicates using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

2.3.4. Experiment 4: Regulation of gene expression upon stimulation with 20ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L

Stimulation of Jurkat cells with 20 ng/mL PMA and 1 µg/mL PHA-L resulted in upregulation of *IL-2*, *IL2RA*, *IFNG*, *PKD2*, *NFAT2*, *LEF-1*, *TCF7L2* and downregulation of *PIEZO1* and *TCF3* at 24 and 48 hours (Figure 2.4). *PKD1* gene expression was not regulated in stimulated cells at neither time-point.

Figure 2.4: Expression of genes encoding immunological proteins and transcription factors at 24 hours (A, B) and 48 hours (C, D), after stimulation of Jurkat cells with 20ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L. The C_T values were normalised to the mean of housekeeping genes *TOP1*, *RPL37A* and *ACTB*. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE of the mean. Statistical significance was determined by comparing stimulated replicates with the control replicates using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

2.3.5. Summary of mRNA expression results from all experiments

The strong upregulation of *IL-2* and *IL2RA* compared to the other genes may distort the graphic representation of the regulation, especially for the downregulated genes.

Therefore, the expression fold data and the statistical p values for each gene investigated in the above experiments was summarised in Table 2.2.

The results for *IFNG*, *TCF7L2*, *TCF3* and *LEF-1*, investigated in the optimized experiment 4, but not in the previous experiments, are displayed in Table 2.3.

The 24-hour fold expression was also performed relative to the mean of housekeeping genes *TOP1*, *ACTB*, *RPL37A* and *GAPDH*, and another time by using the mean of *ACTB*, *RPL37A* and *GAPDH*. The results showed the same patterns of regulation, with only slight differences on the fold expression and p values. The data comparison is shown in Table A.3.1. in the appendix A.3.

Table 2.2: Fold expression of genes of interest upon stimulation of Jurkat cells with PMA and PHA-L in different experiments. Table shows the regulation patterns and the statistical comparison between the stimulated and control replicates (N=6). Statistical different was assessed by T test with Welch's correction.

Experiment	Treatment	Fold expression and statistical difference											
		<i>IL-2</i>		<i>IL2RA</i>		<i>NFAT2</i>		<i>PKD1</i>		<i>PKD2</i>		<i>PIEZO1</i>	
		24hrs	48hrs	24hrs	48hrs	24hrs	48hrs	24hrs	48hrs	24hrs	48hrs	24hrs	48hrs
Experiment 1	50ng/mL PMA +1µg/mL PHA vs Untreated	32.33 (p****= 0.0001) ↑	18.77 (p****< 0.0001) ↑	Not assessed	Not assessed	2.97 (p****= 0.0001) ↑	1.31 (p**= 0.002) ↑	0.67 (p**= 0.002) ↓	0.81 (p= 0.053)	1.70 (p*= 0.022) ↑	2.12 (p****< 0.0001) ↑	Not assessed	Not assessed
Experiment 2	50ng/mL PMA +1µg/mL PHA vs Untreated	65.16 (p****= 0.0001) ↑	48.28 (p****= 0.0004) ↑	1066.37 (p****< 0.0001) ↑	18.74 (p****= 0.0001) ↑	3.76 (p****< 0.0001) ↑	1.44 (p*= 0.015) ↑	1.22 (p= 0.343)	0.92 (p= 0.416)	1.75 (p**= 0.003) ↑	1.97 (p**= 0.0013) ↑	Not assessed	Not assessed
Experiment 3	10ng/mL PMA +1µg/mL PHA vs Untreated	22.32 (p****= 0.0007) ↑	84.19 (p****< 0.0001) ↑	Not assessed	Not assessed	Not assessed	Not assessed	1.19 (p= 0.87)	0.57 (p**= 0.009) ↓	1.33 (p= 0.22)	2.22 (p****= 0.0004) ↑	1.11 (p= 0.89)	0.67 (p**= 0.003) ↓
Experiment 4	20ng/mL PMA +1µg/mL PHA vs Untreated	143.39 (p****= 0.0007) ↑	24.6 (p****< 0.0001) ↑	1233.0 (p****< 0.0001) ↑	344.4 (p****< 0.0001) ↑	4.19 (p****< 0.0001) ↑	2.74 (p****< 0.0001) ↑	0.91 (p= 0.1431)	0.99 (p= 0.7668)	1.18 (p*= 0.0185) ↑	1.33 (p****= 0.0001) ↑	0.58 (p****< 0.0001) ↓	0.74 (p****= 0.0008) ↓

Table 2.3: Fold expression of *IFNG*, *LEF-1*, *TCF7L2* and *TCF3*, and statistical comparison between the stimulated and control replicates (N=6). The expression is relative to the housekeeping genes *TOP1*, *ACTB* and *RPL37A*. Statistical different was assessed by T test with Welch's correction.

Target mRNA	Fold expression: Experiment 4							
	24 hours				48 Hours			
	Control	Stimulated	P value	Statistically different?	Control	Stimulated	P value	Statistically different?
<i>IFNG</i>	1.05	5.67	0.0034	Yes (**)	1.09	4.19	0.0094	Yes (**)
<i>LEF-1</i>	1.00	1.73	0.0085	Yes (**)	1.00	1.87	< 0.0001	Yes (****)
<i>TCF7L2</i>	1.01	1.70	< 0.0001	Yes (****)	1.00	1.72	< 0.0001	Yes (****)
<i>TCF3</i>	1.00	0.67	< 0.0001	Yes (****)	1.01	0.66	0.004	Yes (**)

2.3.5. Expression of CD3 and CD4 in unstimulated and stimulated Jurkat cells

In unstimulated cells at 24 hours, the CD3 was detected in 84.4% of the Jurkat population, while the CD4 was detected in 56.26% of the population (Figure 2.5, C). The cells marked for both CD3 and CD4 accounted for 48.6% of the population, those marked for CD4 but not CD3 accounted for 7.44% of population, while cells marked for CD3 but not CD4 accounted for 35.8% of the population. About 7.9% of the population was negative for both CD3 and CD4.

In cells stimulated with 20 ng/mL PMA for 24 hours, the CD4 was not detectable (Figure 2.5, F). The cells expressing CD3 accounted for 63.4% of the stimulated Jurkat population. The cells negative for both the CD3 and CD4 accounted for 36.5% of the stimulated population (Figure 2.5, F).

Figure 2.5: Expression of CD3 and CD4 in unstimulated and PMA stimulated Jurkats at 24 hours. The scatter plots for unstimulated cells (A) and 20 ng/mL PMA stimulated cells (D), depict the lymphocyte populations. The B and E plots depict the area of unlabelled Jurkat cells. The detection of CD3 and CD4 in unstimulated cells (C), and in PMA stimulated cells (F) at 24 hours. The anti-CD3 antibody was conjugated with FITC and was detected using FL1, whereas anti-CD4 antibody was conjugated with PE and was detected using FL2.

2.4. Discussion

2.4.1. The regulation of cytokine and mechanosensor encoding genes upon stimulation with PMA and PHA-L.

Different experiments showed reproducible result for the regulation of genes of interest in Jurkat E6-1 cells stimulated with the mitogens PMA and PHA-L. The mRNA for *IL-2* and *IL2RA* were upregulated at 24 and 48 hours, as it was expected upon stimulation (Table 2.2). As lymphoblasts, unstimulated Jurkats express *IL-2* and the *IL2RA* which are needed for the maintenance of T cell clones (Pawelec *et al.*, 1982; Liao, Lin and Leonard, 2013). The *IL-2* and *IL2RA* mRNA upregulation at 24 and 48 hours confirmed that the activation of PKC by PMA and crosslinking of CD3 by PHA-L resulted in the activation and expansion of Jurkat T cells. In addition, activated Jurkat cells upregulated *IFNG* mRNA upon activation at 24 and 48 hours compared to the unstimulated controls (Table 2.3). The *IFNG* expression in the unstimulated cells showed that this cytokine is also inherently produced in Jurkat E6-1.

The *IL-2* and *IL2RA* were upregulated strongly in Jurkats at 24 hours, whereas at 48 hours the mRNA for these genes was not strongly upregulated for stimulation with 20 and 50 ng/mL PMA and 1 µg/mL PHA-L (Table 2.2). At the time, it was thought that the high starting cell concentration or the strong stimulation was causing a decline of clones at 48 hours after an initial strong response at 24 hours, resulting in lower mRNA levels for these genes. However, the results showed that changing the starting cell concentration had little effect on the mRNA transcripts of *IL-2* and *IL-2RA* upon stimulation (Table 2.2). Later, after reviewing bibliography, it was found that the *IL-2* and *IL2RA* synthesis and production in T cells follow a pattern of high upregulation between 12 and 24 hours, and lower expression between 24 and 48 hours (Cantrell and Smith, 1983, Abbas, Lichtman and Pillai, 2018,p218). Therefore, in the activated T cells, the lowered *IL-2* and *IL2RA* mRNA at 48 hours compared to the 24 hours was a physiological response (Table 2.2).

Interesting results were obtained for the genes encoding mechanosensors *PIEZO1*, polycystin 1 (*PKD1*) and polycystin 2 (*PKD2*) (Table 2.2).

The mRNA transcripts of *PIEZO1* were found downregulated in stimulated cells. Jurkat cells stimulated with 10 ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L downregulated *PIEZO1* at 48 hours, whereas the cells stimulated with 20ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L downregulated *PIEZO1*

at both 24 and 48 hours, showing that strengthening the stimulation resulted in earlier regulation of this gene (Table 2.2).

The mRNA transcripts for *PKD1* were found downregulated for the stimulation with 50 ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L at 24 hours in the first experiment, but no regulation was observed in the second experiment. The stimulation with 10 ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L also downregulated *PKD1* at 48 hours compared to the control cells. However, no regulation was recorded at neither time-point for the stimulation with 20 ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L. The downregulation pattern of *PKD1* was reproduced in 2 out of 4 experiments, but the time-point of regulation was differing. The other changing parameter in the experiments had been the cell number per volume suspension, which speculatively could have some effect on the expression of *PKD1* mRNA, because PC1 has shown to be involved in cell-cell contact through its cluster of Ig-like repeats (Ibraghimov-Beskrovnaya, 2000).

The mRNA for *PKD2* was upregulated at 24 and 48 hours for stimulations with 20 and 50 ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L. For the stimulation with 10 ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L, *PKD2* was not upregulated at 24 hours, showing that this stimulation is weaker and induces gene regulation at 48 hours only. The *PKD2* was upregulated in all experiments, which demonstrated that the regulation of this gene is important during the activation of Jurkat cells with PMA and PHA-L (Table 2.2).

The above results showed that these mechanosensor-encoding genes were regulatable upon the activation of the Jurkat cells, and their products may be involved during or after the initial activation process. Indeed, even though not known at the time when these experiments were performed, it has been demonstrated that PIEZO1 is involved in T cell activation by optimising the TCR signalling, regulating Ca²⁺ signalling, and inducing cytoskeletal rearrangements which stabilise the immune synapse (Liu *et al.*, 2018; Liu and Ganguly, 2019). The experiments have shown PIEZO1 to be important in earlier stages of CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cell activation (Liu *et al.*, 2018). The downregulation of *PIEZO1* could be because the mechanosensory channel loses the importance in latter stages of activation or that the downregulation of mRNA and/or protein is done to stabilise signalling.

Polycystins have shown to affect the proliferation of T cells, as loss of expression or function of polycystin 1 and/or polycystin 2 has shown to decrease proliferation of EBV immortalized

lymphoblastoid cells, which would result in decreased lymphocyte production (Aguiari *et al.*, 2004; Van Laecke *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, kidney disease resulting from mutation of *PKD1* gene has shown to also be characterised by lymphopenia (Van Laecke *et al.*, 2018). The downregulation of *PKD1* could also be related to latter stages of activation that regulate differentiation and lower proliferation capacity. For example, in haematopoietic cell lines K562 and HL60, the PC1 downregulation in response to PMA stimulation has been associated with the differentiation of cells (Aguiari *et al.*, 1998). The *PKD1* was the only gene not having a reproducible pattern of regulation in the four experiments, and further experiments to assess its expression at protein levels were performed in chapter 6.

The silencing of *PKD2* in Jurkat cells or mutation of the gene in ADPKD2 T cells has shown to strongly reduce ATP-evoked calcium, and induce cell aggregation and proliferation (Magistrini *et al.*, 2019).

The upregulation of *PKD2* at 48 hours could be also related to later activation processes that result in differentiation of cells, or maintenance of cell proliferation. The regulation patterns of *PIEZO1* and *PKD2*, could be necessary for the modulation of Ca²⁺ signalling in the Jurkat cells during the activation, as observed in primary T cells and other tissues (Mekahli *et al.*, 2012; Liu *et al.*, 2018; Magistrini *et al.*, 2019).

The regulation of these genes can also be indicative of changes in mechanosensation in different stages of T cell activation. This is more clear in the case of *PIEZO1*, which is needed for mechanosensation in early T cell activation events such as antigen presentation and immune synapse stabilisation (Liu and Ganguly, 2019).

In addition, it must be noted that the patterns of regulation of these genes may be affected by the cancerous nature of the Jurkat cells. For example, PC1 has been considered a weak onco-suppressor (Zheng *et al.*, 2008), and its signalling and expression, as well as those of PC2 and *PIEZO1*, may be dysregulated in Jurkat cells due to mutations or exaggerated signalling compared to the primary T cells (Bartelt *et al.*, 2009). This thought was tested in the work presented in the following chapter, in primary T cells extracted from healthy PBMCs and stimulated with the same mitogens.

2.4.2. Transcription factor expression

The NFAT2 is part of the calcineurin-NFAT pathway, which is activated by Ca²⁺ release from TCR signalling (Hogan, 2003; Macian, 2005). The *NFAT2* mRNA was upregulated in different experiments, and at both 24 and 48 hours for the stimulation with 50 and 20 ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L (Table 2.2). The regulation of this gene indicated activation and upregulated Ca²⁺ signalling, which may increase the demand for encoding this transcription factor (Hogan, 2003).

The other two transcription factor genes investigated included *LEF-1* and *TCF7L2*, in the experiment 4. The mRNA for these transcription factors were found upregulated in stimulated cells at both 24 and 48 hours (Table 2.3). Upon WNT signalling, the *LEF-1* and *TCF7L2* can be regulated, and their products act as activators or repressors of genes, depending on the tissues considered (Cadigan and Waterman, 2012; Hrckulak *et al.*, 2016). The upregulation could be indicative of involvement of WNT signalling in Jurkat cell activation, influencing cell proliferation and survival of clones (Cadigan and Waterman, 2012).

The expression of these genes in Jurkats was investigated for comparison with the regulation patterns in activated primary T cells in the next chapter.

2.4.3. The CD4 expression of the surface of Jurkat cells

The Jurkat E6-1 cells have been considered as CD4⁺ cells, however the expression of this marker is described differently in different publications as mentioned in the introduction. For this reason, it was important to measure CD4 expression in Jurkats and assess whether they could be considered as a CD4⁺ T cell model. The CD4 was detected in half of the unstimulated Jurkat population, whereas in stimulated cells with PMA for 24 hours, the CD4 became undetectable. It has been shown that PMA induces a rapid downregulation of CD4 from the surface of T cells and lymphocytic cell lines, as well as from CD4-transfected nonlymphoid cells by increasing endocytosis and altering intracellular trafficking (Pelchen-Matthews, Parsons and Marsh, 1993). Overall, antigen presentation, or cross-linking antibodies against CD4, the CD3 complex, or CD2 can induce a reduction in cell surface CD4 expression (Pelchen-Matthews, Parsons and Marsh, 1993).

The uneven expression of the CD4 could be influenced by the state of activation that the Jurkat cells have. As lymphoblast, having activated TCR pathways and constitutive IL-2 expression, Jurkat cells can be considered weakly activated (Pawelec *et al.*, 1982; Bartelt *et al.*, 2009), but may be at different levels of activation within the unstimulated population, probably affected by paracrine IL-2 signalling (Bismuth *et al.*, 1985; Kim, Imbert and Leonard, 2006; Liao, Lin and Leonard, 2013; Ross and Cantrell, 2018). When PMA was used to stimulate the cells, the CD4 was downregulated in the whole population, probably as a result of cells getting uniformly activated by the stimulation (Figure 2.5).

Overall, it could be that the CD4⁻ cells in the unstimulated population were in a different stage of constitutive activation than the rest of the cells, but the possibility that the CD4 expression is ectopic in Jurkat cells remains. Whether the CD4⁻ cells have higher proliferation rate, or whether the marker is still expressed after many passages is interesting and can be investigated further, but it was irrelevant to this project and it was not further experimented. Furthermore, future investigation involving flow cytometry analysis should include an apoptotic marker such as annexin V or cell death marker like propidium iodide, to explain the cells that were CD3⁻CD4⁺ and CD4⁻CD3⁻, which could be apoptotic or dying cells.

Perhaps the most important outcome of the investigation of CD4 expression in the unstimulated population was that it showed some heterogeneity regarding expression of cell markers, which was to be taken under consideration in the following experiments and interpretation of their results. When testing new techniques such as “nanokicking” presented in the following chapters, that is not known to have any effect on the Jurkat cells, uneven expression of a marker in the unstimulated population can be problematic. For example, in the event when “nanokick” stimulation would not have any effect on Jurkat cells, but by chance significantly more CD4⁺ cells were placed in the control samples than in the experimental samples, when looking at mRNA or protein levels, it would seem that the experimental samples have downregulated CD4. That can give the wrong interpretation that the technique is working, but the seemingly downregulated pattern in this example was not as result of the stimulation but rather differences in distribution of CD4 positive or negative cells.

To avoid such scenarios, the assessment of reproducibility and the use of positive controls were deemed crucial in determining whether the Jurkat cells and others would respond to the 1000Hz “nanokick” stimulation.

2.4.3. Conclusion

The observations from the experiments presented above were useful for the work in the following chapters, which investigated the gene expression in primary cells upon activation, and Jurkat cell responses to the vibrational mechanical stimulation. One aspect that was chosen as crucial when investigating gene regulation patterns was the reproducibility of results between experimental runs, which would indicate that the patterns of regulation toward chemical or mechanical stimulation were as observed.

The genes encoding mechanosensors *PIEZO1* and *PKD2* were regulated upon stimulation with PMA and PHA-L. Their mRNA regulation patterns have not been described before, and the above experiments revealed that these genes were regulatable upon activation of Jurkat cells, and that their products may be needed at different stages of T cell activation.

Furthermore, upregulated expression of transcription factors involved in Ca²⁺ signalling such as *NFAT2*, and WNT pathway such as *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1*, indicated activation and proliferation and acted as template for comparison with the primary T cells in the following chapter.

In addition to the gene regulation patterns, the CD4 expression on the surface of cells was investigated as a side experiment. Based on the results showing CD4 expression in only half of the unstimulated population, and past papers (Dong, Jackson and Murphy, 1999; Bartelt *et al.*, 2009), the status of Jurkat cells as CD4⁺ cells should be considered with caution. The lymphoblast status is undoubtedly more suitable for Jurkats, which expand actively and have constitutive IL-2 production and activated TCR signalling (Pawelec *et al.*, 1982; Bartelt *et al.*, 2009). The activation of T cells through TCR signalling is similar in CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells, and the CD4 and CD8 main function is the targeted delivery of LCK to the relevant TCR-CD3 complex (Artyomov *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, Jurkat E6-1 cells can provide a model for the activation of both CD4 and CD8 cells, as they have been historically utilised (Abraham and Weiss, 2004).

Chapter 3

PIEZO1 mRNA transcripts downregulate upon activation and early differentiation of CD8⁺ T cells

Abstract

While many cells such as CD4⁺ T cells, plasmacytoid dendritic cells, Natural Killer cells and B cells are involved in autoimmune responses in alopecia areata, the CD8⁺ T cells are considered the main contributors to the disease phenotype and are necessary and sufficient to cause the hair loss. The work presented on this chapter was done in accordance with the requirements of the project about studying the mechanobiology of the immune cells in relation to alopecia areata. Based on the results from Jurkat cells presented in the previous chapter, there was a pattern of regulation for the genes encoding mechanosensors upon chemical activation of cells. In addition, published studies have shown that mechanosensor PIEZO1 is involved in the regulation of the activation process in T cells and is necessary for the mechanosensation that occurs during antigen presentation. The work presented in this chapter is comprised of one optimisation experiment and one main experiment which looked at the expression patterns of genes encoding for cytokines, effector proteins, cell surface markers, mechanosensors and transcription factors in activated CD8⁺ T cells.

3.1. Introduction

The CD8⁺ T cells are involved in immune responses that provide protection against intracellular pathogens and tumour cells (Zhang and Bevan, 2011; Farhood, Najafi and Mortezaee, 2019). In addition to these protective roles, the CD8⁺ T cells can also contribute to the initiation, progression and regulation of autoimmune responses in different autoimmune pathologies (Walter and Santamaria, 2005). In autoimmune alopecia areata, the CD8⁺ T cells, more specifically CD8⁺NKG2D⁺ T cells, have been identified as major contributors of hair loss and are the first to infiltrate around the hair follicles (Gilhar, Etzioni and Paus, 2012; Xing *et al.*, 2014; Pratt *et al.*, 2017; de Jong *et al.*, 2018). These cells are necessary and sufficient for the induction of the disease in mouse models (Xing *et al.*, 2014; Pratt *et al.*, 2017). The CD8⁺ T cells target hair follicle cells which present autoantigens on MHC class I, and their effector responses result in the premature termination of the anagen phase and hair loss in the alopecia areata patients (Simakou *et al.*, 2019).

The activation of CD8⁺ T cells results in clonal expansion and differentiation into effector or memory phenotypes, and it is a necessary first step in immune responses involving these cells (Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011). This process is characterised by expression of certain genes that are needed for the clonal expansion, effector proteins and transcription factors (Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011). Below is an introductory description about the roles that the protein products of genes that were investigated in this study have in CD8⁺ T cells.

3.1.1 Cytokines, receptors, and transcription factors used for assessment of CD8⁺ T cell activation and effector differentiation

Interleukin 2 (IL-2) is expressed upon T cell activation and it is needed for the clonal expansion as well as differentiation of T cells (Liao, Lin and Leonard, 2013). In CD8⁺ T cells, the IL-2 has roles in generation of effector and memory cytotoxic cells by regulation of genes and transcription factors that determine the cell phenotypes (Pipkin *et al.*, 2010). It has also been shown that persistent IL-2 signalling promotes effector phenotype at the expense of memory CTL development (Pipkin *et al.*, 2010). However, during an immune response the CD4⁺ T cells are the principle producers of IL-2 and cooperate with CD8⁺ T cells to promote the initial expansion of the response as well as the formation of durable memory cells that can elicit protective secondary responses (Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011). In addition to the IL-2 signalling, the CD8⁺ T cell differentiation into effector or memory phenotypes is determined by a combination of IL-2 signalling with other cytokines such as IL-12, IL-21 and IL-15 (Mitchell, Ravkov and Williams, 2010; Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011).

IL-2 signals in T cells through the high affinity IL-2 receptor comprised of IL2RA (CD25), IL2RB (CD122) and the gamma chain (γ_c) (Liao, Lin and Leonard, 2013; Ross and Cantrell, 2018). The IL2RA is not constitutively expressed but it is upregulated upon the activation of T cells and clonal expansion, making it a marker of cell activation and proliferation (Leonard *et al.*, 1985; Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011; Pekalski *et al.*, 2013). The IL-2 and IL-12 can also influence the expression of IL2RA in CD8⁺ T cells (Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011).

Interferon gamma (IFN- γ) is a cytokine produced from effector CD8⁺ T cells (Pipkin *et al.*, 2010; Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011). IFN- γ , together with perforin and granzymes are induced at the transcriptional level after activation upon infections, but most, if not all, antigen-specific CD8⁺ T cells express IFN- γ and granzyme B, whereas only a fraction of these

express perforin, and IFN- γ expression does not necessarily correlate with cytolytic activity (Johnson *et al.*, 2003; Peixoto *et al.*, 2007; Zaiss, Sijts and Mosmann, 2008; Pipkin *et al.*, 2010). The IFN- γ , produced from the autoreactive CD8⁺NKG2D⁺ T cells, is considered as the main cytokine which drives the pathogenesis of alopecia areata, by collapsing the immune privilege of the hair follicles and interfering with the hair growth cycle and stem cell regeneration (reviewed in Simakou *et al.*, 2019). IFN- γ is produced from CD8⁺ T cells upon stimulation with mitogens like PMA and PHA (Li *et al.*, 1995), which in this study were used in combination to activate these cells. In addition, protein kinase C (PKC) activation by PMA has shown to stabilise the mRNA transcripts and increase IFN- γ production in CD8⁺ T cells (Kaldy and Schmitt-Verhulst, 1995).

Granzyme B (GZMB) is a cytolytic serine protease which is utilised by the cytotoxic CD8⁺ T cells to eliminate virus-infected cells or tumour cells by induction of apoptosis (Bots and Medema, 2006). The GZMB is another effector protein of CD8⁺ T cells, and its expression has shown to be influenced by the IL-2 signalling (Pipkin *et al.*, 2010; Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011). In addition, while IFN- γ can be detected in a CD8⁺ T cell population containing resting memory cells, the GZMB has shown to be detected only in activated effector CD8⁺ T cells, distinguishing the cells that have gone recent activation or reactivation (Nowacki *et al.*, 2007).

The nuclear factor of activated T cells-2 (NFAT2 or NFATc1) is part of the calcineurin-NFAT pathway which is an important pathway involved in the activation of T cells and IL-2 expression (Macian, 2005; Gaud, Lesourne and Love, 2018). The NFAT2 has shown to control the effector function of murine CD8⁺ T cells by induction of expression of genes such as *Tbx21* encoding for a key transcription factor of effector CD8⁺ T cells, *Gzmb* encoding the cytolytic enzyme granzyme B, as well as many genes encoding for glycolytic proteins (Klein-Hessling *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, upon activation of cytotoxic CD8⁺ T cells, the NFAT2 has shown to regulate apical F-actin, recruitment of lytic granules and mitochondria to the immune synapse, and induction of numerous cytokine genes such as *Il2*, *Ifng* and *Il3*, and the chemokine genes *Ccl3*, *Ccl4*, and *Xcl1* (Klein-Hessling *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, in acute viral infection, NFAT2 has shown to be necessary for the differentiation of memory CD8⁺ T cells (Xu, Keller and Martinez, 2019).

In addition to the roles that the NFAT transcription factors have on T cell activation, they have also shown to regulate CD8⁺ T cell exhaustion (i.e. persistent antigen stimulation results in CD8⁺ T cells having a gradual decrease in effector functions), by induction of a transcriptional program that encodes for inhibitory surface receptors such as PD-1 and TIM3 (Martinez *et al.*, 2015). In addition, transcriptional profiling of exhausted *ex vivo* murine CD8⁺ T cells has shown higher expression of mRNA encoding NFAT2, compared to naïve, effector, and memory T cell subsets (Wherry *et al.*, 2007). The different roles of this transcription factor in CD8⁺ T cells might be attributed to different NFAT2 gene products: NFATc1/αA which is highly expressed in activated T cells and supports the effector function of lymphocytes, including glycolysis, and NFATc1/βC which is mainly expressed in resting T cells and supports the induction of tolerance and exhaustion of lymphocytes (Klein-Hessling *et al.*, 2017).

Another gene investigated in this chapter is transcription factor 3 (*TCF3*), encoding for a protein called E2A and two isoforms E12 and E47, belonging to a group of helix-loop-helix proteins known as E proteins (Murre, 2005). The E proteins have shown to be important in lymphocyte development and differentiation, and E2A cooperates with Notch signalling to promote T cell lineage commitment in haematopoietic progenitors (Murre, 2005; Ikawa *et al.*, 2006). In thymocytes the E proteins E2A and HEB, have shown to maintain the cells in double positive CD4⁺CD8⁺ stage, allowing transition to single positive cells after the αβTCR is produced (Jones and Zhuang, 2007).

The E2A has roles in mature CD8⁺ T cells as well. In infected mouse models, the E2A has shown to influence the response of CD8⁺ T cells towards the infection (D'Cruz *et al.*, 2012). E protein expression in early stages of infection has shown to be upregulated by CD8⁺ T cells (D'Cruz *et al.*, 2012). Deficiency in the E proteins E2A and HEB, has resulted in increased frequency of terminally differentiated effector KLRG1^{hi} CD8⁺ T cells in mice during infection, and decreased generation of longer-lived memory precursor cells during the immune response (D'Cruz *et al.*, 2012). Similarly, it has been shown that inhibition of E2A by the transcription factor inhibitor of DNA binding Id2 results in repression of memory CD8⁺ T cell differentiation (Masson *et al.*, 2013). The inhibition of E2A from the Id2 impairs CD8⁺ T cell memory differentiation by inhibiting E2A-mediated expression of *Tcf7* (TCF1) (Masson *et al.*, 2013).

Another study in mice which has looked into the epigenetic landscapes that regulate CD8⁺ T cell differentiation, has shown that terminal-effector CD8⁺ T cells have depletion of binding motifs (i.e. genomic sequences that specifically bind to transcription factors) for TCF-1, LEF-1 and E2A, whereas naïve, memory-precursor and memory CD8⁺ T cells have shown enrichment for these motifs, which has corresponded with the well-characterized roles of these transcription factors in regulating the differentiation of memory populations (Yu *et al.*, 2017).

The LEF1, alongside TCF1, has shown to be important for the CD8⁺ identity in double positive (DP) CD4⁺CD8⁺ thymocytes (Xing *et al.*, 2016). Even though these transcription factors are not required for DP thymocytes to choose the CD8⁺ fate, LEF-1 and TCF1 have shown to be essential for establishing CD8⁺ T cell identity by repressing the CD4⁺ T cell program using intrinsic histone deacetylase (HDAC) activity embedded within the two factors (Xing *et al.*, 2016). The roles of LEF-1 are not limited in thymocytes only. For example, human naïve CD8⁺ T Cells have shown to downregulate LEF-1 following activation *in vitro* and *in vivo*, linking this transcription factor with the activation and proliferation process of these cells (Kaech *et al.*, 2002; Willinger *et al.*, 2006). In addition, LEF-1 and TCF1 have both shown to be involved in the differentiation of naïve CD8⁺ T cells to effector and memory phenotypes (Xue and Zhao, 2012).

Another transcription factor of the WNT pathway investigated in this study was the TCF7L2, encoding for a product known as T cell factor-4 (TCF4) (Hrckulak *et al.*, 2016). This gene has been shown to belong in the gene expression signature of activated and expanding CD8⁺ T cells in acute EBV infection, with potential roles in differentiation into memory phenotypes (Greenough *et al.*, 2015). In another study involving mature CD8⁺ T cells, the TCF4 has shown to be involved in downstream β -catenin signalling which mediates expression of CD4 and produces a CD4^{dim}CD8^{bright} T cell phenotype (Schenkel *et al.*, 2010).

And finally, the investigation included genes which encode cell surface molecules IL-7 receptor (IL-7Ra, *IL7R*) and killer cell lectin-like receptor G1 (KLRG1), which are used to identify CD8⁺ memory T cell precursors among the effector population. IL7R is also a marker of resting T cells (Szabo *et al.*, 2019). Short-lived effector cells (TSLEC) express high levels of KLRG1 and low levels of IL-7Ra, whereas memory precursor cells express low levels of KLRG1 and high levels of IL-7Ra (Kaech *et al.*, 2003; Mitchell, Ravkov and Williams, 2010).

Effector cells with high IL7R expression have shown to contain increased amounts of antiapoptotic molecules, and preferentially give rise to memory cells that could persist and confer protective immunity, compared to the effector cells with low IL7R expression (Kaech *et al.*, 2003). Thus, expression of IL7R can also identify memory cell precursors (Kaech *et al.*, 2003).

In addition, transcript analysis in TEM and TCM cells, has shown higher expression of *Ii7r* and *Tcf7* in TCM cells (Arsenio *et al.*, 2014). The products of these genes which encode regulators of T lymphocyte survival and longevity, may underlie the superior ability of TCM cells to persist *in vivo* (Arsenio *et al.*, 2014).

The KLRG1 is a natural killer cell receptor expressed by T cells that exhibit impaired proliferative capacity (Voehringer, Koschella and Pircher, 2002; Thimme *et al.*, 2005). It has been shown that that expression of KLRG1 by virus-specific CD8⁺ T cells in humans and mice is induced by repetitive antigen stimulation (Thimme *et al.*, 2005).

In addition, it has been demonstrated that KLRG1⁺ effector CD8⁺ T cells display developmental plasticity, as they were able to downregulate KLRG1 and to efficiently differentiate into all memory T cell lineages (Herndler-Brandstetter *et al.*, 2018). Such plasticity has been considered a driving force in generating phenotypic and functional diversity within TCM, TEM, and TRM cells (Herndler-Brandstetter *et al.*, 2018).

3.1.2. The involvement of mechanosensors in the activation of CD8⁺ T cells

Mechanosensor PIEZO1 has shown to play important roles in the activation of T cells (Liu and Ganguly, 2019). In CD8⁺ T cells, the mechanosensor is involved in mechanosensation during antigen presentation, which optimises their activation process. In these cells, PIEZO1 has shown to potentiate TCR activation upon binding antibodies, and induce Ca²⁺ influx which causes the necessary cytoskeletal rearrangements needed for optimal TCR signalling during antigen presentation (Liu *et al.*, 2018; Liu and Ganguly, 2019). The regulation of *PIEZO1* mRNA upon activation of CD8⁺ T cells has not been reported.

The roles of polycystin 1 (*PKD1*, PC1) and polycystin 2 (*PKD2*, PC2) are not known in CD8⁺ T cells. It has been observed that loss of expression or function of polycystins has resulted in decreased proliferation of EBV-immortalized lymphoblastoid cells and lymphocyte production (Aguiari *et al.*, 2004; Van Laecke *et al.*, 2018). In renal epithelial cells, PC1 and

PC2 work to amplify IP3-induced Ca²⁺ release (Mekahli *et al.*, 2012), which in T cells is a crucial step in the TCR signalling pathways that leads to downstream activation of calcineurin and NFAT and regulation of *IL-2* expression (Gaud, Lesourne and Love, 2018). Similar to PIEZO1, PC1 and PC2 have shown to influence cell responses by regulation of Ca²⁺ signalling (Mekahli *et al.*, 2013; Liu *et al.*, 2018).

3.1.3. The aim of the experiments

The aim of the experiments in this chapter was to investigate the expression of multiple genes encoding for activation markers, mechanosensors and transcription factors, upon activation of primary CD8⁺ T cells extracted from the blood of a healthy donor. The focus of the experiments was directed at the expression patterns of genes encoding for mechanosensors such as PIEZO1, which recently has shown to be a crucial protein involved in the activation of T cells (Liu *et al.*, 2018; Liu and Ganguly, 2019). The fact that mechanosensors are involved in CD8⁺ T cell activation by optimising TCR signalling (Liu and Ganguly, 2019), shows how important the mechanosensation is for this process.

Manipulation of mechanosensor expression can be therapeutic for autoimmune conditions such as alopecia areata, and in this study the expression patterns of the genes which encode such proteins were investigated upon activation of healthy CD8⁺ T cells by the mitogens PMA and PHA-L.

3.2. Methods

3.2.1. Isolation of PBMCs from full blood

The PBMCs were collected from blood of healthy donors. The blood was obtained from the cell bank at the University of Glasgow (donor ID numbers 2803/20 and 2823/20). The blood, histopaque (Sigma-Aldrich, 10771) and PBS (Gibco, 10010015) were allowed to come to room temperature. The blood was then collected into 50mL tubes and diluted with equal volumes of PBS. In sterile 15mL tubes, 4mL of histopaque were aliquoted and blood was added on top using a pastette. This was followed by centrifugation at 2100 rpm (828 x g) for 25 minutes, without brake and at room temperature, in order to separate the PBMCs from the red blood cells. After the separation, the PBMCs were collected using a pastette and transferred on 30mL PBS in a 50mL tube. The cells were washed by centrifugation at 400 x g for 10 minutes at 4°C. The supernatant was discarded, and cells were transferred to a 15mL tube for another wash with PBS by centrifugation at 200 x g for 10 minutes at 4°C. After that, the cells were suspended in 1mL PBS and counted using a haemocytometer. For the cells count, a small amount of the PBMC stock were diluted in Trypan blue (Sigma-Aldrich, T8154) to exclude dead cells.

3.2.2. CD8⁺ T cells isolation from PBMC

The CD8⁺ T cells were isolated from PBMCs by negative selection using the MojoSort kit (BioLegend, 480011). The PBMCs were washed in RPMI 1640 (Gibco, 31870025) by centrifugation at 200g for 10 minutes at 4°C. They were suspended in RPMI 1640 in a FACS tube at a concentration between 1×10^7 and 1×10^8 cells/mL, depending on the amount of PBMCs. The biotin antibody cocktail was added to the cell suspension, and the PBMCs were incubated on ice for 15 minutes. The biotin-antibody cocktail contained biotin anti-CD4, CD11b, CD16, CD14, CD19, CD20, CD36, CD56, TCR- $\gamma\delta$, CD123, CD235ab. After that, streptavidin nanobeads were added to the cells, which were incubated for another 15 minutes on ice. At the end of the incubation period, the cells were washed by adding RPMI 1640 up to 4mL, and centrifugation at 300g for 5 minutes at 4°C. The supernatant was discarded, and cells were suspended in 2.5mL RPMI 1640, mixing well to prevent aggregates. The tube was placed in a magnet for 5 minutes. The CD8⁺ T cells were isolated by collection of the liquid. The magnetic separation was repeated a second time for maximum yield, as recommended by the manufacturers.

3.2.3. Preparation of the growth medium used for CD8⁺ T cell growth

The growth medium used for primary CD8⁺ culture was composed of RPMI 1640, supplemented with FBS (10% of volume), 2mM L-glutamine, 100µm/mL penicillin-streptomycin and 2-mercaptoethanol. The volume of each component for preparing 500mL growth medium were 454.5 mL RPMI 1640 (Gibco, 31870025), 50 mL FBS (Gibco, A3160802), 5 mL 100X L-Glutamine (Gibco, 25030024), 5mL 100x Pen-Step (Gibco, 15070063) and 500µL of 50 mM 2-mercaptoethanol (Gibco, 31350010).

3.2.4. Experimental designs

For the first experiment there were 4 replicates of unstimulated CD8⁺ T cells and 4 replicates of 20 ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA stimulated CD8⁺ T cells. The cells were seeded at a concentration of 1×10^5 cells/mL and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C and 5% CO₂ conditions. At the extraction point, in order to maximise the RNA yield in the resting unstimulated cells, the replicates for each condition were pooled into two replicates, meaning two replicates of untreated cells and two replicates of stimulated cells.

For the second and main experiment, the isolated CD8⁺ T cells were expanded by supplementing the growth medium with a low PMA concentration of 10ng/mL, and incubation at 37°C and 5% CO₂ for 24 hours. After the expansion period, the PMA was washed by centrifugation at 1500 rpm (423 x g) for 10 minutes at 20°C, and cells were counted. Five control replicates of unstimulated CD8⁺ blasts were seeded on wells of a 24-well plate at concentration of 2×10^5 cells/mL (1mL suspension) and cultured in growth medium. Five experimental replicates containing the same cell density were seeded and incubated in PMA and PHA-L supplemented growth medium at concentrations of 20ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L. The cells were incubated for 24 hours before extraction. At the end of the incubation period, images of cells were taken using EVOS microscope for visualisation of clonal expansion.

3.2.5. RNA extraction

After the stimulation for 24 hours, the cells were brought into suspension by tapping the plates. The suspension from each replicate was transferred into respectively labelled 1.5mL RNase-free tubes and the cells were pelleted by centrifugation at 3000 rpm (1200 x g) for 5 minutes. The supernatant was discarded and 500µL Trizol reagent (Invitrogen, AM9738) was added to homogenise the pellet. In order to account for any cells left in the wells,

500mL Trizol reagent was added and then collected to the respective tubes to top up the Trizol solution to 1mL. The Trizol extracts were stored in -80°C until ready for RNA extraction. The lysed cells solutions were thawed on ice and then homogenised using a 25g syringe. The RNA extraction from the lysed cells in Trizol solution was done by separating the aqueous phase after addition of 0.2mL chloroform and centrifugation at 13000 rpm ($17950 \times g$) for 15 minutes at 4°C . The RNA was washed with isopropanol and 75% ethanol and stored in 40 μL of nuclease-free water (Gibco, 10977035). Quantification of the RNA in ng/ μL was done on Nanodrop 1000, using the RNA nucleic acid programme.

3.2.6. DNase treatment

The DNase treatment was performed following the protocol of DNA-free Kit (Invitrogen Thermofisher Scientific, AM1906), in order to degrade any genomic DNA that contaminated the RNA solutions during extraction. The maximum RNA concentration for each sample was 5 μg per 50 μL DNase reaction. Removal of genomic DNA contamination allowed efficient detection of amplification during the real-time PCR.

3.2.7. Complementary DNA synthesis

The synthesis of cDNA was done as instructed on the protocol of High-Capacity cDNA Reverse transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems, 4368814). The reactions were comprised of 10 μL of 2X Reverse Transcription mastermix and 10 μL of purified RNA solution from the previous step. Reaction was started by warming at 25°C for 10 minutes, followed by incubation at 37°C for 2 hours for the synthesis of the cDNA, and termination of reaction at 85°C for 5 minutes. The newly synthesised cDNA was stored at -20°C until used for PCR reactions.

3.2.8. Polymerase chain reactions

The PCR amplifications were performed in 25 μL reactions containing 12.5 μL PowerUp SYBR Green (Applied Biosystems, A25742), 0.5 μL Forward Primer and 0.5 μL Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1 μL of cDNA, and topped up to 25 μL with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035). The collected C_T values were used for the $\Delta\Delta C_T$ relative quantification of expression, comparing the stimulated cells to the untreated controls. The ΔC_T was obtained by comparison of C_T values of genes of interest to the mean C_T of housekeeping genes *ACTB*, *GAPDH* and *RPL37A*.

The primer pair used for amplification of the housekeeper *ACTB* were *ACTB* forward 5'-ATTGCCGACAGGATGCAGAA-3' and *ACTB* reverse 5'-GCTGATCCACATCTGCTGGAA-3'. The primer sequences for amplification of housekeeper *GAPDH* were *GAPDH* forward 5'-CGAGATCCCTCCAAAATCAA-3' and *GAPDH* reverse 5'-TTCACACCCATGACGAACAT-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of the housekeeper *RPL37A* were *RPL37A* forward 5'-ATTGAAATCAGCCAGCACGC-3' and *RPL37A* reverse 5'-AGGAACCACAGTGCCAGATCC-3'.

The primer sequences for amplification of *IL-2* transcripts in the first experiment run were *IL-2* forward 5'-GAATCCCAAACCTACCAGGATGCTC-3' and *IL-2* reverse 5'-TAGCACTTCTCCAGAGGTTTGAGT-3'. The second primer sequences for amplification of *IL-2*, that were used in the second experiment. were *IL-2''* forward 5'-AGAACTCAAACCTCTGGAGGAAG-3' and *IL-2''* reverse 5'-GCTGTCTCATCAGCATATTCACAC-3'.

The primer sequences for amplification of *IL2RA* were *IL2RA* forward 5'-GAGACTTCTGCCTCGTCACAA-3' and *IL2RA* reverse 5'-GATCAGCAGGAAAACACAGCCG-3'.

The primer sequences for amplification of *IFNG* were *IFNG* forward 5'-TCGGTAACTGACTTGAATGTCCA-3', and *IFNG* reverse 5'-TCCTTTTTCGCTTCCCTGTTTT-3'. The primer sequences for amplification of *IFNGR1* were *IFNGR1* forward 5'-AAAGTCAGAAGAATTTGCTGTAT-3' and *IFNGR1* reverse 5'-ACTGAAGGGTGAAATATGTC-3'.

The primer pair used for amplification of *PIEZO1* were *PIEZO1* forward 5'-CATCTTGGTGGTCTCCTCTGTCT-3' and *PIEZO1* reverse 5'-CTGGCATCCACATCCCTCTCATC-3'.

The primer pair used for detection of *PKD1* were *PKD1* forward 5'-CGCCGCTTACTAGCTTCGAC-3' and *PKD1* reverse 5'-ACGCTCCAGAGGGAGTCCAC-3'. The primer pair for amplification of *PKD2* were *PKD2* forward 5'-GCGAGGTCTCTGGGGAAC-3' and *PKD2* reverse 5'-TACACATGGAGCTCATCATGC-3'.

The primer pair used for amplification of *NFAT2* were *NFAT2* forward 5'-CACTCTGCTGCCTTACACA-3' and *NFAT2* reverse 5'-AAGATGCGAGCATGCGACTA-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *TCF3* were *TCF3* forward 5'-TGACCTCCTGGACTTCAGC-3' and *TCF3* reverse 5'-ACCTGAACCTCCGAACTGC-3'. The primer pair used for the amplification of *TCF7L2* were *TCF7L2* forward 5'-CCGGGAAAGTTTGAAGAAG-3' and *TCF7L2* reverse 5'-ACTGAAAATGGAGGGTTCGG-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *LEF-1* were *LEF-1* forward 5'-GACAGTGACCTAATGCACGT-3' and *LEF-1* reverse 5'-CCACCTTCTGCCAAGAATCT-3'.

The primer pair used for amplification of *GZMB* were *GZMB* forward 5'-CGACAGTACCATTGAGTTGTGCG-3' and *NFAT2* reverse 5'-TTCGTCCATAGGAGACAATGCCC-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *IL7R* were *IL7R* forward 5'-ATCGCAGCACTCACTGACCTGT-3' and *IL7R* reverse 5'-TCAGGCACTTTACCTCCACGAG-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *KLRG1* were *KLRG1* forward 5'-CCTTTTGCTGGATTGGTCTGAGG-3' and *KLRG1* reverse 5'-TTGATGGCACCGCATGTCTGCA-3'.

The primers for *IL-2*, *NFAT2* and *GAPDH* were obtained from Dagna *et al.* (Dagna, Pritchett and Lusso, 2013). The primers for *ACTB* and *RPL37A* were obtained from Maeß *et al.* (Maeß, Sendelbach and Lorkowski, 2010). The primers for the amplification of *IL2RA*, the second primer pair for amplification of *IL-2*, *GZMB*, *IL7R* and *KLRG1* were purchased from Origene (Cat. number: HP200397, HP200553, HP207492, HP205921, and HP208879, respectively.) The primer sequences for *PKD1* and *PKD2* were obtained from Dalagiorgou *et al.* (Dalagiorgou *et al.*, 2013). Primers amplifying *TCF3*, *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1* were provided from Dr. Robin Freeburn. Primers amplifying *PIEZO1* were designed using the NCBI primer design tool for the mRNA sequence NM_001142864.4. Primers amplifying *IFNG* were designed using the NCBI primer design tool for the mRNA sequence NM_000619.3. The primers amplifying the *IFNGR1* were also designed similarly, targeting the mRNA sequences designated NM_000416.3, NM_001363526.1, NM_001363527.1, corresponding to transcript variants 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

The efficiency of primers taken from the literature has been assessed in the corresponding papers mentioned above. All reaction efficiencies have also been checked by analysing the melt curve and the T_m of each primer pair, as shown in appendix A.2.2.

3.2.9. DNA gel electrophoresis

The amplified PCR products were run in 2% agarose gels for visualisation of the amplicons and determination of fragment lengths in base pairs (bp). The gels were made of 3.5g of agarose powder (Thermo Scientific, R0492) dissolved in 175 mL 1X TBE, and 1 μ L ethidium bromide. The gel was left to solidify for at least 30 minutes, after which the DNA products were added to the wells. The electrophoresis took place at 120V for 45 minutes. Fragment sizes were identified by comparing the travel distance of the amplicons, to the travel distance of fragments from a 100 bp DNA ladder (HyperLadder™ Bioline, 33056).

3.2.10. Statistical analysis

The gene expression data were presented as mean of five replicates \pm SE, with little exception where amplification was not detected in all replicates as described in the results. The analysis of statistical significance between the stimulated cells versus controls, was done using unpaired T test with Welch's correction. Statistical analysis was carried out using GraphPad Prism® version 6. P values <0.05 were accepted as significant.

3.3. Results

3.3.1. Experiment 1: Detection of housekeeping genes

Transcripts of the housekeeping genes *ACTB*, *RPL37A* and *GAPDH* were detected in all samples. No amplification occurred in the negative controls. The T_m for *ACTB* was 85.59°C, and the length of amplicons was 150bp. The T_m for *RPL37A* was 82.01°C and the length of amplicons was 94bp. The T_m for *GAPDH* was 86.69°C and the length of amplicons was 170bp. The T_m and the amplicon lengths for each housekeeper were at the expected values for efficient and specific reactions.

Figure 3.1: The T_m and the amplicon lengths for the housekeeping genes *ACTB* (A), *RPL37A* (B) and *GAPDH* (C). The amplifications were performed in 25 μ L reactions containing 12.5 μ L power-up SYBR green, 0.5 μ L forward primers, 0.5 μ L reverse primers, 10.5 μ L nuclease-free H₂O and 1 μ L cDNA.

3.3.2. Experiment 1: *IL-2* and *IL2RA* were detected only in stimulated cells.

The mRNA transcripts for the *IL-2* and *IL2RA* were detected and amplified only in the stimulated cells. No amplification occurred in the control samples and the negative controls. For the *IL-2*, in the untreated control samples there were primer dimers, but in the presence of the cDNA template from the stimulated cells, the dimers were not observed. The T_m for these genes were at the desired values and the amplicon lengths were 115bp and 126bp for *IL-2* and *IL2RA*, respectively. The difference in C_T values of the genes of interest and the housekeeper mean C_T value (i.e. ΔC_T), was 10.02 for *IL-2* and 8.56 for *IL2RA*, showing that there were more mRNA transcripts for the receptor compared to the *IL-2*.

Figure 3.2: The T_m and the amplicon lengths for the *IL-2* (A), and *IL2RA* (B). The amplifications were performed in 25 μL reactions containing 12.5 μL power-up SYBR green, 0.5 μL forward primers, 0.5 μL reverse primers, 10.5 μL nuclease-free H_2O and 1 μL cDNA.

Table 3.1: The ΔC_T for the *IL-2* and *IL2RA*. ΔC_T is the difference of the C_T value of the genes of interest with the C_T value of the housekeeping genes, here presented as mean of C_T of *ACTB*, *RPL37A* and *GAPDH*.

Sample	<i>ACTB</i> (C_T)	<i>RPL37A</i> (C_T)	<i>GAPDH</i> (C_T)	Housekeeper's mean (C_T)	<i>IL2RA</i> (C_T)	<i>IL2RA</i> (ΔC_T)	<i>IL-2</i> (C_T)	<i>IL-2</i> (ΔC_T)
C1	26.14	28.81	33.19	29.38	-	-	-	-
C2	27.22	29.35	34.11	30.23	-	-	-	-
S1	23.95	27.34	30.16	27.15	35.89	8.74	37.30	10.15
S2	22.75	26.52	29.01	26.09	34.53	8.44	36.00	9.90

3.3.3. Experiment 1: Detection of *NFAT2*, *PIEZO1*, *PKD1* and *PKD2*

The mRNA transcript of the *NFAT2* and *PKD2* were detected in all replicates. The *PIEZO1* mRNA transcripts were detected on the first control sample and the stimulated samples, but not on the second control sample. *PKD1* was not detected in any of the samples in 40 cycles of PCR.

Figure 3.3: Detection of *NFAT2* (A), *PIEZO1* (B) and *PKD2* (C) in CD8⁺ T cells, and fold expression in control and stimulated cells. Statistical analysis for comparing the fold expression of *NFAT2* and *PKD2* in stimulated cells versus control cells was done by T test with Welch's correction. The T test statistical analysis could not be performed for *PIEZO1*, which was not amplified in one of the control samples.

Table 3.2: Analysis of fold expression using the $\Delta\Delta C_T$ method for the genes of interest in CD8⁺ T cells, experiment 1. These genes were detected in both unstimulated and stimulated CD8⁺ T cells, with exception of *PIEZO1* which was detected in only one of the controls. Statistical analysis was performed using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

Gene	Sample	ΔC_T	$\Delta\Delta C_T$	Fold expression	Mean Fold expression	Statistical difference
<i>NFAT2</i>	C1	5.44	-0.32	1.25	1.02	No significance (p = 0.063)
	C2	6.07	0.32	0.80		
	S1	8.13	2.37	0.19	0.18	
	S2	8.26	2.51	0.18		
<i>PKD2</i>	C1	9.35	0.42	0.75	1.04	No significance (p = 0.206)
	C2	8.52	-0.42	1.34		
	S1	9.71	0.78	0.58	0.42	
	S2	10.85	1.92	0.26		
<i>PIEZO1</i>	C1	2.66	0.00	1.00	1.00	Not applicable
	C2	-	-	-		
	S1	7.27	4.61	0.04	0.04	
	S2	7.04	4.38	0.05		

3.3.4. Detection of *IFNG* mRNA in resting and stimulated cells

The *IFNG* transcripts were detected in the unstimulated cells and the stimulated cells. Calculation of the fold change showed increased mRNA levels in the stimulated cells, but at different amounts. The statistical analysis comparing the unstimulated cells with the stimulated, found no significant difference.

Figure 3.4: Expression of *IFNG* in control and stimulated CD8⁺ T cells, relative to housekeeping genes *ACTB*, *RPL37A* and *GAPDH*. The expected amplicon sizes for the primers used in the experiments were, *ACTB* 150 bp, *RPL37A* 95 bp, *GAPDH* 170 bp and *IFNG* 100 bp, which were confirmed by migration of fragments by electrophoresis in a 2% agarose gel.

3.3.5. Experiment 2: Visualisation of CD8⁺ clonal expansion upon stimulation

The cells stimulated with 20 ng/mL PMA and 1 μ g/mL PHA-L were undergoing clonal expansion and were arranged in clumps in all five replicates. The unstimulated cells were confluent and settled at the bottom of the wells in monolayer. Few small clumps were visible in the unstimulated cells, but not at the magnitude as the ones that were stimulated. Morphologically, cells looked healthy and very few cell fragments were observed amongst the replicates for both unstimulated and stimulated cells. Even though many of the cells had settled, they were not adherent, and slight agitation of the plate would result in them floating.

Figure 3.5: Visualisation of CD8⁺ T cells expansion upon stimulation with 20 ng/mL PMA and 1 µg/mL PHA-L (F-J), compared to the unstimulated cells (A-E). The images are representative of each replicate (N=5) and were taken after incubation for 24 hours. The clumps of CD8⁺ clones were visible for the stimulation with PMA and PHA-L, whereas the unstimulated cells were settled in monolayer.

3.3.6. Experiment 2: Gene expression patterns in stimulated CD8⁺ lymphoblasts

A difference in mRNA levels when comparing cells upon stimulation with 20 ng/mL PMA and 1 µg/mL PHA-L with the unstimulated controls, were *IL2RA*, *IFNG*, *PIEZO1*, *PKD1*, *TCF3* and *LEF-1*.

The mRNA transcripts of *IL2RA* were upregulated in the stimulated cells, whereas the mRNA transcripts for *IFNG*, *PIEZO1*, *PKD1*, *TCF3* and *LEF-1* were downregulated upon stimulation for 24 hours.

There was no difference in mRNA levels between the stimulated and unstimulated cells for *IL-2*, *PKD2*, *NFAT2* and *TCF7L2*. The *IFNGR1* was not detected in any or the samples in 50 cycles of PCR.

Figure 3.6: The expression of genes of interest in CD8⁺ T cells at 24 hours, relative to the mean of housekeepers *ACTB*, *GAPDH* and *RPL37A*. The data presented as mean of 5 replicates ± SE of the mean, with exception of control *IL-2* which was detected in 4 out of 5 replicates. Statistical significance was assessed by unpaired T test with Welch's correction. P values <0.05 were considered significant.

3.3.7. Experiment 2: Regulation of *GZMB*, *IL7R* and *KLRG1* showed predisposition for short-lived effector phenotype

The *GZMB* mRNA transcripts were upregulated 10-fold in the stimulated cells, compared to the unstimulated controls. The mRNA transcripts for *IL7R* and *KLRG1* were downregulated upon stimulation 20 ng/mL PMA and 1 µg/mL PHA-L compared to the unstimulated controls. The *IL7R* transcripts were downregulated strongly (fold change 0.03) compared to the control cells. The *KLRG1* transcripts were also downregulated (fold change 0.28). In addition, the downregulation of *IL7R* mRNA transcripts was 10 times stronger compared to the *KLRG1*.

Figure 3.7: The expression of *GZMB* (A), *IL7R* (B) and *KLRG1* (C) in control and stimulated CD8⁺ T cells at 24 hours. The *GZMB* mRNA transcripts were upregulated (A). Both *IL2R* and *KLRG1* were downregulated compared to the controls (B, C), but the *IL7R* transcripts were downregulated 10 times more than *KLRG1* (D). Data presented as mean of 5 replicates ± SE of the mean. Statistical significance was assessed by unpaired T test with Welch's correction. P values <0.05 were considered significant.

Table 3.3: Fold change for the genes of interests in the unstimulated and stimulated CD8⁺ T cells, and statistical difference. The fold expression was calculated using the formula $2^{-(\Delta\Delta C_T)}$. The mean is representative of 5 replicates (N=5), with exception of unstimulated *IL-2* (N=4). Statistical analysis was performed using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

Target mRNA	Mean Fold Expression		P value	Statistically different
	Unstimulated	20 ng/mL PMA + 1 µg/mL PHA-L		
<i>IL-2</i>	1.07	1.48	0.214	No
<i>IL2RA</i>	1.05	2.02	0.047	Yes (*)
<i>IFNG</i>	1.01	0.62	0.006	Yes (**)
<i>GZMB</i>	1.01	10.06	0.0012	Yes (**)
<i>IL7R</i>	1.00	0.03	< 0.0001	Yes (****)
<i>KLRG1</i>	1.00	0.28	< 0.0001	Yes (****)
<i>PIEZO1</i>	1.01	0.36	0.0006	Yes (***)
<i>PKD1</i>	1.07	0.61	0.047	Yes (*)
<i>PKD2</i>	1.13	0.68	0.145	No
<i>NFAT2</i>	1.02	0.83	0.121	No
<i>TCF3</i>	1.00	0.46	< 0.0001	Yes (****)
<i>LEF-1</i>	1.00	0.66	0.0003	Yes (***)
<i>TCF7</i>	1.01	0.26	< 0.0001	Yes (****)
<i>TCF7L2</i>	1.02	1.00	0.912	No

3.4. Discussion

3.4.1. Comments on the activation of CD8⁺ T cells

The results from the first experiment, showed that mRNA encoding for IL-2 and IL2RA was not detected in the resting cells, but only upon stimulation. These cells were alive and looking healthy, and housekeeping genes that are constitutively expressed were detected by PCR in all control and stimulated samples. Regulatable genes such as the *IL2RA* have been observed to be expressed only upon activation and are not detected in resting T cells (Leonard *et al.*, 1985; Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011; Pekalski *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, in order to have more cells for more replicates and higher transcription, especially for genes like *IL-2* and *IL2RA* which would indicate the cells were actively expanding, it was necessary to use an expansion method as described above for the second experiment.

The initial activation of the cells only with 10 ng/mL PMA for 24 hours after isolation from PBMCs, resulted in expression of *IL2RA* in CD8⁺ T cells, whereas the *IL-2* was detected in only 9 out of 10 samples. The original PMA concentration used to activate the resting CD8⁺ T cells was washed away, allowing the unstimulated control cells to support their culture through IL-2 production, whereas the stimulated cells were exposed to 20 ng/mL PMA and 1 µg/mL PHA-L. So overall, the second experiment can also be presented as a comparison of gene expression between unstimulated and stimulated CD8⁺ lymphoblasts, following the definition that T cells which become activated and expand are defined as such (Abbas, Lichtman and Pillai, 2018, p24).

The weak activation of unstimulated cells and expression of genes, allowed for the $\Delta\Delta C_T$ calculations to take place, and the statistical analysis of the fold expression values between the experimental and control replicates to be performed. The experiment also showed that PMA alone can be used to cause a transition of CD8⁺ T cells from resting into activation, without using synergetic stimulation with PHA or ionomycin and risking strong activation and expansion. The strong activation could have resulted in potent regulation of genes, overshadowing the effects of the stimulation with PMA and PHA-L in the next step. A strong initial activation could also result in downregulation of genes, which would make it difficult to detect upon further stimulation.

3.4.2. Regulation of genes encoding activation markers, effector proteins and surface mechanosensors.

The results from the second experiment showed no difference in *IL-2* transcripts between the stimulated and unstimulated controls. This could be because of the detection in late cycles for the unstimulated controls, and the loss of one replicate, could have affected the statistical test comparing between the groups.

Nevertheless, the detection of *IL-2* transcripts showed that the cells had been activated and allowed for comparison. The absence of a difference in *IL-2* mRNA between the stimulated cells and controls can also be explained biologically. The IL-2 production in CD8⁺ T cells is lower compared to the CD4⁺ T cells, which are the major contributors of this cytokine in immune responses (Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011). In fact, the CD4⁺ T cells support the expansion and differentiation of CD8⁺ T cells by IL-2 and other cytokines (Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011; Valbon, Condotta and Richer, 2016). In addition, the IL-2 production in activated primary T cells is regulated, peaking around 12 hours but declining by 24 hours, which could explain why the mRNA levels in stimulated CD8⁺ T cells became comparable to the controls cells (Boyman and Sprent, 2012, Abbas, Lichtman and Pillai, 2018, p218).

The *IL2RA* mRNA was detected in all samples but upregulated in stimulated cells showing active cell expansion/proliferation. The expansion of the stimulated cells was also visible through light microscopy, by the presence of clumps comprised of CD8⁺ clones (Figure 3.5). The upregulation of this gene was expected for the stimulation with mitogens PMA and PHA-L and upon activation of CD8⁺ T cells (Leonard *et al.*, 1985; Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011). In addition, the *IL2RA* mRNA detection was also expected due to IL-2 signalling which regulates the expression of the gene (Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011).

The *IFNG* was expressed in the CD8⁺ T cells, but interestingly, it was at lower levels in the cells stimulated with PMA and PHA-L at 24 hours, compared to the unstimulated controls. The IFN- γ was expected to upregulate in response to PMA and PHA stimulation. ELISA results for produced IFN- γ on isolated CD8⁺ T cells after stimulation with PHA and IL-2, PMA and ionomycin, or plate-bound anti-CD3 and PMA, have shown that the cytokine is upregulated for all these treatments (Li *et al.*, 1995). In addition, based on the first experiment, the *IFNG* seemed upregulated upon stimulation, although the statistical

analysis showed no significant difference, probably due to the different fold expression values of 1.7 and 3.9 fold in the stimulated samples (N=2) (Figure 3.4).

Furthermore, while the mRNA for IFN- γ can degrade quickly, the PKC activation by PMA has shown to stabilise the transcripts and increase IFN- γ production (Kaldy and Schmitt-Verhulst, 1995). Similarly, in murine effector and memory CD8⁺ T cells, the PKC has shown to mediate mRNA stability of *Ifn γ* and *Il2* and enhance the shift of mRNA from light to heavy polyribosomes, affecting translation (Salerno *et al.*, 2017).

In relation to the IL-2 production and increased *IL2RA* expression, based on previous observations, the IFN- γ was expected to be upregulated upon IL-2 signalling (Pipkin *et al.*, 2010; Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011). One explanation for the downregulation was the absence of a third signal, usually a cytokine like IL-12, IL-21 and IL-15, which would drive effector cell or memory cell differentiation, and increase the production of IFN- γ (Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011; Valbon, Condotta and Richer, 2016). These cytokines, including the IL-2, are mostly provided to the CD8⁺ T cells by the CD4⁺ T cells or antigen presenting cells (Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011), and were not added to the culture in this experiment. There may also be a case where the *IFNG* gene was upregulated at earlier time-points higher than in the controls, but downregulated at 24 hours either due to the lack of additional signals such as IL-12, or because of some negative-feedback loop caused by IFN- γ production. This makes it necessary that the expression this gene is assessed at different time-points in the future studies.

In addition, the mRNA regulation pattern does not always correspond to the pattern of protein production, due to *IFNG* RNA stability and subsequent translational and posttranslational processes, as described earlier (Salerno *et al.*, 2017), and the cytokine may still be highly produced in these cells at 24 hours. For example, considering the early T cell activation marker CD69, the induction of *CD69* mRNA upon activation of T lymphocytes is very rapid, peaking around 3 hours after induction and declining very quickly to resting levels by 8 hours (Santis *et al.*, 1995). This rapid degradation of the *CD69* mRNA has suggested that mRNA levels may contribute to the regulation of protein expression on the cell surface, even though the loss of *CD69* transcripts occurs well before the highest levels of cell surface CD69 are reached at 24 hours (Santis *et al.*, 1995). Nevertheless, the difference

in *IFNG* transcripts at 24 hours between the stimulated and unstimulated CD8⁺ T cells, was indicative of a response towards the stimulation.

The mRNA for another effector protein, *GZMB*, was upregulated strongly in the stimulated cells. The upregulation of this gene, and the regulation of *IFNG* could indicate that the cells could be obtaining an effector phenotype. The *GZMB* have shown to be increased upon IL-2 signalling in naïve T cells (Pipkin *et al.*, 2010). In addition, the upregulation of *GZMB* could also be a result of effector CD8⁺ T cells originating from reactivated memory cells, as described in a previous study (Nowacki *et al.*, 2007).

The mRNA for *PIEZO1* was downregulated for at 24 hours in the stimulated cells. This pattern of regulation was similar to what was observed in Jurkat cells in Chapter 2 for the same stimulation. The downregulation could be because the roles of *PIEZO1* have been involved in the initial activation signalling (i.e. optimisation of TCR signalling and cytoskeletal rearrangements in the immune synapse)(Liu *et al.*, 2018; Liu and Ganguly, 2019), and the channel may not be that necessary during the clonal expansion. That does not exclude the possibility that existing channels, even if downregulated, still carry out functions during this stage, especially related to Ca²⁺ signalling (Liu *et al.*, 2018). The regulation of *PIEZO1* at protein level should be investigated in the future to observe how the mRNA downregulation translate for protein production.

The mRNA for *PKD1* was also downregulated, with similar pattern to that observed in Jurkat cells in two experiments involving PMA and PHA-L stimulation. The mRNA levels for *PKD2* in stimulated cells were comparable to the unstimulated controls. The PCR for *PKD2* was repeated twice showing similar results. In Jurkat cells, the mRNA for this gene was higher in the stimulated cells than in the controls, but in primary CD8⁺ T cells there was no difference. The loss of expression of *PKD1* and *PKD2* has resulted in decrease of proliferation in virus-immortalised lymphoblasts (Aguiari *et al.*, 2004; Van Laecke *et al.*, 2018). However, the downregulation of the mRNA is not the same as loss of expression, as the protein may still be produced at lower levels or found on the surface of cells. Therefore, without knowing what happens at protein level, the interpretation as to what the downregulation of *PKD1* means is difficult and this aspect should be addressed in future work. One suggestion could be that the *PC1* and *PC2* are still regulating proliferation, but the downregulation of *PC1*

could be necessary in later stages for cell differentiation, similar to what has been observed in other haematopoietic lines (Aguari *et al.*, 1998).

3.4.3. Regulation of transcription factors *NFAT2*, *TCF3*, *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1*

There was no difference in mRNA levels of *NFAT2* in the stimulated cells compared to the unstimulated controls. The *NFAT2* is involved in T cell activation as part of the calcineurin-NFAT pathway, which results in the expression for the IL-2 gene (Macian, 2005; Jaalouk and Lammerding, 2009; Müller and Rao, 2010; Gaud, Lesourne and Love, 2018), and in CD8⁺ T cells has shown to play roles in the activation and differentiation into effector or memory cells, as well as in cell exhaustion (Martinez *et al.*, 2015; Klein-Hessling *et al.*, 2017; Xu, Keller and Martinez, 2019). In exhausted murine CD8⁺ T cells, the mRNA for *NFAT2* was upregulated compared to the naïve, effector and memory subtypes (Wherry *et al.*, 2007).

In the results of this chapter, the *NFAT2* was not regulated at 24 hours as a result of PMA and PHA stimulation. It is possible that *NFAT2* was upregulated in early stimulation but decreased to levels comparable to the controls at 24 hours. The *NFAT2* differentially promote CD8⁺ T cell differentiation into memory population, thus the transcription factor not only plays a role in T cell activation but it is also crucial for driving proper CD8⁺ T cell commitment potential (Xu, Keller and Martinez, 2019).

In addition, the regulation of expression would be important because *NFAT2* is involved in cell exhaustion, and its transcripts have been found increased in exhausted CD8⁺ T cells (Wherry *et al.*, 2007). Therefore, the observed *NFAT2* expression pattern could indicate that the cells were not exhausted due to 24 hours-long TCR signalling caused by crosslinking the CD3 with PHA-L and activating PKC with PMA.

LEF-1 mRNA was downregulated in activated cells in response to stimulation with PMA and PHA-L. The *LEF-1* is associated with T cell quiescence and thus resting cells (Szabo *et al.*, 2019). It has been showed that human naïve CD8⁺ T cells downregulate the *LEF-1* and *TCF1* (*TCF7*) upon activation to antigen presentation *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Kaech *et al.*, 2002; Willinger *et al.*, 2006). In a study involving infected mouse models, the *LEF-1* mRNA in activated antigen-specific CD8⁺ T cells remained downregulated in all time-points that were investigated post infection, over a period of a month (Kaech *et al.*, 2002). Similarly, it has

been shown that activated and proliferating CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells in response to HTLV-1, downregulate LEF-1 and TCF1 (Ma *et al.*, 2015).

The LEF-1 is usually an activator of the WNT pathway, which induces proliferation (Hrckulak *et al.*, 2016). However, in resting T cells LEF-1 may be responsible for the quiescence of the cells because more of the inhibitory isoforms of LEF1 have been identified in resting CD8⁺ T cells compared to Jurkat lymphoblasts (Willinger *et al.*, 2006). Therefore the downregulation of LEF-1 in CD8⁺ T cells may be necessary for proliferation and clonal expansion (Willinger *et al.*, 2006). The downregulation of the LEF-1 protein in the activated CD8⁺ T cells has been demonstrated (Willinger *et al.*, 2006), and was also reproduced in this study at mRNA level upon stimulation with PMA and PHA-L. The downregulation of the LEF-1 mRNA in activated human CD8⁺ T cells in this study was also comparable to observations from the activated antigen-specific murine CD8⁺ T cells, and could be similar in duration as in the study mentioned earlier (Kaech *et al.*, 2002).

The mRNA levels for *TCF7L2* were comparable to the unstimulated cells. Little is known about the roles of TCF7L2 in mature CD8⁺ T cells. It has been shown that the TCF7L2 is expressed in CD8⁺ T cells activated and expanded in response to acute EBV infection (Greenough *et al.*, 2015). The authors mention that TCF7L2 was expressed low and could be related to differentiation of CD8⁺ T cells toward a resting memory phenotype (Greenough *et al.*, 2015). In another study, a dominant-negative construct for TCF4 (i.e. a mutated product that adversely affects the normal, wild-type product encoded from *TCF7L2*), diminished CD4 expression on mature CD8⁺ T cells by 50% in response to T cell activation (Schenkel *et al.*, 2010). This study has demonstrated that the induced activation of β -catenin signalling results in expression of CD4 in mature CD8⁺ T cells, and that the normal TCF4, a downstream effector of such signalling, could be involved in occurrence of CD4^{dim}CD8^{bright} T cells (Schenkel *et al.*, 2010). The TCF7L2 has shown to act as both activator and suppressor of the canonical pathway (Thiele *et al.*, 2001; Hrckulak *et al.*, 2016), with potential roles in both expansion and differentiation into cell phenotypes as in the above examples. However, due to the limited knowledge, the interpretation of the results obtained in this study can be difficult. The expression pattern of *TCF7L2* shown in this report, could be due to regulation or adjustment of gene expression at 24 hours, or related to the roles that the transcription factor has in CD8⁺ T cells.

The mRNA for TCF3 (E2A) was downregulated in the stimulated cells at 24 hours compared to the unstimulated controls. The E2A has shown to be involved in the activation of CD8⁺ T cells, as well as determination of memory phenotypes, as introduced above (D'Cruz *et al.*, 2012; Masson *et al.*, 2013). The downregulation of TCF3, can be indicative that the cells are activated and distancing from resting naïve or memory phenotypes, and probably directing towards a short-lived effector phenotype.

Overall, the regulation for the transcription factors above indicates T cell activation, and possibly early effector differentiation.

3.4.5. The *IL7R* and *KLRG1* expression of stimulated CD8⁺T cells indicated predisposition for short-lived effector phenotype.

The strong upregulation of *GZMB* and regulation of *IFNG* transcripts, as well as different transcription factors, showed that the cells were not just activating but could be differentiating into effector cells (Nowacki *et al.*, 2007; Sarkar *et al.*, 2008; Pipkin *et al.*, 2010). In order to assess the development of effector phenotypes, an assessment of mRNA regulation for cell marker *IL7R* and *KLRG1* took place.

The *IL7R* was strongly downregulated, which could result in cells being IL7Ra⁻ with time. The IL7Ra is important for providing survival signals into the cells, and differentiation into long lived memory cells (Kaech *et al.*, 2003). Downregulation or low expression of IL7R results in cells which are short lived (Kaech *et al.*, 2003). The *KLRG1* was also downregulated but at lower levels than *IL7R*, and the KLRG1 protein might take longer to downregulate from cell surface. The downregulation of *KLRG1* could also be related to increased proliferative capacity my stimulation with mitogens, as increased protein has been associated with low or impaired proliferation capacity (Voehringer, Koschella and Pircher, 2002; Thimme *et al.*, 2005).

These results are indicative that the CD8⁺ T cell are activated, proliferating and are acquiring effector phenotypes, most likely short-lived. However, such differentiation as assessed by gene regulation can be in early stages, and the cell fate could still be manipulated, probably upon further stimulation by the IL-2, IL-15 or other cytokines (Mitchell, Ravkov and Williams, 2010; Pipkin *et al.*, 2010; Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011). This statement could be

supported by the *KLRG1* downregulation, which recently has shown to be involved in CD8⁺ T cell plasticity (Herndler-Brandstetter *et al.*, 2018).

3.4.6. Limitations of the study and future work

Aspects that remain to be studied further include different time-points and identification of CD8⁺ T subtypes before and after stimulation, and protein work to observe how the mRNA expression patterns translate to protein expression.

Different time-point analysis would provide more data and help with the interpretation of the observed expression pattern of *IFNG*, *NFAT2* and genes encoding for mechanosensory proteins in early and later time-points.

Identification of cells before the work is important to expand the observation of this study. The extracted population as described in the method have consisted of resting naïve and memory CD8⁺ T cells. The presence of memory CD8⁺ T cells could explain the detection of *IFNG* in the unstimulated cells in the first experiment (Nowacki *et al.*, 2007). In this study, the heterogeneity of the population was taken under consideration when interpreting the results, so that the description is valid for the activation of naïve CD8⁺ cells and reactivation of resting memory cells. However, it would be important to check such observation furthermore in isolated naïve or memory populations because differences could occur because of population heterogeneity.

Further work could include protein expression for understanding mRNA to protein relationships, and whether the downregulation of transcription for *PIEZO1*, *PKD1*, and transcription factors, translates in downregulation of protein expression.

3.5. Conclusion

The CD8⁺ T cells stimulated with PMA and PHA-L became activated and regulated genes at 24 hours. Genes like *IL2RA* and *IL-2* are expressed only in activated cells but not resting cells, whereas genes like *LEF-1* and *IL7R* are regulatable upon activation. Other genes encoding for transcription factors indicated activation and proliferation/expansion, as well as effector differentiation as early as 24 hours. This differentiation process could be at early stages and might have required further supplementation with cytokines to progress. Gene regulation patterns for transcription factors also suggested that the cells were distancing from resting memory phenotype and acquiring more of a short-lived effector phenotype.

Regarding the genes encoding for mechanosensors, the *PIEZO1* and *PKD1* were downregulated. Similar regulation of *PIEZO1* was observed in Jurkat cells stimulated with the same mitogens at the same concentrations. *PIEZO1* has shown to influence T cell activation, and in this experiment, it was shown that the mRNA encoding this mechanosensory channel was regulated in early activation and differentiation stages.

Manipulation of *PIEZO1* expression or function could thus interfere with the activation or differentiation of CD8⁺ T cells. This is an interesting hypothesis that should be tested in future work in relation to alopecia areata, because interference with activation or effector differentiation can be therapeutic. In addition, the mechanosensory roles of *PIEZO1* in mechanosensation during the disease should be investigated.

Overall, the experiment of this chapter showed interesting mRNA regulation patterns for the chosen genes of interest upon induction of activation of primary CD8⁺ T cells by PMA and PHA-L.

Chapter 4

Assessment of 'Nanokick' bioreactor functionality

Abstract

The mechanical stimulation of cells in the following chapters was performed on a bioreactor platform, which utilises the reverse piezo electric effect to generate nano-scale vibrations. This bioreactor, nicknamed as “Nanokick bioreactor”, is not commercially available and for the duration of this project has been in a process of development and optimisation. For this reason, the functionality of the bioreactor in our possession had to be checked continuously, in order to assess its stability and to validate the stimulation for the subsequent biology experiments. This chapter presents the data collected for a period of almost two years, from the initial work until the moment when the bioreactor significantly failed to generate the desired vibrations and could not be calibrated.

4.1. Introduction

Nanokick bioreactor generates nano-scale vibrations by utilising reverse piezoelectric effect (Curtis *et al.*, 2013; Childs *et al.*, 2016; Robertson *et al.*, 2018) (Figure 4.1). Reverse piezoelectric effect converts an electrical signal into a mechanical force, or a mechanical vibration as in this project. This is achieved by a signal generator sending an electrical current on piezos beneath the platform. The electrical current then causes the piezos to strain and constrict around a point of equilibrium, therefore generating the desired vibrations (Figure 4.1, B).

For the biological experiments conducted as part of this PhD projects, the bioreactor provided means of applying mechanical stimulation on the cells. This mechanical stimulation was characterised by 1000Hz vibrations of 20-60 nm amplitude, which were applied vertically on the Z axis across the plate's surface and onto the cells. The cells received stimulation by incubation on the top of the bioreactor's platform, on magnet clamped 6-well or 24-well plates, and at 37°C and 5% CO₂ as required for their vitality (Figure 4.2). Past studies which have applied nano-scale vibrational stimuli on cells have recorder responses such as alteration of cell

behaviour and enhancements of differentiation processes (Curtis *et al.*, 2013; Pemberton *et al.*, 2015; Childs *et al.*, 2016).

The bioreactor must be stable and be able to generate the desired vibrations without variance in frequency and with little variance in the amplitude. The bioreactor was calibrated before the start of the biology work, but it was necessary to be checked periodically in order to assess functionality and determine the amplitude range of the vibrations that the cells would be exposed to. This chapter covers the work performed in order to validate the bioreactor's stability and ability to provide the desired stimulation in the biology experiments.

Figure 4.1: Piezoelectric effect is characteristic of crystalline structures, and many biological structures such as bones or DNA are piezoelectric. Upon application of forces on piezo materials (A), electricity is generated by arrangement of charges across the piezo. This is known as direct piezoelectric effect (A). Reverse piezo electric effect (B), occurs when an electrical current causes deformation of the piezo materials, as their molecules rearrange in response to the electron flow. Reverse piezoelectric effect therefore provides good means of converting electricity to mechanical forces, and in the Nanokick bioreactor, is used for the generation of low amplitude and high frequency vibrations.

Figure 4.2: Signal generator (left) and the Nanokick bioreactor in the incubator (right). Magnet-clamped 6-well plates can be seen on top of the platform.

4.2. Methods

4.2.1. Laser interferometry for measuring the frequency and amplitude

Laser interferometry was used to measure the frequency and the amplitude of the vibrations on the surface of the wells, which is the site where the mechanical stimulation was applied on the cells. Frequency and the amplitude of the vibrations were measured continuously over periods of 2-3 months, before and after experiments, to allow continuous assessment of the bioreactor's functionality. The measurements were performed on the bioreactor twice; once after being left at room temperature (25°C) and another time after being incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The identification number of the bioreactor used in this project is NTB3014.

During the laser interferometry, a continuous helium-neon beam (wavelength 632.8 nm) is reflected from the surface of the well at a distance of 25-30 cm and directed into the interferometer (SIOS Meßtechnik GmbH SP S-120) to create an interference pattern with a reference beam. Alignment of the beam is achieved by utilising an oscillator signal that appears as a circle on the oscilloscope's screen. The interferometers output is then analysed by INFAS Vibro computer software (SIOS Meßtechnik GmbH: Interferometry Analysis Software for Vibrometers), which performs a fast fourier transform (FFT) and plot the amplitude of motion in frequency space.

Figure 4.3: Laser interferometry is used for measurement of nano-scale displacements on the surface of bioreactor's platform. The amplitude and frequency of vibration are measured and utilised for the calibration of the bioreactor and to assess its stability.

Figure 4.4: INFAS Vibro Interface (A). The black arrow represents the peak used as the reference for interferometry, and the red arrow showing the peak at 1kHz represents the frequency of the generated vibrations. When zoom in to the 1 kHz peak (B), the amplitude of vibrations in nm is recorded on the top right of the screen (blue arrow, B).

4.2.2. Checking the temperature of medium for heat generation

The applied vibrations could generate friction forces and heat (Talai, Desai and Heyns, 2017), so to rule out such phenomenon, the temperature of 2 mL medium (RPMI-1640, ATCC 302001) incubated on magnet-clumped well plates was recorded at 4, 8, 24, 32 and 48 hours. The incubation of the medium was done at 37°C and 5% CO₂. Temperature was measured using alcohol and electronic thermometers (Fisherbrand™). The alcohol thermometers were left for 10 minutes in each well and were shaken in the beginning of each measurement to lower the alcohol scale from the previous measurement. The electronic thermometers recorded the temperature over 5 minutes per well. Both types of thermometers were placed in each well together to record the temperature simultaneously. A control well was designed where the RPMI 1640 medium was left away from the platform and its temperature was measured constantly (Figure 4.5).

Figure 4.5: Experimental set-up to observe the temperature of vibrated RPMI 1640. A control tube containing RPMI 1640 was left away from the platform, while the experimental wells contained media on 6-well plates clamped with magnet on the vibrating bioreactor's platform.

4.3. Results

4.3.1. Bioreactor calibration and validation

The bioreactor is calibrated by plotting the input voltage vs displacement (amplitude) at a certain frequency. The calibration was performed by the manufacturers of the bioreactor (Figure 4.6). Before the project the bioreactor was set to generate 1000Hz vibrations. The amplitudes were measured daily, after incubation at 37°C, for one week in order to validate bioreactor's stability. Laser interferometry results indicated that the platform was vibrating at 1000Hz and the mean amplitude was around 30 nm. The standard deviation range of 12 – 13 for whole platform measurements was accepted as normal from the manufacturers of the bioreactor, values over 15 would indicate issues with the generated vibrations, and values over 20 meant the bioreactor had become unstable. These amplitude range and standard deviation values were stable for the duration of the initial assessment (Figure 4.7).

Figure 4.6: Input voltage (V) versus well displacements (nm) as measured by laser interferometry. There is a direct relationship between the voltage and the amplitude of vibrations (Curtis *et al.*, 2013; Robertson *et al.*, 2018).

12-well Plates			
Week measurements			
37°C			
Day	Frequency (Hz)	Mean Platform Displacement (nm)	STDEV
1	1000	31	12.8
2	1000	32.1	11.7
3	1000	32.4	12.2
4	1000	33	12
5	1000	32.3	12.5
6	1000	32.3	12.8

Figure 4.7: Measurements of the frequency and amplitude of the bioreactor for one week after incubation at 37°C. The results are presented as mean of 120 measurement \pm STDEV. The STDEV range of 12 – 13 for whole platform measurements was accepted as normal from the manufacturers of the bioreactor, whereas values over 20 meant the bioreactor had become unstable.

4.3.2. Amplitude and frequency of the platform's measurements

The results from the measurements of amplitude across the platform showed that the bioreactor was stable for about one year (Figure 4.8, Table 4.1). The right side of the platform stayed relatively stable for another six months (Table 4.1). The mean amplitude of the platform and the standard deviation increased in the beginning of the year 2 (Table 4.1). The increase of standard deviation of the mean, from about 14 to around 24, indicated increase in amplitude variance across the platform. A visual representation of such variance can be seen in Figure 4. and Figure 4.. The range of amplitude as for the final measurements on July 2019, for 6-well plates was 13 – 103 nm, whereas for 24-well plates which increase the number of platform spots investigated, was 7 – 133 nm (Table 4.1, Figure 4.9, Figure 4.10). A difference between the left side and the right side was also visible (Table 4.1). The platform's right side was more stable overall, but eventually the amplitudes started to vary (Table 4.1). Very high amplitude spots and very low amplitude spots existed across the platform, as shown from the analysis of amplitude range on the left and right side, and as platform mean (Table 4.1).

Another interesting observation was that there was a difference in mean amplitude of the platform when the bioreactor was incubated at room temperature (20 - 25°C) and when it was incubated at 37°C (Figure 4.8, A). At room temperature the mean amplitude and the variance remained stable with time (Table 4.2), in great contrast to what was observed when the bioreactor was placed at 37°C.

Figure 4.8: Measurements of platform's frequency and amplitude. Comparison of mean amplitudes generated on the platform after incubation incubated at room temperature and at 37°C (A). The amplitudes were measured using laser interferometry on the surface of 6-well plates. The results are presented as mean of 60 measurements \pm STDEV. On the right, the varying pattern of mean amplitude over 2017- 2019 period (B).

Table 4.1: Comparison of amplitudes across the platform as measured on 6-well plates and 24-well plates. The amplitude ranges are presented for the left side of the bioreactor, the right side (close to the electrical supply entry) and as mean amplitude across the platform. Variance of measurements was determined by standard deviation of the mean.

Date	Left Side Mean (N=30)	Left Side STDEV (N=30)	Amplitude Range (nm) (N=30)	Right Side Mean (N=30)	Right Side STDEV (N=30)	Amplitude range (nm) (N=30)	Mean Platform Amplitude (nm) (N=60)	Platform STDEV (N=60)	Platform Amplitude Range (N=60)
Jan-18	23.59	13.29	9.5 - 50.2	43.71	4.17	38.4 - 50.8	33.65	14.58	9.5 - 50.8
Mar-18	30.77	17.92	12.8 - 67.3	45.66	4.99	38.8 - 53.9	38.22	15.05	12.8 - 67.3
Jun-18	23.51	11.98	9.5 - 46.8	40.27	10.31	23.7 - 52.4	31.89	13.94	9.5 - 52.4
Nov-18	49.05	30.63	23.3 - 83.2	41.57	13.10	22.8 - 67.5	45.31	17.77	22.8 - 83.2
Mar-19	58.97	30.63	28.3 - 120.8	43.50	13.21	23.9 - 62.4	51.24	24.65	23.9 - 120.8
Jul-19	51.29	26.36	26.5 - 103.5	38.94	16.00	13.1 - 58.4	45.12	22.50	13.1 - 103.5
24-well plate									
Date	Left Side Mean (N=120)	Left Side STDEV (N=120)	Amplitude Range (nm) (N=120)	Right Side Mean (N=120)	Right Side STDEV (N=120)	Amplitude range (nm) (N=120)	Mean Platform Amplitude (nm) (N=240)	Platform STDEV (N=240)	Platform Amplitude Range (N=240)
Jun-18	22.73	12.53	7.7 - 63.1	39.02	12.08	9.3 - 57	30.87	14.75	7.7 - 63.1
Mar-19	64.77	37.28	13.4 - 160.2	40.88	13.93	6.8 - 59.2	52.83	30.53	6.8 - 160.2
Jul-19	52.99	29.03	9.6 - 133.3	38.65	15.98	6.5 - 56.8	45.82	24.46	6.5 - 133.3

Table 4.2: Mean platform amplitude of the bioreactor sitting at room temperature. Measurements performed on 6-well plates and variance of amplitude across the platform was determined by the standard deviation of the mean.

6-well plates			
20-25°C			
Date	Frequency (Hz)	Mean Platform Amplitude (nm)	STDEV (N=60)
Jan-18	1000	36.50	17.21
Mar-18	1000	32.85	12.48
Jun-18	1000	27.03	13.72
Nov-18	1000	30.87	11.92
Mar-19	1000	35.37	12.63
Jul-19	1000	27.24	12.16

Figure 4.9: Mean amplitude per well (6-well plate) on the left and right sides of the platform, early measurement point (A) and last measurement point (B). Mean amplitude is the average of 5 different measurements per well. The amplitude was measured using laser interferometry. The top image (A) represents data measured on January 2018, whereas the lower image (B) represents data measured in July 2019.

Figure 4.10: Mean amplitude per well (24-well plate) on the left and right sides of the platform, early measurement point (A) and last measurement point (B). Mean amplitude is the average of 5 different measurements per well. The amplitude was measured using laser interferometry. The top image (A) represents data measured on June 2018, whereas the lower image (B) represents data measured in July 2019.

4.3.3. Temperature of the vibrated medium

The temperature values obtained by the alcohol thermometers and the electronic ones were inconsistent as the thermometers recorded different temperatures of medium (Figure 4.11). The temperature of the RPMI 1640 incubated at the wells of 6-well plates and vibrated, according to the electronic thermometers was 36.9°C (as mean of time-points), whereas according to the alcohol thermometers, it was 38°C (as mean of time-points) (Figure 4.11).

Figure 4.11: Mean temperature of medium vibrated at 1000Hz, measured by electronic and alcohol thermometers and compared to the control. Data presented as mean of 12 wells/time-point ± SE.

4.4. Discussion

4.4.1. Validation of the bioreactor's functionality for biology work

Laser interferometry measurements of the frequency and the amplitude have shown that the bioreactor generated vibrations at a constant frequency (1000Hz), but with varying amplitude. The first three measurements showed that the bioreactor was working on the accepted parameters regarding the mean platform amplitude and standard deviation of the mean (Figure 4.8, Table 4.1). The measurements were taking place before and after experiments, in order to closely monitor the amplitude and frequency of the mechanical stimulation that was applied on the cells.

However, starting from the fourth measurement point until the sixth and last, the bioreactor displayed instability (Table 4.1). The issues started on the left side of the bioreactor, which was vibrating at higher and more variable amplitudes with time. The amplitudes recorded on different spots of the platform were more varying, and during the final measurement the right side which had been the most stable one was also affected. The upper parts of the right side had a decrease in amplitude (Figure 4.10). This was opposite to the platform side which had the higher amplitude (Figure 4.10), so that indicate that the whole platform had gone unstable, probably due to piezos' contact with the platform being impaired with time. As the bioreactor started to display unusual amplitudes after the fourth measurement point, the areas of platform still suitable for work became limited, with only certain areas on the right side of the platform still having the amplitudes used in earlier experiments. That made it difficult for running experiments for assessment of result reproducibility, because the amplitude of stimulation had changed and the number of replicates that could be fitted on the platform had limited. After the sixth measurement point, the vibrations had affected almost the whole platform, and the bioreactor was deemed unsuitable for further work.

Interestingly, at room temperature the mean amplitude and standard deviation remained relatively consistent (Table 4.2). One possible explanation for the differences in platform amplitudes at room temperature and 37°C can be that temperature can affect the platform's contact with the piezos, by causing slight metal contraction and expansion. The bioreactor was initially calibrated while incubated at 37°C (Figure 4.7), and the biological

experiments had to take place inside an incubator environment comprised of 37°C and 5% CO₂, so the stability at room temperature was irrelevant.

4.4.2. Theoretical discussion about the effects of varying amplitude

The amplitude and frequency can be used to approximately calculate the forces the cells are experiencing by utilising Newton's second law of motion:

$$\mathbf{F} = m\mathbf{a}$$

The force applied (**F**), is calculated using the mass of the cells (**m**) and acceleration (**a**). The cell mass is calculated as cell surface area multiplied by media height and by media density (Curtis *et al.*, 2013; Childs *et al.*, 2016). The peak acceleration of a sinusoidal vibration can be calculated using the amplitude (**A₀**) and frequency (**f**):

$$\mathbf{Acceleration}_{peak} = \mathbf{A}_0(2\pi f)^2$$

In theory, the variance of amplitude across the platform and in each well can be translated in different forces applied on the cells and varying stimulation. Considering a theoretical approach, by keeping the frequency constant, the only variable at the peak acceleration equation is the amplitude (**A₀**). So, for amplitude (**A₀**) of 100 nm, compared to amplitude (**A₀**) of 10 nm, there is a 10-fold change in the peak acceleration. Keeping the mass constant, by having the same cell population, density and suspension, that would result in a force over 10 times greater in the wells vibrated at 100 nm as opposed to the ones vibrated at 10 nm. This can make an issue as cells located on different spots of the platform would experience different forces. The increase of variance with time can also affect reproducibility, because there are different stimulation parameters (i.e. amplitude of vibration) with each repetitive run.

As counter-arguments, it has been suggested from past studies which have applied the same nanovibrational stimulation on osteoblasts, that the cell responses are frequency-driven rather than amplitude-driven. Firstly, the older bioreactor models have had a greater variance on the generated displacements (e.g. amplitudes of 5-50 nm), but cell responses were greatly affected by such variance when frequencies were kept constant (Curtis *et al.*, 2013). In addition, osteogenesis studies that have used vibrations of similar frequencies (e.g. 1000Hz) but different amplitudes, have had similar results in terms of osteoblast

differentiation (Nikukar, Reid, Tsimbouri, Riehle, Adam S. G. Curtis, *et al.*, 2013; Tsimbouri *et al.*, 2017). Secondly, it has been suggested that cells behave differently at different frequencies, regardless of the amplitude, which can be an indication that responses are driven by the frequency of the vibrations (Curtis *et al.*, 2013; Nikukar, Reid, Tsimbouri, Riehle, Adam S. G. Curtis, *et al.*, 2013; Childs *et al.*, 2016).

However, this must be approached with caution because not all cell types respond the same to the stimuli. Besides, the studies on osteoblast need to address in depth the roles of amplitude and frequency on those particular cells, and not deduce just on observations in an empirical manner. Ideally, the parameters of any new type of stimulus that has not been studied in depth, must be as stable as possible in order to conclude stimulation-response relationships and later, the reproducibility of results.

4.4.3. Temperature differences when measures by alcohol and electronic thermometers.

Measurement of the incubated medium temperature showed a 1-2 degree centigrade difference when using alcohol thermometers versus electronic thermometers (Figure 4.11). The difference that was observed can be due to the way the thermometers work. The alcohol thermometers measure increases in temperature by red-pigmented ethanol expanding across a capillary while the electronic thermometers (Fisherbrand™) use a metallic sensor to record the temperature.

The alcohol thermometers are very sensitive to motion and vibrations, which can affect the capillary distance where the ethanol will expand. In this study, the thermometers were left inside the medium, but made contact with the surface of the well, which was vibrating. It can be speculated that the 1000Hz vibration could enhance the expansion of ethanol in the capillary, and thus recording a higher temperature than what was recorded by the electronic sensor. The alcohol thermometer in the control tube measured exactly 37°C, and so did the electronic sensor.

It can be suggested that the difference in the recorded temperature is a result of thermometer differences, rather than real representation of medium temperature. In addition, since the sensor is less affected by the vibrations, then the measurements done with the electron thermometer can be considered more accurate depictions of the medium's temperature (Figure 4.11).

4.4.4. Importance of temperature assessment for biology work.

Temperature can affect the way lymphocytes function. Increased temperature has shown to affect the stiffness (i.e. Young modulus) of Jurkat cells, particularly by decreasing it and making the cells softer (M. Li *et al.*, 2015). These changes can interfere with the way Jurkat cells sense and respond to the mechanics of their environment, as well as how they interact between themselves and other cell types (M. Li *et al.*, 2015). In addition, increases in temperature, as in fever, have shown to affect Jurkat and primary CD4⁺ lymphocytes by enhancing their IL-2 production for both strong and weak CD28 co-stimulation, as well as changing the plasma membrane fluidity and macromolecular clustering (Zynda *et al.*, 2015).

Alterations in temperature could add another variable parameter in the stimulation, so it was imperative to ensure no difference in temperature existed in the vibrated medium compared to the sitting control. By validating that the bioreactor does not alter the medium's temperature, the qualitative experiment described in this chapter ruled out any temperature influence on the cell behaviour.

Chapter 5

In vitro assessment of Jurkat T cell responsiveness to the 1000Hz nanovibrational stimulation

Abstract

Many studies in the past decades have shown that cells are capable of sensing and responding to mechanical stimulation. In this chapter, the human T cell leukaemia (Jurkat) cells were used as a model to investigate the effects of nanovibrational stimulation (1000Hz) on T cell activation. The response to the 1000Hz stimulation was assessed by regulation of expression of genes encoding for activation markers *IL-2*, *IL2RA (CD25)*, and *NFAT2 (NFATc1)*, and genes encoding for mechanosensors *PIEZO1*, *PKD1* and *PKD2*. The secretion of IL-2 in the supernatant was also investigated. Whether the Jurkat cells respond to the 1000Hz stimulation when applied in isolation was inconclusive, with sometimes results showing as if the Jurkat cells were responding to the stimulation, and other times not. An inconsistency in expression of genes between repetitive runs added more doubt to those results that could indicate response. The report and discussion of the gene expression patterns in Jurkat cells exposed to the 1000Hz stimulation are covered in this chapter.

5.1. Introduction

Human and mammalian cells are constantly exposed to different mechanical forces originating both externally (e.g. gravity, acceleration, touch, sound) and internally (e.g. fluid flow, blood pressure, membrane deformation, cytoskeletal contractility). The cells have evolved mechanisms to sense these mechanical stimuli and convert them into intracellular chemical signals which eventually cause alterations in gene expression and cell behaviour. This phenomenon is known as mechanosensation, and its signalling is called mechanotransduction (Fedorchak, Kaminski and Lammerding, 2014; Piperi, 2015; Tsimbouri, 2015; Robertson *et al.*, 2018). In mammalian cells, physical forces have shown to have an important role in many cellular functions such as stem cell differentiation (Engler *et al.*, 2006), cellular motility (Vogel and Sheetz, 2009) or tumour formation (Weaver *et al.*, 1997). In addition, the physical environment alters the behaviour of tissue cells. Muscle growth in response to exercise, bone remodelling based on their mechanical load, or endothelial cells

aligning under fluid shear stress, are examples of such influence (Fedorchak, Kaminski and Lammerding, 2014).

Research over past decades has shown that physical parameters of tissues can have an effect on immune cells and inflammation overall (Previtera, 2014; Kim *et al.*, 2019). As a matter of fact, the physical properties of tissues tend to be in physiological ranges (Previtera, 2014), which can be altered in disease states (Paszek *et al.*, 2005; Cheng *et al.*, 2006; Chatzizisis and Giannoglou, 2007; Akyildiz *et al.*, 2011). With focus on the T cells, many studies have demonstrated their ability to sense and response to physical parameters. The activation of CD4⁺ T and CD8⁺T cells as assessed by IL-2 production has shown to be greater when antigens are presented on softer substrates than on the rigid ones (O'Connor *et al.*, 2012). The effects of substrate rigidity are related to TCR mechanosensing because activation of naïve T cells on softer substrates has shown to be more linked to CD3 rather than costimulatory CD28 signalling (Judokusumo *et al.*, 2012). The triggering of TCR and activation of CD4⁺ T cells is affected by mechanical forces during antigen presentation (Hu and Butte, 2016). The mechanical forces affect the binding strength and interaction of the TCR with the antigen, resulting in TCR activation, regulation of Ca²⁺ signalling, and cytoskeletal arrangements in the T cells (Kim *et al.*, 2009; Hu and Butte, 2016; Ben-Shmuel *et al.*, 2019). The CD4⁺ T cell responses to stiffness parameters, include upregulation of different effector cytokines such as TNF- α , IFN- γ , and IL-17, surface molecules like CD69, IL2RA, ICOS and CD40L, and transcription factors like FOXP3, TBX21 and MYC (O'Connor *et al.*, 2012; Saitakis *et al.*, 2017; Liu and Ganguly, 2019). In addition, the mechanical forces are sensed and applied by the effector CD8⁺ T cells when they coordinate cytotoxic activities (Basu *et al.*, 2016; Ben-Shmuel *et al.*, 2019). The stronger the force exerted by the CD8⁺ T cells at the immune synapse, the faster perforins form pores on the target cell membrane, implying that force potentiates cytotoxicity by enhancing perforin activity (Basu *et al.*, 2016).

The importance of mechanosensation in T cells can be also implied by results of studies looking at mechanosensory proteins. It has been shown that the professional mechanosensor PIEZO1 optimises the T cell activation upon antigen presentation (Liu *et al.*, 2018; Liu and Ganguly, 2019), and in mouse models the same mechanosensor is involved in TCR activation in naïve T cells, Th17 cells and regulatory T cells (Dong *et al.*, 2017). There is

evidence that PIEZO1 channels are responsive for the mechanotransduction in response to forces generated upon TCR-pMHC interactions (Liu and Ganguly, 2019). In addition, physical parameters as temperature have also shown to affect T cells. Increased temperature can decrease the stiffness (i.e. Young modulus) of Jurkat T cells, making the cells softer (M. Li *et al.*, 2015). This process can affect the mechanosensation of these cells, as well as how they interact between themselves and other cell types (M. Li *et al.*, 2015). Increases in temperature, as in fever, have shown to enhance the IL-2 production in Jurkat and primary CD4⁺ T cells, for both weak and strong CD28 co-stimulation, as well as affecting the fluidity and membrane macromolecular clustering (Zynda *et al.*, 2015).

These studies have demonstrated that physical parameters of the tissues play important roles for the activation and behaviour of the T cells, acting alongside the well-identified chemical stimuli. In this *in vitro* study, the activation of Jurkat cells was studied upon mechanical stimulation with vibrations of 1000Hz frequency and nano-scale amplitude.

The nano-scale vibrational stimulation generated by the “nanokicking” method has shown to affect cell behaviour, particularly the mesenchymal stromal cells (MSCs) which have been experimented the most. MSC differentiation into bone cells has shown to be more efficient in the presence of vibrational forces (Nikukar, Reid, Tsimbouri, Riehle, Adam S G Curtis, *et al.*, 2013; Pemberton *et al.*, 2015; Tsimbouri, 2015; Robertson *et al.*, 2018).

Mechanotransduction in these studies has shown to include rho kinases (ROCK) and extracellular signal related kinase (ERK) signalling pathways (Nikukar, Reid, Tsimbouri, Riehle, Adam S G Curtis, *et al.*, 2013; Pemberton *et al.*, 2015; Tsimbouri, 2015; Robertson *et al.*, 2018). Nanokicking technique utilises the reverse piezoelectric effect to generate 1000 Hz vibrations of nano-scale amplitude. These vibrations have also shown to enhance processes associated with bone cell maturation (Pemberton *et al.*, 2015; Childs *et al.*, 2016), with some additional studies investigating their effectiveness on prokaryotic cells (Robertson *et al.*, 2018). Suspecting that a wide variety of cells may also be responsive to vibrational mechanical stimulation, this study investigates any effect they may have on T cell activation.

Jurkat T cells were chosen as a good model for studying T cell activation, and they have historically been utilised in *in vitro* studies that developed the field of immunology, contributing to the discovery of T cell receptor (TCR), antigen presentation processes, co-

stimulation and signal transduction in T lymphocytes (Weiss, Wiskocil and Stobo, 1984; Manger *et al.*, 1986; Abraham and Weiss, 2004). Here, the IL-2 regulation was assessed at mRNA and protein level, in addition to the regulation of genes encoding for T cell activation and proliferation marker *IL2RA*, and mechanosensors *PIEZO1*, *PKD1* and *PKD2*. T lymphocytes are the focus of this research based on their ability for developing and directing antigen-specific immune responses. These cells play important roles in human health as they are involved in the protection of the body from pathogens and tumours cells. However, they are also involved in several pathological conditions, such as autoimmunity and immunodeficiency. Understanding the effect of mechanical stimuli on immune cells can lead to optimisation of therapies which until recently have only considered chemical aspects in the outcome and effectiveness of disease treatments.

5.2. Methods

5.2.1. Jurkat E6-1 Growth

Jurkat clone E6-1 (ATCC® TIB-152™) were reconstituted from liquid nitrogen storage and allowed to recover for 2 weeks in cultures, splitting every 2-3 days. The culture medium needed for cell growth was composed of RPMI-1640 (ATCC, 30-2001), 10 % Foetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (Gibco, A3160802) and 1% Antibiotic-Antimycotic 100X mix (Gibco, 15240062). Cells were cultured in 25mL suspension, in T75 flasks. For such volume, they were harvested by mixing the suspension using a sterile pipette and centrifugation at 1400 rpm (260 x g) for 7 minutes. The cells were split into new suspensions at initial cell concentration of no less than 1×10^5 cells/mL. The cells were cultured at 37°C, 5% of CO₂ until ready for the experiments.

5.2.2. Nanokick bioreactor preparation

Plates (6-well plates) which would be clamped on the bioreactor had magnet sheets (First4Magnets, D-F4MA43MHP) attached at least 24 hours before the start of the experiment. The magnet sheets attached better with time by removal of the air pockets. The Nanokick bioreactor (model NTB3014) was incubated at 37°C for 2 days prior to the start of experiments, which was the temperature at which the bioreactor displacements were calibrated. In addition, incubation prior to the experiment was useful for avoiding condensation upon immediate translocation of the bioreactor from room temperature into incubator environment.

5.2.3. Mechanical stimulation experimental set up

Jurkat E6-1 cells underwent 1000Hz stimulation on magnet-clamped 6-well plates, with six replicates incubated for 24 hours and the other six for 48 hours. Time-point respective control samples were also incubated similarly, but they were not stimulated. Each replicate contained 3×10^5 cells in 2mL (1.5×10^5 cells/mL) suspension of complete media, prepared as described above. The experiments took place at 37°C, 5% CO₂, and 95% air incubator as recommended for the Jurkat E6-1 cells (LEEC, 190D CO₂). Three repetitive and identical experiments were performed in order to confirm the observations and assess reproducibly.

5.2.4. RNA extraction

After the stimulation periods of 24 and 48 hours, the cells were collected and transferred into respectively labelled 15mL tubes. The cells were pelleted by centrifugation at 1300 rpm (224 x g) for 7 minutes. The RNA from the pelleted Jurkat cells was extracted using the Ribozol-chloroform method for cells in suspension as recommended by the manufacturers (VWR LifeScience, 9508-200 mL). The cells were lysed using 1 mL Ribozol solution and homogenised using a 25g syringe. The RNA extraction from the lysed cells in Ribozol solution was done by separating the aqueous phase after addition of 0.2mL chloroform and centrifugation at 13000 rpm (17950 x g) for 15 minutes at 4°C. The RNA was washed with isopropanol and 75% ethanol and stored in 30µL of nuclease-free water (Gibco, 10977035). Quantification of the RNA in ng/µL was done on Nanodrop 1000, using the RNA nucleic acid programme.

5.2.5. DNase treatment

The DNase treatment was performed following the protocol of DNA-free Kit (Invitrogen Thermofisher Scientific, AM1906), in order to degrade any genomic DNA present in the RNA solutions. The maximum RNA concentration for each sample was 5µg per 50µL DNase reaction.

5.2.6. Complementary DNA synthesis

The synthesis of cDNA was performed as instructed on the protocol of High-Capacity cDNA Reverse transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems, 4368814). The reaction was comprised of 10µL of 2X Reverse transcription mastermix and 10µL of purified RNA solution from the previous step. Reaction was started by warming at 25°C for 10 minutes, followed by incubation at 37°C for 2 hours for the synthesis of the cDNA, and termination of reaction at 85°C for 5 minutes. The newly synthesised cDNA was stored at -20°C until used for PCR reactions.

5.2.7. Real-time PCR

The PCR gene amplifications were performed in 25 µL reactions containing 12.5 µL SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied Biosystems™, 4309155), 0.5 µL Forward Primer and 0.5 µL Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1 µL of cDNA and topped up to 25 µL with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035). The collected C_T values were used for the ΔΔC_T relative quantification of expression, comparing the stimulated cells to the untreated controls. The

ΔC_T was obtained by comparison of C_T values of genes of interest to the mean C_T of housekeeping genes *GAPDH* and *TOP1* for experiment run 1 and run 3, and the mean C_T of housekeeping genes *GAPDH*, *RPL37A* and *ACTB* for experiment run 2. As a note, a defect in the melt curve of the housekeeper *TOP1* was detected for the run 2 during analysis and so the PCR work, including the molecular work, was repeated from beginning later in the project, on the stored original RNA. At that time, I had stopped using *TOP1* as housekeeper, and instead used the *RPL37A*, *ACTB* and *GAPDH*. In addition, for the repeated run 2, PowerUp SYBR Green (Applied Biosystems, A25742) was used for the preparation of reactions, with similar reaction set up as described above. This chapter presents the results from the validated run 2.

The primer sequences used for the amplification of *IL-2* transcripts in the first and third experiment run were *IL-2* forward 5'-GAATCCCAAACCTACCAGGATGCTC-3' and *IL-2* reverse 5'-TAGCACTTCCTCCAGAGGTTTGAGT-3'. The second primer sequences for amplification of *IL-2*, used in the second run were *IL-2''* forward 5'-AGAACTCAAACCTCTGGAGGAAG-3' and *IL-2''* reverse 5'-GCTGTCTCATCAGCATATTCACAC-3'. The primer sequences used for amplification of *IL2RA* were *IL2RA* forward 5'-GAGACTTCCTGCCTCGTCACAA-3' and *IL2RA* reverse 5'-GATCAGCAGGAAAACACAGCCG-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *NFAT2* were *NFAT2* forward 5'-CACTCCTGCTGCCTTACACA-3' and *NFAT2* reverse 5'-AAGATGCGAGCATGCGACTA-3'. The primer pair used for the amplification of *PKD1* were *PKD1* forward 5'-CGCCGCTTCACTAGCTTCGAC-3' and *PKD1* reverse 5'-ACGCTCCAGAGGGAGTCCAC-3'. The primer pair used for the amplification of *PKD2* were *PKD2* forward 5'-GCGAGGTCTCTGGGGAAC-3' and *PKD2* reverse 5'-TACACATGGAGCTCATCATGC-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *PIEZO1* were *PIEZO1* forward 5'-CATCTTGGTGGTCTCCTCTGTCT-3' and *PIEZO1* reverse 5'-CTGGCATCCACATCCCTCTCATC-3'.

The primer sequences used for amplification of housekeeper *GAPDH* were *GAPDH* forward 5'-CGAGATCCCTCCAAAATCAA-3' and *GAPDH* reverse 5'-TTCACACCCATGACGAACAT-3'. The primer pair used for the amplification of housekeeper *TOP1* were *TOP1* forward 5'-GACGAATCATGCCCCGAGGAT-3' and *TOP1* reverse 5'-CAGTGTCGCTGTTTCTCCT-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of the housekeeper *RPL37A* were *RPL37A* forward 5'-ATTGAAATCAGCCAGCACGC-3' and *RPL37A* reverse 5'-AGGAACCACAGTGCCAGATCC-3'. The

primer pair used for amplification of the housekeeper *ACTB* were *ACTB* forward 5'-ATTGCCGACAGGATGCAGAA-3' and *ACTB* reverse 5'-GCTGATCCACATCTGCTGGAA-3'.

The primers for *IL-2*, *NFAT2* and *GAPDH* were obtained from Dagna *et al.* (Dagna, Pritchett and Lusso, 2013). The primers for *ACTB* and *RPL37A* were obtained from Maeß *et al.* (Maeß, Sendelbach and Lorkowski, 2010). The primers for the amplification of *IL2RA* and the second primer pair for amplification of *IL-2* were purchased from Origene (Cat. number: HP200397 and HP200553). The primer sequences for *PKD1* and *PKD2* were obtained from Dalagiorgou *et al.* (Dalagiorgou *et al.*, 2013). Primers amplifying *PIEZO1* were designed using the NCBI primer design tool for the mRNA sequence NM_001142864.4, and primers amplifying *TOP1* were gifted by Dr. Fiona Menzies and had been designed for the mRNA sequence NM_003286.3.

5.2.8. ELISA for quantification of supernatant IL-2

On the third run, after separating the cells from suspension at 24 and 48 hours, the supernatant was collected for quantification of secreted IL-2. The supernatant was separated from the cells by centrifugation at 1500 rpm (300 x g) for 10 minutes and was carefully collected into new sterile 1.5mL tubes, avoiding disturbance of the pellet. The IL-2 in the supernatant of the Jurkat cells was measured using the sandwich ELISA method, for the quantification of the cytokine (Life technologies, EH21L22). The absorbance was measured using a plate reader (BioTek™, ELx800™) and the concentration was calculated using a standard curve generated from the reconstituted standards.

5.2.9. Statistical analysis

The data were presented as mean of six replicates \pm SE. Statistical difference of samples was calculated using unpaired T test with Welch's correction. The expression of each gene in the stimulated cells was compared to the untreated cells, separately for 24 and 48 hours. For analysing the ELISA results, unpaired T test with Welch's correction was used to compare the concentrations in the supernatant of the stimulated cells versus the untreated cells at 24 and 48 hours. Statistical analysis was carried out using GraphPad Prism® version 6. P values <0.05 were accepted as significant.

5.3. Results

5.3.1. Experiment run 1: *IL-2* and *PKD2* expression was regulated in stimulated cells at 48 hours

The results from run 1 showed higher levels of *IL-2* mRNA in stimulated cells compared to the untreated control (1.89 fold higher) at 48 hours (Figure 5.1, B). At the same time-point, in the stimulated cell there were higher levels of *PKD2* mRNA than in the controls (1.29 fold higher) (Figure 5.1, B). There was no difference in mRNA transcript levels of *NFAT2* and *PKD1* in stimulated cells compared to the respective controls at 48 hours (Figure 5.1, B). No regulation was recorded in the stimulated cells at 24 hours (Figure 5.1, A).

Figure 5.1: Gene expression in 1000Hz stimulated Jurkat cells at 24 hrs (A) and 48 hrs (B), run 1. Fold expression was calculated using the $\Delta\Delta C_T$ method. The C_T values were normalised to the mean of housekeeping genes *GAPDH* and *TOP1*. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE of the mean. Statistical significance was determined by comparing stimulated replicates with the control replicates using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

5.3.2. Experiment run 2: *IL-2*, *IL2RA* and *NFAT2* were regulated in stimulated cells

The *IL2RA* mRNA levels were found lower (0.56 fold) in the stimulated cells at 24 hours compared to the control (Figure 5.2, A). No other gene was regulated at 24 hours (Figure 5.2, A). At 48 hours, there was no difference in *IL2RA* mRNA levels in the stimulated cells compared to the controls (Figure 5.2, B). At this time-point, the *IL-2* was upregulated 1.67 fold in the stimulated cells and the *NFAT2* was upregulated 1.29 fold, compared to the untreated controls (Figure 5.2, B). The gene encoding for mechanosensors *PIEZO1*, *PKD1* and *PKD2* were not regulated neither at 24 nor 48 hours (Figure 5.2).

Figure 5.2: Gene expression in 1000Hz stimulated Jurkat cells at 24 hrs (A) and 48 hrs (B), run 2. Fold expression was calculated using the $\Delta\Delta C_T$ method. The C_T values were normalised to the mean of housekeeping genes *GAPDH*, *RPL37A* and *ACTB*. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE of the mean. Statistical significance was determined by comparing stimulated replicates with the control replicates using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

5.3.3. Experiment run 3: *PKD1* and *PIEZO1* downregulated in stimulated cells at 48 hours.

There was no regulation of gene expression at 24 hours (Figure 5.3, A). At 48 hours, the *PKD1* mRNA levels in the stimulated cells were lower (0.66 fold) compared to the untreated cells (Figure 5.3, B). The *PIEZO1* mRNA levels were also downregulated at 48 hours in stimulated cells (0.74 fold) compared to the control (Figure 5.3, B). The genes encoding for the activation markers *IL-2* and *IL2RA* were not regulated neither at 24 nor 48 hours (Figure 5.3).

Figure 5.3: Gene expression in 1000Hz stimulated Jurkat cells at 24 hrs (A) and 48 hrs (B), run 3. Fold expression was calculated using the $\Delta\Delta C_T$ method. The C_T values were normalised to the mean of housekeeping genes *GAPDH* and *TOP1*. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE of the mean. Statistical significance was determined by comparing stimulated replicates with the control replicates using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

5.3.4. Concentration of IL-2 in the supernatant of untreated and stimulated cells

There was no difference in the concentrations of IL-2 in the supernatant of Jurkat cells that were stimulated with 1000Hz compared to the untreated controls at both 24 and 48 hours (Figure 5.4).

Figure 5.4: Concentration of the IL-2 (pg/mL) in the supernatant of control and stimulated Jurkat cells at 24 (A) and 48 hours (B). The supernatant was extracted by centrifugation at 1500 rpm (300 x g) for 10 minutes. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE. Statistical difference between the groups was assessed by unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

5.3.5. Relationship between *IL-2* expression, *IL-2* secretion and *IL2RA* regulation

The ELISA results showed that the *IL-2* accumulates in the supernatant of cells with time, because there were higher levels of *IL-2* detected in the supernatants from 48 hours samples, compared to those of 24 hours samples (Figure 5.5). A comparison of gene expression of *IL-2* and *IL2RA* in untreated Jurkat cells from run 2 and run 3, showed that the *IL-2* expression was steady with time, while the *IL2RA* upregulated with time (Figure 5.6). *IL2RA* at run 2 was upregulated 3.9 fold ($p^{***} = 0.0001$) (Figure 5.6, A) and at run 3 was upregulated 9.1 fold ($p^{****} < 0.0001$) (Figure 5.6, B). The differences in relative fold expression were due to the differences in the ΔC_T between the genes of interest and the housekeepers' means, but the pattern was reproducible (Figure 5.6).

Figure 5.5: Comparison of IL-2 concentrations in the supernatant of Jurkat cells between time-points of 24 and 48 hours. Statistical difference between the groups was determined by unpaired T test with Welch's correction. P values lower than 0.05 were considered significant.

Figure 5.6: Comparison of *IL-2* and *IL2RA* expression in unstimulated Jurkat cells between 24 and 48 hours. Results representative of experiment run 2 (A) and run 3 (B). Fold expression was calculated using the $\Delta\Delta C_T$ method, comparing the C_T values of the untreated cells at 48 hours with those of the untreated cells at 24 hours. The C_T values were normalised to the mean of housekeeping genes *ACTB*, *GAPDH*, and *RPL37A* for run 2, and *GAPDH* and *TOP1* for run 1. Statistical difference between the groups was determined by unpaired T test with Welch's correction. P values lower than 0.05 were considered significant.

5.4. Discussion

5.4.1 Discussing the results from the three experimental runs

The activation marker *IL-2* was recorded upregulated in stimulated cells at 48 hours in experiment run 1 and run 2, but not on the third run. The *IL-2* concentration in the supernatant of stimulated cells on run 3 was also comparable to the unstimulated control cells. The inducible *NFAT2* was recorded upregulated in stimulated cells at 48 hours in the second run. The transcription factor is involved in the calcineurin/NFAT pathway which signals downstream to the nucleus to induce *IL-2* expression in the T cells during activation (Macian, 2005). While *NFAT2* upregulation corresponds with the observed *IL-2* upregulation on the second run, this gene was not regulated in the first run, which also had *IL-2* upregulated at 48 hours. In addition, *IL2RA* (*CD25*), another marker of T cell activation and proliferation (Leonard *et al.*, 1985; Pekalski *et al.*, 2013), was not regulated at 48 hours. The *IL-2* can regulate the expression of its own receptor (Bismuth *et al.*, 1985; Kim, 2002; Kim, Imbert and Leonard, 2006; Liao, Lin and Leonard, 2013; Ross and Cantrell, 2018), so for increased *IL-2* expression and subsequent production, the *IL2RA* mRNA was expected to be increased at 48 hours as well. In addition, the *NFAT2* can regulate *IL2RA* expression by binding its promoter region (Schuh *et al.*, 1998; Kim, 2002; Kim, Imbert and Leonard, 2006), so there was further reason to expect *IL2RA* regulation in the second run.

One explanation for the lack of *IL2RA* regulation when *IL-2* upregulates at 48 hours, could be that the observed increase of *IL-2* mRNA does not influence the *IL-2* protein production, hence it can be suggested that no autocrine regulation of *IL2RA* took place. In addition to the existing literature (Bismuth *et al.*, 1985; Kim, 2002; Kim, Imbert and Leonard, 2006; Liao, Lin and Leonard, 2013), this autocrine effect was demonstrated in this study by the observation that the increased *IL-2* in the supernatant with time caused upregulation of the *IL2RA* expression (Figure 5.5, Figure 5.6). Another explanation could be that the *IL-2* has just started to upregulate at 48 hours, with the *IL2RA* expected to upregulate a bit later.

However, at 48 hours and later, the nutrient depletion (Wensveen *et al.*, 2011; Park and Pan, 2015), acidification of the medium (Bohloli *et al.*, 2016; Cherezova *et al.*, 2018), and/or cytokine accumulation (e.g. *IL-2*) (Figure 5.6), could potentially affect Jurkat cell responses. The increased cell number at 48 hours, in just 2 mL medium suspension, would result in fast nutrient depletion and build-up of metabolic products. The Jurkat cells are lymphoblasts and

actively proliferating, and depletion of nutrients with time has shown to actively induce apoptosis in these cells (Wensveen *et al.*, 2011). The nutrients and metabolism have also shown to influence the processes that lead to T cell activation and differentiation (Park and Pan, 2015). In addition, as the cells metabolise and proliferate, the metabolic products make the medium acidic as indicated by a shift of colour of the phenol red to yellow (SALK, YOUNGNER and WARD, 1954). Acidic pH has shown to increase the proliferation and reduces the drug-induced apoptosis in Jurkat lymphoblasts (Bohloli *et al.*, 2016). Changes in the extracellular pH have shown to affect the activity of the TRPV5 and TRPV6 calcium channels and regulate the entry and level of intracellular Ca^{2+} in Jurkat cells, with high pH increasing Ca^{2+} entry and low pH reducing Ca^{2+} entry (Cherezova *et al.*, 2018). The changes in the pH, especially acidosis, occurs during inflammation and in diseased tissues, and so the lymphocytes have evolved to be sensitive to such processes (Cherezova *et al.*, 2018). These changes in behaviour and intracellular signalling due to environmental influences on the cells with time can affect the gene regulation beyond 48 hours and limit the work due to decreased cell viability. In addition, these factors may have a random effect on the cells because they may not occur at the same rate and magnitude, causing phenotypical variances within the experimental and control populations. These influences could be ignored for strong stimulations that are known to have an effect the Jurkat cells, but for the 1000Hz “nanokicking” stimulation for which the cells’ responsiveness is unknown, it is better to avoid as many external influences as possible. To avoid these issues, in adherent cells, the old medium can be carefully removed, and fresh medium can be added, but since Jurkats are cells in suspension this is impossible to be performed.

The *IL2RA* was found downregulated at 24 hours on the run 2. The decline of *IL2RA* production would result in decreased response to IL-2 signalling which can potentially lead to decreased proliferation and clonal decline (Miyatake and Maeda, 1997; Swiatecka-Urban, 2003; Kim, Imbert and Leonard, 2006). The decline of Jurkat clones, however, would also affect the levels of *IL-2* and other gene transcripts compared to the control cells, which was not observed in the experiment. Without confirmation on the third run and no other response observed for any other gene at 24 hours, the *IL2RA* downregulation at that time-point in the stimulated cells of run 2 remains unexplainable. Furthermore, the lack of *IL-2* and *IL2RA* regulation in the third experimental run, casted doubts on the recorded

regulation patterns seen in the first two runs. These doubts were further supported by the results of IL-2 quantification in the supernatant, which did not detect differences in secreted IL-2 between the stimulated and control cells at 24 and 48 hours (Figure 5.4). The lack of reproducibility for the *NFAT2* results between the first and second run, when *IL-2* was upregulated, similarly raises questions and makes it necessary for more repetitive runs to be performed in the future.

The genes encoding for mechanosensors *PIEZO1*, *PKD1* and *PKD2* were randomly regulated, with *PKD2* found upregulated at 48 hours on first run, and *PIEZO1* and *PKD1* found downregulated on the third run. None of these genes were regulated in experiment run 2. Based on the randomness of regulation, the discussion of results about these genes was limited. Their pattern of regulation, when occurred in the respective experimental runs, resembles that observed in the chemical stimulation experiments, where *PKD2* was found upregulated and *PIEZO1* and *PKD1* downregulated upon activation of Jurkat cells, as shown in the previous chapter. However, due to the lack of reproducibility and limited observations in the three runs, the resemblance in regulation patterns could be a coincidence.

Because of the lack of reproducibility and the varying patterns of gene expression between the experimental runs, it cannot be established that the Jurkat cells respond towards the 1000Hz stimulation. The randomness of gene expression patterns across the three runs, even for results that looked promising like the *IL-2* upregulation in the first two runs, may be purely by chance or influenced by random parameters other than the 1000Hz stimulation, like metabolic or environmental stressors that build up in the medium at 48 hours. A comparison of the stimulation's amplitude with the expression was investigated to see any correlation. The first two experimental runs were performed around June - August 2018, while the third was performed in early February 2019. The corresponding amplitude ranges and variance of amplitude, as portrayed by the standard deviation of the mean, were taken from the calibration points close to the experimental periods. The comparison was performed using the amplitude values on the right side of the bioreactor, which was used for the 48 hours stimulation of Jurkat cells, and for which time-point the *IL-2* was found upregulated in the first two runs. From the Table 5., it can be seen that on the third run, there was a change in the range and variance of amplitudes, although not that high, which

could have contributed in lower *IL-2* fold expression and variance between the biological replicates resulting in loss of statistical significance. Could such correlation show that the alterations and variance of amplitude were responsive for the absence of *IL-2* upregulation in the third run? With caution, it must be stated that this could just be a correlation by chance, and that the comparison may not be valid because a response of Jurkat cells towards the stimulation was not established, but it was rather assumed. A better assessment would have been performed on the left side of the bioreactor, where the cells were stimulated for 24 hours, which had the greatest variance in generated displacements (amplitudes). However, with the only exception of the *IL2RA* in run 2, no other gene was regulated at 24 hours in all the experimental runs, showing no cell response towards the stimulation at this time-point.

Following the work presented in this chapter, the investigation of the Jurkat responsiveness to the 1000Hz stimulation continued with focus at actin cytoskeleton and gene expression patterns upon combined mechanical and chemical stimulations. This work is presented in the following chapters.

5.4.2. *IL-2* expression, secretion, and influence on the *IL2RA*

Past studies have shown that the *IL-2* can influence the expression of its own receptor, more specifically the *IL2RA* or CD25 (Bismuth *et al.*, 1985; Kim, 2002; Kim, Imbert and Leonard, 2006; Liao, Lin and Leonard, 2013). In this study, it was observed that there was an increase of *IL-2* concentration in the supernatant of unstimulated Jurkat cells with time (Figure 5.5). Interestingly, in mRNA level, the *IL-2* transcripts remained unchanged with time (Figure 5.6). This observation agreed with published bibliography, which has described *IL-2* production in Jurkat cells as constitutive (Pawelec *et al.*, 1982). However, the *IL2RA* transcripts were increased with time, most likely as a result of accumulated *IL-2* proteins in the supernatant (Figure 5.6). This interesting observation not only provided a good visualisation about the relationship between the *IL-2* mRNA, *IL-2* protein and *IL2RA* expression, but it was also linked to the design of this study. The accumulation of the *IL-2* with time is one of the parameters that could influence the cell behaviour at later time-points, hence it was decided to compare gene expression within time-points and not between 24 and 48 hours (i.e. comparing stimulated cells with the untreated control at 24 and 48 hours separately).

5.4.3. Aspects that remain to be studied in the future

More repetitive runs for reproducibility and confirmation of results must be performed in future studies. The gene expression upon 1000Hz stimulation, with some promising results like the *IL-2* regulation in the first two runs must be checked again in repetitive experiments. Unfortunately, the loss of bioreactors left side in early 2019, and changes in the whole platform in the following months, made the repetitions during this project impossible, as the bioreactor's stimulation had become variable and uncontrollable.

Furthermore, the gene expression should be followed by quantification of the IL-2 in the supernatant. This was performed only for the third run presented in this chapter. The ELISA quantification of the IL-2 can help determining whether the *IL-2* mRNA upregulations, if present, translate into higher amounts of IL-2 proteins. This can show the biological importance of such regulation when the fold expression in the stimulated cells is low, as recorded in this study between 1.5 and 2 fold, because for small amounts of mRNA transcripts that is most likely an insignificant response. If there is no change in IL-2 protein levels, the stimulation has little to no influence over T cell processes such as proliferation and clonal expansion.

In addition, assays to observe and quantify changes in proliferation and metabolism could also be performed, in order to reinforce the gene expression and ELISA results and conclude cell responses to the stimulation.

Furthermore, to address the *IL2RA* scenarios discussed earlier, for longer periods of stimulation beyond 48 hours, greater volumes of medium could be used to provide the cells with enough nutrients. The effects of the increased medium volume and cell density should be taken in consideration when estimating the physical forces that will be applied on the cells, as well as considering that the floating cells may get weaker stimulation compared to those close to the surface. Longer time-points may be necessary for investigating if there is any effect of the 1000Hz stimulation on the activation of primary resting T cells, however, the conditions for how long these cells can go without IL-2 supplementation or chemical activation should be taken under consideration (Raulf-Heimsoth, 2008). The application of the mechanical 1000Hz stimulation in combination with chemical signals (e.g. anti-CD3, anti-CD28, PMA or PHA), or on primary lymphoblasts that have been chemically activated, may

be preferred. In this PhD project, the basis for such work is provided in the experiments performed on Jurkat cells, presented here and in the following chapters.

Table 5.1: Gene expression patterns in Jurkat cells stimulated with 1000Hz vibrations in three repetitive experimental runs, at 24 and 48 hours. The stimulated cells were compared to the untreated controls, and the statistical significance was determined by unpaired T test with Welch’s correction. P values lower than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Experiment	Treatment	Regulation of genes											
		<i>IL-2</i>		<i>IL2RA</i>		<i>NFAT2</i>		<i>PKD1</i>		<i>PKD2</i>		<i>PIEZO1</i>	
		24hrs	48hrs	24hrs	48hrs	24hrs	48hrs	24hrs	48hrs	24hrs	48hrs	24hrs	48hrs
Run 1	1000Hz vs Untreated	No difference (p= 0.14)	↑ 1.89 Fold (p**** < 0.0001)	Not assessed	Not assessed	No difference (p= 0.78)	No difference (p= 0.9)	No difference (p= 0.07)	No difference (p= 0.82)	No difference (p= 0.82)	↑ 1.29 Fold (p*= 0.034)	Not assessed	Not assessed
Run 2	1000Hz vs Untreated	No difference (p= 0.74)	↑ 1.67 Fold (p** < 0.009)	↓ 0.56 Fold (p*= 0.019)	No difference (p= 0.19)	No difference (p= 0.32)	↑ 1.29 Fold (p* < 0.025)	No difference (p= 0.08)	No difference (p= 0.81)	No difference (p= 0.8)	No difference (p= 0.63)	No difference (p= 0.44)	No difference (p= 0.17)
Run 3	1000Hz vs Untreated	No difference (p= 0.64)	No difference (p= 0.07)	No difference (p= 0.71)	No difference (p= 0.1)	Not assessed	Not assessed	No difference (p= 0.12)	↓ 0.66 Fold (p*= 0.01)	No difference (p= 0.42)	No difference (p= 0.68)	No difference (p= 0.73)	↓ 0.74 Fold (p*= 0.03)

Table 5.2: Comparison of stimulation’s amplitude with *IL-2* gene expression. The increased variance of amplitude values might have affected the expression of *IL-2* in experimental replicates and resulted in loss of statistical significance. This must be approached with caution because the cell response is being assumed, but it was not concluded by the experiments.

Experimentation time period	Amplitude range (nm) Platform right side (48hrs stimulation)	Amplitude mean (nm) Platform right side	Standard deviation	Experiment	<i>IL-2</i> fold change 48 hours (stimulated vs control)	Statistical significance
May - August 2018	24 - 52	40.27	10.3	Run 1	1.89	p<0.0001 (****)
				Run 2	1.67	p= 0.009 (**)
January - March 2019	24 - 62	43.5	13.2	Run 3	1.43	p=0.07

Chapter 6

Effects of 1000Hz stimulation on actin cytoskeleton and polycystin 1 distribution in Jurkat cells; optimisation and experiments

Abstract

The effects of the 1000Hz stimulation on the actin cytoskeleton, cell shape and polycystin 1 distribution in Jurkat T cells were investigated in the experiments of this chapter by immunofluorescence. Actin cytoskeleton is involved in mechanotransduction in different cells, and in T cells it has shown to influence TCR signalling and processes occurring at the immune synapse. The mechanosensitive roles of polycystin 1 in T cells are unknown, however the protein is found expressed on these cells. PC1 distribution patterns could show changes in cell polarity, as well as interaction with actin cytoskeleton. However, the work on Jurkat cells proved challenging. The cells' small size, spherical shape and large nuclei occupying most of the cytoplasmic space made it difficult to determine any patterns of F-actin cytoskeleton or PC1 localisation. More dynamic responses were recorded for cells in the presence of chemical stimulants. This was used as a basis for the following work on the stimulation of Jurkat cells with combined mechanical and chemical treatment. An interesting observation from this chapter is the strong detection of PC1 in cells undergoing division, regardless of the stimulation.

6.1. Introduction

Morphologically, Jurkat cells are small lymphoblasts with a diameter of 10-20 μ m (Figure 6.1). The majority of their cytoplasmic space is occupied by the nucleus. Light microscopy can provide information about how healthy the cells look, their confluency, apoptosis, and a check of the medium sterility of the cell culture. However, while light microscopy can be used to observe some morphological changes in cells during experimental runs, such as cell size or apoptosis, it is not useful for observing responses such as cytoskeletal arrangements, protein locations and cell polarity. All these morphological changes could indicate cell responses to the mechanical stimulation with 1000Hz nanovibrations. In order to accurately visualise changes of actin cytoskeleton, cell shape and distribution pattern of the mechanosensor polycystin 1 (PC1, TRPP1), immunofluorescent staining of Jurkat E6-1 cells was performed in the experiments presented in this chapter.

Figure 6.1: Jurkat cells stained with Giemsa staining method. The cells are around 10-20µm in diameter, with their nuclei (purple), occupying most of the cytoplasmic content (blue).

The cytoskeleton is a central regulator and mediator of both mechanosensation and mechanotransduction (Osborn *et al.*, 2006; Ben-Shmuel *et al.*, 2019). Actin cytoskeleton is important for providing the cell shape, motility and polarity, which influences tissues and organs' shape and functions (Sánchez-Corrales and Röper, 2018). Misalignment of the actin cytoskeleton can lead to pathologies, as in the case of atherosclerosis where low fluid shear stress at arteriole branching causes deformation of endothelial cells cytoskeleton, which leads to problems with mechanotransduction, cell shape and disease phenotype (Osborn *et al.*, 2006).

Actin cytoskeleton plays an important role in lymphocyte mechanobiology. For example, force-dependent activation of the T cell receptor (TCR) requires cytoskeletal function (Comrie and Burkhardt, 2016). The process of actin polymerisation itself is a response driven by TCR and costimulatory signalling pathways, but actin also plays an active role in T cell activation by mechanosensation of forces exerted by the T cells and DCs at the immune

synapse (Comrie and Burkhardt, 2016). In Jurkat T cells, actin cytoskeletal-derived forces have shown to increase the mechanosensitivity of the TCR, and inhibiting actin dynamics has led to reduction of traction forces produced by the cells (Hui *et al.*, 2015). Similarly, in primary T cells, inhibition of F-actin dynamics has led to diminished force-dependent activation upon TCR-antigen binding, by reducing Ca^{2+} signalling (Hu and Butte, 2016). In addition, in natural killer (NK) cells, actin cytoskeleton is involved in processing signalling events, activation threshold, and generation of forces which are used in immune synapses (Ben-Shmuel *et al.*, 2019), while in B cells actin dynamics influence the spread of cells and force-dependant aggregation of antigens at the immune synapse leading to activation (Fleire, 2006) .

The expression and distribution of polycystin 1 in Jurkat cells was also investigated in the work presented in this chapter. Polycystin 1 (PC1, 460 kDa), is a large transmembrane protein that consists of 11 transmembrane segments, with a short intracellular C-terminal region (200 AA) and a large extracellular N-terminal part (3000 AA) containing several protein motifs (Qiu and Yu, 2013; Piperi, 2015). These include a G protein-coupled receptor proteolytic site, two cysteine-flaunted leucine-rich repeats, 16 Ig-like domains and a C-lectin domain. The terminal-C region contains a coiled-coil domain as well as a G protein binding site (Qiu and Yu, 2013; Piperi, 2015). Scientific data support interaction of PC1 with many proteins localised at focal adhesion points, adherent junctions, and desmosomes (Piperi, 2015), and its roles as mechanosensor have been investigated in kidneys (Nauli *et al.*, 2003), cardiovascular system (Qiu and Yu, 2013; Pedrozo *et al.*, 2015), bone (Xiao and Quarles, 2010; Dalagiorgou *et al.*, 2013, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2014) and the central nervous system (CNS)(Ohata *et al.*, 2015; Galati, 2016). In addition, it has been observed that PC1 regulates actin cytoskeleton and the direction of cell migration in epithelial cells (Yao *et al.*, 2014). PC1 has also shown to regulate actomyosin contractions in response to sensing extracellular stiffness (Nigro *et al.*, 2019). PC1 and actin interactions may also be involved in mechanotransduction in primary cilia and adherent junctions of epithelial cells (Retailleau and Duprat, 2014). Furthermore , in context of this study, since PC1 is involved in regulation of intracellular Ca^{2+} signalling (Mekahli *et al.*, 2013; Qiu and Yu, 2013), it may also contribute to the activation of the Jurkat cells in response to the 1000Hz nanovibrational stimulation.

The work presented in this chapter was designed as expansion of the previous experiments which investigated the responses of Jurkat cells to the 1000Hz stimulation, by providing visual data on any changes to the cytoskeleton and PC1 expression. In addition, this study looked at any effect that combination of the 1000Hz stimulation with chemical stimulation (i.e. PMA and PHA) can have on Jurkat cells.

6.2. Methods

6.2.1. Actin staining on cytopsin-attached cells

Cytopsin is a method which used centrifugation forces to fixate suspended cells on a slide surface. Two cell suspension of 5×10^4 and 2.5×10^4 cells/ml were centrifuged at 1300 rpm (equivalent to 500 x g in the cytopsin centrifuge) for 3 minutes and fixated with 4% paraformaldehyde for 10 minutes. The actin dye (ActinGreen™ 488 ReadyProbes™ Reagent) (Thermofisher Scientific, R37110) was prepared by diluting 30µL of the dye in 100µL PBS. ActinGreen Reagent is a selective, high-affinity F-actin probe conjugated to green-fluorescent Alexa Fluor® 488 dye (Ex/Em: 495/518 nm). 50µL of the ActinGreen solution were added on the cells, which were then incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes, protected from light. The stain was washed with PBS and eventually a coverslip was mounted on top of the cells containing Neomount DAPI mounting media (NeoBiotech, NB-23-00166-2), which also counterstained with DAPI (Ex/Em: 360/460 nm).

6.2.2. Cells stimulated on poly-L lysine coated coverslips

This experiment aimed to observe any morphological changes on Jurkat cells, by focusing on the actin cytoskeleton and the membrane. Cells underwent mechanical treatment (1000Hz), chemical treatments (40ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L), and a combined mechanical and chemical treatment (40ng/mL PMA, 1µg/mL PHA-L and 1000Hz), while the control cells were left untreated. ActinGreen™ 488 Probes were used to stain F-actin, whereas the membrane was stained using the carbocyanine dye NeuroDiO (CellBrite™, 30021) (Ex/Em: 484/501 nm). There were different coverslips for each dye.

Poly-L-lysine coated 12mm coverslips (EMS 72294-02) were put on the wells of 24-well plates. Cell suspensions containing 1×10^5 cells in 200µL on fresh medium (RPMI 1460, 10% FBS), or in medium supplemented with PMA and PHA-L for the chemically treated cells, were added on the wells containing the coverslips. The cells were incubated for 1 hour at 37°C, 5% CO₂ to allow cells to settle. After one hour, another 200µL of media (or supplemented media) were added to allow sufficient nutrients for up to 48 hours incubation. The coverslips were extracted at 24 and 48 hours after the cells were fixated with 4% paraformaldehyde for 10 minutes. The coverslips used for actin investigation were incubated for 10 minutes with 30µL of ActinGreen probes, protected from light. The membrane investigation dyes were incubated for 25 minutes with the 200µL carbocyanine-

RPMI solution. The coverslips were mounted on slides using the Neomount DAPI solution and incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes before observation.

6.2.3. Polycystin 1 antibody optimisation

This optimisation experiment was done in order to find the best concentration of anti-Polycystin 1 antibody for staining the Jurkat cells. The anti-PC1 antibody (bs-2157R-A594) is a polyclonal antibody conjugated with AlexaFluor®594 (Ex/Em: 590/617 nm), targeting the N-terminus region of the protein. The cells were plated on Ibidi 24 well μ -Plates (Cat: 82406) with a thin polymer surface and darker walls, optimised for immunofluorescence. The plates were coated with 1X poly-L-lysine (Boster Biological Tech, AR0003) for 24 hours, and 3×10^5 cells in 300 μ l suspension were added in the wells and incubated for 1 hour at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Then the supernatant was slowly removed, and cells were fixated on the surface with 4% paraformaldehyde for 10 minutes and blocked with 5% BSA, 1% ovalbumin in 1X tris-buffered saline (TBS) for 2 hours at room temperature. After it, antibody solution of 1:50, 1:100, and 1:200 dilutions of the main stock (1 μ g/ μ l), were added in each corresponding wells. Another well was left in TBS only, in order to assess auto-fluorescence of Jurkat clone E6-1. The plates were incubated at 4°C overnight and were counterstained with DAPI solution (NucBlue™ Fixed Cell ReadyProbes™ Reagent), for 10 minutes at room temperature protected from light.

6.2.4. Investigating the effects of 1000Hz stimulation in the presence of PHA-L

For this experiment, 300 μ l suspensions of 2×10^5 cells/mL were plated on 24-well plates and underwent different treatments, such as mechanical nanovibrations (1000Hz), chemical treatment (1 μ g/mL PHA-L), and combined mechanical and chemical treatment (1 μ g/mL PHA-L and 1000Hz). Control cells were left untreated. At the end of their stimulation period (24 and 48hrs), the cells were extracted in suspension and plated on Ibidi 24 well μ -Plates, and allowed to settle for 45 minutes at 37°C, 5% CO₂. After that, the cells were fixated with 4% paraformaldehyde, and stained using the anti-PC1 antibody (1:100 dilutions) as described above. At the end, the cells were counterstained with ActinGreen probes and NucBlue DAPI solution for 10 minutes each. Immunofluorescence was investigated by exciting the dyes at their wavelength and recording emission, using Olympus IX71 microscope, at 40X and 100X magnifications.

6.2.5. Quantification of PC1 expression in Jurkat cells undergoing mitosis.

The quantification of PC1 expression in dividing and non-dividing Jurkat cells was assessed by measuring the corrected total cell fluorescence (CTCF) using ImageJ. Measurement parameters such as the area, integrated density and mean grey value were collected for individual cells, on images randomly chosen from the results of the experiment described in paragraph 6.2.4. The images were taken at 100X magnification, because the small size of Jurkat cells was hindering the cell outlines in the lower magnifications. Similar measurements of the background were performed in non-fluorescent regions nearby the cells. The corrected total cell fluorescence was calculated using the formula:

CTCF = Integrated Density – (Area of selected cell X Mean fluorescence of background readings)

The CTCF corrects for difference that may occur in fluorescent signal due to the surface area of the cell, cell flatness, and background noise. This method has been described and utilised in published studies (Burgess *et al.*, 2010; McCloy *et al.*, 2014). The statistical comparison of CTCF data between dividing and non-dividing cell was assessed by T test with Welch's correction, using GraphPad Prism.

6.3. Results

6.3.1. Cytospin changes cell shape and probably damages cytoskeleton

The cells attached on the slides with the cytospin rotational force, seemed to have had damaged actin cytoskeleton. The cytoskeleton seemed damaged, with “wrinkle” formations and discontinued fibres (A-D) Some cells had lost their integrity, with only the nuclei and some cytoskeletal fibres remaining (B). Other cells had been strongly forced against the surface and each other, giving the illusion their cytoskeletons had merged together (D).

Figure 6.2: Actin staining of cytoskeleton on cells fixated on the slide with rotational force (100X). Cells were fixated by centrifugation at 1300rpm (500 x g) for 3 minutes, and 4% paraformaldehyde. F-actin (green) was stained by ActinGreen probes conjugated with Alexa Fluor® 488. Nuclei (blue) were stained by the Neomount DAPI mounting reagent.

6.3.2. Cytoskeletal changes when cells are stimulated with PMA, PHA and 1000Hz

Cells grown on coverslips showed changes in the actin cytoskeleton for the different treatments they underwent. The cells had weakly adhered in all slides, with fewer cells adhering at 48 hours.

At 24 hours, the PMA and PHA stimulation caused cytoskeletal changes, with cells extending cytoskeleton in order to adhere on the e surface. The control cells and 1000Hz stimulated cells had maintained their rounded shape. The highest amount of cytoskeletal changes was observed for the combined PMA, PHA and 1000Hz stimulation at 24 hours. The Jurkat cells for this stimulation were more active, more confluent and seemed to have adhered better on the surface of the coverslips.

At 48 hours' time-point, very few cells could be found on the coverslips. For the combined stimulation, there were only cytoskeletal and nuclear fragments spread throughout the slides. The cells at the control and those treated only with PMA and PHA seemed healthier than the cells stimulated with 1000Hz and combined treatment.

As a note: the larger nucleus size in the control cells at 24 hours and control and chemically stimulated cells at 48 hours is result of image cropping I wrongfully performed before realising it was changing the apparent size of the cells. This cropping could not be reversed because I had altered the original images, and by the time I started the analysis of the pictures the fluorescence in the original slides had decayed. The cropping of images was not performed for other treatments.

Figure 6.3: Jurkat cells undergoing different treatments on coverslips at 24 hours. 1×10^5 cells in $200 \mu\text{L}$ suspension was put in each well, containing poly-L-lysine coated coverslips at the bottom. At 24 hours, the suspension was removed and adherent cells were fixated chemically with 4% paraformaldehyde. F-actin (green) was stained by ActinGreen probes conjugated with Alexa Fluor[®] 488. Nuclei (blue) were stained by DAPI reagent. Changes in nuclear size are due to image cropping. Images taken at 40X magnification.

Figure 6.4: Jurkat cells undergoing different treatments on coverslips at 48 hours. 1×10^5 cells in $200 \mu\text{L}$ suspension were put in each well, containing poly-L-lysine coated coverslips at the bottom. At 48 hours, the suspension was removed, and adherent cells were fixated chemically with 4% paraformaldehyde. F-actin (green) was stained by ActinGreen probes conjugated with Alexa Fluor® 488. Nuclei (blue) were stained by DAPI reagent. Changes in nuclear size are due to image cropping. Images taken at 40X magnification.

6.3.3. Membrane changes in cells stimulated with PMA, PHA and 1000Hz

Cells stimulated on coverslips displayed changes in the membrane shape at 24 and 48 hours.

At 24 hours, the untreated cells had usual morphology: round cells with large nuclei. The PMA and PHA treatment had caused the membranes to spread and change shape. The 1000Hz stimulated cells were also round, but few had interesting membrane projections. The cells undergoing PMA, PHA and 1000Hz combined treatment, were “stickier” with spread membranes and close to one another.

At 48 hours, the results showed decline of the cells. There were few cells adherent for all treatments and fewer compared to the 24 hours. The control cells and those stimulated with PMA and PHA treatment were still healthy. Interestingly, in the presence of the 1000Hz stimulation, cells seemed stressed and had bubble like formations on their membrane, while the cells undergoing the combined treatment were dying as visible by their disintegrating membrane and nuclei.

Figure 6.5: Membrane of Jurkat cells undergoing different treatments on coverslips at 24 hours. 1×10^5 cells in $200 \mu\text{L}$ suspension were put in each well, containing poly-L-lysine coated coverslips at the bottom. At 24 hours, the suspension was removed and adherent cells were fixated chemically with 4% paraformaldehyde. Membrane (yellow) was stained by carbocyanine dye NeuroDiO. Nuclei (blue) were stained by DAPI reagent. Images taken at 40X magnification

Figure 6.6: Membrane of Jurkat cells undergoing different treatments on coverslips at 48 hours. 1×10^5 cells in $200 \mu\text{L}$ suspension were put in each well, containing poly-L-lysine coated coverslips at the bottom. At 24 hours, the suspension was removed and adherent cells were fixated chemically with 4% paraformaldehyde. Membrane (yellow) was stained by carbocyanine dye NeuroDiO. Nuclei (blue) were stained by DAPI reagent. Larger nuclear size for the control cells due to image cropping. Images taken at 40X magnification.

6.3.4. Polycystin 1 antibody optimisation results

Polycystin 1 was detected in Jurkat cells at all antibody dilutions. The brightest fluorescent was for the more concentrated solution (1:50). The fluorescence intensity diminishes with dilution, but nevertheless the protein is detectable using 1:100 and 1:200 antibody dilutions. The visual results showed that PC1 was upregulated in dividing cells, while being expressed uniformly across the membrane in normal and untreated cells. The Jurkat cells did not show any auto-fluorescence, for the filters used to excite the immunofluorescent conjugates in the experiments shown in this chapter.

Figure 6.7: Detection of PC1 (red) using the AlexaFluor594 conjugated anti-PC1 antibody, diluted 1:50, at 40X magnification. PC1 is detected around the cells (B, E, H), defining their shape (C, F, I). Nuclei (blue) stained with DAPI (A, D, G).

Figure 6.8: Detection of PC1 (red) using the AlexaFluor594 conjugated anti-PC1 antibody, diluted 1:50, at 100X magnification. PC1 was detected around the cells (B, E, H), defining their shape (C, F, I). Nuclei (blue) stained with DAPI (A, D, G).

Figure 6.9: Detection of PC1 (red) using the AlexaFluor594 conjugated anti-PC1 antibody, diluted 1:100, at 40X magnification. PC1 was very well detected for this dilution too (B, E, H), and the antibody helped localise the protein in the cells (C, F, I). Nucleus stained by DAPI (blue).

Figure 6.10: Detection of PC1 (red) using the AlexaFluor594 conjugated anti-PC1 antibody, diluted 1:100, at 100X magnification. PC1 was very well detected for this dilution and the antibody helped localise the protein in the cells (B, E, and H). Nuclei (blue) stained with DAPI (A, D, G).

Figure 6.11: Detection of PC1 (red) using the AlexaFluor594 conjugated anti-PC1 antibody, diluted 1:200, at 40X magnification. PC1 was detected around the cells (B, E, H), defining their shape (C, F, I). Nuclei (blue) stained with DAPI (A, D, G).

Figure 6.12: Detection of PC1 (red) using the AlexaFluor594 conjugated anti-PC1 antibody, diluted 1:200, at 100X magnification. PC1 was detected around the cells (B, E, H), defining their shape (C, F, I). Nuclei (blue) stained with DAPI (A, D, G).

6.3.5. Polycystin 1 and actin cytoskeleton in cells stimulated with PHA, 1000Hz and both

6.3.5.1. Untreated cells at 24 hours.

Untreated cells of the control wells at 24 hours showed usual Jurkat morphology and were at the expected confluency for this time-point (Figure 6.13). Large multinucleated cells and replicating cells were also observed. Polycystin 1 (PC1) was detected in all cells, but it was upregulated in the dividing cells. Very few disintegrating cells were visible. The cytoskeletal features and PC1 distribution become more visible at 100X magnification due to Jurkat cells' small size (10-20 μ m) (Figure 6.14).

Figure 6.13: Untreated Jurkat cells at 24 hours, at 40X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.14: Untreated Jurkat cells at 24 hours, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

6.3.5.2. Cells stimulated with 1000Hz nanovibrations for 24 hours.

The cells stimulated with 1000Hz nanovibrations displayed the characteristic Jurkat cell morphology (Figure 6.15). For this stimulation, cells were seen arranged in both clumps (Figure 6.16) and monolayer (Figure 6.17). The greatest changes in morphology were observed in the clump structures, for both actin and PC1 distributions (Figure 6.16, D, E). Polycystin 1 was detected stronger in cells preparing or undergoing division. Very few disintegrating cells were visible.

Figure 6.15: Jurkat cells stimulated with 1000Hz nanovibrations for 24 hrs, at 40X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.16: A cell clump from the 1000Hz stimulated Jurkat cells at 24 hrs, 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.17: Jurkat cells stimulated with 1000Hz nanovibrations for 24 hrs, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

6.3.5.3. Cells stimulated with PHA-L for 24 hours.

Cells undergoing chemical treatment with PHA-L were found mostly in clumps (Figure 6.18). The confluency of the cells that had adhered to the surface of the well was lower compared to the untreated and 1000Hz stimulated cells. Some disintegrating cells were seen for the PHA stimulation. The cell features were more distinguishable at 100X magnification (Figure 6.19, Figure 6.20). The expression of PC1 was different in the cells, uneven, and upregulated in the replicating cells. The changes in cell morphology were greater in the cells arranged in clumps, with actin and PC1 co-localising as shown by the formation of the yellow colour (Figure 6.19, F). Non-clumping cells were displaying the morphology variance expected in a Jurkat cell population (Figure 6.20).

Figure 6.18: Jurkat cells stimulated with 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ PHA-L for 24 hours, at 40X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.19: Clumped Jurkat cells stimulated with 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ PHA-L for 24 hours, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.20: Non-clumping Jurkat cells stimulated with PHA-L for 24 hours, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

6.3.5.4. Cells stimulated with PHA-L and 1000Hz for 24 hours.

The cells treated with PHA-L and 1000Hz were arranged in both clumps (Figure 6.22) and monolayer (Figure 6.21). The confluency of the cells that had adhered to the surface of the well was lower compared to the untreated cells and those stimulated only with 1000Hz nanovibrations, but seemed higher compared to the cells treated with PHA-L only. Some disintegrating cells were seen for the PHA stimulation. These dying cells seemed to be at a greater number for this treatment compared to the others at this time-point. The cells had adhered less than the untreated and 1000Hz-only treated samples and the confluency was visually similar to PHA-only treated samples (Figure 6.43).

Figure 6.21: Jurkat cells treated with both PHA-L and 1000Hz for 24 hours, at 40X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.22: Clumped Jurkat cells treated with both PHA-L and 1000Hz for 24 hours, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.23: Jurkat cells in small clumps treated with both PHA-L and 1000Hz for 24 hours, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.24: Jurkat cells treated with both PHA-L and 1000Hz for 24 hours, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

6.3.5.5. Untreated cells at 48 hours.

Untreated cells at 48 hours were confluent, although there were still spaces between them (Figure 6.). The cells had variable morphology, most of the cells were round with large nuclei, some were large and multinucleated and many had pseudopods, all normal characteristics of Jurkat population (Figure 6.25). Cell features were more distinguishable at 100X (Figure 6.26, Figure 6.27). Many cells stayed close to each other in clump-resembling structures (Figure 6.27), but cells were not tightly connected as when chemically stimulated. The PC1 expression was higher in some cells than the others, especially those undergoing or finishing the replication process. Very few disintegrating cells observed in population.

Figure 6.25: Untreated Jurkat cells at 48 hours, at 40X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.26: Untreated Jurkat cells at 48 hours, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.27: Untreated Jurkat cells at 48 hours, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

6.3.5.6. Cells stimulated with 1000Hz nanovibrations at 48 hours.

Cells undergoing 1000Hz stimulation at 48 hours were confluent and very similar in population morphology to the untreated cells. Large multinucleated cells, replicating cells and normal-looking cells were present throughout the samples (Figure 6.28). The cells were found forming a monolayer, but large clumps of cells were also present (Figure 6.29). The morphology of cells was characteristic of Jurkat populations (Figure 6.30, Figure 6.31). Expression of PC1 was varying in different cells and was higher in cells undergoing or finishing replication.

Figure 6.28: Jurkat cells stimulated with 1000Hz nanovibrations for 48 hrs, at 40X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.29: Jurkat cells stimulated with 1000Hz nanovibrations for 48 hrs, forming a large clump (40X). Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.30: Jurkat cells stimulated with 1000Hz nanovibrations for 48 hrs, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.31: Clumped Jurkat cells stimulated with 1000Hz nanovibrations for 48 hrs, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

6.3.5.7. Cells stimulated with PHA-L for 48 hours.

The confluency of Jurkat cells stimulated with 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ PHA-L was lower compared to the untreated and 1000Hz-treated samples (Figure 6.32). Most of the cells were found on large (Figure 6.33) or small clumps (Figure 6.34), and they had various morphologies and PC1 expression (Figure 6.32). Dying cells were visible in the samples undergoing this treatment at this time-point. The dying cells had their nucleus shrunk and fragmented, disintegrating actin cytoskeleton, and high PC1 content (Figure 6.34).

Figure 6.32: Jurkat cells stimulated with PHA-L for 48 hours, at 40X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.33: Large clump of Jurkat cells stimulated with PHA-L for 48 hours, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.34: A small clump of Jurkat cells stimulated with PHA-L for 48 hours, at 40X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F). In the image, a dying cell can be seen at the bottom of the clump, having a small bright fragmented nucleus (A), and disappearing actin cytoskeleton (D). PC1 is detectable in the dying cell (E).

6.3.5.8. Cells stimulated with PHA-L and 1000Hz nanovibrations for 48 hours.

Jurkat cells which were stimulated with the combined PHA-L and 1000Hz treatment were less confluent than the control and 1000Hz stimulated cells. They were arranged mostly in large (Figure 6.35) and small clumps (Figure 6.36). The cells in clumps had usual Jurkat cell morphology (Figure 6.38). Some clumps were very dense (Figure 6.37) and in some the cells were seen tightly attached to one another (Figure 6.39). Jurkat cells that had not clumped were also present (Figure 6.40). Many disintegrating cells found for this stimulation, which visually looked at higher levels compared to the others.

Figure 6.35: Large clump of Jurkat cells treated with both PHA-L and 1000Hz for 48 hours, at 40X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.36: Smaller clump of Jurkat cells treated with both PHA-L and 1000Hz for 48 hours, at 40X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.37: Dense clumps of Jurkat cells treated with both PHA-L and 1000Hz for 48 hours, at 40X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.38: Clump of Jurkat cells treated with both PHA-L and 1000Hz for 48 hours, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.39: Small clump of Jurkat cells treated with both PHA-L and 1000Hz for 48 hours, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.40: Jurkat cells treated with both PHA-L and 1000Hz for 48 hours, at 100X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

Figure 6.41: Jurkat cells undergoing PHA-L and 1000Hz treatment at 48 hours (100X). In this example image, there is a large multinucleated cell, having displayed actin projections upon contact with another cell, while having very thin actin around the borders (B, D). There seem to be at least 8 nuclei in such cell (A). The cells also expressed PC1 around it, and in the contact projections with the other cell (C, E). Such uneven cytoskeletal and protein distributions are potentially indicative of cell polarity at the interaction zone. The two cells in the vicinity had finished mitosis, had “folded” actin cytoskeleton, and strongly expressed PC1 (B-F).

Figure 6.42: Disintegrating cells seen at 48 hours in PHA-L and 1000Hz stimulated samples, at 40X magnification. Nuclei (blue) were stained with DAPI (A), F-actin (green) was stained with ActinGreen probes (B) and PC1 (red) was labelled using anti-PC1 antibody (C). Actin cytoskeleton (D), polycystin 1 distribution (E) and actin and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells (F).

6.3.5.9. PHA-L stimulation reduces adhesion of cells on the surface

As observed from the results above, in the presence of PHA, Jurkat cells tended to clump and were adhering less compared to the untreated cells and 1000Hz-only stimulated samples. While clumping was seen in all samples and treatments, it was more visible in the presence of the PHA-L (Figure 6.43), and could have resulted in cells floating away from the poly-L-lysine surface, and being unable to adhere. Differences in confluency of cells that had adhered on the surface were more visible at 48 hours, when the untreated cells and those stimulated only with 1000Hz had the higher confluency (Figure 6.43).

Figure 6.43: Comparison in cell confluency between treatments, at 40X magnification. F-actin was labelled green using ActinGreen probes, PC1 was labelled red using anti-PC1 antibody, and nuclei were stained blue using DAPI.

6.3.5.10. Visual comparison of cells between different treatments at 24 and 48 hours

In order to show population changes between treatments, four random pictures were selected for each treatment and time-point and presented together. Jurkat cell populations as observed at 40X are shown in the Figure 6.44. The image shows the small size of Jurkat cells at this magnification, the randomness of PC1 and actin distribution, and the uneven fluorescent signal coming from clumped or unevenly situated cells (Figure 6.44). The Jurkat cells have maintain their usual Jurkat morphology, with the expected variance in cell shape for these cell populations (Figure 6.44).

The cell characteristics become more visible at 100X magnification (Figure 6.45). The morphology of clamped cells and individual cells is more defined for this magnification. Variance in Jurkat populations existed, and PC1 was seen higher in cell preparing or undergoing division (Figure 6.45).

Figure 6.44: Comparison of Jurkat populations for different treatment at 24 and 48 hours, at 40X magnification. F-actin was labelled green using ActinGreen probes, PC1 was labelled red using anti-PC1 antibody, and nuclei were stained blue using DAPI.

Figure 6.45: Comparison of Jurkat cells for different treatment at 24 and 48 hours, at 100X magnification. F-actin was labelled green using ActinGreen probes, PC1 was labelled red using anti-PC1 antibody, and nuclei were stained blue using DAPI.

6.3.6. Polycystin 1 was strongly detected in dividing cells

Polycystin 1 fluorescence was stronger in dividing cells compared to the non-dividing cells. This observation was independent of the type of stimulation, because the dividing cells in untreated controls, and stimulated samples all had higher PC1 fluorescence than the rest of non-dividing cells. The dividing cells were identifiable because they were undergoing chromatin condensation, chromosomal separation, by the presence of an actin ring during the end of mitosis, or as two small daughter cells that had recently finished division (Figure 6.46).

The visual assessment was reinforced by measuring the corrected total cell fluorescence using imageJ. The mean CTCF for PC1 was 1.88-fold higher in dividing cells compared to the non-dividing cells (p value = 0.0011) (Figure 6.47).

Figure 6.46: Polycystin 1 was strongly detected in cells undergoing division, upon visual assessment of cells (red arrows). F-actin was labelled green using ActinGreen probes, PC1 was labelled red using anti-PC1 antibody, and nuclei were stained blue using DAPI.

Figure 6.47: Corrected total cell fluorescence of PC1 in dividing versus non-dividing Jurkat cells. The PC1 was expressed approximately 2-fold higher in cells undergoing mitosis (N=21) compared to the non-dividing cells (N=61). The statistical comparison was performed using T test with Welch's correction.

6.4. Discussion

6.4.1. Optimisation conclusions

Results showed that cytopspin may not be a good method for investigating cytoskeletal changes, as the centrifugation force could harm the cell structures (Figure 6.2). In addition, any morphological changes on the cells would be affected by the rotational force used to fixate the cells on the surface of the slide. The technique may be useful to optimise the volumes of antibodies and probes for use in staining, as it is a quick and easy method for fixating cells in suspension.

The antibody staining on the other hand showed that the AlexaFluor594 conjugated anti-PC1 antibody was able to detect the protein when the main stock ($1\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$) was diluted with blocking solution 1:50, 1:100, and 1:200 (Figure 6.7, Figure 6.8, Figure 6.9, Figure 6.10, Figure 6.11, Figure 6.12). The intensity visually dropped with every dilution, but nevertheless the PC1 was detected.

Another observation from the optimisation tests was that the best magnification for visualising the Jurkat cells was 100X, because they are very small, 10-20 μm in diameter. To put in the perspective, in a previous study using the "nanokicking" method, the mesenchymal stromal cell (MSC) nucleus alone was about 20-25 μm , whereas the whole cells were large, about 100-200 μm in diameter (Nikukar, Reid, Tsimbouri, Riehle, Adam S. G. Curtis, *et al.*, 2013). The small size of the cells made it difficult for observing cytoskeletal alignment. This was challenging because Jurkat cells have little free cytoplasmic space and are mostly spherical in 3D, in difference to the MSCs which tend to have a large and mostly flat cytoplasmic space.

6.4.2. Mechanical stimulation of cells grown on coverslips.

This initial experiment was followed by challenges. First, there was no way to quantify the vibrations or any resonance on the coverslip, as the liquid medium on top would distort the lasers path. Measuring the vibrations of the dry coverslips without the medium would not be representative of the real stimulation, as the liquid medium could alter the vibrations of the coverslip by preventing full contact with the surface of the well, or by adding resistance to the movement of the coverslip. Another problematic factor was that although the coverslip resided at the bottom of the well, there was a layer of liquid beneath it, so the

coverslip remained floating. A vibrating coverslip while floating can generate fluid waves on the edges, which can affect cells. This could be an issue because fluid dynamics cannot be ruled out as potential mechanical stimuli. Second, and more importantly from a biology perspective, the adherence of cells in the slides was low, with the majority of the population not attaching into the poly-L-lysine coated surface. Therefore, the results observed for this experiment may not be representative of the whole Jurkat populations.

Based on the observations performed on the cells that had adhered on the coverslips, at 24 hours there were changes of actin cytoskeleton and membrane shape for the treatments compared to the controls. The cells that underwent only chemical treatment (40ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L) had spread membranes and seemed “stickier” compared to the untreated cells and 1000Hz- treated cells, which had largely maintained their spherical shape. This can be attributed to their activation when stimulated with the drugs (Figure 6.3). The membrane spread in chemically stimulated cells was also visible when labelling the membrane with NeuroDiO dye (Figure 6.5). Interestingly, the greatest response at 24 hours was observed for the Jurkat cells treated both chemically and mechanically, with PMA, PHA and 1000Hz. In these cells the actin cytoskeleton showed that the cells were spread more than those treated only with PMA and PHA, had projections connecting each other, and their morphology was affected at a greater degree than in any other treatment (Figure 6.). This could be indicative of an enhanced response when the chemical and mechanical stimuli were combined. The membrane staining results for the combined treatment similarly showed spread Jurkat cells in stronger contact with one another, more than in any other treatment method at 24 hours (Figure 6.5).

At 48 hours, there was a decline of the cell clones. This was attributed to the very large number of cells per suspension (1×10^5 cells in 200µL), which by 48 hours would have cause the cells to overgrow, consume the nutrients and decline. This issue was fixed in the next experiment, which had 6×10^4 cells in 300µL suspension, to allow enough space and nutrients for the cells to grow.

While cell fragments and low cell density could be seen in the untreated cells, PHA-L stimulated cells and 1000Hz stimulated cells, the greatest cell death was for the combined chemical and mechanical stimulation, as evident by wide-spread nuclear fragments with remnants of actin filaments (Figure 6.4). Similarly, for the combined treatment, the

membrane staining showed that the cytoplasmic membrane had almost gone, leaving discontinued labelled fragments around small nuclear fragments (Figure 6.6). Another interesting observation at 48 hours was that the living cells undergoing 1000Hz stimulation were unhealthy-looking too. Their actin cytoskeleton was spread but also weakly fluorescent, and the F-actin filaments seemed discontinued (Figure 6.4). In support of this, membrane stain showed the cells with bubble-like formations on their membranes, which were indicative of apoptosis (Figure 6.6) (Zhang *et al.*, 2018). In apoptotic cells, caspases carry out proteolytic cleavage of proteins and cytoskeleton components such as actin and catenin (Kurokawa and Kornbluth, 2009), which would explain the discontinued actin lines seen in the cells at this time-point. During the final step of apoptosis, the plasma membrane will first undergo blebbing (formation of circular bulges), a transient stage which rapidly evolves toward bleb separation and generation of apoptotic bodies (Zhang *et al.*, 2018). This was clearly visible in cells which had the membrane labelled a 48 hours (Figure 6.6). The end stage of apoptosis are apoptotic bodies (Zhang *et al.*, 2018), which were visible in the combined treatment coverslips, and could be indicative that the cells stimulated by the combined treatment had a strong response by 24 hours, and a quick decline by 48 hours (Figure 6.3, Figure 6.4).

Due to the issues with cell death at 48 hours, it could be suggested that only the 24 hours observations were representative of possible cell responses. Such observations at 24 hours suggested that a stronger response existed for the combined chemical and mechanical stimulation, compared to the rest. The 1000Hz stimulation alone did not seem to affect the morphology of cells grown on coverslips at this time-point.

6.4.3. Actin cytoskeleton and PC1 distribution in Jurkat cells undergoing different treatments

The small size of Jurkat cells, their round 3D shape, and uneven cell outline due to small pseudopods made the investigation of the actin cytoskeletal morphology and PC1 distribution difficult to assess. As general observation, the PHA-L caused clumping of the cells and resulted in less cells adhering to the poly-L-lysine coated wells (Figure 6.43). The enhanced clumping of the cells undergoing PHA treatment could be related to the fact that PHA causes agglutination (Sharon, 2004). The clumps are also clones of cells with enhanced proliferation that do not detach from one another after mitosis, features that could be

related to the mitogenic and agglutination effects of PHA (Sharon, 2004). In addition, PC1 was strongly detected in cells that were undergoing cell division, showing that the protein expression was affected by the cell cycle (Figure 6.46).

At 24 hours, it was observed that the more dynamic changes had occurred in the presence of PHA-L, where the Jurkat cells were clumped and displayed uneven actin and PC1 distribution patterns. Actin and PC1 were outlining the cell to cell contact areas between the clumped Jurkats, as shown by yellow colour in the merged fluorescent channels (Figure 6.19, Figure 6.45). The cells stimulated with 1000Hz seemed to be arranged in clusters at a greater extent than the untreated cells, as seen in 40X magnification (Figure 6.44). Although the cell in some of the clumps for the 1000Hz treatment were displaying interesting features (Figure 6.19), such morphologies could be comparable to those of cell clumped in other treatments and the untreated cells, especially around large multinucleated Jurkats (Figure 6.45). The treatments were not showing any major influence to the cytoplasmic space or spreading of the cells, with few rare exceptions in populations (Figure 6.45). The greatest changes in morphology were for cells in the clumps, probably because of cell-to-cell interactions and cell distortion due to localisation in the clumps (Figure 6.45).

At 48 hours, there was no difference in cell populations in the untreated and 1000Hz stimulated samples (Figure 6.44). No differences in individual cells were observed between these conditions as well (Figure 6.45). The cells stimulated with PHA-L or combined PHA and 1000Hz were mostly arranged in clumps (Figure 6.44). It was observed that for the combined treatment, many of the clumps seemed to be more tightly connected to one another (Figure 6.39). This could indicate either enhanced cell contact or enhanced proliferation, causing the cells to divide fast but not detach after mitosis. It must be noted that this is a qualitative assessment, and position of the clump can influence perception about how tight the cells are connected. In addition, tight clumps could also be seen for cells stimulated with PHA-L only (Figure 6.34). Another interesting observation was that there were greater numbers of dying or disintegrating cells in the presence of the PHA-L, compared to the untreated and 1000Hz stimulated populations. These cells were detected by nuclear fragmentation, weak and disrupted F-actin, as well as PC1 detection on what was remaining of the cells membrane compartments around nuclear fragments (Figure 6.42). It seemed from observation that these disintegrating cells were at greater numbers for the

combined PHA-L and 1000Hz treatment, compared to the PHA-L stimulation alone. This could be indicative of enhanced Jurkat cell proliferation, followed by increased apoptotic rate. However, this was also qualitative observation and did not quantify cell death, making it subjective to assume differences between the PHA-only and the combined stimulation, or assess proliferation or apoptotic rates in Jurkat cells undergoing the combined treatment.

6.4.4. Polycystin 1 upregulation in dividing cells

Another interesting observation from the immunofluorescent staining was that polycystin 1 was upregulated in dividing cells (Figure 6.46), a feature observed in all treatments, and during technique optimisation. The expression of polycystin 1 in dividing cells was about 2-fold higher than in non-dividing cells (Figure 6.47).

Loss of expression or function of polycystin 1 and/or polycystin 2 has shown to decrease proliferation of Epstein–Barr virus immortalized lymphoblastoid cells, which would result in decreased lymphocyte production (Aguiari *et al.*, 2004; Van Laecke *et al.*, 2018). In addition, kidney disease resulting from mutation of *PKD1* gene has shown to also be characterised by lymphopaenia (Van Laecke *et al.*, 2018). In leukaemic cell lines K562 and HL60, differentiation of the cells has been followed by downregulation of PC1, which was also followed by reduction of proliferation (Aguiari *et al.*, 1998). These studies have observed a direct relationship between PC1 and cell proliferation, which could explain why the PC1 was higher in cells preparing or undergoing division. Similarly to the haematological examples above, in colorectal cancer, overexpression of PC1 leads to more aggressive forms of disease, with higher proliferation rates (Gargalionis *et al.*, 2015). Inhibition of PC1 in colorectal cancer cells has resulted in decreased proliferation and suppression of epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition (Gargalionis *et al.*, 2015).

However, the roles of PC1 in cell division and proliferation are not fully understood and can be controversial. Some studies on other cell types have shown that PC1 overexpression is indirectly related to proliferation. PC1 has been considered an onco-suppressor, which when overexpressed can halt cell cycle at G₀/G₁ phase and induce apoptosis in HepG2, A549, and SW480 cancerous lines, partially through Wnt and a caspase-dependent pathway (Zheng *et al.*, 2008). In kidney cells, inhibition of expression or loss of PC1 has led to increased proliferation, resulting in oscillations of intracellular Ca²⁺, triggering nuclear factor of activated T cell (NFAT) activation and leading to cell cycle progression (Aguiari *et al.*,

2008). In addition, in kidney epithelial cells, PC1 has shown to control the ERK-dependent phosphorylation of tuberin, resulting in the downregulation of mTOR and its downstream targets p70S6K and 4EBP1, while loss of PC1 has led to activation of mTOR and increased cell size and proliferation (Distefano *et al.*, 2009). Furthermore, PC1 has shown to exert control of the cell cycle by STAT1/p21^{waf1} signalling, and mutations of the protein can prevent activation of the pathway leading to cell proliferation (Bhunja *et al.*, 2002). In addition to the studies involving cancerous cell lines, loss of PC1 expression has led to increased proliferation of keratinocytes through activation of ERK-dependent mTOR pathway in psoriasis, and autoimmune disease affecting the skin (Gargalionis *et al.*, 2018).

It is possible that the roles of PC1 vary cell to cell, particularly those associated with proliferation. For example, in different cancer cells the relationship between PC1 and proliferation is dependent on the main characteristic pathways that predominate in particular cell types (Papavassiliou *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, with caution it can be suggested that there could be a direct link between PC1 protein expression and Jurkat cells division and/or proliferation, similar to other haematological studies involving immortalised lymphoblastoid cells (Aguiari *et al.*, 2004; Van Laecke *et al.*, 2018), and leukaemic cell lines K562 and HL60 (Aguiari *et al.*, 1998).

6.4.5. Overall challenges and rationale for following experiments

The 3D spherical shape, small and varying size, and cell outline of Jurkats was a challenge in the assessment of actin cytoskeletal changes or PC1 distribution. The location of the cells, dispersed or in clumps, was affecting the shape and intensity emitted from the fluorophores. For examples, some cells were sitting on top of the others, and by focusing on the lower ones, the cells on top would appear as a bright light, affecting the recorded fluorescence from the cells beneath. In tightly packed clumps, the cells' outline and shapes were even more difficult to assess. The cells stimulated with PHA-L were mostly clumped, which made the confluency appear lower, a factor that would also have affected the quantification of fluorescent signal for whole population. For these reasons, the quantification of the fluorescence for whole images was not performed due to inaccuracies that would result from such factors. Due to the inability to quantify fluorescence for whole stimulated populations, it was decided that following experiment would try to quantify

fluorescent signal by flow cytometry. Future work may need to involve confocal microscopy or 3D scanning microscopy to address the issues related to the shape of the Jurkat cells.

The quantification of PC1 expression was performed for individual cells, using the corrected total cell fluorescence equation as described in published studies (Burgess *et al.*, 2010; McCloy *et al.*, 2014). This method circumvents some of the issues with Jurkat cells such as the variance in cell size and surface area, while considering any background fluorescent signal. However, the technique was difficult to apply for cells arranged in dense clumps.

Clumping and problems with adhesion affected the cell numbers and confluency. The lower confluency for the PHA samples could be due to the fact that PHA clumps the cells and the floating clumps attach weakly to the poly-L-lysine, or that the large clumps attached only on one side are detached easily from the surface as the suspension is removed. Furthermore, the confluency could be similar to the controls, but most of the PHA-L stimulated samples were arranged in large clumps, giving the impression of low confluency (Figure 6.37).

Quantification of cell proliferation by counting DAPI stained nuclei in this case would be inaccurate, so in the next experiments, a proliferation assay for cells in suspension was chosen to assess the growth rate of the cells.

The apoptosis of Jurkat cells, as observed in the above experiments by characteristic disintegration patterns cannot be quantified simply by immunofluorescent staining, as many of the dead cells could not adhere or were removed with the suspension. In the following experiments, it was decided that the apoptosis in the Jurkat population upon stimulation was determined by flow cytometry for detection of apoptotic markers.

Overall, from the limited observations on cells grown on coverslips for 24 hours and actin and PC1 distribution experiment, it was hypothesised that the Jurkat cells may respond to the combination of the mechanical and chemical stimuli. Although no conclusion for such hypothesis was determined in the immunofluorescent experiments, the results of this work proved helpful in designing the following experiments which aimed to test the responses to the combined PHA-L and 1000Hz stimulation, presented in the next chapter.

Chapter 7

Assessment of Jurkat T cell activation in response to the combined PHA-L and 1000Hz stimulation

Abstract

In the previous chapters, the effects of 1000Hz stimulation on gene expression and on cytoskeletal arrangements and cell morphologies showed inconclusive results. The *IL-2* expression analysis upon 1000Hz stimulation had shown that the *IL-2* transcripts were upregulated at 48 hours in two experimental runs, but the expected relationship with other markers such as *IL2RA* was not observed and on the third run no regulation was reported. The morphology studies were also largely inconclusive due to challenges arising from Jurkat 3D shape and small size, with the exception that some effect could be present in the combined stimulation, such as enhanced cell to cell contact and clumping. It was hypothesised that a response could be better assessed when using the 1000Hz nanovibrations as co-stimuli. This was also based on rationale from mechanobiology studies of T cells which have shown that mechanical forces optimise TCR triggering. At the same time, the work presented here took under consideration many optimisation aspects concluded from challenges of the first experiments and expanded the number of techniques used for assessing cellular responses. Overall, from the experimental results of this chapter, it can be suggested that a response to the mechanical 1000Hz stimulation is possible if it is combined with the chemical stimulant PHA-L.

7.1. Introduction.

Many of the studies that have assessed the activation of T cells in response to mechanical cues have used the mechanical stimuli in addition to the established TCR and co-stimulatory signals. The mechanosensation of CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells for softer substrates, which has resulted in enhanced IL-2 production has been linked to forces affecting TCR-CD3 signalling, more than the co-stimulatory CD28 signalling (Judokusumo *et al.*, 2012; O'Connor *et al.*, 2012). Other studies have demonstrated that the direction of forces applied on the TCR upon specific pMHC ligation affects the signalling, with TCR being an anisotropic mechanosensor capable of converting the mechanical stimuli into biochemical ones (Kim *et al.*, 2009), and that the magnitude, duration and frequency of forces applied upon TCR-

pMHC ligation affect activation of T cells by prolonging the lifetime of TCR-pMHC bonds allowing for stronger Ca^{2+} signalling (Liu *et al.*, 2014). Similarly, in studies that have shown involvement of the actin cytoskeleton and the professional mechanosensor channel PIEZO1 in T cell mechanotransduction, the physical forces have had an additional effect to the TCR triggering upon antigen presentation by stabilising the immune synapse and TCR-pMHC interaction (Hu and Butte, 2016; Ben-Shmuel *et al.*, 2019; Liu and Ganguly, 2019).

Furthermore, the enhanced IL-2 production in Jurkat and primary T cells upon increasing the temperature, has shown to be an additional effect of thermal forces to mostly anti-CD3 stimulation, but also anti-CD28 co-stimulation at a weaker degree (Zynda *et al.*, 2015).

So, the above-mentioned studies have shown that the physical parameters and mechanical stimuli can affect the T cell activation by acting as additional signals needed for the triggering of the TCR and intracellular signalling. In order to replicate such methodology, the experiment presented in this chapter were designed to use a combination of chemical and mechanical stimuli. The phytohaemagglutinin (PHA-L), was used for the chemical stimulation, because it can cross-link the CD3 and induce downstream TCR signalling (Weiss, Wiskocil and Stobo, 1984; Ohtsuka, Kaziro and Satoh, 1996). The simultaneous mechanical stimulation comprised of vibrations of 1000Hz frequency and 20 – 60 nm amplitude range.

The aim of such experiment was to use the combination of the chemical (PHA-L) and mechanical (1000Hz vibrations) stimulation on Jurkat cells and assess their responses in context of T cell activation. The response was assessed by gene regulation, quantification of IL-2 production, cell growth assays and apoptotic assays using flow cytometry. Genes investigated in order to determine response include the activation markers *IL-2* and *IL2RA*, as well as those encoding for mechanosensors *PIEZO1*, *PKD1* and *PKD2*, and transcription factors such as *NFAT2* and *LEF-1*.

In addition, due to inability to quantify the fluorescent signal of polycystin 1 from the immunofluorescent experiment of the previous chapter, an attempt to quantify the expression in response to PMA stimulation by flow cytometry took place.

7.2. Methods

7.2.1. Jurkat E6-1 Growth

Jurkat clone E6-1 cells (ATCC® TIB-152™) were reconstituted from liquid nitrogen storage and allowed to recover for 2 weeks in cultures, splitting every 2-3 days. The culture medium needed for cell growth was composed of RPMI-1640 with L-glutamine (Capricorn Scientific, RPMI-HA), 10 % Foetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (Gibco, A3160802) and 1% Antibiotic-Antimycotic 100X mix (Gibco, 15240062). The cells were cultured at 37°C, 5% CO₂ until ready for the experiments.

7.2.2. Nanokick bioreactor preparation

Plates (24-well plates) which would be clamped on the bioreactor had magnet sheets (First4Magnets, D-F4MA43MHP) attached 48 hours before the start of the experiment. The magnet sheets attached better with time by elimination of the air pockets. The Nanokick bioreactor (model NTB3014) was incubated at 37°C for 2 days prior to the start of experiments, which was the temperature at which the bioreactor displacements were calibrated. In addition, incubation prior to the experiment was useful for avoiding condensation upon immediate translocation of the bioreactor from room temperature to the incubator's environment, avoiding precipitation of water on top of the platform. The vibrations applied in the experiments of this chapter had a frequency of 1000Hz and amplitude range of 20-60 nm.

7.2.3. Experimental set up

For the experiments, the Jurkat cells in cultures were collected from T75 flasks (25mL suspension) and pelleted by centrifugation at 1500 rpm (300 x g) for 10 minutes.

The first experiment involved 6 replicates of untreated cells, 6 replicates of PHA-treated cells and 6 replicates of PHA and 1000Hz treated cell, for 24 and 48 hours. The untreated cells were diluted at a concentration of 5×10^5 cells/mL in complete growth medium and 500µL suspension were added in the control wells. The cells which would undergo PHA-L and combined PHA-L + 1000Hz treatment were diluted at a concentration of 5×10^5 cells/mL, similar to the untreated samples, but in complete medium supplemented with PHA-L (Sigma Aldrich, 11249738001) at a concentration of 1 µg/mL. Then 500µL of cell suspension was added in the respective wells. The cells undergoing the combined treatment were added in

a magnet-clamped plate and put on the bioreactor. Cells were allowed to rest for 10 minutes before the nanovibrational stimulation started. The experiment took place at 37°C, 5% CO₂, 95% air incubator as recommended for the Jurkat E6-1 cells (LEEC 190D CO₂).

The second experiment was designed to further investigate the responses towards the combined stimulation at 24 hours, by comparing a control group of PHA-L stimulated cells to the experimental PHA-L and 1000Hz stimulated cells. Each group contained 7 replicates, but the cell number, PHA-L concentration and incubation parameters were identical as for the first experiment described above.

7.2.4. Supernatant collection and IL-2 ELISA

After 24 and 48 hours incubation periods, the cells were collected from the wells into 1.5 mL centrifuge tubes. The supernatant was separated from the cells by centrifugation at 1500 rpm (300 x g) for 10 minutes for the first experiment, and 4500 rpm (2693 x g) for 7 minutes for the second experiment. The supernatants were carefully collected into new sterile 1.5mL tubes, avoiding disturbance of the pellet. The IL-2 in the supernatant of the Jurkat cells was measured using a sandwich ELISA method, for the quantification of the cytokine (Life technologies, EH21L22). The absorbance was measured using a plate reader (BioTek™ ELx800™) and the concentration was calculated using a standard curve generated from the reconstituted standards.

7.2.5. RNA extraction

The RNA from the pelleted Jurkat cells was extracted using the Ribozol-Chloroform method for cells in suspension as recommended by the manufacturers (VWR LifeScience, 9508-200 mL). The cells were lysed using 1 mL Ribozol solution and homogenised using a 25g syringe. The RNA extraction from the lysed cells in Ribozol solution was done by separating the aqueous phase after the addition of 0.2mL chloroform and centrifugation at 13000 rpm (17950 x g) for 15 minutes at 4°C. The RNA was washed with isopropanol and 75% ethanol and stored in 30µL of nuclease-free water (Gibco, 10977035). Quantification of the RNA in ng/µL was done on Nanodrop 1000, using the RNA nucleic acid programme.

7.2.6. DNase treatment

The DNase treatment was performed following the protocol of DNA-free Kit (Thermofisher Scientific, AM1906), in order to degrade any genomic DNA that had contaminated the RNA

solutions during extraction. The maximum RNA concentration for each sample was 5µg per 50µL DNase reaction.

7.2.7. Complementary DNA synthesis

The synthesis of cDNA was done as instructed on the protocol of High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems, 4368814). The reaction was comprised of 10µL of 2X RT Mastermix and 10µL of purified RNA solution from the previous step. Reaction was started by warming at 25°C for 10 minutes, followed by incubation at 37°C for 2 hours for the synthesis of the cDNA, and termination of reaction at 85°C for 5 minutes. The newly synthesised cDNA was stored at -20°C until used for PCR reactions.

7.2.8. Real-time PCR

For the first experiment, the PCR amplifications were performed in 25µL reactions containing 12.5µL SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied Biosystems™, 4309155), 0.5µL Forward Primer and 0.5µL Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1µL of cDNA and topped up to 25µL with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035). The collected C_T values for *IL-2* and *IL2RA* were used for relative quantification of expression of each gene compared to the housekeeping gene *GAPDH*, using the $\Delta\Delta C_T$ method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001). The experimental C_T values were normalised one time with the untreated control for the assessment of gene expression in the two stimulation conditions, and another time using the PHA-L treated cells as a control for the assessment of gene expression in the PHA-L + 1000Hz treated cells alone.

For the second experiment, the PCR reactions were carried out using the PowerUp SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied Biosystems, A25742), with similar volumes as described for the first experiment. The relative expression of genes was calculated using the $\Delta\Delta C_T$ method, where the ΔC_T was assessed as difference of the C_T of genes of interest minus the C_T mean of three housekeeping genes, *GAPDH*, *ACTB* and *RPL37A*. The $\Delta\Delta C_T$ was the difference of the ΔC_T of each sample to the mean ΔC_T of the control cells stimulated only with PHA-L. The fold change was calculated using the equation $2^{(-\Delta\Delta C_T)}$ as described in the Livak's method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001).

The primer sequences for amplification of the housekeeper *GAPDH* transcripts were *GAPDH* forward 5'-CGAGATCCCTCCAAAATCAA-3' and *GAPDH* reverse 5'-TTCACACCCATGACGAACAT-

3'. The primer pair used for amplification of the housekeeper *ACTB* transcripts were *ACTB* forward 5'-ATTGCCGACAGGATGCAGAA-3' and *ACTB* reverse 5'-GCTGATCCACATCTGCTGGAA-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of the housekeeper *RPL37A* transcripts were *RPL37A* forward 5'-ATTGAAATCAGCCAGCACGC-3' and *RPL37A* reverse 5'-AGGAACCACAGTGCCAGATCC-3'. The primer sequences used for the amplification of *IL-2* transcripts were *IL-2* forward 5'-GAATCCCAAACCTACCAGGATGCTC-3' and *IL-2* reverse 5'-TAGCACTTCCTCCAGAGGTTTGAGT-3'. The primer sequences used for the amplification of *IL2RA* transcripts were *IL2RA* forward 5'-GAGACTTCCTGCCTCGTCACAA-3' and *IL2RA* reverse 5'-GATCAGCAGGAAAACACAGCCG-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *NFAT2* were *NFAT2* forward 5'-CACTCCTGCTGCCTTACACA-3' and *NFAT2* reverse 5'-AAGATGCGAGCATGCGACTA-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *PIEZO1* were *PIEZO1* forward 5'-CATCTTGGTGGTCTCCTCTGTCT-3' and *PIEZO1* reverse 5'-CTGGCATCCACATCCCTCTCATC-3'. The primer pair used for the amplification of *PKD1* were *PKD1* forward 5'-CGCCGCTTACTAGCTTCGAC-3' and *PKD1* reverse 5'-ACGCTCCAGAGGGAGTCCAC-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *PKD2* were *PKD2* forward 5'-GCGAGGTCTCTGGGGAAC-3' and *PKD2* reverse 5'-TACACATGGAGCTCATCATGC-3'.

The primers for *IL-2*, *NFAT2* and *GAPDH* were obtained from Dagna *et al.* (Dagna, Pritchett and Lusso, 2013). The primers for the amplification of *IL2RA* were purchased from Origene (Cat. number: HP200397). The primers for *ACTB* and *RPL37A* were obtained from Maeß *et al.* (Maeß, Sendelbach and Lorkowski, 2010). The primer sequences for *PKD1* and *PKD2* were obtained from Dalagiorgou *et al.* (Dalagiorgou *et al.*, 2013). Primers amplifying *PIEZO1* were designed using the NCBI primer design tool for the mRNA sequence NM_001142864.4. The efficiency of the primers taken from literature has been assessed in the corresponding published papers (Maeß, Sendelbach and Lorkowski, 2010; Dagna, Pritchett and Lusso, 2013; Dalagiorgou *et al.*, 2013). However, the PCR efficiency for some of the primers used in the experiments of this chapter was also assessed in this project and recorded as 98.6% for *IL-2*, 97.2% for *GAPDH* and 95.6% for *IL2RA*.

7.2.9. Resazurin viability and proliferation assay

Cell viability and proliferation was assessed using the AlamarBlue® assay (BioRad, BUF012B). The assay was performed in 96-well plates, which contained 20 replicates of untreated cells,

20 replicates of PHA-treated cells and 20 replicates of PHA and 1000Hz treated cells. Each well contained 1×10^5 cells/mL in $100 \mu\text{L}$ of complete growth medium for the untreated cells and PHA-L ($1 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) supplemented medium for the cells undergoing PHA and the combined stimulation. The magnet plate for the cells undergoing the combined treatment was prepared 24 hours prior to the experiment, and the bioreactor was incubated for at least 24 hours at 37°C before the vibrations were applied. The Jurkat cells underwent the respective stimulation for 24 hours at 37°C , 5% CO_2 , and 95% air conditions. After that, $10 \mu\text{L}$ AlamarBlue[®] reagent were added in each well, and the cells were additionally incubated for 4 hours to allow the reduction of the reagent. During this period, the stimulations continued. At the end of the 4-hour period, the reduction of AlamarBlue[®] reagent was assessed by measurement of the absorbance at 570nm and 600nm, as well as by measurement of fluorescent intensity for 560nm excitation and 590nm emission. The apparatus used for the measurement of absorbance and fluorescence was SynergyHT plate reader (BioTek) and the software was BioTek Gen5.

7.2.9.1. Calculations of cell viability/proliferation.

The calculation of the cell growth was performed by normalizing with the untreated cells, using formulas provided by the manufacturer (BioRad, AlamarBlue[®]).

Absorbance data at 570nm and 600nm were analysed using the formula:

$$\text{Percentage difference between treated and control cells} = \frac{(\text{O2} \times \text{A1}) - (\text{O1} \times \text{A2})}{(\text{O2} \times \text{P1}) - (\text{O1} \times \text{P2})} \times 100$$

Where: O1 is the molar extinction coefficient of oxidised AlamarBlue[®] at 570nm and equals 80586, O2 is the molar extinction coefficient of oxidised AlamarBlue[®] at 600nm and equals to 117216, A1 is the absorbance of the test well at 570nm, A2 is the absorbance of the test well at 600nm, P1 is the absorbance of untreated positive control at 570nm and P2 is the absorbance of the untreated positive control at 600nm.

Fluorescence intensity data were assessed using the formula:

$$\text{Percentage difference between treated and control cells} = \frac{\text{FI 590 of test well}}{\text{FI 590 of untreated control}} \times 100$$

Where: FI 590 is the fluorescence intensity at 590nm emission (560nm excitation), measured for both top and bottom optics.

7.2.10. Assessment of apoptosis using flow cytometry

Apoptosis of Jurkat cells was assessed by flow cytometry for detection of apoptotic marker Annexin V in the stimulated populations versus the untreated controls, using Annexin V-FITC Apoptosis Detection Kit (Abcam, ab14085). Cells were incubated in 24-well plates for 24 hours, at a concentration of 1.5×10^5 cells/mL in 500 μ L suspension. The experimental replicates involved Jurkat cells stimulated with PHA-L at concentrations of 20 μ g/mL, 10 μ g/mL and 1 μ g/mL, and combined PHA-L and 1000Hz nanovibrational stimulation for the same PHA concentrations. Control cells were left unstimulated in complete growth medium as described above. After 24 hours the cells were collected in respective sterile flow cytometry tubes (BD biolab, 352054) and the supernatant was removed by centrifugation at 1300 rpm (224 x g) for 7 minutes. In order to completely remove the PHA-L from the samples, the cells were washed with 2mL FACS buffer, composed of 1X PBS (99%), FBS (1%) and supplemented with EDTA (0.5 % of volume). After the wash step, the cells were reconstituted in 500 μ L of 1X Annexin V binding buffer (Abcam, ab14085). This was followed by addition of 5 μ L of AnnexinV-FITC (Ex. 488nm, Em. 530nm) and 5 μ L of Propidium Iodide (PI) (Abcam, ab14085). The cells were incubated at room temperature for 5 minutes in the dark.

The cell labelling was detected by flow cytometry on FACSCalibur™ apparatus, using the FITC signal detector (FL1) for Annexin V and the phycoerythrin emission signal detector (FL2) for PI staining. The results were collected using CellQuest Pro software and analysed using FlowJo version 10.

7.2.11. Surface staining of polycystin 1 on Jurkat cells

Three replicates of unstimulated cells and three replicates of stimulated cells with 20 ng/mL PMA were used in this experiment. The cell suspension contained 1×10^6 cells/mL. The Jurkat cells were pelleted by centrifugation at 1200 rpm (190 x g) for 7 minutes. The supernatant was discarded, and cells were resuspended in 1 mL FACS buffer (1X PBS with 2% FBS and 2mM EDTA). The wash step was repeated another time, and the 100 μ L of cells were transferred into sterile FACS tubes. To each tube, 1 μ L of anti-PC1 (bs-2157R-A594) polyclonal antibodies conjugated with AlexaFluor®594 were added to the cells. The cells

were incubated in dark for 30 minutes on ice. After incubation, 1 mL of chilled FACS buffer were added to each tube, and cells were washed three times by centrifugation at 1300 rpm for 8 minutes at 4°C. The supernatant was discarded, and cells resuspended in 500µL of FACS buffer. The fluorescence was measured using the BD FACSCalibur apparatus.

7.2.12. Statistical analysis

The ELISA data are presented as mean of replicates \pm SE. The data were compared within the same stimulation time-point. Statistical difference of results was calculated using one-way analysis of variation ANOVA followed by Tukey multiple-comparison test to compare between the treatments.

The viability assay data are presented as mean of 20 replicates \pm SE. The Statistical analysis between the PHA and PHA+1000Hz treatments was performed using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

The gene expression data are presented as mean of six replicates \pm SE and the statistical difference for each gene is assessed by unpaired T test analysis with Welch's correction, comparing expression of genes in test samples to the respective controls, separately for 24 and 48 hours.

Statistical analysis was carried out using GraphPad Prism® version 6. P values <0.05 were accepted as significant.

7.3. Results

7.3.1. Lower concentration of IL-2 in supernatant of cells undergoing the combined PHA and 1000Hz treatment compared to PHA-only stimulation

The PHA-L induced upregulation of IL-2 secretion in the supernatant of Jurkat cells compared to the untreated cells at both 24 and 48 hours ($P < 0.0001$) (Figure 7.1, A, B). Interestingly, at 24 hours, in the supernatant of cells that underwent the combined stimulation (i.e. PHA-L and 1000Hz), there were lower levels of IL-2 (1.3 fold less) compared to the supernatant of cells stimulated only with PHA-L ($P < 0.05$) (Figure 7.1, A). No difference in the concentration of IL-2 in the supernatant of cells undergoing the PHA-L stimulation alone or in combination with 1000Hz nanovibrations was detected at 48 hours (Figure 7.1, B). Results from the quantification of IL-2 concentrations in the supernatant of control and stimulated cells are summarised in Table 7.1.

Figure 7.1: Concentration of the IL-2 (pg/mL) in the supernatant of Jurkat cells undergoing different stimulations for 24 (A) and 48 (B) hours. The supernatant was extracted by centrifugation at 1500rpm for 10 minutes. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE, and statistical difference was assessed by ANOVA followed by Tukey test. Statistical comparison of the treatments to the untreated control: $p^{****} < 0.0001$. Statistical comparison between the PHA and the combined treatment: $p^{***} < 0.05$.

Table 7.1: Comparison of secreted IL-2 at 24 and 48 hours from Jurkat cells undergoing different treatments.

Time-point	Stimulation	Mean concentration (pg/mL)	Fold difference to the untreated control	Statistical difference Stimulation vs Control	Fold difference between stimulations	Statistical difference between stimulations
24 hours	Untreated	14.53	1	-	-	-
	PHA	94.12	6.48	p< 0.0001 (****)	1.30	p=0.002 (***)
	PHA+1000Hz	72.44	4.98	p< 0.0001 (****)		
48 hours	Untreated	25.05	1	-	-	-
	PHA	81.02	3.23	p< 0.0001 (****)	1.08	Not significant
	PHA+1000Hz	75.30	3.01	p< 0.0001 (****)		

7.3.2. *IL2RA* transcripts upregulate the same for the PHA and the combined PHA+1000Hz treatments

The mRNA transcripts of *IL2RA* were upregulated in the presence of PHA-L at 24 and 48 hours (Figure 7.2), relative to the housekeeping gene *GAPDH* and the untreated control. No difference was recorded in *IL2RA* mRNA levels of PHA-stimulated cells compared to those which underwent the combined PHA-L and 1000Hz stimulation (Figure 7.2, A, B). A second $\Delta\Delta C_T$ analysis performed using the PHA-stimulated cells as control also showed no statistically significant difference in mRNA levels of *IL2RA* between the treatments (Figure 7.3).

Figure 7.2: *IL2RA* gene expression relative to the housekeeping gene *GAPDH* and the untreated control, at 24 (A) and 48 (B) hours. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE. Statistical analysis assessed by ANOVA followed by Tukey multiple-comparison test (p**<0.0001, p***<0.05).**

Figure 7.3: *IL2RA* gene expression relative to the housekeeping gene *GAPDH* and the PHA stimulated Jurkat cells as control, at 24 (A) and 48 (B) hours. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE. Statistical analysis between the groups was assessed by unpaired t test with Welch correction (statistical significance $p < 0.05$).

7.3.3. *IL-2* gene expression between PHA and PHA+1000Hz stimulated cells

No difference was recorded between in *IL-2* transcript levels between the treatments (Figure 7.4, Figure 7.5). The combined treatment caused increased *IL-2* transcript levels at 48 hours compared to the untreated (Figure 7.4, B). The lack of statistical significance between chemically treated cells and the untreated control could be attributed to the variance between replicates, resulting from low levels of *IL-2* produced by the untreated cells (Figure 7.4). A second comparison using the PHA-treated cells as control, also showed no difference in *IL-2* mRNA levels between PHA and the combined PHA and 1000Hz stimulation (Figure 7.5).

Figure 7.4: *IL-2* gene expression relative to the housekeeping gene *GAPDH*, compared to the untreated control, at 24 (A) and 48 (B) hours. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE. Statistical analysis assessed by ANOVA followed by Tukey multiple-comparison test ($p^* < 0.05$). Statistical comparison was also performed using unpaired t test between different groups, with similar results to the ANOVA analysis.

Figure 7.5: *IL-2* gene expression relative to the housekeeping gene *GAPDH*, compared to the PHA-L stimulated Jurkat cells as control, at 24 (A) and 48 (B) hours. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE. Statistical analysis between the groups was assessed by unpaired T test with Welch correction (statistical significance $p < 0.05$).

7.3.4. Experiment 2: Higher levels of IL-2 in the supernatant of cells undergoing PHA and 1000Hz stimulation

After 24 hours stimulation, the concentration of the IL-2 in the supernatant of cells stimulated with the combined PHA and 1000Hz treatment was higher (1.9 fold difference, $p=0.021$) than in PHA-only treated cells (Figure 7.).

Figure 7.6: Concentration of the IL-2 (pg/mL) in the supernatant of Jurkat cells undergoing different stimulations for 24 hours. The supernatant was extracted by centrifugation at 4500rpm for 7 minutes. Data presented as mean of 7 replicates \pm SE, and statistical difference between the groups was assessed by unpaired t test, $p^*<0.05$

7.3.5. Experiment 2: PHA and 1000Hz stimulation upregulate *IL-2* and mechanosensors' transcripts

Comparison of gene expression between PHA-L and PHA-L and 1000Hz stimulation showed differences in gene expression (Figure 7.). The levels of mRNA transcripts for *IL-2*, *NFAT2*, *PKD1*, *PKD2* and *PIEZO1* were upregulated in cells treated with PHA-L and 1000Hz compared to the PHA-only treated cells (Figure 7.). No difference in mRNA transcripts was recorded for *IL2RA* and *LEF-1*. Results are summarised in Table 7..

Figure 7.7: Gene expression in Jurkat cells undergoing different stimulations at 24 hours, relative to the mean of housekeeping genes *GAPDH*, *RPL37A* and *ACTB*. Data presented as mean of 7 replicates \pm SE. Statistical analysis between the groups was assessed by unpaired T test with Welch's correction (statistical significance $p < 0.05$).

Table 7.2: Summary of gene expression results from experiment 2. The data represent the mean fold expression of 7 replicates. Statistical significance between treatments was determined by unpaired T test with Welch's correction (statistical significance $p < 0.05$).

Gene transcripts (mRNA)	Stimulation	Mean Fold expression	P value
<i>IL-2</i>	PHA	1.02	0.0339 (*)
	PHA+1000 Hz	1.32	
<i>IL2RA</i>	PHA	1.00	Not significant
	PHA+1000 Hz	1.05	
<i>NFAT2</i>	PHA	1.01	0.0011 (**)
	PHA+1000 Hz	1.38	
<i>LEF-1</i>	PHA	1.01	Not significant
	PHA+1000 Hz	1.14	
<i>PKD1</i>	PHA	1.01	0.0021 (**)
	PHA+1000 Hz	1.41	
<i>PKD2</i>	PHA	1.00	0.0204 (*)
	PHA+1000 Hz	1.25	
<i>PIEZO1</i>	PHA	1.01	0.0035 (**)
	PHA+1000 Hz	1.34	

7.3.6. Higher cell growth in cells stimulated with PHA and 1000Hz compared to the PHA-only treatment.

The analysis of data gathered from the AlamarBlue® assay showed a higher viability/proliferation of Jurkat cells for the combined PHA and 1000Hz treatment. The p values obtained for each assessment method are summarised in Table 7.3. The stimulation with PHA-L alone had led to a slight decrease in growth compared to the untreated cells, while the combined treatment had enhanced the growth of cells compared to the control. No statistical analysis could be performed about the growth inhibition or enhancement compared to the control because the readings from the untreated cells were already incorporated in the obtained percentage differences. The results also showed that fluorescent readings were more sensitive than the absorbance, as seen by lower variance in reading across the 20 replicates. The analysis of Jurkat cell growth is summarised in Table 7.3.

Figure 7.8: Comparison of cell growth in Jurkat cells undergoing PHA-L and PHA-L + 1000Hz stimulation for 24 hours. The data for each group are normalised to the untreated control. Data presented as mean of 20 replicates \pm SE. Statistical difference between the groups analysed using unpaired T test with Welch's correction ($p^{**}<0.05$, $p^{***}<0.05$, $p^{****}<0.0001$).

Table 7.3: Comparison of Jurkat cell growth using AlamarBlue® assay and of different methods used for data collection.

Data reading method	Stimulation	Mean difference compared to the control (%)	Standard deviation	Growth inhibition compared to the control (%)	Growth enhancement compared to the control (%)	Difference between treatments (%)	Statistical difference between treatments
Absorbance	PHA-L	95.85	4.75	4.15	-	18.36	p = 0.003 (**)
	PHA-L + 1000Hz	114.21	23.92	-	14.21		
Fluorescence (Top optics)	PHA-L	94.49	4.84	5.51	-	8.76	p = 0.0005 (***)
	PHA-L + 1000Hz	103.25	8.84	-	3.25		
Fluorescence (Bottom optics)	PHA-L	92.51	4.49	7.49	-	11.71	p < 0.0001 (****)
	PHA-L + 1000Hz	104.22	7.64	-	4.22		

Figure 7.9: Annexin V detection and Propidium iodide (PI) staining in Jurkat cells undergoing different stimulations. The untreated cells were used to assess the levels of Annexin V detection in population in absence of chemical (PHA-L) or mechanical (1000Hz) stimuli (G). The cells were chemically stimulated with 20 µg/mL PHA-L (A), 10 µg/mL PHA-L (C) and 1 µg/mL PHA-L (E). The cells stimulated with the combined treatment were incubated with the same PHA-L concentrations, additionally stimulated with 1000Hz nanovibrations (B, D, F). The cell labelling was detected by flow cytometry on FACSCalibur™ apparatus, using the FITC signal detector (FL1) for Annexin V and the phycoerythrin emission signal detector (FL2) for PI staining.

Table 7.4: Detection of apoptosis in Jurkat cells stimulated with different concentrations of PHA-L and 1000Hz. The table shows Annexin V and Propidium Iodide (PI) positive and negative cells in the stimulated Jurkat cells as percentage of whole population.

Stimulation	Marker		Result interpretation	Population percentage	Number of cells	Total cells/events
	Annexin V	PI				
20 µg/mL PHA-L	-	-	Healthy cells	33.20%	5067	15258
	+	-	Early apoptotic cells	41.20%	6286	
	+	+	Late apoptotic or dead cells	24.90%	3800	
	-	+	Dead cell debris	0.69%	105	
20 µg/mL PHA-L + 1000Hz	-	-	Healthy cells	33.10%	4472	13521
	+	-	Early apoptotic cells	43.40%	5867	
	+	+	Late apoptotic or dead cells	22.60%	3056	
	-	+	Dead cell debris	0.93%	126	
10 µg/mL PHA-L	-	-	Healthy cells	35.10%	4681	13350
	+	-	Early apoptotic cells	42.90%	5727	
	+	+	Late apoptotic or dead cells	21.80%	2908	
	-	+	Dead cell debris	0.26%	34	
10 µg/mL PHA-L + 1000Hz	-	-	Healthy cells	40.40%	5003	12369
	+	-	Early apoptotic cells	42.70%	5280	
	+	+	Late apoptotic or dead cells	16%	1974	
	-	+	Dead cell debris	0.91%	112	
1 µg/mL PHA-L	-	-	Healthy cells	78.10%	8935	11434
	+	-	Early apoptotic cells	10.60%	1207	
	+	+	Late apoptotic or dead cells	11.10%	1270	
	-	+	Dead cell debris	0.19%	22	
1 µg/mL PHA-L + 1000Hz	-	-	Healthy cells	82.30%	9112	11076
	+	-	Early apoptotic cells	8.57%	949	
	+	+	Late apoptotic or dead cells	8.95%	991	
	-	+	Dead cell debris	0.22%	24	
Untreated control	-	-	Healthy cells	90.70%	10087	11120
	+	-	Early apoptotic cells	3.25%	361	
	+	+	Late apoptotic or dead cells	5.83%	648	
	-	+	Dead cell debris	0.22%	24	

Table 7.5: Median Fluorescence Intensity (MFI) for Annexin V and PI in Jurkat cells undergoing different treatments.

Stimulation	Signal	Percentage of positive cells	Median Fluorescence Intensity (MFI)
20 µg/mL PHA-L	Annexin V/ FITC	66.10%	777
	Propidium Iodide	25.59%	8.06
20 µg/mL PHA-L + 1000Hz	Annexin V/ FITC	66.00%	514
	Propidium Iodide	23.53%	5.78
10 µg/mL PHA-L	Annexin V/ FITC	64.70%	359
	Propidium Iodide	22.06%	3.89
10 µg/mL PHA-L + 1000Hz	Annexin V/ FITC	58.70%	253
	Propidium Iodide	16.91%	3.19
1 µg/mL PHA-L	Annexin V/ FITC	21.70%	33.1
	Propidium Iodide	11.29%	2.59
1 µg/mL PHA-L + 1000Hz	Annexin V/ FITC	17.52%	32.5
	Propidium Iodide	9.17%	2.31
Untreated control	Annexin V/ FITC	9.08%	20
	Propidium Iodide	6.05%	4

Figure 7.10: Median Fluorescence Intensity (MFI) for the Annexin V (A) and Propidium Iodide (B) in Jurkat cells. The numbers represent the PHA-L concentrations in µg/mL. The MFI was calculated using FlowJo version 10 for the Annexin V/FITC (FL-1) and PI (FL-2).

Figure 7.11: Detection of PC1 by flow cytometry in Jurkat cells stimulated with 20ng/mL PMA for 24 hours. The cells were single labelled using anti-PC1 antibody conjugated with AlexaFluor 594. The fluorescence was read using FL2 (A, B, E, F) and FL4 (C, D, G, H). The results for the unstimulated cells are shown in graphs A-D, and the results for the PMA stimulated cells are shown in graphs E-H.

7.4. Discussion

The results from the first experiment showed a difference in the secretion of IL-2 in response to the PHA-L and the combined PHA-L and 1000Hz stimulations at 24 hours (Table 7.1). In this experiment, the IL-2 concentration in the supernatant of cells stimulated with PHA-L and 1000Hz was lower than the IL-2 concentration in the supernatant of cells stimulated only with PHA-L (Figure 7.1, Table 7.1). The upregulation of IL-2 in the presence of PHA-L compared to the unstimulated control cells acted as validation of a response, because this molecule has shown to upregulate the IL-2 in Jurkat and primary T cells (Gerosa, Mingari and Moretta, 1986; Manger *et al.*, 1986; De La Rosa *et al.*, 1992).

At mRNA level, the results did not show any difference between treatments. There was no statistically significant difference in *IL-2* transcripts between the cells stimulated with PHA-L or the combined treatment (Figure 7.4, Figure 7.5). Similarly, there was no difference in the *IL2RA* transcripts between the treatment groups (Figure 7.2, Figure 7.3). The mRNA for *IL2RA* was upregulated in the presence of PHA-L compared to the unstimulated control, as expected (Figure 7.2). The *IL-2* transcripts were not statistically increased compared to the control, due to a variance in the fold change for both the PHA-L stimulated cells and those stimulated with the combined PHA-L and 1000Hz when compared to the controls.

The lower IL-2 in the supernatant could not be explained with the results of the first experiment only, so a second experiment was performed. This was an experiment that looked at the differences in IL-2 production and gene expression in cells stimulated for 24 hours with PHA-L as controls, and cell stimulated with PHA-L and 1000Hz as experimental populations. While there was a difference in the IL-2 concentration in the supernatant of cells stimulated with PHA-L and 1000Hz compared to the cells stimulated only with PHA-L, unlike in the first experiment, this time there were higher IL-2 levels for the combined treatment (Figure 7.6).

In addition, in the second experiment there was a link between the produced IL-2 and the mRNA encoding it, which was upregulated in the cells stimulated with PHA-L and 1000Hz compared to the PHA-L only controls (Figure 7.7). At the same time, *NFAT2*, *PIEZO1*, *PKD1* and *PKD2* were upregulated for the combined treatment, whereas the mRNA levels for *IL2RA* and *LEF-1* were comparable to the controls (Figure 7.7, Table 7.2). Unlike in the first

experiment, for better and more reliable quantification, normalisation with three housekeepers was performed, and better SYBR green mastermix was used for the polymerase chain reactions as mentioned in the methods.

The results from the second experiment showed that the combined treatment was enhancing IL-2 responses in Jurkat T cells for 24 hours stimulation (Table 7.2). The higher levels of mRNA encoding for mechanosensors and *NFAT2* could indicate enhanced calcium signalling. *PIEZO1*, *PC1* and *PC2* have all shown to regulate Ca^{2+} signalling (Mekahli *et al.*, 2013; Liu *et al.*, 2018), while the *NFAT2* is part of the calcineurin-NFAT pathway which is activated by Ca^{2+} ions (Macian, 2005). It has also been shown that polycystin 1 and polycystin 2 work to amplify IP3-induced Ca^{2+} release (Mekahli *et al.*, 2012), which is a crucial step in the TCR signalling pathways that leads to downstream activation of calcineurin and NFAT and regulation of *IL-2* expression (Gaud, Lesourne and Love, 2018). However, there was no change in the *IL2RA* mRNA levels (Table 7.2), which was expected for enhanced activation and IL-2 signalling (Bismuth *et al.*, 1985; Kim, 2002; Kim, Imbert and Leonard, 2006; Liao, Lin and Leonard, 2013). Absence of any difference in *IL2RA* mRNA between treatments was also seen in the first experiment (Figure 7.2). Therefore, the question was raised whether there was any important biological effect that the observed IL-2 changes between the treatments would have on Jurkat populations, looking at proliferation and apoptosis by comparing the PHA-L stimulation with the combined PHA-L and 1000Hz.

As leukaemic cells, Jurkats have both high proliferation and apoptotic rates, with the former being higher in order for clonal expansion to take place (Lin *et al.*, 2002). The enhanced IL-2 would boost cell proliferation and the survival of clones (Liao, Lin and Leonard, 2013), however, due to a lack of response from the proliferation marker *IL2RA*, this needed further investigation. The cell growth was assessed using the resazurin (Alamar blue® reagent) assay which can be used to indicate changes in active proliferation and cell viability (Rampersad, 2012; Helm *et al.*, 2017). The absorbance and fluorescence results from the resazurin assay showed that there was higher cell growth in the cells undergoing the combined PHA-L and 1000Hz stimulation, compared to the ones undergoing only PHA-L stimulation at 24 hours (Table 7.3).

If considering the fluorescent readings as more accurate, due to the lower variance between the 20 replicates (Table 7.3), the difference between the treatment was due to some protection against a decline in cell growth compared to the untreated control induced by the PHA-L (Table 7.3). For example, the results from the PHA-L and 1000Hz were comparable to the untreated control (normalised as 100%), whereas the cell growth for the PHA-L only stimulation was about 8% lower than the untreated control (Table 7.3).

The PHA-L stimulation can result in decreased viability because the compound has shown to have both mitogenic and apoptotic abilities. For example, in Jurkat cells PHA stimulation can induce activation-induced cell death through Fas ligand signalling (Chwae *et al.*, 2002), and upregulation of FAS ligand expression occurs early upon PHA stimulation in these cells (Drury *et al.*, 2010). The activation-induced cell death is a normal process, which is useful for preventing excessive proliferation of lymphocytes, contributing to processes like tolerance and control of inflammation (Drury *et al.*, 2010).

Therefore, the results from the resazurin assay could indicate that the enhanced IL-2 in the cells stimulated with the combined treatment was protective against PHA-L induced apoptosis, but not affecting proliferation, as seen in the results presented in Table 7.3 for the fluorescence readings. This could explain the lack of difference in *IL2RA* mRNA levels between the treatments.

However, the cell viability needed to be assessed more specifically by using assays that look at apoptosis and cell death in isolation. In addition, it must be noted that in Jurkat cells the resazurin triggers cellular ROS production and thereby initiates a stress response leading to mitochondrial dysfunction, cell damage and death (Erikstein *et al.*, 2010). This damaging oxidative effect has shown to be associated with the resazurin reduction reaction, and it has shown to be stronger between 4-24 hours (Erikstein *et al.*, 2010). For this reason, to minimise such effect, the cells were incubated with resazurin reagent for 4 hours only, and the right controls were prepared as needed for normalisation of the obtained data for the stimulated cells, as described in the methodology above. However, for this additional fact, it was necessary that parameters such as cell viability or apoptosis be assessed by additional methods.

The apoptotic assay was performed by assessing binding of Annexin V and the uptake of Propidium iodide in Jurkat cells stimulated with different treatments. The surface of healthy cells is composed of lipids that are asymmetrically distributed on the inner and outer leaflet of the plasma membrane (Crowley *et al.*, 2016). One of these lipids, phosphatidylserine (PS), is normally restricted to the inner leaflet of the plasma membrane and it is only exposed to the cell cytoplasm (Crowley *et al.*, 2016). However, during apoptosis lipid asymmetry is lost and PS becomes exposed on the outer leaflet of the plasma membrane (Crowley *et al.*, 2016). Annexin V, a 36-kDa calcium-binding protein, binds to PS, and in the assay Annexin V labelled with FITC was used to detect PS that is exposed on the outside of apoptotic cells (Crowley *et al.*, 2016). Annexin V can also stain necrotic cells because these cells have ruptured membranes that permit Annexin V to bind to PS across all sides of plasma membrane (Crowley *et al.*, 2016). However, apoptotic cells can be distinguished from necrotic cells by co-staining with propidium iodide (PI) because PI enters necrotic or dead cells but is excluded from apoptotic cells (Crowley *et al.*, 2016).

The percentage of apoptotic, necrotic/dead cells and healthy cells in population is shown in the Table 7.4. The results show a higher percentage of healthy cell for the combined stimulation compared to the respective PHA-L treatments (Table 7.4). More importantly, the difference in the median fluorescence intensity, which is the brightness of FITC signal coming from Annexin V positive cells, shows that the combined treatment may protect against cell apoptosis compared to the respective PHA-L concentrations (Table 7.5).

The observed decreased apoptosis was related to the resazurin assay and the increased IL-2 signalling. The IL-2 would increase the survival of clones (Liao, Lin and Leonard, 2013; Ross and Cantrell, 2018). However, it must be noted that no statistical significance could be performed for this test. Even though the experiment was designed to have 4 replicates per treatment, before the measurement of events using flow cytometry, these replicates were erroneously pooled into one. The results of the annexin V assay are therefore representative of one measurement per treatment. While they still show interesting results, the lack of analysis of statistical significance makes the interpretation of results unreliable. The data collected for this assay in this chapter can be used for comparison in future experimental repeats.

7.4.1. Conclusion

The results from the experiments presented in this chapter were interesting because a difference in response between treatments was recorded in Jurkat cells at 24 hours, in the first two experiments and in the follow-up assays. Therefore, based on the results of this chapter, it can be suggested that the Jurkat cells could probably respond to the mechanical 1000Hz stimulation when it is applied in addition to the chemical PHA-L stimulation *in vitro*. Possible responses to the combined stimulation include enhancement of IL-2 production and increase in cell survival by lowering apoptotic rates.

However, this observation needs further confirmation and certain issues should be taken in consideration. For example, the first experiment showed lower IL-2 in the supernatant of cells stimulated with PHA-L and 1000Hz compared to the cells stimulated only with PHA-L, whereas the second experiment showed higher IL-2 levels in the supernatant of cells which underwent the combined treatment at 24 hours. The different and not reproducible patterns of IL-2 production lowered the confidence when interpreting the results.

In addition, the *IL2RA* mRNA levels were comparable between the treatments in both experiments, despite what was to be expected due to the enhanced IL-2 production as recorded in the second experiment. Since the resazurin results seemed influenced mostly by an increase in the survival of the clones rather than enhanced proliferation, which was also reinforced by the observations of the apoptotic assay (without statistical analysis unfortunately), it could be assumed that the lack of *IL2RA* regulation is because the combined treatment does not affect cell division and proliferation. However, as counter argument to that, the increased IL-2 in the supernatant should increase the *IL2RA* transcripts, as it was shown in the experiments of Chapter 5. The enhanced IL-2 production would also affect both survival and expansion of clones, so seeing a selective effect is strange and will need further confirmation and clarification. Furthermore, the lack of a difference between the treatments at 48 hours, in terms of IL-2 production and *IL2RA* regulation, showed that the 24 hours results were not representative of an early response that increased with time.

Unfortunately, as the bioreactor failed its stability and functionality tests, a repetition of the Annexin V assay and some of the experiments which could help answering some of the issues mentioned above could not be performed. Further work was also halted due to the

bioreactor's malfunction. As a final note, these experiments were performed between the second and the third failed calibration points (March - July 2019), on a site of the bioreactor where the displacements (nm) were most stable.

7.4.2. Future research

The observed changes between the cell responses to PHA-L and the combined PHA-L and 1000Hz stimulations need to be investigated further and checked for reproducibility. The cell proliferation could also be tested by flow cytometry for the IL2RA (CD25), in order to address the lack of *IL2RA* mRNA regulation in these experiments. There are also other techniques looking at caspase activity, than can be used to further assess apoptosis, in addition to repeating the methodology applied in this chapter.

The combined stimulation should be assessed for different PHA-L concentrations, and the cell viability to such concentrations should be assessed beforehand. In this chapter, this approach was skipped due to the limited timeframe between the last two failed calibration points. The concentration of the PHA-L as 1µg/mL was chosen as the preferred PHA-L concentration from published studies (Manger *et al.*, 1986; De La Rosa *et al.*, 1992) and work performed in the previous chapter. The 1 µg/mL PHA-L is the lower concentration of lectin that is sufficient to induce IL-2 upregulation in Jurkats, but not the strongest (Manger *et al.*, 1986; De La Rosa *et al.*, 1992), which could overshadow any effects of the mechanical stimulus. However, performing a viability assessment for different PHA-L concentrations, is a very important step to provide a basis for interpretation of results.

The IL-2 production as measured by ELISA should also be repeated, because even though a change in supernatant concentrations between treatment as was recorded in two experiments, in the first one the IL-2 levels were lower for the combined treatment, whereas in the second they were higher.

To clarify the detection of lower IL-2 concentrations in the supernatant for what could be an enhanced response in Jurkats or primary T cell in the presence of the PHA-L, the soluble IL2RA (sIL2RA or sCD25) should also be quantified by ELISA. The sIL2RA can efficiently bind the IL-2 (Russell *et al.*, 2012) and that could impair the detection of the cytokine by ELISA. The soluble IL2RA has been associated with conditions that involve T cells and inflammation (Rubin, 1990; Karim *et al.*, 2018), and it has immunomodulatory roles in autoimmune

conditions (Maier *et al.*, 2009; Russell *et al.*, 2012). In one study of multiple sclerosis, the sIL2RA inhibited IL-2 signalling, but yet enhanced cell proliferation and expansion (Maier *et al.*, 2009), whereas another *in vitro* study has shown that the sIL2RA acts as a decoy receptor for the IL-2, locally sequestering the cytokine and enhancing Th17 development and responses (Russell *et al.*, 2012). For the type of experiments presented in this chapter, the sIL2RA could be used to explain lower levels of IL-2 in the supernatant, if they are reproducibly detected in future repeats. Furthermore, an increase or decrease in sIL2RA could be indicative of a response towards the combined stimulation.

7.4.3. Detection of PC1 by flow cytometry.

This experiment was designed to quantify the PC1 expression in whole stimulated Jurkat population, something that could not be performed by the immunofluorescent staining for the issues discussed in the previous chapter. However, this experiment failed because the PC1 was not detected in Jurkat cells by flow cytometry (Figure 7.11). Based on the results from immunofluorescent staining presented on the previous chapter, the PC1 should be at least detected in the unstimulated cells. It is thought that the inability to detect the fluorescent signal is related to the FL2 and FL4 signal detectors which were used for the readings but are not specific for detecting AlexaFluor 594 signal. Another explanation is that the polyclonal anti-PC1 did not bind the target protein or it was washed away during preparation. The whole-population expression of PC1, as well the expression of PIEZO1 and PC2 should be looked in the future experiment, because they can be used to assess the expression of these proteins upon stimulation, as well as compare the results at protein level with the corresponding mRNA patterns that were recorded in the previous chapters.

Chapter 8

Analysis of gene expression patterns during monocyte-macrophage differentiation upon stimulation with 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3 and 1000Hz nanovibrations

Abstract

The work presented in this chapter looked at the monocyte to macrophage differentiation upon the stimulation with vitamin D3, 1000Hz vibrations, and towards a combination of both stimuli. This investigation was performed by looking at many genes encoding for macrophage differentiation markers such as *CD14* and *CD36*, antigen presenting molecules such as *HLA-DRA*, mechanosensors such as *PIEZO1* and *PKD2* and transcription factors such as those belonging to the TCF/LEF pathway. Regulation of *PIEZO1*, *PKD1* and *PKD2* during macrophage differentiation had not been described before. Unlike the Jurkat cells, the THP-1 monocytes were more responsive to the 1000Hz stimulation when applied in isolation. Based on the results obtained in this study, the 1000Hz stimulation caused *PIEZO1* and *TCF3* upregulation in THP-1 monocytes. However, such effect was lost in the presence of the vitamin. Furthermore, the 1000Hz stimulation did not affect macrophage differentiation because it did not affect the transcriptional regulation of *CD14* and *TCF/LEF* genes. On the other hand, vitamin D3 had a strong effect on the macrophage differentiation, reproducible in both adherent and suspension cells. The vitamin D3-induced macrophage differentiation was characterised by *HLA-DRA* downregulation, *TCF7L2* upregulation and *LEF-1* downregulation.

8.1. Introduction

Macrophages play important roles in health and disease through phagocytosis of pathogenic microorganisms, by releasing inflammatory mediators, by inducing and maintaining inflammation, and removing apoptotic cells and repairing tissues (Gordon, 2007; Mosser and Edwards, 2008). Macrophages already present in specific tissue are called tissue-resident macrophages (Lavin *et al.*, 2015). Tissues-resident macrophages are derived from the yolk sac at the embryonic stage, are replicated in tissues to maintain cell number, and

have different morphology and function depending on the tissue where they reside (Lavin *et al.*, 2015). Such macrophages include the alveolar macrophages in the lung, the Kupffer cells in the liver and macrophage-like microglia in the nervous system. However, in the case of tissue injury or infection, monocytes derived from bone marrow circulating in peripheral blood migrate to the affected tissues where they differentiate into macrophages, and are subsequently involved in the inflammatory response (Shi and Pamer, 2011).

The cellular functions of tissue-resident macrophages and peripheral blood-derived macrophages are affected by the tissue-specific microenvironment, which can create many types of mechanical stress on cells (McWhorter, Davis and Liu, 2015; Mennens, van den Dries and Cambi, 2017). Stiffness and topography, which are mechanical properties of the extracellular matrix, regulate the differentiation, proliferation, and function of macrophages such as phagocytosis (Patel *et al.*, 2012). In addition, macrophages in tissues are exposed to alterations of pressure which affect the secretion of cytokines such as IL-6, TNF- α and IL-1 β , (Ferrier *et al.*, 2000; Mevov *et al.*, 2002). Other mechanical forces that these cells experience originate from dynamic mechanical loading, such as continuous and cyclic stretch and compression (McWhorter, Davis and Liu, 2015; Mennens, van den Dries and Cambi, 2017).

THP-1 cells are human immortalised monocytes derived from human acute monocytic leukaemia and have been extensively used to study macrophage differentiation, functions, signalling pathways, and nutrient and drug transport (Chanput, Mes and Wichers, 2014; Bosshart and Heinzelmann, 2016). Just like normal monocytes, THP-1 cells have shown to respond to mechanical stressors. For example, in models of atherosclerosis, biomechanical strain on THP-1 cells can induce expression of the class A scavenger receptor, an important lipoprotein receptor in atherogenesis (Yamamoto, Ikeda and Shimada, 2003). In addition, DNA microarray analysis has shown that cyclic mechanical strain in THP-1 cells induces expression of genes, some encoding for inflammatory markers such as IL-8 and IEX-1 (Yamamoto, Ikeda and Shimada, 2003). In these cells, biomechanical deformation influences the degradation of extracellular matrix, monocyte differentiation, and promotion of atherosclerosis (Yamamoto, Ikeda and Shimada, 2003). In addition, it is known that as THP-1 cells become adherent, a process associated with differentiation (Tsuchiya *et al.*, 1982; Schwende *et al.*, 1996). This process may also result in altered mechanosensitivity.

In the experiments presented in this chapter, the THP-1 cells were stimulated with vitamin D3 (1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3), 1000Hz nanovibrations or both, in order to investigate the expression of genes that could indicate differentiation or mechanosensitivity changes in these cells. In the following text, the combined treatment refers to the combination of 50 nM vitamin D3 and 1000Hz vibrations. The cell responses were investigated in both adherent and suspension THP-1 monocytes upon each stimulation, in order to avoid any confusion in results due to potential differences between the populations. Vitamin D3 has shown to promote monocyte differentiation into macrophages and targets multiple genes, such as the differentiation markers *CD14* and *CD36* (Nurminen, Seuter and Carlberg, 2019).

The genes of interest include *CD14* and *CD36*, which are differentiation markers of monocyte/macrophage lineage with roles in immune responses (Zhang *et al.*, 1994; Maeß, Sendelbach and Lorkowski, 2010). *CD14* cooperates with other proteins to mediate the innate immune response to bacterial lipopolysaccharide whereas *CD36* is a scavenger receptor involved in phagocytosis (Woo *et al.*, 2016). Other genes of interest involved in immunology include *HLA-DRA*, which encodes for the alpha subunit of MHC class II needed for antigen presentation, and *HLA-DMB* which encodes for molecules needed to load the antigen into MHC class II molecules (Riberdy *et al.*, 1992; Sloan *et al.*, 1995).

Since there is mechanical stress applied by the 1000Hz nanovibrational stimulation, the expression of genes encoding mechanosensors was investigated. The chosen genes of interest encode for cation channels *PIEZO1* and *PKD2* (*PC2*, *TRPP2*), and the g-coupled receptor *PKD1* (*TRPP1*, *PC1*). Of these proteins, in monocytes the *PIEZO1* has shown to signal in response to cyclical hydrostatic pressure, resulting in *HIF1 α* stabilization and secretion of molecules, such as endothelin-1 (*EDN1*), and neutrophil chemoattractant *CXCL2* (Solis *et al.*, 2019). The *PIEZO1* signalling to the cyclical pressure has induced inflammation and infiltration of monocytes, which recruit neutrophils in order to clear pulmonary *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* infection via *EDN1* (Solis *et al.*, 2019). The roles of polycystins in monocyte mechanosensation were unknown at the time this chapter was written.

The expression patterns of many genes encoding for transcription factors were also investigated. These include *NFAT2*, involved in Ca^{2+} pathways (Müller and Rao, 2010), and those involved in the *TCF/LEF* pathway which plays roles in monocyte differentiation (Thiele

et al., 2001). Overall, this experiment was designed to give an insight into the differentiation process of THP-1 monocytes into macrophages under different stimulation parameters, compare between treatments and look into mechanosensor expression.

8.2. Methods

8.2.1. THP-1 monocyte growth

THP-1 cells (ATCC® TIB-202™) were reconstituted from -80°C storage and allowed to recover for 2 weeks in cultures, splitting when confluency reached around 8×10^5 cells/mL. The culture medium needed for cell growth was composed of RPMI-1640 with L-glutamine (Capricorn Scientific, RPMI-HA), 10 % Foetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (Gibco, A3160802) and 1% Antibiotic-Antimycotic 100X mix (Gibco, 15240062). The cells were cultured at 37°C, 5% CO₂ until ready for the experiments.

8.2.2. Nanokick bioreactor preparation

Plates (24-well plates) which would be clamped on the bioreactor had magnet sheets (First4Magnets, D-F4MA43MHP) attached 48 hours before the start of the experiment, for better adhesion and removal of air pockets with time. In addition, the Nanokick bioreactor (model NTB3014) was incubated at 37°C for 2 days prior to the start of experiments, which is the temperature at which the bioreactor displacements were calibrated. Incubation prior to the experiment was also useful for avoiding condensation upon immediate translocation of the bioreactor from room temperature to incubator environment.

8.2.3. Experimental set up

The THP-1 cells were collected from T75 flasks (25mL suspension) and pelleted by centrifugation at 1500 rpm (300 x g) for 10 minutes. The experiment involved 4 replicates of untreated cells, 4 replicates of cells treated with 50nM 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3 (Sigma-Aldrich, D1530), 4 replicates of cells treated with 1000Hz nanovibrations (amplitude 30 - 60 nm), and 4 replicates of cells treated simultaneously with 50nM 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3 and 1000Hz stimulation. The cells underwent stimulation for 3 days (72 hours). The cell density per each replicate was 1.5×10^5 cells/mL, in 1mL suspension plated on 24-well plates (Thermofisher Scientific, 142475). The experiments took place at 37°C, 5% CO₂, 95% air incubator (LEEC 190D CO₂).

8.2.4. RNA extraction

The RNA was extracted separately for the suspension and adherent cells. Cell suspension was slowly removed and added to sterile RNA-free 1.5mL tubes. The cells in suspension were pelleted by centrifugation at 3000 rpm (1200 x g) for 5 minutes. The supernatant was

discarded and 1mL Trizol reagent (Invitrogen, AM9738) was added to homogenise the pellet. For the adherent cells, 1mL Trizol reagent was added directly on the wells. The lysed cells were homogenised using a 25g syringe. The RNA extraction from the lysed cells in Trizol solution was done by separating the aqueous phase after addition of 0.2mL chloroform and centrifugation at 13000 rpm (17950 x g) for 15 minutes at 4°C. The RNA was washed with isopropanol and 75% ethanol and stored in 30µL of nuclease-free water (Gibco, 10977035). Quantification of the RNA in ng/µL was done on Nanodrop 1000, using the RNA nucleic acid programme.

8.2.5. DNase treatment

The DNase treatment was performed following the protocol of DNA-free Kit (ThermoFisher Scientific, AM1906), in order to degrade any genomic DNA that contaminated the RNA solutions during extraction. The maximum RNA concentration for each sample was 5µg per 50µL DNase reaction. Removal of genomic DNA contamination allowed efficient detection of amplification during the real-time PCR.

8.2.6. Complementary DNA synthesis

The synthesis of cDNA was done as instructed on the protocol of High-Capacity cDNA Reverse transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems, 4368814). The reaction was comprised of 10µL of 2X RT Mastermix and 10µL of purified RNA solution from the previous step. Reaction was started by warming at 25°C for 10 minutes, followed by incubation at 37°C for 2 hours for the synthesis of the cDNA, and termination of reaction at 85°C for 5 minutes. The newly synthesised cDNA was stored at -20°C until used for PCR reactions.

8.2.7. Real-time PCR

Real-time PCR was used to quantify gene expression in adherent and suspension THP-1 cells. The PCR amplifications were performed in 25µL reactions containing 12.5µL PowerUP SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied Biosystems™, A25742); 0.5µL Forward Primer and 0.5µL Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1µL of cDNA and topped up to 25µL with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035).

The primer pair used for amplification of the housekeeper *RPL37A* were *RPL37A* forward 5'-ATTGAAATCAGCCAGCACGC-3' and *RPL37A* reverse 5'-AGGAACCACAGTGCCAGATCC-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of the housekeeper *ACTB* were *ACTB* forward 5'-

ATTGCCGACAGGATGCAGAA-3' and *ACTB* reverse 5'-GCTGATCCACATCTGCTGGAA-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *CD36* were *CD36* forward 5'-TCACTGCGACATGATTAATGGTACA-3' and *CD36* reverse 5'-ACGTCGGATTCAAATACAGCATAGAT-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *CD14* were *CD14* forward 5'-ACGCCAGAACCTTGTGAGC-3' and *CD14* reverse 5'-GCATGGATCTCCACCTCTACTG-3'. The primer pair for amplification of *HLA-DRA* were *HLA-DRA* forward 5'-TAAGGCACATGGAGGTGATG-3' and *HLA-DRA* reverse 5'-GTACGGAGCAATCGAAGAGG-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *HLA-DMB* were *HLA-DMB* forward 5'-CTCTCACAGCACCTCAACCA-3' and *HLA-DMB* reverse 5'-TAGAAGCCCCACACATAGCA-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *PIEZO1* were *PIEZO1* forward 5'-CATCTTGGTGGTCTCCTCTGTCT-3' and *PIEZO1* reverse 5'-CTGGCATCCACATCCCTCTCATC-3'. The primer pair used for detection of *PKD1* were *PKD1* forward 5'-CGCCGCTTCACTAGCTTCGAC-3' and *PKD1* reverse 5'-ACGCTCCAGAGGGAGTCCAC-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *PKD2* were *PKD2* forward 5'-GCGAGGTCTCTGGGGAAC-3' and *PKD2* reverse 5'-TACACATGGAGCTCATCATGC-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *NFAT2* were *NFAT2* forward 5'-CACTCCTGCTGCCTTACACA-3' and *NFAT2* reverse 5'-AAGATGCGAGCATGCGACTA-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *TCF3* were *TCF3* forward 5'-TGACCTCCTGGACTTCAGC-3' and *TCF3* reverse 5'-ACCTGAACCTCCGAAGTGC-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *TCF4* were *TCF4* forward 5'-AGTGCGATGTTTTACCTCC-3' and *TCF4* reverse 5'-CCTGAGCTACTTCTGTCTTC-3'. The primer pair used for the amplification of *TCF7L2* were *TCF7L2* forward 5'-CCGGGAAAGTTTGAAGAAG-3' and *TCF7L2* reverse 5'-ACTGAAAATGGAGGGTTCGG-3'. The primer pair used for amplification of *LEF-1* were *LEF-1* forward 5'-GACAGTGACCTAATGCACGT-3' and *LEF-1* reverse 5'-CCACCTTCTGCCAAGAATCT-3'.

The primers for TCFs and LEF-1 transcription factors were generously provided by Dr. Robin Freeburn. Primers amplifying *PIEZO1* were designed using the NCBI primer design tool for the mRNA sequence NM_001142864.4, and primers amplifying *CD14* were designed similarly for the mRNA sequences NM_001174105.2 (*CD14* mRNA transcript variant 4), NM_001040021.3 (*CD14* mRNA transcript variant 2), NM_000591.4 (*CD14* mRNA transcript variant 1) and NM_001174104.1 (*CD14* mRNA transcript variant 3). The primers for *NFAT2*

were obtained from Dagna *et al.* (Dagna, Pritchett and Lusso, 2013), primers for *HLA-DRA* and *HLA-DMB* were obtained from Ulbricht *et al.* (Ulbricht *et al.*, 2012), primers for *PKD1* and *PKD2* were obtained from Dalagiorgou *et al.* (Dalagiorgou *et al.*, 2013), and primers from *CD36*, *ACTB* and *RPL37A* were obtained from Maeß *et al.* (Maeß, Sendelbach and Lorkowski, 2010).

The efficiency of primers taken from existing literature has been assessed in published papers (Fukuda, Mitsuoka and Schmid-Schönbein, 2004; Maeß, Sendelbach and Lorkowski, 2010; Ulbricht *et al.*, 2012; Dagna, Pritchett and Lusso, 2013; Dalagiorgou *et al.*, 2013). The collected C_T values were used for the $\Delta\Delta C_T$ relative quantification of expression, comparing the stimulated cells to the untreated controls. The ΔC_T was obtained by comparison of C_T s of genes of interest to the mean C_T of two housekeeping genes *RPL37A* and *ACTB*. These housekeeping genes are considered to be the best for the analysis of RNA expression in THP-1 cells (Maeß, Sendelbach and Lorkowski, 2010).

8.2.8. Statistical analysis

The gene expression data are presented as mean of four replicates \pm SE, with little exception where some particular genes were not detected in all replicates. The analysis of statistical significance between the stimulated cells versus controls, and between each type of stimulation was done using unpaired T test with Welch's correction. Statistical analysis was carried out using GraphPad Prism® version 6. P values <0.05 were accepted as significant.

8.3. Results

8.3.1. Regulation of genes encoding proteins with roles in immunity

Results showed that *CD14* gene was upregulated only by stimulation with vitamin D3 in both adherent and suspension cells. Mechanical stimulation with 1000Hz nanovibrations did not have any effect on this gene (Figure 8.1, A, B).

The *CD36* gene in adherent cells was upregulated only by vitamin D3 stimulation (Figure 8.1, C). In suspension cells, 1000Hz stimulation caused an upregulation of *CD36*, just like the stimulation with the vitamin (Figure 8.1, D). However, by comparing between vitamin D3-only and vitamin D3 and 1000Hz stimulation, it was observed that there were lower *CD36* mRNA levels for the combined stimulation, so the mechanical stimulus had an downregulating effect on this gene when vitamin D3 was present. Also, the upregulation caused by vitamin D3 and the combined treatment was higher than the one caused by 1000Hz-only stimulation (Figure 8.1, C, D).

The *HLA-DRA* gene in suspension cells was downregulated in response to vitamin D3 stimulation (Figure 8.1, F). In adherent cells this gene was downregulated for all the treatments (Figure 8.1, E). There was no difference between treatments, which meant they all regulated this gene at the same rate/amount.

The *HLA-DMB* gene was affected only in suspension cells (Figure 8.1, H). It must be noted that in adherent cells little transcripts were obtained for this gene, which made its detection in few replicates impossible in 40 PCR cycles, lowering the number of replicates per treatment. Vitamin D3 caused upregulation whereas the 1000Hz stimulation caused downregulation of *HLA-DMB* (Figure 8.1, H). The difference between vitamin D3-only and the combined vitamin D3 and 1000Hz, showed that this mechanical stimulus weakened the vitamin-induced upregulation of this gene.

The results from these genes have been summarised in comprehensive manner in Table 8.1, which also includes the p values from the statistical analysis.

Figure 8.1: Regulation of genes with roles in immunology in adherent and suspension THP-1 cells undergoing different treatments for 72 hours. The genes investigated were *CD14* (A, B), *CD36* (C, D), *HLA-DRA* (E, F) and *HLA-DMB* (G, H). Data presented as mean of 4 replicates \pm SE of the mean, except for *CD36* (N=3) in control adherent cell, and *CD14* (N=3) and *CD36* (N=2) in 1000Hz stimulated adherent cells. Statistical significance assessed by unpaired T test with Welch's correction. P values lower than 0.05 were considered significant.

Table 8.1: Summary of the gene expression patterns for *CD14*, *CD36*, *HLA-DRA* and *HLA-DMB*, and comparison between stimulations. The relative expression was assessed by real-time PCR. The C_T values of genes of interest were compared to the mean C_T of housekeepers *ACTB* and *RPL37A* for the ΔC_T and normalised to the untreated control for the $\Delta\Delta C_T$. The fold expression was calculated using the formula $2^{(-\Delta\Delta C_T)}$. Statistical significance between the groups was determined by using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

Treatment	Regulation patterns of immune-related genes							
	<i>CD14</i>		<i>CD36</i>		<i>HLA-DRA</i>		<i>HLA-DMB</i>	
	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension
50nM D3 vs Untreated	↑ 650.90 Fold (p**= 0.003)	↑ 573.92 Fold (p*= 0.016)	↑ 3.13 Fold (p**= 0.007)	↑ 3.66 Fold (p***= 0.0004)	↓ 0.089 Fold (p**= 0.0011)	↓ 0.16 Fold (p***= 0.0001)	No difference (p= 0.18)	↑ 2.17 Fold (p**= 0.0016)
1000Hz vs Untreated	No difference (p= 0.90)	No difference (p= 0.99)	No difference (p= 0.06)	↑ 1.43 Fold (p*= 0.013)	↓ 0.065 Fold (p**= 0.0022)	No difference (p= 0.18)	No difference (p= 0.83)	↓ 0.86 Fold (p*= 0.04)
50nM D3+1000Hz vs Untreated	↑ 542.09 Fold (p**= 0.0011)	↑ 428.90 Fold (p*= 0.036)	↑ 2.27 Fold (p*= 0.023)	↑ 2.66 Fold (p***= 0.0009)	↓ 0.096 Fold (p**= 0.002)	↓ 0.19 Fold (p****< 0.0001)	No difference (p= 0.24)	↑ 1.51 Fold (p**= 0.0071)
Treatment	Comparison of expression between treatments							
	<i>CD14</i>		<i>CD36</i>		<i>HLA-DRA</i>		<i>HLA-DMB</i>	
	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension
50nM D3 vs 1000Hz	↑ 559.5 Fold (p**= 0.003)	↑ 564.9 Fold (p*= 0.016)	↑ 9.28 Fold (p**= 0.004)	↑ 2.55 Fold (p***= 0.0003)	No difference (p= 0.57)	↓ 0.15 Fold (p***= 0.0001)	No difference (p= 0.58)	↑ 2.51 Fold (p***= 0.0008)
50nM D3 vs 50nM+1000Hz	No difference (p= 0.24)	No difference (p= 0.41)	No difference (p= 0.14)	↑ 1.38 Fold (p**= 0.008)	No difference (p= 0.87)	No difference (p= 0.14)	No difference (p= 0.09)	↑ 1.43 Fold (p**= 0.006)
50nM+1000Hz D3 vs 1000Hz	↑ 466.0 Fold (p**= 0.001)	↑ 422.2 Fold (p*= 0.036)	↑ 6.73 Fold (p**= 0.006)	↑ 1.85 Fold (p**= 0.002)	No difference (p= 0.39)	↓ 0.18 Fold (p****< 0.0001)	No difference (p= 0.61)	↑ 1.75 Fold (p**= 0.0022)

8.3.2. Regulation of genes encoding mechanosensors

The *PIEZO1* gene was upregulated by the 1000Hz stimulation in both adherent and suspension cells (Figure 8.2, A, B). Vitamin D3 had no effect on the expression of this gene, whereas in the combined treatment the upregulating effect of 1000Hz was lost. While comparing the combined vitamin D3 and 1000Hz to the 1000Hz-only stimulation, there was no statistical difference observed, which can indicate that the mechanical stimulation may still have any effect on gene expression in the suspension cells undergoing the combined treatment, however the p value was very close to the 0.05 limit (i.e. 0.052).

The *PKD1* gene expression was not affected by any of the stimulations in both adherent and suspension cells (Figure 8.2, C, D).

The *PKD2* gene in suspension cells was upregulated only by vitamin D3. In adherent cells, the gene was upregulated by vitamin D3, but downregulated from the 1000Hz stimulation. The lack of difference between the vitamin D3 and the combined 1000Hz and vitamin D3 in the adherent cells meant that the vitamin influences the regulation of *PKD2* while the effects of the mechanical stimulus were lost.

Results are summarised in a concise manner in Table 8.2.

Figure 8.2: Regulation of genes encoding mechanosensors in adherent and suspension THP-1 cells undergoing different treatments for 72 hours. The genes investigated were *PIEZO1* (A, B), *PKD1* (D, C), and *PKD2* (E, F). Data presented as mean of 4 replicates \pm SE of the mean, except for *PIEZO1* and *PKD2* (N=3) in the adherent control cells. Statistical significance assessed by unpaired T test with Welch's correction. P values lower than 0.05 were considered significant.

Table 8.2: Summary of the gene expression patterns for *PIEZO1*, *PKD1*, *PKD2*, and comparison between stimulations. The relative expression was assessed by real-time PCR. The C_T values of genes of interest were compared to the mean C_T of housekeepers *ACTB* and *RPL37A* for the ΔC_T and normalised to the untreated control for the $\Delta\Delta C_T$. The fold expression was calculated using the formula $2^{-(\Delta\Delta C_T)}$ Statistical significance between the groups was determined by using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

Treatment	Regulation patterns of mechanosensor-encoding genes					
	<i>PIEZO1</i>		<i>PKD1</i>		<i>PKD2</i>	
	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension
50nM D3 vs Untreated	No difference (p= 0.29)	No difference (p= 0.23)	No difference (p= 0.6)	No difference (p= 0.2)	2.47 Fold (p***= 0.0096)	2.32 Fold (p***= 0.0004)
1000Hz vs Untreated	11.44 Fold (p*= 0.025)	1.39 Fold (p*= 0.044)	No difference (p= 0.3)	No difference (p= 0.8)	0.6 Fold (p*= 0.024)	No difference (p= 0.72)
50nM D3+1000Hz vs Untreated	No difference (p= 0.09)	No difference (p= 0.7)	No difference (p= 0.4)	No difference (p= 0.2)	1.95 Fold (p***= 0.0013)	2.38 Fold (p**= 0.0021)
Treatment	Comparison of expression between treatments					
	<i>PIEZO1</i>		<i>PKD1</i>		<i>PKD2</i>	
	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension
50nM D3 vs 1000Hz	0.11 Fold (p*= 0.026)	0.59 Fold (p*= 0.015)	No difference (p= 0.2)	No difference (p= 0.06)	4.09 Fold (p***= 0.0036)	2.2 Fold (p****< 0.0001)
50nM D3 vs 50nM+1000Hz	No difference (p= 0.99)	No difference (p= 0.48)	No difference (p= 0.15)	No difference (p= 0.91)	No difference (p= 0.16)	No difference (p= 0.74)
50nM+1000Hz D3 vs 1000Hz	0.12 Fold (p*= 0.027)	No difference (p= 0.052)	No difference (p= 0.54)	No difference (p= 0.055)	3.24 Fold (p***= 0.0001)	2.3 Fold (p**= 0.0039)

8.3.3. Regulation of genes encoding transcription factors

The *NFAT2* transcripts were downregulated for all treatments in adherent cells (Figure 8.3, A). There was no difference between treatments showing that they downregulated *NFAT2* at the same level (Figure 8.3, A). In suspension cells however, the gene was only downregulated for the combined 1000Hz and vitamin D3 stimulation (Figure 8.3, F). The comparison of the combined treatment with the 1000Hz-only stimulation in suspension cells showed that the two processes combined to downregulate gene (Figure 8.3, F).

In adherent cells, the vitamin D3 and the 1000Hz stimulation have opposite effects on the expression of *TCF3* (Figure 8.3, B). However, in the combined treatment the vitamin D regulation prevails, as observed by lack of difference between the vitamin D-only and vitamin D and 1000Hz stimulations (Figure 8.3, B). Interestingly in suspension cells, *TCF3* is regulated only by the 1000Hz stimulation (Figure 8.3, G).

The *TCF4* gene expression was regulated only in response to vitamin D3 stimulation in both suspension and adherent cells (Figure 8.3, C, H). The *TCF7L2* gene expression was also regulated only in response to vitamin D3 stimulation in both suspension and adherent cells (Figure 8.3, D, I).

The *LEF-1* in suspension cells was downregulated in response to the vitamin D3 stimulation (Figure 8.3, J). A higher downregulation in the cells stimulated only with vitamin D3 compared to the combined stimulation could indicate that the 1000Hz lowered the effect that the vitamin has on *LEF-1* expression (Figure 8.3, J). In the adherent cells little transcripts were obtained for this gene. The gene was downregulated in vitamin D3 stimulated cells, but no statistically significant difference in the combined stimulation cells (Figure 8.3, E). In adherent cells, no gene transcripts were detected in 1000Hz stimulated samples in both 40 and 50 PCR cycles (Figure 8.3, E).

Results for these genes are summarised in a concise manner in Table 8.3.

Figure 8.3: Expression of genes encoding for transcription factors in adherent cells (A-E), and suspension cells (F-J) after stimulation at 72 hours. Data presented as mean of 4 replicates \pm SE of the mean. Statistical significance assessed by unpaired T test with Welch's correction. P values lower than 0.05 were considered significant.

Table 8.3: Summary of the expression patterns for genes encoding transcription factors, and comparison between stimulations. The relative expression was assessed by real-time PCR. The C_T values of genes of interest were compared to the mean C_T of housekeepers *ACTB* and *RPL37A* for the ΔC_T and normalised to the untreated control for the $\Delta\Delta C_T$. The fold expression was calculated using the formula $2^{(-\Delta\Delta C_T)}$. Statistical significance between the groups was determined by using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

Treatment	Regulation patterns of genes encoding transcription factors									
	<i>NFAT2</i>		<i>TCF3</i>		<i>TCF4</i>		<i>TCF7L2</i>		<i>LEF-1</i>	
	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension
50nM D3 vs Untreated	↓ 0.52 Fold (p*=0.046)	No difference (p=0.08)	↓ 0.63 Fold (p*=0.013)	No difference (p=0.82)	↓ 0.48 Fold (p**=0.0032)	↓ 0.5 Fold (p***=0.001)	↑ 2.63 Fold (p*=0.031)	↑ 1.85 Fold (p**=0.0052)	↓ 0.3 Fold (p*=0.0491)	↓ 0.37 Fold (p***=0.0005)
1000Hz vs Untreated	↓ 0.12 Fold (p***=0.0004)	No difference (p=0.15)	↑ 4.73 Fold (p*=0.04)	↑ 1.69 Fold (p*=0.018)	No difference (p=0.07)	No difference (p=0.3)	No difference (p=0.093)	No difference (p=0.998)	No amplification detected	No difference (p=0.7)
50nM D3+1000Hz vs Untreated	↓ 0.31 Fold (p***=0.0006)	↓ 0.69 Fold (p*=0.04)	↓ 0.69 Fold (p*=0.023)	↑ 1.27 Fold (p*=0.014)	↓ 0.37 Fold (p**=0.0016)	↓ 0.55 Fold (p**=0.003)	↑ 2.36 Fold (p*=0.012)	↑ 2.1 Fold (p**=0.0063)	No difference (p=0.1)	↓ 0.66 Fold (p**=0.0011)
Treatment	Comparison of expression between treatments									
	<i>NFAT2</i>		<i>TCF3</i>		<i>TCF4</i>		<i>TCF7L2</i>		<i>LEF-1</i>	
	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension	Adherent	Suspension
50nM D3 vs 1000Hz	No difference (p=0.075)	No difference (p=0.14)	↓ 0.13 Fold (p*=0.031)	↓ 0.58 Fold (p*=0.013)	↓ 0.18 Fold (p*=0.032)	↓ 0.54 Fold (p****<0.0001)	No difference (p=0.32)	↑ 1.84 Fold (p**=0.0034)	n/a	↓ 0.36 Fold (p**=0.0014)
50nM D3 vs 50nM+1000Hz	No difference (p=0.28)	No difference (p=0.15)	No difference (p=0.44)	↓ 0.77 Fold (p*=0.045)	No difference (p=0.28)	No difference (p=0.13)	No difference (p=0.63)	No difference (p=0.29)	No difference (p=0.3)	↓ 0.56 Fold (p*=0.011)
50nM+1000Hz D3 vs 1000Hz	No difference (p=0.052)	↓ 0.84 Fold (p*=0.02)	↓ 0.15 Fold (p**=0.009)	No difference (p=0.08)	↓ 0.14 Fold (p*=0.029)	↓ 0.59 Fold (p****<0.0001)	No difference (p=0.46)	↑ 2.09 Fold (p**=0.0047)	n/a	↓ 0.65 Fold (p**=0.0027)

8.4. Discussion

8.4.1. Comments on the experimental design

The stimulation of THP-1 monocytes using 50nM vitamin D3, 1000Hz nanovibrations, or both, was performed over a period of 72 hours. The 72 hours time-point is a good early observation point for THP-1 stimulation, especially when using vitamin D3 as stimulant (Schwende *et al.*, 1996).

The chosen concentration of 50nM vitamin D3 (1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3) for the chemical stimulation was not high, but still strong enough to observe changes in THP-1 cells. Usually 100nM of the vitamin is used for assessment of differentiation at early time-points (Zhang *et al.*, 1994; Schwende *et al.*, 1996), but lower concentrations (e.g. 10nM) are also used for longer periods such as 7 days incubation (Piemonti *et al.*, 2000). The 50nM concentration was chosen so that the effects of vitamin D3 would not be too strong to hide any synergetic or antagonising effects during simultaneous stimulation with the 1000Hz nanovibrations. The concentration choice was also made based on preliminary work provided from Dr Robin Freeburn.

8.4.2. Regulation of genes encoding for *CD14*, *CD36*, *HLA-DRA* and *HLA-DMB*

Stimulation with vitamin D3, which also served as a positive control for the induction of differentiation, resulted in upregulation of the *CD14* and *CD36* mRNA in both adherent and suspension cells (Table 8.1). This pattern of regulation for these two markers was expected to occur during monocyte to macrophage development (Zhang *et al.*, 1994; Maeß, Sendelbach and Lorkowski, 2010). The *CD14* is an important marker of the THP-1 monocyte differentiation into macrophage and it upregulates strongly upon vitamin D3 stimulation (Schwende *et al.*, 1996; Gocek *et al.*, 2012). In addition, *CD14* and *CD36* are primary target genes for vitamin D3 in THP-1 monocytes (Nurminen, Seuter and Carlberg, 2019).

Stimulation with vitamin D3 downregulated the *HLA-DRA* expression in both adherent and suspension cells (Table 8.). Downregulation of the HLA-DR protein has been observed in primary monocytes treated with vitamin D3 (Tokuda and Levy, 1996), as well as in dendritic cells (Ferreira *et al.*, 2015). The downregulation of HLA-DR and other inflammatory proteins in dendritic cells has shown to be part of tolerance processes induced by vitamin D3 signalling (Ferreira *et al.*, 2015). The mRNA for the beta subunit of *HLA-DM* was upregulated

for vitamin D3 in suspension cells (Table 8.1). This molecule is important for antigen loading of the MHC class II by removal of CLIP from HLA-DR (Riberdy *et al.*, 1992; Sloan *et al.*, 1995), and it can be suggested the upregulation is related to the decreased *HLA-DR* production. In one study, HIV-infected THP-1 monocytes had loss of mRNA for *HLA-DR*, but the mRNAs for *HLA-DM* continued to be transcribed, showing that genes may have non-corresponding expression patterns (Shao and Sperber, 2002).

The 1000Hz stimulation caused upregulation of the *CD36* and downregulation of *HLA-DMB* in suspension cells, whereas in adherent cells it only downregulated the *HLA-DRA* (Table 8.1). In the combined treatment, the 1000Hz weakened the upregulation of *HLA-DMB* by the vitamin (Table 8.1). The 1000Hz stimulation also weakened the upregulation of *CD36* by the vitamin D3, but without changing the regulation pattern with possibly no biological significance (Table 8.1). The *HLA-DRA* was downregulated from all treatments at the same level in adherent cells, which was an interesting observation showing similar mRNA regulation in response to vitamin D and mechanical stimulus (Table 8.1).

Overall, the results from the immunology-related genes showed that the strongest response was for the vitamin D3 which resulted in upregulation of *CD14* and *CD36*, and downregulation of *HLA-DRA*, in both adherent and suspension cells. The 1000Hz stimulation in isolation could affect the expression of some of the genes, but with weak effects on *CD36* only in suspension monocytes, and no influence on the *CD14*. While the mechanical stimulus showed to upregulate the *CD36* in cells when applied in isolation and interfere with the vitamin D3 in the combined treatment, its effects were limited in suspension cells in the former and overshadowed by the vitamin in the later.

8.4.3. Regulation of genes encoding for *PIEZO1*, *PKD1* and *PKD2*

An interesting observation of the experiments performed in this chapter was *PIEZO1* regulation in response to the 1000Hz stimulation. The mRNA levels for this gene were upregulated only for this treatment (Table 8.2). The vitamin D3 did not affect the expression of *PIEZO1* mRNA, but interestingly, cancelled the effect of the 1000Hz stimulation in the combined treatment (Table 8.2). Such observation is difficult to be interpreted, but one hypothesis was that *PIEZO1* mRNA was upregulated due to demand for sensing the mechanical perturbation. The lack of *PIEZO1* regulation in the presence of the vitamin D

could be either due to signalling which prevented the regulation of this gene, or because such regulation was not necessary for the differentiation process.

Another gene that was regulated in response to vitamin D3 was *PKD2* (*TRPP2*) encoding for polycystin 2. The vitamin upregulated this gene in both adherent and suspension cells (Table 8.2). The 1000Hz stimulation had downregulated *PKD2* only in adherent cells, whereas for the combined treatment, the presence of the vitamin cancelled any effect of the mechanical stimulus. This observation was similar to what was observed for *PIEZO1* when combining the 1000Hz with vitamin D3. In addition, the vitamin D3 caused upregulation of *PKD2*, whereas the 1000Hz stimulation caused downregulation in adherent cells (Table 8.2).

The *PKD1* mRNA, encoding for the polycystin 1, was not regulated in response to any of the stimulations applied in these experiments (Table 8.2). At best of my knowledge, upon searching for existing literature, the regulation patterns of *PKD1* and *PKD2* during THP-1 macrophage differentiation are unknown. Similarly, the regulation of these genes to vitamin D3 stimulation are not studied in THP-1 cells. One study has shown that polycystin 1 downregulates during HL60 macrophage differentiation, but that response was towards PMA stimulation (Aguari *et al.*, 1998).

Overall, regulation of the genes encoding for *PIEZO1* and *PKD2* in response to the nanovibrations occurred only when the mechanical stimulus was applied in isolation. The mechanosensory roles of the proteins encoded from these genes may not be needed in the presence of vitamin D3, which is sufficient to drive the differentiation of monocytes to macrophages on its own. The regulation of *PKD2* in response to vitamin D3 was also interesting and it could indicate that polycystin 2 channels are important for the macrophage differentiation process.

8.4.4. Regulation of genes encoding for transcription factors

Transcription factors can have characteristic patterns of expression in different tissues, and during cell development (Lambert *et al.*, 2018). The regulation of transcription factors in this study was investigated to observe the dynamics of gene regulation upon stimulation with vitamin D3 and 1000Hz vibrations, and potentially identify if such stimuli could affect pathways related to macrophage differentiation (e.g. TCF/LEF) (Malsin *et al.*, 2019).

It must be mentioned that some confusion exists about the nomenclature of the TCFs. The mammalian TCF/LEF family comprises of four nuclear factors designated TCF7, LEF1, TCF7L1, and TCF7L2, which are also known as TCF1, LEF1, TCF3, and TCF4, respectively (Hrckulak *et al.*, 2016). Confusion also exists between the nomenclature of genes and the corresponding products. For example, a gene called *TCF3* (NCBI gene ID: 6929), also known as *E2A*, encodes a product that is different from TCF3 encoded from *TCF7L1* (NCBI Gene ID: 83439). Similarly, *TCF4* (NCBI gene ID: 6925), encodes for TCF4 which is a different protein from the TCF4 encoded from *TCF7L2* (NCBI Gene ID: 6934). In this experiment, the mRNA investigated belongs to genes *TCF3* (*E2A*), *TCF4*, *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1*, with the last two investigated in the context of WNT canonical pathways in monocyte-derived macrophages (Malsin *et al.*, 2019).

The pathways which involve TCF3 and TCF4 can be complex and are not fully understood in context of monocyte to macrophage differentiation. Therefore, the discussion here was based only in the results obtained in this experiment. The *TCF4* mRNA was downregulated only in response to vitamin D3 stimulation in both suspension and adherent cells (Table 8.3). The *TCF3* mRNA was regulated in a more interesting pattern. In adherent cells, the *TCF3* mRNA was downregulated in response to vitamin D3 but upregulated for the 1000Hz stimulation. However, when the 1000Hz and vitamin D3 were used in combination, the regulation by the vitamin prevailed. In suspension cells however, the *TCF3* was not affected by the vitamin D3 but rather the 1000Hz vibrations, being upregulated in similar pattern as in the adherent cells undergoing the same mechanical stimulation (Table 8.3).

The *NFAT2* mRNA was downregulated in adherent cells for all the treatments, without difference between each other (Table 8.3). Interestingly, in suspension cells, the mRNA was downregulated only for the combined treatment, which could be due to some synergetic effect (Table 8.3). The NFATs are important transcription factors for production of proinflammatory cytokines in T and B cells (Macian, 2005), but their role is not only limited to the adaptive immune cells. It has been showed that the NFATs are required for Toll-like receptor (TLR)-initiated innate immune responses in bone marrow-derived macrophages (Minematsu *et al.*, 2011). In THP-1 monocytes *in vitro*, the NFAT2 has shown to inhibit the release of high mobility protein box-1 (HMGB1) (Zhao Q *et al.*, 2016), a proinflammatory protein with roles in inflammation and autoimmunity (Magna and Pisetsky, 2014). The

suppression of NFAT2 expression by siRNA has resulted in increased HMGB1 in the supernatant of cells (Zhao Q *et al.*, 2016). About the roles of the vitamin on NFAT2, in T cells, the $1\alpha,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ and its receptor complex (VDR-RXR) have shown to inhibit NFAT activity (Wöbke, Sorg and Steinhilber, 2014), but its effect on monocytes and *NFAT2* mRNA are not known.

In this study, the downregulation of *NFAT2* mRNA in the adherent cells, which are considered to be in a more advanced stage of differentiation than the suspension cells (Tsuchiya *et al.*, 1982; Schwende *et al.*, 1996), could be related to the production of proinflammatory proteins after the maturation of the monocytes into macrophages. This statement and the downregulation of *NFAT2* for the combined treatment in suspension cells must be investigated further in the future.

The mRNA for *TCF7L2* was upregulated only in response to vitamin D3 in both adherent and suspension cells, with the 1000Hz stimulation having no effect on the cells when applied alone or in combination with the vitamin (Table 8.3). Macrophage differentiation is accompanied by *TCF7L2* (*TCF4*) upregulation, which in combination with β -catenin forms a complex that regulates expression of genes in monocytes (Thiele *et al.*, 2001; Tickenbrock, 2006; Malsin *et al.*, 2019).

The mRNA for *LEF-1* was downregulated in response to vitamin D3 stimulation (Table 8.3). In the adherent cells little RNA was obtained for this gene, and no amplification occurred for the 1000Hz stimulation (Table 8.3). This needs to be investigated in the future to explain whether the lack of amplification was due to very low transcripts levels in total RNA, or because of some inhibitory effect that 1000Hz vibrations may have. The downregulation of *LEF-1* by the vitamin D3 was interesting. The *LEF-1* is considered an activator of the WNT canonical pathway, by preventing breakdown of β -catenin (Hrckulak *et al.*, 2016), and in THP-1 *LEF-1* is needed for the localisation of β -catenin in the nucleus (Morgan *et al.*, 2019). In this experiment, *LEF-1* regulation had opposite pattern to that of *TCF7L2* (Table 8.3). The *TCF7L2* has shown to act as both activator and suppressor of the canonical pathway (Thiele *et al.*, 2001; Hrckulak *et al.*, 2016), so the pattern of regulation may be associated to opposite attributes to *LEF-1*.

Since the *TCF7L2* is needed for THP-1 differentiation, whereas the *LEF-1* is responsible for proliferation in THP-1 cells, the upregulation of *TCF7L2* and downregulation of *LEF-1* upon vitamin D3 stimulation could be associated with increased differentiation and decreased proliferation potentials as the cells become macrophages (Schwende *et al.*, 1996; Thiele *et al.*, 2001; Tickenbrock, 2006; Malsin *et al.*, 2019; Morgan *et al.*, 2019). In addition, in other cancer models, the regulation of *LEF-1* and *TCF7L2* has shown to be inversely correlated (Kriegl *et al.*, 2010; Eichhoff *et al.*, 2011).

Overall, the *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1* were regulated by the vitamin D3, while the roles of 1000Hz stimulation on *LEF-1* need more investigation. The results for the vitamin D3 stimulation indicate an inverse relationship in mRNA regulation between *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1*, which could be signature of THP-1 macrophage differentiation.

8.4.5. Comments on the potential effects of the 1000Hz stimulation on THP-1 maturation.

The mechanical stimulation when applied alone caused upregulation of the *CD36* marker, and some other genes that could indicate response, but the observations between the adherent and suspension cells were inconsistent. The *CD36* was upregulated in suspension monocytes, but not in the adherent cells (Table 8.3). In the suspension monocytes, other regulated genes included *HLA-DMB* (downregulated), *PIEZO1* (upregulated), and *TCF3* (upregulated), with *LEF-1* not being detected. In adherent cells, there was no change in differentiation markers like *CD36* and *CD14*, but some of the genes were regulated, such as *HLA-DRA* (downregulated), *PIEZO1* (upregulated), *PKD2* (downregulated) and *NFAT2* (downregulated). The adherent cells are considered to be in a more advanced state of differentiation (Tsuchiya *et al.*, 1982; Schwende *et al.*, 1996), and it could be that the mechanical stimulus is perceived differently. Therefore, the 1000Hz stimulation may have some weak effect on the maturation of suspension cells, which ceases once the cells become adherent. That would explain the weak upregulation of *CD36* occurring only in suspension cells, but not in adherent cells. Furthermore, in the adherent cells the regulation of *HLA-DRA*, *NFAT2*, *TCF3*, *PIEZO1* and *PKD2*, may be more involved in post-maturation processes, such as production of proinflammatory proteins, antigen presentation or tissue mechanosensation (Tokuda and Levy, 1996; Zhao Q *et al.*, 2016; Solis *et al.*, 2019).

Based on the above discussion, the response of THP-1 monocytes toward the 1000Hz stimulation could be limited to an enhancement of cell transition from suspension to

adhesion, compared to the unstimulated control cells. Furthermore, in terms of monocyte differentiation into macrophage, the response is biologically inferior to that of the vitamin D3 as seen by weak *CD36* regulation, or lack of regulation for the *CD14* and TCF/LEF transcription factors. Such response was absent in adherent cells, unlike for the vitamin D3 stimulation, so the adherent cells stimulated with the 1000Hz may not undergo or complete the differentiation process.

When looking at the combined stimulation, the cells treated with vitamin D3 and 1000Hz had lower mRNA levels for *CD36* and *HLA-DMB* than the cells stimulated only with vitamin D3, slightly weakening the effect of the vitamin in upregulation of these genes. Similarly, the combination of the 1000Hz with the vitamin D3 resulted in lowering the downregulating effect that the vitamin had on the mRNA encoding *LEF-1*. In suspension cells, *TCF3* was regulated only in response to the 1000Hz stimulation, and that regulation was maintained in these cells even at the presence of vitamin D3. However, in adherent cells, the addition of vitamin D3 cancelled and reversed the effect of the mechanical stimulation on *TCF3* regulation. Similarly, for *PIEZO1* and *PKD2*, the addition of the vitamin D3 cancelled the effects of the 1000Hz stimulation. *HLA-DRA* and *NFAT2* seemed to be regulated at the same level for each treatment with no additive or diminishing effect upon combination of stimuli. In the combined stimulation, the results indicated that gene regulation was influenced by the vitamin, and that the 1000Hz stimulation had no effect on the differentiation of cells.

8.5. Conclusion and future research

This study showed interesting results about mRNA regulation of genes of interest in THP-1 monocytes stimulated with 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3, 1000Hz nanovibrations, or both.

The vitamin D3 caused regulation of genes that are associated with monocyte maturation into macrophages, encoding for surface markers such as *CD14* and *CD36*, antigen presenting molecules such as *HLA-DR* and transcription factors of the TCF/LEF pathway. In this experiment, it was observed that the vitamin D3 did not induce regulation of *PIEZO1* or *PKD1*, but upregulated *PKD2*, which may be involved in the differentiation process. Based on literature research at the time this chapter was written, the mRNA regulation patterns of *PIEZO1*, *PKD1* and *PKD2* in vitamin D3-stimulated THP-1 cells have not been previously described. The effects of vitamin D3 were strong in both suspension and adherent cells.

The 1000Hz nanovibrational stimulation may have a weak effect on THP-1 differentiation, mostly in suspension cells where it upregulated the *CD36*. Inconsistent gene regulation patterns were observed in the adherent cells and suspension cells, with exception of *PIEZO1* and *TCF3*. By looking at transcriptional regulation of differentiation markers and transcription factors, it could be that the 1000Hz stimuli in the environment made the cells behave differently compared to the untreated controls, but with no effects on macrophage differentiation process.

For the combined treatment, the 1000Hz could weakly interfere with the effects of vitamin D3 on the regulation of *CD36* and *HLA-DMB*, but without changing or significantly altering the regulation patterns. One exception was the upregulation of *TCF3* in suspension cells stimulated with the combined treatment. On the contrary, the vitamin D3 cancelled the effect of the 1000Hz stimulation on many genes, even for the expression of mechanosensors *PIEZO1* and *PKD2*. Therefore, the THP-1 differentiation process in THP-1 cells stimulated with the combined vitamin D3 and 1000Hz was driven by the vitamin, which cancelled and/or overshadowed the interferences of the mechanical stimulus.

However, it must be mentioned that the observations of these experiments should be checked for reproducibility in the future. Confidence to the results was given by obtaining the expected gene regulation patterns towards vitamin D3 stimulation, and validation of PCR techniques which was performed by melt curve analysis. A weak point of the experiment presented in this chapter, was that during the stimulation for three days, there was little RNA obtained from the adherent cells, and for some genes there was no detection of mRNA, which resulted in loss of replicates. In suspension cells, there was good amount of RNA and no replicates were lost. Longer incubation periods of 4 to 5 days could be used in the future, in order to allow more cells to become adherent and circumvent the low RNA issues.

Furthermore, the interpretation of results in this chapter was based only in the obtained gene patterns. The effects of stimuli on protein level should be taken under consideration for a more complete interpretation. For example, the expression of *PIEZO1* channels and their roles in mechanosensation towards the 1000Hz stimulation must be investigated, and *PC2* (*PKD2*, *TRPP2*) roles in the differentiation of THP-1 monocytes into macrophages upon vitamin D3 stimulation should be looked in context of Ca^{2+} and intracellular signalling. Other experiments may also look at the morphological changes, proliferation, and/or adhesion

rates. In addition, the experimental work can further advance to see the effect that the mechanical 1000Hz stimulus, alone or in combination with chemical stimulant like LPS or IL-6, may have on fully mature and adherent macrophages.

Overall, while the results presented in this chapter were interesting, they should be tested for reproducibility and reinforced with other techniques for better and more complete interpretation of biological events.

Chapter 9

Final discussion and conclusions

9.1. Mechanobiology and autoimmunity

The work presented in this thesis assessed the mechanosensitivity of T cells and monocytes/macrophages in *in vitro* experiments. The immune cells have the ability to sense and respond to the physical properties of their extracellular environment (Previtera, 2014; Kim *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, the external mechanical perturbations can influence immune cell phenotypes and regulate their responses (Kim *et al.*, 2019).

T cells are capable of developing antigen-specific immune responses, but in the process of generating a large and diverse repertoire of cells, some of them may express TCRs which recognize self-antigens and could target self-tissues (Dornmair *et al.*, 2003). T cells are therefore major contributors in autoimmune pathologies (Dornmair *et al.*, 2003). In alopecia areata, the CD8⁺ T cells are involved in autoimmune responses that result in disease phenotype, and are the first to recruit around the lower part of hair follicles during the anagen in patients with the condition (Simakou *et al.*, 2019). The CD4⁺ T cells have also shown to be involved in autoimmune responses targeting hair follicle cells (Simakou *et al.*, 2019).

The monocytes and macrophages participate in the pathogenesis of autoimmune diseases, mainly through their proinflammatory and fibrogenic properties (Ma *et al.*, 2019). These cells are involved in autoimmune diseases such as SLE, RA, MS, and T1D (Ma *et al.*, 2019). In these pathologies, the heterogeneity of monocyte and macrophage subpopulations varies significantly, and their polarized M1 or M2 phenotypes usually play important roles in disease progression (Ma *et al.*, 2019). The roles of monocytes and macrophages in autoimmune alopecia areata are unknown.

9.1.1. The potential roles of mechanosensation in autoimmunity

In the thymus, the T cells with moderate affinity to the self-antigens are selected to be released in circulation (Moran and Hogquist, 2012). The cells that show strong affinity for self-antigens are deleted, protecting the host from autoreactive T cells (Moran and Hogquist, 2012; Xing and Hogquist, 2012). This process is known as central tolerance (Xing

and Hogquist, 2012). Although the mechanisms of central tolerance are efficient, they cannot eliminate all self-reactive lymphocytes, partly because not all self-antigens are expressed in the thymus (Xing and Hogquist, 2012). Therefore, peripheral tolerance mechanisms exist, and these are crucial to control tolerance of lymphocytes that first encounter their cognate self-antigens outside of the thymus, such as in the case of food antigens, developmental antigens, and antigens displayed during chronic infection (Xing and Hogquist, 2012). Both anergy and deletion of self-reactive T cells can occur in the periphery (Xing and Hogquist, 2012).

Mechanobiology studies have shown that the mechanical forces applied during the interaction of TCR with peptide-loaded MHC complexes influence the activation of T cells. The magnitude, duration, and frequency of forces applied upon TCR-pMHC ligation prolong the lifetime of TCR-pMHC bonds allowing for stronger Ca^{2+} signalling (Liu *et al.*, 2014). Application of an external tangential but not a normal force (~ 50 pN) via optical tweezers has resulted in the activation of TCR-CD3 signalling (Kim *et al.*, 2009). The anti-CD3 monoclonal antibodies that are used widely in research for the activation of T cells mimic this force via their intrinsic binding mode (Kim *et al.*, 2009). The force-dependent activation of the TCR has shown to require cytoskeletal function (Comrie and Burkhardt, 2016). In addition, recent studies have shown that the mechanosensory PIEZO1 channels have important roles in the activation of T cells during antigen presentation (Liu and Ganguly, 2019). PIEZO1-induced mechanotransduction results in the optimisation of TCR triggering and cytoskeletal arrangements which stabilise the immune synapse (Liu *et al.*, 2018).

These studies have shown that mechanosensation influences T cell activation, by affecting the TCR signalling and the magnitude of the 'first signal'. Therefore, it is possible that the altered physical properties of tissues and cell mechanosensation could enhance the TCR triggering for self-antigens, thus lowering the activation threshold. Such process could interfere with the peripheral tolerance and lead to inflammation and/or autoimmunity.

In addition, the physical properties of tissues such as stiffness or pressure, have shown to affect the activation, cytokine production, and phagocytic activity in macrophages (Yamamoto, Ikeda and Shimada, 2003; Shiratsuch and Basson, 2005; Patel *et al.*, 2012; McWhorter, Davis and Liu, 2015). The altered physical parameters of tissues can lead to

activation of macrophages and production of proinflammatory cytokines, which can contribute to autoimmune pathogenesis (Kim *et al.*, 2019; Ma *et al.*, 2019).

9.2. Summary of research aims

The first objective of this project was to investigate the expression of genes which encode mechanosensors upon activation of Jurkat and primary CD8⁺ T cells after stimulation with PMA and PHA-L. These compounds activate components of the TCR pathway (Figure 9.1). PMA is a small compound analogous to diacylglycerol (DAG) and activates protein kinase C (PKC) (Isakov and Altman, 2002), whereas the PHA crosslinks the CD3 and the costimulatory molecule CD2 (Weiss, Wiskocil and Stobo, 1984; Manger *et al.*, 1986; Tiefenthaler and Hünlg, 1989). The mechanosensor-encoding genes chosen for investigation were *PIEZO1*, *PKD1* and *PKD2*. The expression of genes encoding for mechanosensors was also investigated in THP-1 monocytes upon their differentiation into macrophages induced by the vitamin D3. In addition, in THP-1 monocytes, the expression of these genes was also investigated in response to the stimulation with 1000Hz vibrations and the combined vitamin D3 and 1000Hz treatment.

The gene expression analysis also included markers of T cell and macrophage differentiation, cytokines, and transcription factors, in order to assess the activation and differentiation status of the cells. The work performed to meet the first objective was presented in Chapters 2, 3 and 8, although the chemical stimuli were used as positive controls or in combination with the 1000Hz mechanical stimulus in other chapters.

Figure 9.1: Activation of TCR signalling pathways by PHA-L and PMA. In T cells, TCR signal transduction is initiated upon binding of TCR to peptide-loaded MHC complexes on antigen presenting cells (APCs). The SCR family protein tyrosine kinase LCK is recruited to the TCR by binding of CD4 or CD8 to the MHC class II and MHC class I, respectively. LCK phosphorylates immunoreceptor tyrosine-based activation motifs (ITAMs) in the CD3 chains, allowing docking and activation of the protein tyrosine kinase ZAP70. ZAP70 phosphorylates the transmembrane adaptor protein linker for activation of T cells (LAT), leading to the recruitment of multiple adaptors and effector molecules with will propagate signalling into the nucleus. One of these pathways results in the activation of phospholipase Cy1 (PLC γ 1), which hydrolyses the phosphatidylinositol 4,5-biphosphate (PIP2) to inositol 3,4,5-triphosphate (IP3) and diacylglycerol (DAG). IP3 production results in increased concentrations of intracellular Ca²⁺ and subsequent activation of calcineurin-NFAT pathway. The DAG activates protein kinase C- θ (PKC- θ) and subsequent NF κ B signalling pathway. DAG also activates the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathway, by activation of RAS guanyl nucleotide-releasing protein (RASGRP), which is not depicted in this image. The accumulation of transcription factors and their translocation into the nucleus results in T cell proliferation, migration, and cytokine production. The TCR pathway can also be activated in vitro using the mitogen phytohaemagglutinin (PHA) and phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA). PHA crosslinks TCR-CD3 resulting in TCR signalling and activation of Ca²⁺ pathways. PMA is analogous to DAG and activates PKC- θ and its pathway. The stimulation with PMA and PHA results in polyclonal activation of T cells.

The second objective was to look at the effects of the 1000Hz mechanical stimulus on T cells and monocytes. Such stimulation was applied on the cells using a device nicknamed as “nanokick bioreactor”, which generated vibrations of nano-scale amplitudes and 1000Hz frequency. This type of stimulation has been used to study differentiation of bone cells with successful results (Nikukar, Reid, Tsimbouri, Riehle, Adam S G Curtis, *et al.*, 2013; Pemberton *et al.*, 2015; Tsimbouri, 2015; Robertson *et al.*, 2018). The stimulation was applied in isolation or in combination with chemical signals, in order to investigate its effects on Jurkat T cells and THP-1 monocytes. The performed experiments in Chapters 5, 6, 7 and 8, aimed to identify whether the cells were responding to such vibrational stimulation, and if yes, determine whether the stimulation was antagonising or enhancing the cell activation or differentiation process.

As part of the project, the assessment of bioreactor’s stability was important in order to validate the stimulation and ensure that the device was working properly. The “nanokick” device model provided for this project was still under development and optimisation. Therefore, it could become unstable with time and not generate the vibrations of the desired amplitude or frequency. The assessment of bioreactor’s stability was performed every 3 - 4 months, before and after experiments, ensuring that the cells were exposed to uniform vibrations and were not randomly stimulated. The assessment of bioreactor’s stability is presented in Chapter 4.

The third and final objective was to analyse all the results from the experiments and determine whether the observations could support the hypothesis that the 1000Hz nano-scale stimulation could be used as alternative therapy for alopecia areata. The current therapies for alopecia areata which target the autoimmune responses have had limited results on patients, and research to find more efficient treatments is ongoing (Simakou *et al.*, 2019).

A summary of the findings from this project, in response to the above objectives, is presented in this discussion chapter. The interpretation of results was performed in a scientific manner, based on the outcome of carefully designed experiments and existing literature.

9.3. T cells regulate mechanosensor transcription upon activation

The experiments presented in Chapter 2 and 3, demonstrated that *PIEZO1* mRNA gets downregulated in both Jurkat and CD8⁺ T cells upon activation with PMA and PHA-L (Table 9.1). The activation of CD8⁺ T cells was confirmed by the upregulation of *IL2RA* (*CD25*) and downregulation of resting T cell markers *LEF-1* and *IL7R* (Szabo *et al.*, 2019). *PIEZO1* plays important roles in early activation events, by optimising TCR signalling (Liu *et al.*, 2018). Upon generation of mechanical forces during antigen presentation, *PIEZO1* channels open and increase intracellular Ca²⁺ levels, which is followed by activation of calpain and rearrangements of cytoskeleton (Liu and Ganguly, 2019). This process results in stabilisation of the immune synapse and optimisation of TCR signalling (Liu and Ganguly, 2019). In activated Jurkat cells, the *PIEZO1* mRNA was downregulated at 48 hours as well. The downregulation of *PIEZO1* transcription may be necessary to lower the expression of these channels for the regulation of Ca²⁺ signalling in later stages, or to modulate mechanosensation during effector functions.

In addition, stimulation with 20 ng/mL PMA and 1 µg/mL PHA-L downregulated *PKD1* in the CD8⁺ T cells, but not in Jurkat cells. The downregulation of *PKD1* had been recorded in other Jurkat experiments for the stimulation with 50 ng/mL PMA and 1 µg/mL PHA-L at 24 hours, and for the stimulation with 10 ng/mL PMA and 1 µg/mL PHA-L at 48 hours. However, the downregulation of *PKD1* was not observed in all experiments which used the Jurkat cells.

Another gene encoding the mechanosensor PC2, *PKD2*, was found upregulated in Jurkat cells in different experiments, but was not regulated in CD8⁺ T cells (Table 9.). The assessment of *PKD2* expression using PCR was repeated twice in CD8⁺ T cells, but at both times showing results comparable the untreated controls. The lack of regulation of *PKD2* and *NFAT2* in CD8⁺ T cells, may indicate that modulation of Ca²⁺ signalling is important in these cells (Table 9.).

Overall, the results showed some interesting difference in the regulation of genes encoding mechanosensors between Jurkat cells and CD8⁺ T cells, but more importantly they showed the same regulation pattern for *PIEZO1*. This observation could indicate that *PIEZO1* mRNA downregulation is signature of T cell activation and could be of great importance for the process.

9.4. Comparison of gene expression between activated Jurkat and CD8⁺ T cells

Jurkat cells are a good model for studying T cell activation (Abraham and Weiss, 2004). However, as immortalised cell lines they lack components that regulate TCR signalling (e.g. PTEN), and their intracellular signalling pathways are exaggerated in comparison to normal T cells (Bartelt *et al.*, 2009; Gioia *et al.*, 2018). In this project, a comparison of gene regulation patterns upon the activation of Jurkat and CD8⁺ T cells was performed (Table 9.). The cells were activated by the stimulation with 20 ng/mL PMA and 1 µg/mL PHA-L for 24 hours. Jurkat cells had strong *IL-2* and *IL2RA* upregulation, which was to be expected due to their constitutive activated state and exaggerated intracellular signalling (Bartelt *et al.*, 2009). The CD8⁺ T cells had upregulated *IL2RA* but not *IL-2* at 24 hours. The *IL-2* expression in primary T cells is regulated, with a peak between 4 and 12 hours and declining after 24 hours (Boyman and Sprent, 2012, Abbas, Lichtman and Pillai, 2018, p218). In addition, the CD8⁺ T cells are supported with *IL-2* by the CD4⁺ T cells, which are the main contributors of this cytokine in immune responses (Cox, Harrington and Zajac, 2011; Valbon, Condotta and Richer, 2016). The *IL-2* and *IL2RA* expression and upregulation in Jurkat and CD8⁺ T cells acted also as positive control to confirm T cell activation in response to the stimulation.

The Jurkat cells had increased *NFAT2*, *LEF-1*, and *TCF7L2* mRNA levels (Table 9.). The *TCF3* (encoding E2A) was downregulated in both cell types upon activation. The *NFAT2* and *TCF7L2* were not regulated in CD8⁺ T cells at 24 hours, whereas *LEF-1* was downregulated. The *LEF-1* is a marker of resting T cells, and its downregulation in activated CD8⁺ T cells was expected (Kaech *et al.*, 2002; Willinger *et al.*, 2006; Szabo *et al.*, 2019). The upregulation of *LEF-1* in Jurkat cells was interesting. The *LEF-1* is usually an activator of the WNT pathway, and induces cell proliferation (Hrckulak *et al.*, 2016), therefore, its upregulation in Jurkats could be related with enhanced proliferation which is influenced by the canonical WNT signalling. The involvement of this pathway in Jurkat proliferation could also be supported by the upregulated *TCF7L2* mRNA levels (Table 9.). The difference of *LEF-1* regulation patterns upon the activation and proliferation of Jurkat and CD8⁺ T cells, could be explained by the higher presence of the inhibitory isoforms of *LEF-1* in resting CD8⁺ T cells compared to Jurkat lymphoblasts before the stimulation (Willinger *et al.*, 2006).

The elevated *NFAT2* mRNA in Jurkat cells could be due to demand of this transcription factor in response to the stimulation which enhances the already exaggerated Ca²⁺ signalling

in these cells (Bartelt *et al.*, 2009). In contrary, the mRNA levels of *NFAT2* were not upregulated in activated CD8⁺ T cells at 24 hours, which could indicate that the expression of this transcription factor is controlled, probably due to its roles in cell exhaustion (Wherry *et al.*, 2007). The downregulation of *TCF3* (*E2A*) required further investigation to be fully interpreted, but it could be associated with proliferation and/or activation of T cells (Park, Nolan and Sun, 1999; D’Cruz *et al.*, 2012; Masson *et al.*, 2013).

Overall, the regulation of transcription factors was more controlled in CD8⁺ T cells, which unlike the immortalised Jurkat cells, can differentiate into effector cells and regulate their proliferation potential.

Another difference between the cells was observed for the *IFNG*, gene encoding IFN- γ . The *IFNG* mRNA was upregulated in Jurkat cells, but counterintuitively downregulated in CD8⁺ T cells at 24 hours. The CD8⁺ T cells were having high upregulation of *GZMB*, encoding for another effector protein, and they were acquiring a short-lived effector phenotype, as determined by the downregulation pattern of *IL7R* and *KLRG1*. As discussed in the Chapter 3, the IFN- γ could still be produced by the CD8⁺ T cells, but the transcripts were being downregulated for normalising the production.

Table 9.1: Comparison between the expression of genes in Jurkat cells and CD8⁺ T cells, upon stimulation with 20 ng/mL PMA and 1 μ g/mL PHA-L at 24 hours.

Target mRNA	Fold expression in Jurkat T cells			Fold expression in CD8 ⁺ T cells		
	Stimulated vs control	P value	Statistically different?	Stimulated vs control	P value	Statistically different?
<i>IL-2</i>	158.23	0.0005	Yes (***)	1.48	0.214	No
<i>IL2RA</i>	1367.93	0.047	Yes (*)			
<i>PIEZO1</i>	0.64	0.0006	Yes (****)			
<i>PKD1</i>	1.01	0.8944	No	0.61	0.047	Yes (*)
<i>PKD2</i>	1.30	0.0027	Yes (**)	0.68	0.145	No
<i>IFNG</i>	6.27	0.006	Yes (**)			
<i>NFAT2</i>	4.64	<0.0001	Yes (****)	0.83	0.121	No
<i>LEF-1</i>	1.91	0.0003	Yes (****)			
<i>TCF7L2</i>	1.88	<0.0001	Yes (****)	1.00	0.912	No
<i>TCF3</i>	0.74	< 0.0001	Yes (****)			

9.5. The expression of polycystin 1 at mRNA and protein level

The expression of *PKD1* mRNA in Jurkat cells was not reproducible. In some experiments of Chapter 2, *PKD1* downregulated and in other experiments the mRNA levels were comparable to the controls. This lack of reproducibility did not occur for any other gene upon activation of Jurkat cells with PMA and PHA-L. In primary CD8⁺ T cells, *PKD1* was downregulated at 24 hours in activated cells by PMA and PHA-L.

PC1 expression was investigated further in the Chapter 6 by immunofluorescent staining of the protein on the surface of the cells. Because Jurkat cells in the stimulated samples were arranged in clumps, the assessment of fluorescence intensity for whole population could not be performed (i.e. PC1 in stimulated Jurkat cells compared to unstimulated controls). However, PC1 staining was visually stronger in dividing cells, which were undergoing chromatin condensation, mitosis, or were finishing cell division (Figure 9.2). This was observed regardless of treatment, showing that PC1 in Jurkat cells was upregulated during cell division. Assessment of total cell fluorescence intensity, using the CTCF equation in order to correct for cell surface area and background noise (Burgess *et al.*, 2010; McCloy *et al.*, 2014), showed that in dividing cells PC1 was expressed about 2-fold higher than in the non-dividing cells (Figure 6.47).

This observation indicated that PC1 expression could be affected by the cell cycle. Therefore, the differences in expression of PC1 in cells depending on their cell cycle could affect the mRNA levels in whole population, even if the gene was not regulated in response to the treatment. That would explain why *PKD1* mRNA was sometimes downregulated, and other times comparable to controls.

For the mechanical stimulus, in Chapter 7, *PKD1* was found upregulated in one experiment when comparing cells stimulated with PHA-L and 1000Hz versus cells stimulated with PHA-L only, but this was only one experiment and must be tested for reproducibility in the future. The application of 1000Hz stimulation in isolation, in Chapter 5, did not affect the expression of *PKD1* in two experiments, but downregulated its mRNA in the third experiment. However, in the third experiment, there was no response towards the stimulation when looking at *IL-2* mRNA and protein production, and *IL2RA*, so the stimulated population was comparable to the control. This observation reinforces the interpretation that the random detection of the *PKD1* downregulation in the experiments was not due to a

response but rather the heterogenous expression of *PKD1* in Jurkat cells during their cell cycle. In THP-1 monocytes experiments of Chapter 8, *PKD1* mRNA was not regulated for any of the treatments over a period of three days.

In a study looking at TRP mRNA expression in leucocytes from patients with the inflammatory disease non-valvular atrial fibrillation (NVAf), *PKD1* was the only gene that was not regulated from the other members of the family (Düzen *et al.*, 2017). PC1 belongs to TRP family, although it is not a channel like the rest but rather a G-protein-coupled receptor (Zhang, Tran and Wessely, 2018).

The upregulation of PC1 in dividing cells could be related to the roles that this receptor has in T cell proliferation. Loss of expression or function of polycystin 1 and/or polycystin 2 has shown to decrease proliferation of Epstein–Barr virus immortalized lymphoblastoid cells, which results in decreased lymphocyte production (Aguiari *et al.*, 2004; Van Laecke *et al.*, 2018). In addition, lymphopaenia is characteristic in kidney disease which originates from mutations of *PKD1* gene (Van Laecke *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 9.2: Polycystin 1 expression was upregulated in dividing Jurkat cells. The PC1 was detected using an antibody conjugated with AlexaFluor®594, which targeted the extracellular N-terminus region of the protein (A). PC1 was detected in normal Jurkat cells (B). However, the detection of PC1 was stronger in dividing cells during prophase (C), anaphase (D), telophase and cytokinesis (E), and in small daughter cells (F). The PC1 expression was approximately 2-fold higher in dividing cells compared to non-dividing cells.

9.6. Polycystin 2 mRNA regulation in Jurkat cells, primary CD8⁺ T cells, and THP-1 monocytes

The mRNA of *PKD2* was upregulated in all the experiments of the Chapter 2, upon activation of Jurkat cells using PMA and PHA-L. However, in the primary CD8⁺ T cells, the mRNA of this gene was not regulated upon stimulation at 24 hours.

The regulation of *PKD2* upon application of 1000Hz stimulation in Chapter 5 was not reproducible. The *PKD2* mRNA was upregulated at 48 hours in the first experiment, but not regulated in the other two repeated runs. In chapter 7, *PKD2* mRNA was upregulated in cells stimulated with the combined treatment (PHA-L and 1000Hz) versus cells stimulated with PHA-L only, but this was an isolated experiment and must be tested for reproducibility.

In THP-1 monocytes, the vitamin D3 stimulation caused upregulation of *PKD2* in both adherent and suspension cells. The 1000Hz stimulation downregulated the *PKD2* mRNA in the adherent cells compared to the control. However, in the presence of vitamin D3, the effects of 1000Hz were completely cancelled, and the *PKD2* was upregulated as when the cells were stimulated with vitamin D3 only.

The upregulation of *PKD2* in Jurkat cells and THP-1 monocytes upon activation was similar to a study looking at the expression of TRP genes in leucocytes from inflammatory NVAF, in which the *PKD2* mRNA was found upregulated compared to healthy individuals (Düzen *et al.*, 2017).

The results from *PKD2* regulation in T cells were interesting. The experiments of Chapter 2 showed that *PKD2* was upregulated in association with Jurkat cell activation and proliferation. However, Jurkat cell aggregation and proliferation have been induced by the silencing of *PKD2* or mutation of the gene in ADPKD2 T lymphocytes, as a result of reduced ATP-evoked calcium (Magistrone *et al.*, 2019). These conflicting observations could be a result of complex roles that the PC2 may have in T cell activation and proliferation. Furthermore, the *PKD2* upregulation was not observed in CD8⁺ T cells at 24 hours, which could indicate that the roles of PC2 may be limited in these cells, or that the mRNA expression of this gene is controlled in primary cells.

The PC2 channels are also involved in mechanosensation. PC2 and PC1 form a complex which controls Ca²⁺ signalling and acts as mechanosensor, however, PC2 also forms homotetramers that act as non-selective cation channels (Mekahli *et al.*, 2013; Wang *et al.*, 2019). In addition, in renal cells, PC2 has shown to interact with PIEZO1 through its N-terminus and negatively regulates its stretch sensitivity (Peyronnet *et al.*, 2013; Retailleau and Duprat, 2014). Therefore, the regulation of *PKD2* expression can influence the mechanosensitive abilities of T cells in different stages of their activation and differentiation, which must be further investigated in the future.

The upregulation of *PKD2* mRNA during the differentiation of THP-1 monocytes into macrophages showed that the regulation of this gene was associated with the process. As the monocytes become macrophages in tissues, they are exposed to a variety of mechanical forces (Previtiera, 2014). The physical properties of tissues such as stiffness or pressure, have

shown to affect the activation, cytokine production, and phagocytic activity of macrophages (Yamamoto, Ikeda and Shimada, 2003; Shiratsuch and Basson, 2005; Patel *et al.*, 2012; McWhorter, Davis and Liu, 2015). The upregulation of *PKD2* in experiments of Chapter 8 could suggest that PC2 may be involved in mechanosensation after the macrophage differentiation process.

9.7. Jurkat cell activation upon PHA-L and 1000Hz stimulation

Mechanotransduction in T cells during their activation has been associated with forces that optimise TCR triggering upon antigen presentation or crosslinking of the CD3 with monoclonal antibodies. The mechanical forces can affect the interaction of the TCR with pMHC molecules (Liu *et al.*, 2014), affect the signalling upon crosslinking the CD3 with antibodies (Judokusumo *et al.*, 2012; O'Connor *et al.*, 2012), and/or stabilise the cytoskeleton and the immune synapse thus optimising TCR triggering (Hu and Butte, 2016; Ben-Shmuel *et al.*, 2019; Liu and Ganguly, 2019).

For this reason the effects of the 1000Hz (amplitudes 20 - 60 nm) stimulation were assessed when the CD3 was crosslinked by the PHA-L, which is a lectin that induces TCR-CD3 signalling (Weiss, Wiskocil and Stobo, 1984; Ohtsuka, Kaziro and Satoh, 1996). Furthermore, the combined stimulation was investigated because in Chapter 5, the application of 1000Hz stimulation in isolation had no influence on Jurkat activation as assessed by the expression of *IL-2*, *IL2RA* and *NFAT2* mRNA, and IL-2 secretion in the supernatant.

A response towards the combined stimulation was recorded at 24 hours in different experiments. However, the obtained results were varying. In the first experiment there was lower IL-2 concentration in the supernatant of cells stimulated with PHA-L and 1000Hz compared to the cells stimulated only with PHA-L, whereas in the second experiment there were higher IL-2 levels in the supernatant of cells which underwent the combined treatment at 24 hours.

In addition, the *IL2RA* mRNA levels were comparable between PHA-L and the combined PHA-L and 1000Hz treatments in both experiments, despite the differences of the IL-2 in the supernatant. In Chapter 5, it was demonstrated that the IL-2 accumulation in the supernatant with time, affected *IL2RA* mRNA levels (Figure 5.6). The regulation of *IL2RA*

(CD25) by the IL-2 has also been reported in published literature (Bismuth *et al.*, 1985; Kim, 2002; Kim, Imbert and Leonard, 2006; Liao, Lin and Leonard, 2013; Ross and Cantrell, 2018).

The cell growth assay using resazurin seemed influenced mostly by an increase in the survival of the clones rather than enhanced proliferation, which was also reinforced by the qualitative observations of the apoptotic assay. It could be assumed that the lack of *IL2RA* regulation was because the combined treatment was not affecting cell division and proliferation, but rather protecting the cells from apoptosis. However, as counter argument, the increased IL-2 in the supernatant should have increased the *IL2RA* transcripts, as it was demonstrated in Chapter 5 (Figure 5.6). The enhanced IL-2 production would influence both survival and expansion of clones (Ross and Cantrell, 2018), so seeing a selective effect was unusual.

In addition, the lack of a difference between the treatments at 48 hours, in terms of IL-2 production and *IL2RA* regulation, showed that the 24 hours results were not representative of an early response that increased with time.

Therefore, the experiments assessing the responses of Jurkat cells towards the combined PHA-L and 1000Hz stimulation presented non-reproducible and hard-to-interpret results. The interesting observation from all the experiments was that the differences between the treatments, although varying, were recorded at 24 hours. Further experimentation that was necessary to clarify these results could not be performed because the bioreactor failed calibration three times and could not be replaced.

9.8. Vitamin D3 induced macrophage differentiation and downregulated *HLA-DRA*

The vitamin D3 has shown to target multiple monocyte genes and promote monocyte differentiation into macrophages (Nurminen, Seuter and Carlberg, 2019). Vitamin D deficiency is prevalent in multiple autoimmune diseases, such as MS, T1D, and SLE, and it is highly associated with the risk of autoimmunity (Yang *et al.*, 2013). Low vitamin D levels have been associated with risk of developing alopecia areata, whereas topical vitamin D treatment could be useful for modulating the disease (Lin, Meng and Song, 2019). It is thought that the vitamin D prevents and protects from autoimmune diseases by immunomodulation of macrophage and T cell responses (Yang *et al.*, 2013).

The experiments of Chapter 8 showed that the vitamin D3 stimulation induced differentiation of THP-1 monocytes into macrophages, when looking at transcriptional regulation of *CD14*, *CD36* and transcription factors *TCF7L2* (encoding TCF4) and *LEF-1* (Figure 9.3). The stimulation with vitamin D3 resulted in decreased expression of *HLA-DRA* in differentiating THP-1 cells. Downregulation of the HLA-DR protein has been observed in primary monocytes treated with vitamin D3 (Tokuda and Levy, 1996), as well as in dendritic cells (Ferreira *et al.*, 2015). In dendritic cells, the downregulation of HLA-DR has shown to be part of tolerance processes induced by vitamin D3 signalling (Ferreira *et al.*, 2015). The *HLA-DRA* downregulation in this study was an interesting observation which agreed with the observed immunomodulatory effects of vitamin D in inflammation and autoimmunity (Yang *et al.*, 2013).

The study also identified an inverse relationship between *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1* mRNA regulation upon vitamin D3-induced macrophage differentiation. The *TCF7L2* (TCF4) in combination with β -catenin forms a complex that regulates expression of genes in monocytes and it is thus involved in the differentiation process (Thiele *et al.*, 2001; Tickenbrock, 2006; Malsin *et al.*, 2019), whereas *LEF-1* facilitates nuclear localisation of β -catenin and enhances proliferation in acute myeloid leukaemia cells, including THP-1 cells (Morgan *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, the downregulation *LEF-1* and the upregulation of *TCF7L2* could indicate decreased proliferation and increased differentiation as THP-1 monocytes become macrophages (Schwende *et al.*, 1996; Thiele *et al.*, 2001; Morgan *et al.*, 2019). The inverse relationship of *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1* has also been related to a shift from undifferentiated to differentiated states in other cancer cells (Kriegl *et al.*, 2010; Eichhoff *et al.*, 2011). This pattern of regulation for these two genes can be signature of monocyte to macrophage differentiation.

9.9. Monocyte responses to 1000Hz vibrational stimulation

The cellular functions of tissue-resident macrophages and peripheral blood-derived macrophages are affected by the tissue-specific microenvironment, which can create many types of mechanical stress on cells (McWhorter, Davis and Liu, 2015; Mennens, van den Dries and Cambi, 2017). Stiffness and topography, which are mechanical properties of the extracellular matrix, regulate the differentiation, proliferation, and function of macrophages such as phagocytosis (Patel *et al.*, 2012). In addition, macrophages in tissues are exposed to

alterations of pressure which affect the secretion of cytokines such as IL-6, TNF- α , and IL-1 β (Ferrier *et al.*, 2000; Mevoy *et al.*, 2002). Other mechanical stressors include dynamic mechanical loading, such as continuous and cyclic stretch and compression (McWhorter, Davis and Liu, 2015; Mennens, van den Dries and Cambi, 2017).

The THP-1 monocytes are also responsive to mechanical stressors. In models of atherosclerosis, biomechanical strain on THP-1 cells can induce expression of the class A scavenger receptor, degradation of extracellular matrix, monocyte differentiation, and promotion of atherosclerosis (Yamamoto, Ikeda and Shimada, 2003). In addition, DNA microarray analysis has shown that cyclic mechanical strain in THP-1 cells induces expression of genes, some encoding for inflammatory markers such as IL-8 and IEX-1 (Yamamoto, Ikeda and Shimada, 2003). Furthermore, upon differentiation, THP-1 cells become adherent (Tsuchiya *et al.*, 1982; Schwende *et al.*, 1996), which may result in altered mechanosensitivity.

In this project the THP-1 monocytes were stimulated with 1000Hz (amplitude 30 - 60 nm) vibrations, and a combination of 1000Hz and vitamin D3, to assess any responses that would indicate macrophage differentiation.

The vibrational 1000Hz stimulation resulted in upregulation of *PIEZO1* transcripts in both suspension and adherent cells. However, in the presence of vitamin D3, the effect of 1000Hz stimulation on the regulation of *PIEZO1* was cancelled (Figure 9.3). The 1000Hz stimulation also caused *HLA-DRA* downregulation in adherent cells similar to vitamin D3, but when combined with the vitamin it did not show any synergistic effect. Another gene which was upregulated during the stimulation with 1000Hz vibrations, was *TCF3*. This gene was upregulated in both suspension and adherent cells, but the role of this gene and its products are not known in monocytes. Interestingly, in adherent cells the vitamin D3 cancelled the effect of 1000Hz on the regulation of *TCF3* and downregulated the gene. However, in suspension cells the 1000Hz stimulation continued to upregulate this gene even in the presence of the vitamin. This was the only case in which the effects of 1000Hz strongly influenced the expression pattern of a gene in the presence of the vitamin. In addition, the 1000Hz and the vitamin D3 may have synergistically caused the downregulation of *NFAT2* in suspension cells (Figure 9.3).

The upregulation of *PIEZO1* and *TCF3* upon the application of the 1000Hz stimulation was interesting, but it was not associated with macrophage differentiation, because there was no transcriptional regulation for genes such as *CD14*, and *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1* which would indicate transition from monocytes to macrophages (Figure 9.3). The *CD36* was upregulated for the 1000Hz stimulation in suspension cells. However, in adherent cells, which are at a more advanced stage of differentiation (Tsuchiya *et al.*, 1982; Schwende *et al.*, 1996), the *CD36* mRNA levels were comparable to the unstimulated controls.

In the combined treatment, the differentiation into macrophages took place but it was influenced only by the vitamin D3. The vitamin cancelled the effects of mechanical stimulus for the majority of genes of interest which were affected when the vibrations were applied in isolation, with exception of *TCF3* in suspension cells as mentioned earlier. A comparison of gene regulation between the vitamin D3 and the combined treatment, performed in Chapter 8, concluded that the 1000Hz stimulation was not enhancing or weakening macrophage differentiation, and that the process was driven only by the vitamin.

Overall, unlike Jurkat T cells, THP-1 monocytes were more responsive to the 1000Hz stimulation. However, the mechanical stimulus did not affect the macrophage differentiation process because there was no transcriptional regulation of *CD14* and *TCF/LEF* transcription factors. Furthermore, the influence of the 1000Hz stimulus was diminished or cancelled in the presence of the vitamin. This observation is important, because it suggests that even though the THP-1 monocytes can sense the 1000Hz vibrations when applied in isolation, in inflamed tissues rich in chemical signals such as cytokines and chemokines, the cells may lose the ability to sense and respond to such mechanical stimulus. Lastly, these experiments should be tested for reproducibility in the future.

Figure 9.3: The mRNA regulation of genes of interest in THP-1 monocytes stimulated with vitamin D3, 1000Hz vibrations, and both. The gene expression was assessed separately in adherent and suspension cells within the stimulated population and compared to control adherent and control suspension cells. The monocyte to macrophage differentiation was driven by the vitamin D3. The 1000Hz stimulation upregulated *PIEZO1* and *TCF3* but did not affect the expression of differentiation marker *CD14* and *TCF/LEF* transcription factors. The combination of vitamin D3 with 1000Hz cancelled the effects of the mechanical stimulus on gene expression, with the single exception of *TCF3* in suspension cells. The stimulation with vitamin D3 downregulated *HLA-DRA*, which is possibly related to the immunomodulatory effects of the vitamin. The *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1* were inversely regulated during macrophage differentiation induced by vitamin D3.

9.10. Stability of the “nanokick” bioreactor

One of the objectives of this study was to look at the effects of 1000Hz stimulation on immune cells. This type of nano-scale vibrational stimulation was applied using a device, nicknamed “nanokick bioreactor”. The stability and functionality of the device was checked continuously throughout the project in order to validate the stimulation and make sure the cells were receiving the desired stimuli.

The assessment of the bioreactor’s stability showed that the unit supplied was stable for about a year. However, over a period of 6 months, the device’s amplitude range widened and the variance of amplitudes across the platform increased beyond the accepted values. The range of amplitudes on the bioreactor’s platform in incubator environment (37°C), changed to 6 nm - 130 nm from the 10 - 60 nm in the beginning of the project, whereas the variance of amplitude measurements across the platform, measured by the standard

deviation (SDEV), reached a value of 25 from 14 at the beginning to the project. The bioreactor could not be stabilised, calibrated, or replaced.

The incapability of the bioreactor to provide the desired stimulation meant the work had to be discontinued, as control over the generated vibrations was lost. In addition, the change of amplitudes across the platform with time, meant assessment of experimental reproducibility was impaired, as the parameters of the simulation were changing every experiment.

9.11. Can “nanokicking” be a useful method for treatment of alopecia areata?

The work presented in this project, did not show any conclusive evidence *in vitro* to suggest any therapeutic benefit of the 1000Hz vibrations (10-60 nm amplitudes) for inflammatory conditions. If the results from the stimulation of Jurkat cells with PHA-L and 1000Hz will be reproduced in the future, then the vibrations could be making an environment favourable of T cell expansion and clonal maintenance. However, as experiments of Chapter 7 showed, the application *in vivo* will probably have to be applied during antigen presentation, because it was only when the CD3 was crosslinked by the PHA-L that some response was recorded for the 1000Hz stimulation. When the 1000Hz vibrations were applied alone in Chapter 5, random results were obtained, mostly negative, indicating that the nanoscale 1000Hz stimulation was ineffective in Jurkat T cells.

The results from the monocyte to macrophage differentiation were more interesting as a response was recorded based on *PIEZO1* and *TCF3* upregulation in stimulated adherent and suspension cells, and *CD36* upregulation in suspension cells. However, upon the addition of vitamin D3, the effects of the 1000Hz stimulation were cancelled. This observation demonstrated that while the monocytes could be responsive to the 1000Hz stimulation, the presence of chemical signals would diminish or cancel their response to the mechanical stimulus. Furthermore, the application of 1000Hz stimulus did not show enhancement of macrophage differentiation when the regulation of *CD14* and *TCF/LEF* transcription factors was assessed. *CD14* is expressed at lower levels in THP-1 cells than in normal monocytes and upregulates strongly upon differentiation into macrophages (Bosshart and Heinzlmann, 2016), as was observed in this study at mRNA level for the stimulation with the vitamin D3. The mechanical stimulus upregulated *CD36* in suspension cells but did not

affect *CD14* in neither adherent nor suspension cells, thus any roles that the vibrations could have on the differentiation of THP-1 monocytes into macrophages were unlikely.

The results, while interesting from a cell biology perspective, did not provide conclusive evidence that the application of 1000Hz (10 – 60 nm) vibrations on human patients would provide any benefit for alopecia areata. The *in vitro* study was also highly speculative of such connection, but good results would be useful for supporting animal or patient trials.

However, this project observed poor response towards such stimulation. Furthermore, the 1000Hz stimulation of primary cells, which was planned to follow the Jurkat and THP-1 experiments, did not take place because the bioreactor failed calibration and could not be fixed or replaced. This impaired reproducibility assessments and prevented further experimentation from taking place.

9.12. Contributions and future research

This project identified the *PIEZO1* mRNA regulation as important step in the activation of T cells, and probably early differentiation of CD8⁺ T cells into effector phenotypes. Since its discovery in 2010, PIEZO1 has revolutionised our understanding of cell mechanobiology, and it is considered a professional mechanosensory channel, compared to other putative mechanosensory proteins in the human body (Liu *et al.*, 2018; Zhong *et al.*, 2018). Studies of early activation events such as immune synapse formation and antigen presentation have shown that PIEZO1 is crucial for T cell activation, the first necessary step in initiating the adaptive immune response (Liu *et al.*, 2018). Herein, we demonstrated that *PIEZO1* mRNA downregulates at 24 hours in activated Jurkats and primary CD8⁺ T cells.

The meaning of such downregulation remains to be explored further in the future, especially for what it means in terms of T cell mechanobiology during activation and effector stages. Furthermore, modulation of PIEZO1 expression at mRNA or protein levels, could be beneficial for the manipulation of T cell activation or effector functions. Future work should also include early time-points for analysis of PIEZO1 expression. The expression of *PIEZO1* and *PKD2* in leucocytes or T cell infiltrates from alopecia areata patients should be compared to the healthy individuals, in order to observe any differences that could be characteristic of the pathology.

This study also identified differences in the regulation of genes in the immortalised Jurkat cells and primary T cells. The primary cells showed greater control over the expression of transcription factors involved in Ca^{2+} and WNT signalling such as *NFAT2*, *LEF-1* and *TCF7L2*, whereas in Jurkat cells, the genes encoding these transcription factors remained upregulated with time indicating active signalling. Future work should involve time-point analysis of gene expression in order to better identify the regulation of these genes in primary cells over time and compare to the Jurkat cells.

In THP-1 monocytes, experimental data showed that vitamin D3 stimulation for 3 days induced macrophage differentiation and that the process involved regulation of genes encoding for components of the WNT canonical pathway *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1*. An inverse pattern of regulation for *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1* was identified for vitamin D3 stimulation. *PIEZO1* and *PKD1* were not affected by the vitamin D3 stimulation, but *PKD2* was upregulated in both the adherent and suspension THP-1 cells. This was an interesting observation not identified in previous studies, and polycystin 2 could have important roles in macrophage differentiation that should be investigated in future studies.

Furthermore, *PIEZO1* mRNA was upregulated in THP-1 suspension and adhesion cells only in response to the 1000Hz mechanical stimulation, with vitamin D3 having the ability to cancel such upregulation. While *PIEZO1* may not play roles in macrophage differentiation, it could be involved in the production of compounds or cytoskeletal arrangements for adhesion and migration, as shown in another study (Solis *et al.*, 2019). These roles should be investigated in the future, by looking at morphological changes in vibrated THP-1 cells, and by assessing adhesion or migration of cells.

Future experiments involving THP-1 cells should be expanded to look at morphological changes during macrophage differentiation, as well as production of cytokines. The fully differentiated cells by the vitamin D3 should also be tested further to determine if the vitamin influences an anti-inflammatory M2 phenotype. The effects of the 1000Hz vibrations on fully differentiated and adherent macrophages must also be investigated in the future.

This study also contributed to the formulation of laboratory protocols used for the vibrational stimulation of cells in suspension and identified some of the challenges that

originate from working with these cells and the “nanokick” bioreactor. Future studies should be provided with stable “nanokick” bioreactors and the mechanobiology investigation should not be limited to only one type of mechanical stimulus, but may also involve assessment of cell responses to fluid shear stress and pressure, tissue stiffness, and topography.

Overall, this project identified gene regulation patterns that were previously unknown to science, expanding our understanding of mechanosensor mRNA expression in response to chemical and mechanical stimuli. Understanding the expression patterns of mechanosensors in immune cells can provide new insights into the unknown roles that these proteins have in mechanosensation that influences immune responses and inflammation. This can further unravel their involvement in autoimmune diseases, because mechanotransduction could potentially alter the behaviour of immune and affected tissue cells. PIEZO1 and polycystin 2 expression should be investigated in alopecia areata auto-reactive leucocytes, as they can be potential targets for chemical or mechanical manipulation that can modulate T cell activation or macrophage differentiation.

Appendix

A.1 Primer pairs used for amplification of mRNA sequences

The list of primers used for assessment of RNA expression in the experiments of this PhD projects are presented in Table A.1. The primers were used in real-time polymerase chain reactions to amplify the desired sequences.

The primers have been tested for targeting the desired mRNA by using NCBI primer blast, melt curve analysis, and assessment of fragment length by gel electrophoresis. Information about the use of primers in the experiments can be found in the method sections of each chapter.

There were four housekeeping (or reference) genes used in this thesis, the mean of which was used for the relative quantification of gene expression using the Livak's $\Delta\Delta C_T$ method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001). The efficiency of PCR for the chosen primers that target the RNA of housekeeping genes were similar to one another. The primer efficiency in reactions was measured as 96.43% for *TOP1*, 97.1% for *GAPDH*, 97.9% for *ACTB* and 97.6% for *RPL37A*.

The efficiency of the target genes taken from the literature was assessed in published manuscripts, but also measured for the PCR set up used in this project. The efficiency of primers was assessed to be between 95 – 100%, being close to the efficiency of the housekeeping genes which is needed for good quantification using Livak's method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001).

Table A.1: List of primer sequences used in the real-time PCR reactions for the quantification of transcript expression

Target mRNA	Forward Primer Sequence (5' to 3')	Reverse Primer Sequence (5' to 3')	Fragment Length (base pair)
TOP1	GACGAATCATGCCCGAGGAT	CAGTGTCCGCTGTTTCTCT	381 bp
ACTB	ATTGCCGACAGGATGCAGAA	GCTGATCCACATCTGCTGGAA	150 bp
GAPDH	CGAGATCCCTCCAAAATCAA	TTCACACCCATGACGAACAT	170 bp
RPL37A	ATTGAAATCAGCCAGCACGC	AGGAACCACAGTGCCAGATCC	94 bp
IL-2	GAATCCCAAACCTCACCAGGATGCTC	TAGCACTTCTCCAGAGGTTTGAGT	115 bp
IL-2'	AGAACTCAAACCTCTGGAGGAAG	GCTGTCTCATCAGCATATTCACAC	153 bp
IL2RA	GAGACTTCTGCCTCGTCACAA	GATCAGCAGGAAAACACAGCCG	126 bp
IFNG	TCGGTAACTGACTTGAATGTCCA	TCCTTTTTCGCTTCCCTGTTTT	100 bp
IFNGR1	AAAGTCAGAAGAATTTGCTGTAT	ACTGAAGGGTGAAATATGTC	108 bp
GZMB	CGACAGTACCATTGAGTTGTGCG	TTCGTCCATAGGAGACAATGCCC	122 bp
IL7R	ATCGCAGCACTACTGACCTGT	TCAGGCACCTTACCTCCACGAG	101 bp
KLRG1	CCTTTTGCTGGATTGGTCTGAGG	TTGATGGCACCGCATGTCTGCA	115 bp
CD14	ACGCCAGAACCTTGTGAGC	GCATGGATCTCCACCTCTACTG	122 bp
CD36	TCACTGCGACATGATTAATGGTACA	ACGTCGGATTCAAATACAGCATAGAT	126 bp
HLA-DRA	TAAGGCACATGGAGGTGATG	TACGGAGCAATCGAAGAGG	181 bp
HLA-DMB	CTCTCACAGCACCTCAACCA	TAGAAGCCCCACACATAGCA	197 bp
NFAT2	CACTCCTGCTGCCTTACACA	AAGATGCGAGCATGCGACTA	128 bp
LEF-1	GACAGTGACCTAATGCACGT	CCACCTTCTGCCAAGAATCT	186 bp
TCF3	TGACCTCCTGGACTTCAGC	ACCTGAACCTCCGAAGTGC	97 bp
TCF4	AGTGCGATGTTTTCACTCC	CCTGAGCTACTTCTGTCTTC	104 bp
TCF7L2	CCGGGAAAGTTTGAAGAAG	ACTGAAAATGGAGGGTTCGG	158 bp
PIEZO1	CATCTGGTGGTCTCCTCTGTCT	CTGGCATCCACATCCCTCTCATC	114 bp
PKD1	CGCCGCTTCACTAGCTTCGAC	ACGCTCCAGAGGGAGTCCAC	260 bp
PKD2	GCGAGGTCTCTGGGGAAC	TACACATGGAGCTCATCATGC	149 bp

A.2. Validation of PCR using T_m for the specific primer pair

The specificity of a real-time PCR assay is determined by the primers and reaction conditions used (ThermoFisher, 2012). However, there is always the possibility that even well designed primers may form primer dimers or amplify nonspecific products. A melt curve analysis is added to the end of PCR reactions in order to assess the T_m for each primer pair. Melting curve analysis can only be performed with real-time PCR detection technologies in which the fluorophore remains associated with the amplicon, such as SYBR Green (ThermoFisher, 2012).

The T_m for each primer pair should be the same, regardless of the amount of amplification, if those primers are amplifying their specific sequence. Slight differences in the T_m per primer pair, approximately 1°C, can be recorded by changes in the SYBR mastermixes (e.g. between Applied Biosystems' SYBR Green and Power-up SYBR green), due to slight differences in their composition. Peaks with different T_m can mean primer dimers or unspecific amplification (ThermoFisher, 2012).

A.2.1. PCR melt curves from experiments of Chapter 2

Figure A.2.1.1: The melt curves and Tm for the primer pairs used to amplify the housekeeping genes in the PCRs from the second experiment looking at the activation of Jurkat cells upon PMA and PHA-L stimulation. The reaction set up used was comprised of 12.5 μ L SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied Biosystems™, 4309155), 0.5 μ L Forward Primer and 0.5 μ L Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1 μ L of cDNA and topped up to 25 μ L with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035).

Figure A.2.1.2: The melt curves and T_m for the primer pairs used to amplify the housekeeping genes in the PCRs from the third experiment looking at the activation of Jurkat cells upon PMA and PHA-L stimulation. The reaction set up used was comprised of 12.5 μL SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied Biosystems™, 4309155), 0.5 μL Forward Primer and 0.5 μL Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1 μL of cDNA and topped up to 25 μL with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035).

Figure A.2.1.3: The melt curves and Tm for the primer pairs used to amplify the housekeeping genes in the PCRs from the fourth experiment looking at the activation of Jurkat cells upon PMA and PHA-L stimulation. The reaction set up used was comprised of 12.5 μ L Power-up SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied Biosystems™, A25742), 0.5 μ L Forward Primer and 0.5 μ L Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1 μ L of cDNA and topped up to 25 μ L with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035)

A.2.2. PCR melt curves and technical assessments from Chapter 3

Figure A.2.2.1: The melt curves and T_m for the primer pairs used to amplify the housekeeping genes in the PCRs from the second experiment looking at the activation of CD8⁺ T cells upon PMA and PHA-L stimulation. The reaction set up used was comprised of 12.5 μ L Power-up SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied Biosystems™, A25742), 0.5 μ L Forward Primer and 0.5 μ L Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1 μ L of cDNA and topped up to 25 μ L with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035).

Figure A.2.2.2: The melt curves and T_m for the primer pairs used to amplify the genes of interest in the PCRs from the second experiment looking at the activation of CD8⁺ T cells upon PMA and PHA-L stimulation. The reaction set up used was comprised of 12.5 μL Power-up SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied Biosystems™, A25742), 0.5 μL Forward Primer and 0.5 μL Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1 μL of cDNA and topped up to 25 μL with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035).

Figure A.2.2.3: Melt curve and fragment visualisation using electrophoresis for *IFNG* amplicons. The analysis showed specific amplification of *IFNG* mRNA. The *IFNGR1* mRNA was not detected in neither controls nor the stimulated cells.

Figure A.2.2.4: Fragment electrophoresis for *GZMB*, *IL7R* and *KLRG1* amplicons on 2% agarose gel. Some of the possible primer dimers observed in the melt curve for *GZMB* were not detected in the gel. Weak primer dimers were observed in control 4 and stimulated 3 samples for *KLRG1*, but these were not detected in the melt curve. The negative triplicates displayed no amplicons or primer dimers. The fragments were within the expected lengths

A.2.3. PCR melt curves from the experiments of Chapter 5

Figure A.2.3.1: The melt curves and Tm for the primer pairs used to amplify desired sequences in 1000Hz stimulation experiment run 1. The extra peak for the *TOP1* indicates primer dimer in one of the negative controls. The reaction set up used 12.5 μ L SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied Biosystems™, 4309155), 0.5 μ L Forward Primer and 0.5 μ L Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1 μ L of cDNA and topped up to 25 μ L with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035).

Figure A.2.3.2: The melt curves and T_m for the primer pairs used to amplify desired sequences in 1000Hz stimulation experiment run 2. The reaction set up used 12.5 μ L Power-up SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied Biosystems™, A25742), 0.5 μ L Forward Primer and 0.5 μ L Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1 μ L of cDNA and topped up to 25 μ L with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035). The *IL-2''* symbolises the second pair of primers used for *IL-2* amplification.

Figure A.2.3.3: The melt curves and T_m for the primer pairs used to amplify desired sequences in 1000Hz stimulation experiment run 3. The reaction set up used 12.5 μL SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied Biosystems™, 4309155), 0.5 μL Forward Primer and 0.5 μL Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1 μL of cDNA and topped up to 25 μL with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035).

A.2.4. PCR melt curves from experiments of Chapter 7

Figure A.2.4.1: The Tm for the primers used for detection of *GAPDH*, *IL-2* and *IL2RA*. The PCR amplifications were performed in 25 μ L reactions containing 12.5 μ L SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied BiosystemsTM, 4309155), 0.5 μ L Forward Primer and 0.5 μ L Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1 μ L of cDNA and topped up to 25 μ L with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035).

Figure A.2.4.2: The Tm for the primers used for detection or mRNA for the housekeepers and genes of interest. The PCR amplifications were performed in 25µL reactions containing 12.5µL PowerUp SYBR Green Mastermix (Applied Biosystems, A25742), 0.5µL Forward Primer and 0.5µL Reverse Primer for the respective genes, 1µL of cDNA and topped up to 25µL with nuclease free water (Gibco, 10977035)

A2.5. PCR melt curves from experiments of Chapter 8

Figure A.2.5.1: The melt curves and T_m for the primers used to amplify the housekeeping genes *ACTB* and *RPL37A*. These housekeepers were used as reference genes for the relative quantification of *CD14*, *CD36*, *HLA-DRA*, *HLA-DMB*, *PIEZO1*, *PKD1*, *PKD2*, *NFAT2*, *TCF3*, *TCF4*, *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1*, in suspension and adherent THP-1 cells. Note the reproducibility in T_m in melt curves for *ACTB* and *RPL37A*.

Figure A.2.5.2: Melt curves and the Tm for the primers used in the polymerase chain reactions in THP-1 suspension and adherent monocyte/macrophages. The melt curves belong to primers amplifying mRNA transcripts of *CD14*, *CD36*, *HLA-DRA*, *HLA-DMB*, *PIEZO1*, *PKD1*, *PKD2*, *NFAT2*, *TCF3*, *TCF4*, *TCF7L2* and *LEF-1*, in suspension and adherent THP-1 cells.

A.3. Comparison of gene regulation in Jurkat cells at 24 hours using different housekeeping gene combinations

A comparison of responses toward the stimulation with 20 ng/mL PMA and 1 µg/mL PHA-L between Jurkat cells and CD8⁺ T cells was performed in this thesis. For the primary CD8⁺ T cells, the expression of genes of interest was relative to the mean of three housekeepers, *ACTB*, *GAPDH* and *RPL37A*. In Jurkat cells, the expression was assessed relative to the housekeeping genes, *ACTB*, *RPL37A*, and *TOP1*, as presented in Chapter 2. Later *GAPDH* was quantified by PCR and the results for Jurkat cells were recalculated with four housekeepers. While the results for the above combinations were the same, no calculation for the combination of *ACTB*, *GAPDH* and *RPL37A* had been performed.

This combination was necessary for an analogous approach when comparing the responses between Jurkats and CD8⁺ T cells. Therefore, the relative expression of genes in Jurkat cells was recalculated one more time using the mean of three housekeepers, *ACTB*, *GAPDH* and *RPL37A*.

The results demonstrated that the normalisation with the mean of *ACTB*, *GAPDH* and *RPL37A* (Figure A.3.1, A, B) yielded the same results as for the normalisation with four housekeeping genes (Figure A.3.1, C, D), and the combination with *ACTB*, *TOP1* and *RPL37A* as presented in Chapter 2. Insignificant minor changes in the calculation of fold expression and statistical p value were observed (Table A.3.1).

Figure A.3.1: Expression of genes at 24 hours relative to the mean C_T of *ACTB*, *RPL37A* and *GAPDH* (A, B), and relative to the mean C_T of *TOP1*, *ACTB*, *RPL37A*, and *GAPDH*. Jurkat cells were stimulated with 20 ng/mL PMA and 1 μ g/mL PHA-L, whereas the control cells were incubated with the concentration of DMSO that the stimulated cells would be exposed to upon supplementation of medium with PMA. Data presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE of the mean. Statistical significance was determined by comparing stimulated replicates with the control replicates using unpaired T test with Welch's correction.

Table A.3.1: Comparison of gene expression by normalisation with different housekeeping genes. The expression fold and the statistical significance were unaffected by the use of different combinations of the chosen housekeeping genes.

Target mRNA	Fold expression at 24 hours			
	Relative to <i>ACTB</i> , <i>RPL37A</i> and <i>GAPDH</i>			
	Control	Stimulated	P value	Statistically different?
<i>IL-2</i>	1.04	158.23	0.0005	Yes (***)
<i>IL2RA</i>	1.05	1367.93	<0.0001	Yes (****)
<i>PIEZO1</i>	1.01	0.64	0.0004	Yes (***)
<i>PKD1</i>	1.00	1.01	0.8944	No
<i>PKD2</i>	1.00	1.30	0.0027	Yes (**)
<i>IFNG</i>	1.05	6.27	0.0031	Yes (**)
<i>NFAT2</i>	1.00	4.64	<0.0001	Yes (****)
<i>LEF-1</i>	1.00	1.91	0.0034	Yes (**)
<i>TCF7L2</i>	1.01	1.88	<0.0001	Yes (****)
<i>TCF3</i>	1.00	0.74	0.0002	Yes (***)
Target mRNA	Fold expression at 24 hours			
	Relative to <i>TOP1</i> , <i>ACTB</i> , <i>RPL37A</i> and <i>GAPDH</i>			
	Control	Stimulated	P value	Statistically different?
<i>IL-2</i>	1.03	159.31	0.0006	Yes (***)
<i>IL2RA</i>	1.05	1376.59	<0.0001	Yes (****)
<i>PIEZO1</i>	1.01	0.64	0.0003	Yes (***)
<i>PKD1</i>	1.00	1.01	0.7902	No
<i>PKD2</i>	1.00	1.31	0.0021	Yes (**)
<i>IFNG</i>	1.05	6.32	0.0033	Yes (**)
<i>NFAT2</i>	1.00	4.67	<0.0001	Yes (****)
<i>LEF-1</i>	1.00	1.92	0.0036	Yes (**)
<i>TCF7L2</i>	1.01	1.89	<0.0001	Yes (****)
<i>TCF3</i>	1.00	0.74	0.0004	Yes (***)

A.4. The *TCF7* expression in Jurkat and CD8⁺ T cells.

For the amplification of *TCF7*, the following primer pair was used in the polymerase chain reactions, *TCF7* forward 5'- AGGGAAGCAGGAGCTGCAGC - 3' and *TCF7* reverse 5'- GCACTCTGCAATGACCTTGGC – 3'. This primer pair was obtained from existing literature looking at the expression of this gene in T cells (Ma *et al.*, 2015). The regulation of *TCF7* in this study was similar to what was observed in existing literature, where *TCF7* and *LEF-1* proteins downregulate upon activation of CD8⁺ T cells (Willinger *et al.*, 2006). However, certain technical issues existed with the amplification. The primers generate a short sigmoidal amplification plot, with late-C_T positive negative controls. These were proven to be primer dimers by melt curve and gel electrophoresis, while single bands existed for the controls and experimental samples (Figure A.4.1). The short sigmoidal pattern was observed in Jurkat cells too, in which the *TCF7* was also downregulated as a response to the stimulation with 20 ng/mL PMA and 1µg/mL PHA-L at 24 and 48 hours (Figure A.4.2).

The short sigmoidal amplification plot is not fully understood as to why occurs, but high background signal could be responsible for such pattern. The efficiency of the PCR therefore is difficult to be assessed and could be faulty, although the amplification of the samples seemed specific and good by melt curve analysis and gel electrophoresis.

This gene could be used as another indicator that the process of T cell activation was taking place in the stimulated cells. However, since the patterns of *TCF7* regulation upon activation of CD8⁺ T cells were observed before (Willinger *et al.*, 2006), it was inessential for new primers to be ordered and further investigation to be carried out about this gene. In the later experiments the focus was shifted only at *LEF-1*.

Figure A.4.1: *TCF7* melt curve (A), amplification plot (B), fragment electrophoresis on 2% agarose gel (C), and expression compared to the unstimulated cells (D). Presence of dimers was detected in the melt curve (A) and in the gel (C), while the amplification was represented by a narrow sigmoidal plot (B). For the analysis of fold expression (D), the data were presented as mean of 5 replicates \pm SE of the mean. Statistical significance was assessed by unpaired T test with Welch's correction. P values <0.05 were considered significant.

Figure A.4.2: *TCF7* expression in Jurkat cells stimulated with 20 ng/mL PMA and 1 μ g/mL PHA-L at 24 (A) and 48 hours (B). The expression of *TCF7* in this experiment was relative to the housekeeping genes *TOP1*, *ACTB*, *RPL37A* and *GAPDH*. The data were presented as mean of 6 replicates \pm SE of the mean. Statistical significance was assessed by unpaired T test with Welch's correction. P values <0.05 were considered significant. The T_m for the primers was 84.69°C, but the amplification was a short sigmoidal plot, and the negative control had high background noise.

A.5. Comments on cell density used in experiments of Chapter 5

The starting cell density of 1.5×10^5 cells/mL was chosen on the basis that the cell growth with time would provide a good amount of RNA, and at the same time the culture would not be confluent enough to exhaust the medium nutrients quickly. The starting cell density of 1.5×10^5 cells/mL would result in good confluency over a period of 48 hours, but not at high levels as for the starting density of 2.5×10^5 cells/mL or 5×10^5 cells/mL (Table A.5.1.). The lowest allowed cell density for Jurkat E6-1, according to ATCC, is 1×10^5 cells/mL. The confluency was assessed by microscopy. Assessing of the confluency can be difficult however, as the cells tend to form clumps, so the nature of the examination remains qualitative.

The chosen volume of 2ml suspension was spread in the wells of 6-well plates with not a great depth (height). Such volume was chosen so that the cells were kept close to the vibrating surface of the well. The Jurkat cells, unlike the cells used in previous studies of “nanokicking” stimulation, are cells in suspension and tend not to adhere to the surfaces.

As the useful space of the platform became limited with time, 24-well plates were used for the subsequent experiments, and the depth (height) of the medium had to be changed to allow enough medium for the cells to grow at a lower volume well. However, it was noticed that the cells settled lower in the medium after 15 – 30 minutes, so the distance of cells from the vibrating surface may have not been affected much from the depth of suspension.

Table A.5.1: Cell confluency of 2ml Jurkat suspension at 24 and 48 hours. These images portray untreated Jurkat cells and do not account for any boosting effect on proliferation that certain treatments may have. The results are also qualitative and relatively present the cell confluency, because Jurkats are cells in suspension and as such they tend to float and clump

Starting cell density Time-point	1.5 x 10 ⁵ cells/mL	2.5 x 10 ⁵ cells/mL	5 x 10 ⁵ cells/mL
24 hours			
48 hours			

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